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EDITORIAL NOTE

Zamfara International Journal of Education (ZIJE) is the official Journal of the Faculty of Education, Federal University Gusau, Zamfara State, Nigeria. The Journal publishes article of diverse fields of interest in education. Papers reporting original research and extended version of already established conference and journal articles are welcomed. Papers for publication are selected through peer review process to ensure originality, relevance and readability. ZIJE is published bi-annually June and December.

The aim and scope of the journal is to provide an academic medium and an important reference for the advancement and dissemination of information that supports high level learning, teaching and research in the fields of education.

This edition, Volume 3, Number 6, December, 2023 is poised to present research reports in the following fields of education: Educational Foundations, Science Education, Educational Psychology, Curriculum & Instructional Technology, Guidance & Counselling, Philosophy & History of Education, Sociology of Education, Entrepreneurship Education, Special and Inclusive Education, Physical & Health Education, Religious Education, Gender Studies, Peace & Security Education among others. The articles in this volume are academic and professional discourse written by reputable scholars in their areas of specialization.

The Board remain indebted to its editorial members for the ceaseless support given towards successful publication of the Journal. In the same vein, we acknowledge quite sincerely the assistance and support of our esteemed consulting editors for ensuring the credibility of this edition. Also worthy of appreciation are the authors and their immense contributions to this publication.

Associate Professor Bashir Suleiman

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The Editorial Board of Zamfara International Journal of Education (ZIJE) calls for scholarly articles for review and possible publication in its next edition (Volume 4). ZIJE publishes articles that emphasize on research development and application within the field of Education. All manuscripts are reviewed by editorial review committee. Contributions must be original, not previously or simultaneously published elsewhere, and are critically reviewed before they are published. Papers, which must be written in English Language, should have good grammar and proper terminologies. Also note that prospective articles are subjected to plagiarism assessment to estimate the percentage of originality of the papers. Hence, plagiarism threshold of $\leq 20\%$ is recommended.

Editorial Guidelines

1. Manuscripts including references, appendices, tables and diagrams should be double-spaced and single coded on A4 paper with generous margins (at least 1”/2.5cm).
2. Title should be explicit and not more than 19 words.
3. Title page should be arranged as follows: Title, author(s) full name, affiliation, full addresses, email addresses and phone numbers.
4. Abstract should be single line and not more than 250 words.
5. For conceptual papers, the body should have appropriate headings where necessary.
6. For empirical papers, it should be presented in the following order: Introduction, Objectives of the study, Research Questions and/or Hypotheses, Methodology, Results, Discussion of Findings, Conclusion and Recommendations.
7. Acknowledgement (if any).
8. Quotations of more than 40 words should be indented and typed single spacing with indication of the pages where the quotes were lifted.
9. In-text citations should follow the APA 7th edition format.
10. References should be in range with 7th edition of APA Style.
11. Each table and figure should be presented within the manuscripts, with a brief and self-explanatory title.
12. All text within the table should be clearly legible, and all graphics and legends should be easily distinguished when printed in black and white.
13. Tables should be in horizontal lines only, with only blank space to separate columns.
14. Tables and figures that may be included in the main text of the paper should be numbered separately, in the sequence that they are mentioned in the text.
15. Figures should be saved in a neutral data format such as JPEG, TIFF or EPS.

Submission of Manuscripts & Assessment Fee

Manuscripts should be submitted directly to the Editor-in-Chief or Publication Editor through the following e-mail address: zijefugusau@gmail.com. Articles can be submitted between the periods of January to April ending for June publication, while July to October ending for December publication. Assessment fee for manuscript is #5,000.00 only.

Dr. Abubakar Sadiq Haruna

Publication Editor

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A Qualitative Study on Qur'anic Traditional System of Learning (Tsangaya) in Bauchi Emirate, Bauchi State Nigeria

Umar, Aminu¹

Email: babanwalle@gmail.com

Tel: +2348069827778

Mukhtar, Muhammad Sani (Goni)²

Email: gwani1978@gmail.com

Tel: +2348065323525

Muhammad, Rabi'u Shehu¹

Email: mshehu2002@gmail.com

Tel: +2347069057034

Abubakar, Tijjani³

Email: abubakartijjani9763@gmail.com

Tel: +2347035709763

¹Department of Religious Studies Federal University of Kashere Gombe State, Nigeria

²Department of Arts and Social Science Education Kaduna State University, Kaduna-Nigeria

³Department of Islamic Studies Federal University Dutsinma Katsina State-Nigeria

Abstract

The *Tsangaya* system of education is an Islamic-based educational system that has existed for several centuries in Northern Nigerian Muslim Communities since the coming of the British Colonial Masters. This paper is qualitative research that aims to examine the origin, development, and challenges facing the *Tsangaya* school system in Bauchi Emirate, Bauchi State Nigeria using historical and phenomenological methods. The paper highlights the origin and operations of *Tsangaya* schools in general and Bauchi emirate in particular and some of the challenges being faced. The paper's findings among others revealed that the *Tsangaya* Schools in Bauchi Emirate are facing some degree of neglect from the government, the Muslim Ummah and other religious organizations and bodies. The paper also proffers recommendations for what is to be done to improve and salvage the system in the Bauchi Emirate.

Keywords: Qualitative study, *Tsangaya*, Bauchi Emirate

Introduction

Tsangaya refers to the informal school or place where teaching and learning of the glorious Qur'an and other Islamic sciences take place. According to Idris (2021), the word *Tsangaya* is derived from *Sangaya* in Kanuri, which means educational institution. Consequently, the word was altered to *tsangaya* in the Hausa language. On the other hand, the term *Tsangaya* School is known in some places as *Makarantar Allo* (wooden slate School) perhaps due to the wooden slate that is being used in such schools. Apart from the general name, *Tsangaya* has other names such as *Makarantar Muhammadiyya*, *Makarantar al-Qur'ani*, *Makarantar Toka*, etc. (Dahiru et al, 2022). Meanwhile, the word *Almajiri* is derived from the Arabic word *Almuhajirun* which means migrants. It refers to the students who enrol on the traditional method of acquiring and memorizing the glorious Qur'an in Hausa land, it is also referred to a particular place where children at their tender ages are sent out by their parents to other villages, towns and cities for

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acquiring the knowledge of the glorious Qur'an under the care of a knowledgeable Islamic scholar Alaramma or Mallam (Bukar and Mangari, 2020)

It is believed that the Tsangaya System has a long history of existence. Its origin according to Yahaya (2018) can be traced to the old Timbuktu scholastic culture located at a famous centre of Islamic knowledge and scholarship now located in the present Republic of Mali. While Bukar and Mangari (2020) quoting Dahiru on their part traced the origin of *tsangaya* to the reign of Mai Ali Gaji(1503 C.E) who encouraged and supported the establishment of such centres in many areas for the spread of literacy. This system had over a long period graduated many Islamic scholars who later took the responsibility of teaching and spreading the religion of Islam nationwide. (Dahiru et al, 2022)

The pedagogy of the Tsangaya schools

The Tsangaya school system has an unwritten syllabus that comprises a lower and advanced level of studies that exists in five stages altogether. The elementary level was meant for learning recitation and writing while the advanced level is the stage for the Memorization of the Glorious Qur'an as well as the ability to write it off the heart.

According to Bukar and Mangari (2020), there are five stages in the *Almajiri* Qur'anic School:

- i. **Babbaqu Stage:** this is a stage where pupils of around four to five years are introduced to the basic rudiments of the Qur'an they are made to learn all the Arabic alphabets, recognize the vowels and diacritical marks, form letters and finally memorize about ten shorter chapters of the Quran. Pupils in this stage are from the range of 4 and 11 years of age and are referred to as '*Kolo*' in the Hausa Language
- ii. **Farfaru Stage:** this is a stage where learners are introduced to the skill of mastering the reading of the glorious Qur'an with emphasis on the recognition and identification of the distinction between words with similarities that are not easily identifiable. Students in this stage are mostly adolescents usually between the ages of 12 and 16 and are referred to as '*Titibiri*' in Hausa Language
- iii. **Zube Stage:** this is a stage where pupils are made to copy and read the whole of the Qur'an in parts from the last chapter to the top one without the demand for memorization. The aim here was to make the recitation of the Holy Qur'an softer and flow well and to improve the writing skills of the learners. '*Gardi*' which is for students from 17 years,
- iv. **Haddatu Stage:** this is an advanced stage where pupils start the segment of memorization of the Glorious Qur'an by heart, initially the pupil starts memorizing portions by copying it on a slate and presenting it to the teacher and other experts for corrections and observation, after completing this, the pupil could move to the sequential memorization until the completion of the whole Qur'an. Students in this stage who are referred to as *Alaramma* start from the age of 18 years
- v. **Sātu Stage:** This is the final stage where the student writes parts of the Qur'an from memory without referring to the written text of the Qur'an. The student reads out loud to the hearing of the teacher and other experts around the teacher for orthography writing and recitation. When the writing and recitation are found spotless (clean) the student writes the whole Qur'an off the heart on sheets of paper, which serves as the final dissertation project. Students in this stage are called *Gangaran* and they are from the range of 20 years upward.

The above five stages according to Auta (2021) quoting Adetoro go in line with the category of the pupils which in most cases are based on their ages. The first category is called '*Kolo*' which consists of children aged between 4 and 11 years of age. This is followed by '*Titibiri*' comprising adolescents who are usually between the ages of 12 and 16, '*Gardi*' which is for students from 17 years, *Alaramma* from 18 years, and *Gwani* from 20 years upward.

The integration of Tsangaya Schools

During the pre-colonial era, the tsangaya system was well organized and comprehensively funded by the state from the zakat funds paid by individuals and was under the control of the Emirs. However, with the advent of colonial administration, the emirs were stripped of this responsibility as the colonialists were not interested in the system. Paving the way for the government-funded Western education system popularly known as *Makarantan Boko* Consequently, the tsangaya pupils metamorphosed into what is now known as *Almajirai*, thus creating a vacuum with nobody to take the responsibilities of the Schools. (Auta, 2021).

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As time went on, the *Tsangaya* Scholars took over the responsibilities and deemed it a moral and religious duty to educate these pupils for the sake of Allah. Although funds were scarce and an overwhelming number of pupils to cater to, the system continued to flourish with the support of the immediate community and begging was still not a norm instead they resorted to odd menial jobs to make ends meet. (Bukar and Mangari, 2020).

With the increasing level of poverty in the country, the care of the *Almajiris* became overwhelmingly heavy for the Scholars who were left with no choice but to send these little boys who mostly come from far and near villages without provisions and other essential needs to be moving to houses, streets, motor parks, restaurants, and other public places begging for food.

In its determination to curtail the menace of street begging by children and youth in the name of pursuing Qur'anic Education, the Federal Government introduced the *Tsangaya* Schools integration program in 2010 to ensure that the Qur'anic school or *Tsangaya* Education is integrated into Western education introduced an *Almajiri* Education Program where model *Tsangaya*/*Almajiri* Model schools were established in various parts of the country with most of them concentrated in the Northeast and the Northwest of the country. After the construction of the schools through UBEC, the Federal Government handed them over to their host states through the SUBEBs. The schools according to Amo (2019) were categorized into three models with each model having a varying degree of support and interventions;

Model I schools involve the integration of traditional Qur'anic schools within their original location. There are 101 Model I schools in the country. Statutory facilities provided are a block of two classrooms and furniture, an administrative block including an Office, Store, and Toilets, and a hostel block with pupils' lockers. Others are a recitation hall with store and furniture/mats, VIP Toilets, a borehole with an overhead tank, a guest house, and external walls and fencing.

Model II schools are quite larger than Model I schools and were meant to accommodate more pupils. The 18 Model II schools spread across Nigeria were built to serve a group of Qur'anic schools within their respective states. In addition to them, there are 36 others funded through the (Tertiary) Education Trust Fund. Statutory facilities in such schools are two blocks of 6 classrooms, an administrative block consisting of 5 offices, a library, toilets, a computer room, 2 laboratories, and 2 workshops. Others are staff quarters to accommodate up to 10 members of staff, a hostel block, toilets and laundry, a recitation hall, a hand pump, and a motorized borehole with an overhead tank. Both model I and model II schools were also provided with Beds and Beddings with 50 in each Model I school and 100 in each Model II school. Other infrastructures such as classrooms, pupils' furniture, and teachers' furniture were also provided in each of the schools.

Model III schools are pre-existing *Islamiyyah* and *Ma'ahad* schools supported in terms of rehabilitation and provision of additional infrastructure. Documents from the UBEC and the Federal Ministry of Education did not explicitly state details of such supports as they did for the two other models. One of the documents merely gave the number of Model III schools supported by the Federal government of Nigeria all over the nation as 138 (Amo, 2019).

***Tsangaya* Schools in Bauchi Emirate**

Bauchi Emirate comprises the Alkali, Bauchi, Darazo, Ganjuwa and Toro governments. Being a predominantly Muslim area, the people of the area followed the same pattern of *Tsangaya* Qur'anic schools that are common in most northern Nigeria towns as discussed earlier. According to Ya'u (personal interview on June 23rd March 2022 in Bauchi), it is estimated that there are not less than five hundred *Tsangaya* schools across the seven local governments that are made up of the Emirate. The most popular and oldest among them include:

1. *Tsangaya* of Mallam Garba Gwanki, Bauchi.
2. *Tsangaya* of Alamma Mallam Ya'u Dan Daudawo Bauchi
3. *Tsangaya* of Alamma Mallam Dauda, Jahun Bauchi
4. *Tsangaya* of Alamma Sani Dan Jajere Bakin Kura Bauchi
5. *Tsangaya* of Mallam Ahmadu Kwana Sallah in Doya quarters

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6. *Tsangaya* of Alaramma Mallam Adamu Gudun, Bauchi
7. *Tsangaya* of Alaramma Ahmadu Sabon Fegi Gubi
8. *Tsangaya* of Alaramma Mallam Sani Mai Zube, Jahun Bauchi
9. *Tsangaya* of Alaramma Mallam Adamu Dan Dabirai, Bauchi
10. *Tsangaya* of Malam Adamu Mai Mangoro, Kafin Madaki
11. *Tsangaya* of Alaramma Mallam Yusuf Daudawo, Darazo
12. *Tsangaya* of Mallam Tasi'u Alkaleri
13. *Tsangaya* of Mallam Lawal Limamin Kirfi
14. *Tsangaya* of Mallam Mato Gumau, Toro.

As can be seen, each *Tsangaya* school is named after its founder who is normally the proprietor of the schools, and in line with the tradition earlier discussed, pupils have enrolled in the system on average from the age of 7 and after passing through the stages and upon completion of memorization of the glorious Qur'an students are normally returned to their parents and a graduation ceremony popularly known as *Saukar Karatu* is usually organized by the parents as a mark of appreciation and gratitude to Allah.

Besides these, there are four Model *Tsangaya* Schools built by the federal government in Bauchi Emirate through its *Tsangaya* Schools integration Program:

1. *Tsangaya* Model School Buzaye Bauchi LGA (Model I)
2. *Tsangaya* Model School Dungulbi Bauchi L.G.A.... (Boarding ETF)
3. Model Almajiri School, Darazo LGA (Model II)
4. *Tsangaya* of Mallam Māto Gumau, Toro LGA.

Challenges facing *Tsangaya* Schools in Bauchi Emirate

In his submission Idris (2022) has identified poor feeding and, overpopulation among others as some of the challenges bedeviling the *tsangaya* schools in Nigeria, in Bauchi Emirate some of the identified challenges facing the *tsangaya* schools include;

1. **Financial constrain:** In the general absence of earnings, the *Tsangaya* teachers do not have enough funds to take good care of their families; they house many pupils at a time without provisions of food, and shelter. The study discovered that the *Tsangaya* teachers are enduring critical financial difficulties. They lack resources to take good care of their immediate needs and those of their families, such as enough healthy food, medical bills, housing, transportation and many more. According to Mallam Mu'awiya (personal interview on 2nd December 2023), despite their financial constraints, some *tsangaya* teachers had to take the pain of sourcing some money, to settle the medical bills of their pupils, because some parents wouldn't bother to check their children after they sent them to the *Tsangaya* School.
2. **Lack of recognition by the government and the society:** One of the most pervasive problems of the *tsangaya* schools in Bauchi Emirate in our view is the lack of full recognition by the government and the community. The system does not occupy any meaningful position in the educational policy of the state therefore those who pass through it are not considered the same as those who pass through Western education schools. According to Ya'u, (personal interview, June 23rd March, 2022)" we are not being given recognition by the Government and the community in terms of assistance. It is only a few individuals within the metropolis that still send their children to the *Tsangaya* schools." Most of the participants of such schools are from rural areas, so that's why nobody deems it necessary to rescue the schools. Another factor according to Mallam Mu'awuya is that most people consider the formal school more important than the *tsangaya* schools which explains why they are reluctant to assist them. (Personal interview with Alaramma Mallam Mu'awiya on 3rd December 2023).
3. **Lack of proper funding:** Perhaps due to the lack of recognition from the government and the public in general none of the *tsangaya* receives any form of funding from the various governments. The *Tsangaya* schools are not funded by the Government or individuals for the running of their schools or catering for the welfare of their pupils. They are all funded by the individual efforts of the founders with little support from a few individuals/ (personal

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interview with Alaramma Yusuf Umar on 9th April 2022 in Bauchi.). The little efforts from the federal government through the Universal Basic Education Commission and some NGOs through the construction of hostels are grossly inadequate to cater for the teeming number of Tsangaya schools in the emirate. According to him in the Bauchi metropolis alone which has over two hundred Tsangaya schools only about ten Tsangaya schools got government intervention through the construction of inadequate hostels for their students.

4. **Welfare Problems:** The welfare problems especially those faced by the students of Tsangaya schools (*almajirai*) according to (Ya'u) are multifarious (personal interview). First, they are generally homeless with no accommodation. In about twenty sampled Tsangaya schools visited by the researchers in the Bauchi metropolis, it is discovered that there is no infrastructure other than the house of the *alaramma*, the *almajirai* sleep in the outer rooms of the *alaramma*'s house, in congested rented stalls, or uncompleted buildings. In some cases, there are some selected tsangaya schools such as the tsangaya of Mallam Ya'u Dan Daudawo in Kofar Dumi quarters in Bauchi, the tsangaya of Mallam Sha'aya'u in Jahun quarter, the Tsangaya of Gwani Garba in Kobi Quarters also in Bauchi were some buildings were erected through the intervention of the Universal Basic Education Commission (UBEC) (personal interview with Alaramma Yusuf Umar on 9th April 2022 in Bauchi.). Secondly, most of the *Almajirai* have to beg to get food. Only a few tsangaya schools such as the tsangaya of Sheikh Abdulkadir Musa Jahun and that of Liman Mallam Inuwa Jahun where we discovered that their students don't engage in begging for food. The disadvantages of begging by *almajirai* are numerous. In addition to wasting away a large chunk of their time that they could have used in their Qur'anic studies, begging also exposes them to all sorts of deviant behaviour and immoral practices. Thirdly, as mentioned earlier, most of the *tsangaya* schools *almajirai* have no form of healthcare facility whatsoever (Haruna & Bari, 2019). When they become sick, their *alaramma* does not have the financial capacity to take them to hospitals or even buy drugs for them. Fourthly, most of the *almajirai* do not enjoy other necessities of life such as clothing, shoes, and bedding materials. This is why they are always seen barefooted and in tattered clothes thus, leaving most of them in perpetual dirt with the resultant increased risk of diseases.
5. **Inadequacy and neglect of the Tsangaya integrated schools:** The inadequate number of newly constructed model Tsangaya schools is also another challenge for the Tsangaya schools in the area. According to Alaramma Ya'u (personal interview, June 23rd March 2022 in Bauchi), the introduction of the *Tsangaya* model schools did not solve the challenges facing the Tsangaya schools in the area because according to him considering the number of *Tsangaya* schools in the emirate (which according to him are over 500) four Tsangaya model schools are grossly inadequate. Our investigation shows that out of the four Tsangaya model schools in Bauchi emirate only that of Buzaye in Bauchi local government is properly functional. Poor or lack of maintenance of the existing schools, non-regular payment of salaries and allowances, improper medical facilities, and absence of a feeding program, among others are some of the problems that bedevilled the smooth running of the schools. (Mallam Jamilu Yahaya personal interview on 24th Nay 202222 in Bauchi)

Conclusion

The *Tsangaya* system of education is an Islamic educational system that had existed for several centuries in Northern Nigerian Muslim Communities before the arrival of the British colonialists. The system which graduated many Islamic scholars continued to flourish with the support of the traditional institutions and the immediate community. The traditional arrangement of the *Tsangaya* Qur'anic schools in the Bauchi Emirate is not different from what is obtainable in other *Tsangaya* schools in other states in Northern Nigeria. It has been clearly explained in the write-up that the *tsangaya* system in Bauchi Emirate is facing a lot of challenges. These challenges vary from the poor physical infrastructure that exists in most of the schools to limited curricula to the lack of recognition of the system down to the very deplorable welfare conditions of the *Almajirai* unless these challenges are promptly addressed; they are likely to have disastrous consequences to the development of the emirate and the state in general.

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Recommendations

Given the foregoing explanations on the challenges and conditions of Tsangaya/Qur'anic schools in Bauchi Emirate, the following measures are hereby recommended as a solution for effective sustenance and integration of the Tsangaya/Qur'anic schools in Bauchi Emirate.

1. While all stakeholders have important roles to play in solving these problems the role of the Government in collaboration with the rich people and other voluntary donor agencies is very critical. Needless to say, there is a need for strong political will on the part of the various arms and levels of government which should translate into good policy formulation, appropriate legislation, proper funding, and strong implementation.
2. There is a need for Islamic scholars and Muslim societies to enlighten the Muslims especially the wealthy on the virtue of philanthropy by assisting the tsangaya schools either through the erection of physical structures, provision of food items and other incentives to both the teachers and pupils, this will go a long way in ameliorating some of the challenges bedevilling the tsangaya schools in Bauchi Emirate.
3. In the same vein, Muslim groups, societies and Islamic scholars should intensify efforts to enlighten the Muslim Ummah on the institution of *Waqf* and the need for its establishment so that the tsangaya schools can be managed and funded properly through its proceeds.
4. The stakeholders should cautiously compose an implementable curriculum for the Tsangaya schools and it should contain some aspect of skills acquisition and entrepreneurship. Qualified personnel to train the teachers and their pupils should be hired. The trade skills might include depending on the participants; Carpentry, Tailoring, Shoemaking, Islamic calligraphy, electrical installation, and computers. This will in our view provide job opportunities for the products of these Qur'anic schools.

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Application of ICT-Skills and E-Learning Facilities in Transforming Social Studies Classroom at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

Muhammad, Nasa'i¹

Email: muhdnasai@gmail.com & nmuhammad@abu.edu.ng

Tel: 07036167422

Ismaila, Babangida¹

Email: Babangidaismaila66@gmail.com & P21edas8034@abu.edu.ng

Tel: 08030548281

Sule Hussaini Ibrahim²

Email: Hussainiibrahimsule1@gmail.com

Tel: 08037383109

Department of Arts and Social Science Education, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria
Distance Learning Centre, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria

Abstract

This study offered a thorough exploration of the integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) skills and e-learning facilities in Social Studies classrooms at the secondary school level in Nigeria. Through a comprehensive literature review spanning from 2013 to 2023, the research investigated the transformative potential of technology in reshaping teaching methodologies, student engagement, and the cultivation of digital literacy skills. The findings underscored the challenges of the digital divide, teacher preparedness, and the need for ongoing technical support. Recommendations emanating from the study emphasized the urgency of investing in ICT infrastructure to bridge the digital divide, instituting comprehensive teacher training programs to enhance educators' ICT competencies, providing strategic technical support systems, promoting collaborative learning platforms, and advocating for flexible policy frameworks to adapt to the dynamic nature of educational technology. The study contributes valuable insights to the discourse on educational technology in the context of Nigerian secondary schools, serving as a foundation for informed strategies to harness the benefits of ICT while addressing the identified challenges. Ultimately, this research aimed to guide policymakers, educators, and stakeholders in fostering an inclusive, technology-enhanced learning environment in Social Studies classrooms, aligning with the demands of the 21st-century educational landscape in Nigeria.

Keywords: Information and Communication Technology (ICT), E-learning facilities, Social Studies education, Secondary school level

Introduction

In the contemporary landscape of education, the integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has emerged as a transformative force, reshaping traditional pedagogical approaches (UNESCO, 2013). This study delves into the profound implications of applying ICT skills and leveraging e-learning facilities to enhance the educational experience within the realm of Social Studies at the secondary school level, particularly in the context of Nigeria. As Nigeria grapples with the challenges of providing quality education to its burgeoning youth population (World Bank, 2018), the Secondary School level becomes a critical juncture in a student's academic journey. Social Studies, being integral to holistic education, offers a strategic lens for examining the transformative impact of ICT and e-learning tools on educational practices and outcomes. The Information and Communication Technology (ICT) revolution has ushered in an era where traditional boundaries of classrooms are expanding, transcending the limitations of physical spaces (Selwyn, 2020). Embracing this technological paradigm shift in Social Studies classrooms holds promise for revitalizing the learning experience. Integrating ICT skills into the curriculum enables educators to present

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information in innovative and interactive ways, fostering critical thinking, and collaborative problem-solving, and digital literacy among students (Davis & Tearle, 1999). Additionally, the advent of e-learning facilities offers opportunities for personalized and self-paced learning, catering to the diverse needs and learning styles of students in Nigeria's secondary schools (Ally, 2008).

Meanwhile, E-facilities and skills for Information and Communication Technology had a significant impact on several elements of teaching and learning, affecting both teachers and students in transforming Nigerian Social Studies Classroom. The teachers experienced issues such as a deficiency in information communication technology (ICT) skills, a lack of readiness to utilize online tools, a low level of confidence in conducting online courses, and a lack of understanding of how to incorporate technology into classrooms (Boonmoh et al., 2022). The low level of ICT skills and lack of readiness to utilize E-facilities; made it harder for teachers to create online courses, produce online teaching materials, and modify content to meet changing demands. According to Agbo, (2015) the technology involves the generation of knowledge and processes to develop systems that solve problems and extend human capabilities. In other words, technology can change or alter how people access, gather, analyze, present, transmit, and simulate information. Schools, like all other social institutions, are rapidly embracing information and communication technologies (ICT). Recent research underscores the evolving role of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in education, emphasizing its significance beyond being a mere tool or a replacement for traditional teaching methods. Contemporary perspectives position ICT as a crucial instrument supporting innovative approaches to teaching and learning, with an emphasis on fostering students' skills for collaboration, communication, problem-solving, and lifelong learning (Mann, 2020; Kirschner & De Bruyckere, 2017). The transformative potential of ICT lies in its ability to not only provide increased access to information but also to inspire novel teaching methodologies, facilitating continuous interaction within and beyond the confines of traditional classroom settings (UNESCO, 2019).

While disputes regarding the efficacy of incorporating ICT in education persist, recent studies highlight that the limited use of ICT is not solely attributed to debates over its value but is also influenced by the inadequate availability of ICT resources within schools (Cuban & Pea, 2017; Ottenbreit-Leftwich et al., 2018). Additionally, the dynamics within the typical classroom, encompassing the prevailing realities and cultural aspects (Ekpiwre & Haruna, 2019), along with the knowledge, skills, beliefs, and expertise of teachers, play pivotal roles in shaping the successful integration of ICT into educational practices (Ertmer et al., 2018; Knezek & Christensen, 2019). Furthermore, the non-availability of E-resources further compounds the challenges associated with harnessing the full potential of ICT in education (Owusu-Fordjour et al., 2020). This study seeks to scrutinize the current state of Social Studies education in Nigerian secondary schools, evaluating the extent to which ICT skills and e-learning facilities are integrated into the curriculum. Moreover, it aims to explore the challenges faced by educators in adopting these technologies and the perceptions of students towards this modernized approach to learning. By investigating these aspects, the research endeavours to provide insights into the potential benefits and drawbacks of incorporating ICT in Social Studies classrooms, contributing to the discourse on education reform in Nigeria. As technology continues to evolve, understanding its role in transforming education becomes imperative, and this study strives to shed light on the specific nuances within the Nigerian secondary school context.

Methodology

The present study employed a comprehensive literature review methodology to explore the application of ICT skills and e-learning facilities in transforming Social Studies classrooms at the secondary school level of education in Nigeria. This methodology involved a systematic and critical analysis of existing secondary sources, scholarly articles, academic journals, books, and relevant publications from the years 2013 to 2023. The purpose was to synthesize and evaluate the then-current state of knowledge, identify key trends, challenges, and opportunities, and contribute to the existing discourse on the integration of technology in Social Studies education.

1. **Literature Search and Selection:** A thorough literature search was conducted using academic databases such as PubMed, JSTOR, Google Scholar, and educational research databases. The search focused on studies, articles, and publications related to the integration of ICT skills and e-learning facilities in Social Studies classrooms at the secondary school level in Nigeria.
2. **Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria:** The inclusion criteria for selecting literature involved relevance to the study's focus, publication between 2013 and 2023, and a focus on secondary education in Nigeria. Exclusion criteria

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- involved studies outside the specified timeframe, those not directly related to ICT in Social Studies education, and those not conducted within the Nigerian context.
3. **Data Extraction and Synthesis:** Pertinent information, including key findings, methodologies employed in the primary studies, and limitations, was extracted from the selected literature. The data was then synthesized to identify patterns, recurring themes, and gaps in the existing knowledge base.
 4. **Quality Assessment:** The quality and rigor of the selected literature were assessed using established criteria for evaluating academic sources. This ensured that the synthesized information was based on reliable and valid research.
 5. **Thematic Analysis:** The identified literature was thematically analysed to categorize findings related to the application of ICT skills and e-learning facilities in Social Studies classrooms. This process helped in identifying the common challenges faced, successful strategies employed, and potential areas for further research.
 6. **Ethical Considerations:** Since this study relied on existing literature, ethical considerations primarily involved proper citation and adherence to copyright regulations. All sources were appropriately credited to maintain academic integrity.

Intersection of Social Studies Classroom Dynamics and ICT Integration in Secondary Education

The concept of the Social Studies classroom at the secondary school level has been a subject of considerable scholarly exploration, with an emphasis on understanding its dynamics, challenges, and opportunities. Researchers have delved into the multifaceted nature of Social Studies education, recognizing it as a discipline that plays a pivotal role in shaping students' understanding of societal structures, cultural diversity, and global interconnectedness (Davies, 2013; Clark & Erikson, 2018). The secondary school level, being a critical stage in the educational journey, represents a juncture where students develop a more nuanced comprehension of social issues, civic responsibilities, and historical contexts through the lens of Social Studies.

Several studies have examined the traditional structure of Social Studies classrooms, often characterized by teacher-centred instructional methods and content-focused approaches (Crawford, 2014; Akpan, 2019). Scholars have highlighted the need for a shift toward more interactive, student-centred pedagogies that promote critical thinking, active engagement, and the development of skills essential for informed citizenship (Sawyer & White, 2013; Thornton, 2016). This shift aligns with the broader goals of Social Studies education, aiming to cultivate a generation of individuals capable of navigating complex societal issues and contributing meaningfully to their communities.

The integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and e-learning tools into the Social Studies classroom has emerged as a focal point in recent literature. Researchers underscore the potential of these technologies to enhance the learning experience, providing opportunities for interactive, dynamic, and learner-centric instruction (Ferdig & Kennedy, 2014; Owusu-Fordjour et al., 2021). The application of ICT in Social Studies classrooms at the secondary level has been associated with improved information access, collaborative learning environments, and the development of digital literacy skills crucial for the 21st-century learner (Pelgrum & Anderson, 2017; Voogt et al., 2018). Despite these advancements, challenges persist, and the literature reflects ongoing discussions on issues such as the digital divide, teacher preparedness, and the need for effective professional development to integrate ICT seamlessly into Social Studies classrooms (Kozma, 2015; Baran, 2014; Tondeur et al., 2017). Understanding the existing literature on the concept of Social Studies classrooms at the secondary school level provides a foundation for the current study, which aims to contribute to this discourse by investigating the specific implications and challenges of applying ICT skills and e-learning facilities within the Nigerian educational context. This study seeks to build upon the insights gleaned from the existing literature to inform practical strategies for transforming Social Studies education in secondary schools through the judicious incorporation of modern technological tools.

Review of E-Facilities for Social Studies Classrooms at the Secondary School Level

The exploration of e-facilities for the Social Studies classroom at the secondary school level has been a prominent focus in educational literature, reflecting the increasing recognition of technology's transformative potential in shaping contemporary pedagogical landscapes. Scholars have classified e-facilities into various types, each offering unique opportunities for enhancing the learning experience within the realm of Social Studies. One significant type of

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e-facility is the use of online resources and digital content. Researchers have extensively discussed the benefits of leveraging digital platforms to provide students with access to a vast array of historical documents, multimedia content, and interactive simulations (Berson et al., 2019; Hicks, 2017). These resources not only broaden the scope of learning materials but also cater to diverse learning styles, fostering a more inclusive educational environment.

Virtual Learning Environments (VLEs) have also gained prominence in the literature, presenting comprehensive platforms that facilitate a dynamic and collaborative online space for Social Studies education (Dennen et al., 2013; Ertmer et al., 2019). VLEs incorporate features such as discussion forums, multimedia presentations, and assessment tools, allowing students to engage in meaningful discourse, collaborative projects, and self-paced learning. The integration of VLEs aligns with the contemporary shift toward learner-centred approaches, promoting active participation and critical thinking skills. Simulations and educational games represent another facet of e-facilities in the Social Studies classroom. The literature highlights the potential of simulation software and games to immerse students in historical events, fostering experiential learning and a deeper understanding of complex social issues (Shaffer, 2016; Clark, 2018). These interactive tools not only make learning more engaging but also encourage the development of problem-solving skills and historical empathy. Furthermore, video conferencing and online collaboration tools have emerged as essential e-facilities, particularly in the context of global connectivity and remote learning (Kimmons et al., 2020). These tools facilitate virtual guest lectures, cross-cultural exchanges, and collaborative projects, enriching the Social Studies curriculum with real-world perspectives and diverse cultural insights.

However, despite the evident advantages, literature also underscores challenges associated with the implementation of e-facilities, including issues related to digital equity, teacher training, and the need for continuous technical support (Jacobsen & Mackey, 2016; Hobbs, 2017). Understanding the diverse types of e-facilities available for Social Studies classrooms at the secondary school level is crucial for educators and policymakers, guiding the thoughtful integration of technology to create enriched and inclusive learning environments. This discussion lays the foundation for the subsequent exploration of how these e-facilities can be applied within the Nigerian educational context, emphasizing the potential for transformative impacts on Social Studies education.

Benefits of E-Resources for Social Studies Teachers at the Secondary School Level

The literature surrounding the benefits of e-resources, particularly online teaching facilities, for Social Studies teachers at the secondary school level is rich with insights into how technology can positively impact the teaching-learning dynamic. Researchers have extensively explored the advantages that e-resources bring to the teaching practices of Social Studies educators, highlighting transformative effects on instructional methods, student engagement, and overall learning outcomes.

One paramount benefit emphasized in the literature is the expanded access to diverse and up-to-date learning materials. E-resources empower Social Studies teachers to augment their curricula with a plethora of digital content, ranging from primary source documents and multimedia presentations to virtual field trips and interactive simulations (Mason & Berson, 2020; Hicks, 2015). This not only broadens the scope of materials available but also enables educators to adapt their teaching to current events and evolving societal dynamics. The interactive nature of e-resources stands out as a transformative factor in Social Studies education. Online teaching facilities provide tools for creating dynamic and engaging lessons that cater to diverse learning styles (Lee & Spires, 2022; Baran et al., 2013). The incorporation of multimedia elements, interactive maps, and virtual experiences not only captures students' attention but also facilitates a deeper understanding of complex historical and social concepts. Teachers can leverage these resources to foster critical thinking skills and promote a more participatory classroom environment.

Moreover, the collaborative potential of e-resources has been a recurrent theme in the literature. Online platforms and tools enable Social Studies teachers to engage students in collaborative projects, discussions, and global connections (Brush et al., 2018; Whitworth et al., 2019). This collaborative aspect aligns with the broader goals of Social Studies education, fostering a sense of community and encouraging students to appreciate diverse perspectives, both locally and globally. The efficiency and flexibility offered by e-resources for lesson planning and delivery have been underscored as crucial advantages. Teachers can access and organize a wealth of resources, customize materials to suit specific learning objectives, and employ various assessment tools to gauge student understanding (Doering et al., 2019; Voogt et al., 2013). This streamlining of administrative tasks allows educators to allocate more time to

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engaging with students and tailoring their teaching to individual needs. However, the literature also acknowledges challenges, such as the need for teacher training, concerns about digital equity, and potential distractions in the online environment (Graham et al., 2022; Niess, 2013). Addressing these challenges is essential to fully harness the benefits of e-resources in Social Studies classrooms at the secondary school level.

Impact of ICT Skills for Secondary School Social Studies Teachers

The literature on the benefits of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) skills for Social Studies teachers at the secondary school level highlights the transformative impact that technological proficiency can have on teaching practices, professional development, and overall educational outcomes. Researchers have explored the multifaceted advantages that accrue to educators equipped with ICT skills, recognizing them as instrumental in navigating the complexities of contemporary education. One overarching benefit identified in the literature is the enhancement of teaching methodologies through the integration of ICT skills. Social Studies teachers with adept ICT skills can employ a variety of digital tools and resources to create interactive and engaging lessons (Cuban & Pea, 2017; Chai et al., 2020). Incorporating multimedia presentations, virtual field trips, and interactive simulations not only captures students' interest but also facilitates a deeper understanding of complex social concepts and historical events. Professional development for Social Studies teachers is another key area emphasized in the literature. ICT skills empower educators to participate in ongoing training programs, online communities, and collaborative networks, fostering a culture of continuous learning (Ertmer et al., 2022). This not only keeps teachers abreast of the latest pedagogical approaches but also allows them to share best practices and innovative strategies with their peers. The literature also highlights the role of ICT skills in promoting personalized learning experiences for students. Social Studies teachers equipped with ICT skills can tailor their instruction to accommodate diverse learning styles and abilities (Ertmer et al., 2022; Voogt et al., 2017). Adaptive technologies, online resources, and digital platforms enable educators to address individual needs, providing a more inclusive and student-centric learning environment. Moreover, the acquisition of ICT skills contributes to the development of digital literacy among both teachers and students. Social Studies educators' proficiency in ICT can guide students in navigating the vast digital landscape, critically evaluating online information, and leveraging technology for research and communication (Ritzhaupt et al., 2013; Knezek & Christensen, 2019). This not only prepares students for the demands of the digital age but also cultivates essential skills for active citizenship.

However, challenges related to the digital divide, resistance to change, and the need for comprehensive teacher training are acknowledged in the literature (Ertmer, 2015; Tondeur et al., 2019). Bridging these gaps is imperative to ensure equitable access to the benefits of ICT skills for Social Studies teachers at the secondary school level. The literature review therefore underscores the pivotal role of ICT skills in empowering Social Studies teachers to adapt to the evolving educational landscape. Beyond enriching teaching methodologies, these skills contribute to ongoing professional development, personalized learning, and the cultivation of digital literacy—all essential components for preparing students for an interconnected and technology-driven world.

Challenges in Implementing E-Facilities and ICT Skills in Secondary School Social Studies Classrooms

The literature examining the challenges of e-facilities and ICT skills for Social Studies classrooms at the secondary school level sheds light on the complexities associated with integrating technology into educational practices. Researchers have identified several hurdles that educators face, encompassing both the availability of e-facilities and the development and utilization of ICT skills. One pervasive challenge highlighted in the literature is the digital divide, reflecting disparities in access to technology among students. In many instances, schools may lack the necessary infrastructure and resources to provide consistent access to e-facilities, hindering the implementation of technology-enhanced teaching (Warschauer, 2016; Pelgrum & Anderson, 2017). Moreover, issues of socioeconomic status and geographical location contribute to inequities in students' access to digital tools, exacerbating disparities in educational outcomes. Teacher preparedness and professional development constitute another significant challenge. While technology has the potential to revolutionize teaching practices, many educators may lack the necessary ICT skills and training to effectively integrate e-facilities into their classrooms (Ertmer et al., 2022; Tondeur et al., 2017). Insufficient professional development opportunities and a resistance to change further compound this challenge, hindering the seamless adoption of technology in Social Studies education. The literature also emphasizes the need

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for ongoing technical support and maintenance of e-facilities. Technological glitches, system failures, and the rapid pace of technological advancements necessitate continuous support to ensure that e-facilities function optimally within the classroom environment (Ottenbreit-Leftwich et al., 2022; Elyan & Adwan, 2019). Without adequate technical assistance, educators may face disruptions that impede the smooth flow of lessons and compromise the learning experience.

Furthermore, issues related to the integration of e-facilities with traditional pedagogical methods are discussed in the literature. Balancing the use of technology with other instructional strategies and ensuring that it aligns with curriculum objectives can be a delicate task (Sandholtz et al., 2014; Hew & Brush, 2022). There is a concern that overemphasis on technology may lead to a superficial integration rather than a meaningful transformation of teaching and learning practices in the Social Studies classroom. The rapid evolution of technology introduces a temporal challenge, making it challenging for educators to stay abreast of the latest advancements and incorporate them effectively into their teaching (Kozma, 2015; Voogt & Roblin, 2022). This dynamic nature of technology requires educators to engage in continuous learning and adaptability, placing additional demands on their time and resources.

Other challenges include among others, the following:

- vi. High Cost of ICT Facilities
- vii. Inadequate ICT Infrastructural Facilities in Schools
- viii. Poor Computer Literacy among Teachers and Students
- ix. Poor Implementation of ICT Educational Policies
- x. Unstable Power Supply
- xi. Inadequate Funding

Conclusion

The comprehensive literature review undertaken in this study has illuminated the intricate landscape of integrating ICT skills and e-learning facilities in Social Studies classrooms at the secondary school level in Nigeria. The analysis revealed the transformative potential of technology in enhancing teaching methodologies, fostering student engagement, and cultivating digital literacy skills. However, challenges such as the digital divide, teacher preparedness, and the need for ongoing technical support were identified as significant hurdles. The findings underscore the imperative for a nuanced approach to technology integration, emphasizing equitable access, continuous professional development, and strategic solutions to overcome existing challenges. This study contributes to the broader discourse on educational technology by providing valuable insights into the specific context of Social Studies education in Nigerian secondary schools, laying the groundwork for informed strategies to harness the benefits of ICT and e-learning facilities while addressing associated challenges.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made:

1. Given the challenges associated with the digital divide, policymakers and educational institutions should prioritize substantial investments in ICT infrastructure. Ensuring equitable access to e-learning facilities is essential for creating an inclusive educational environment, especially in regions where technological resources are scarce.
2. To address the identified challenges related to teacher preparedness and professional development, educational authorities should implement comprehensive and ongoing training programs. These initiatives should focus on enhancing teachers' ICT skills, integrating technology into pedagogical practices, and navigating the evolving digital landscape, ultimately fostering a cadre of educators well-equipped for technology-enhanced instruction.
3. Recognizing the need for continuous technical support, educational institutions should establish robust mechanisms to address technological glitches and provide timely assistance to teachers. This includes creating dedicated support teams, establishing helpdesk services, and fostering partnerships with technology experts to ensure the smooth functioning of e-learning facilities.

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4. Policymakers should develop flexible and adaptive policy frameworks that acknowledge the dynamic nature of educational technology. Such frameworks should provide guidance on the integration of ICT in Social Studies classrooms, incentivize innovative approaches, and be responsive to emerging challenges and opportunities, allowing for continuous adaptation to the evolving educational landscape.

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Artificial Intelligence-Based Adaptive Learning: A Tool for Effective Teaching and Learning at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

Suleiman, Aishatu Umar¹

Email: aishasuleimanumar3@gmail.com

Tel: 08035741800

Yahaya, Dauda²

Email: daudayahaya97@gmail.com

Tel: 08036587824

Abubakar, Dalhatu³

Email: dalhatabibakareen007@gmail.com

Tel: 07034994181

¹Department of Educational Foundations and Curriculum, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria.

²Department of Arts and Social Science Education, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria.

³Registry Department, Federal College of Education (Technical) Gusau.

Abstract

Artificial intelligent in educational classrooms for effective instructions; opened up new possibilities for students' and teachers in teaching and learning process at Secondary School level of education in Nigeria. This paper explores the effective teaching and learning at secondary school level of education in Nigeria, using artificial intelligence-based adaptive learning: by determining adaptive learning experiences to learners, promoting teaching and learning as well as curriculum development. Artificial Intelligence has become an indispensable tool for teaching and learning, offering teachers the means to adapt, engage, and personalize learning experiences for students. The researchers delve into pivotal role of AI-based adaptive learning platform in enhancing student engagement and learning outcomes within instructional settings that aids to fill the gaps in education.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, Ai-based adaptive learning, AI at secondary school level.

Introduction

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) usage contributes to the transformation of the learning process towards a student-centered learning environment (Hafa, Moubtassim, 2021). Thus, to determine the benefits of AI-based learning platform on students, it is crucial to look into students' engagement in using AI technology in their learning practice. This study will explore the effectiveness of AI-based adaptive learning platforms on teaching and learning practices at secondary school level of education; traditional classroom settings often struggle to address the individual needs and learning pace of students due to large class sizes and limited resources. The implementation of AI-based adaptive learning platforms has the potential to revolutionize education in Nigeria, enhancing student engagement, motivation, and ultimately, their academic performance. Reports from UNESCO (Miao et al., 2021) and OECD (2021) provide evidence of the potential of AI to improve education by automating various aspects of teaching (e.g., administrative tasks, assessment, evaluation), personalizing learning (e.g., intelligent tutoring systems), and making available new tools (e.g., virtual reality, augmented reality).

Over the last decade, researchers have examined the use of AI in teaching and learning for different purposes. For example, quite a few researchers examined the use of AI applications such as intelligent tutoring systems, virtual reality, and teaching evaluation (Chassignol et al., 2018; Gerard et al., 2015; Guan et al., 2020; Parsia et al., 2020; Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019; Zhai et al., 2020), as well as the use of more general pedagogical methods (game based learning, collaborative learning) in teaching and learning in various contexts and disciplines (Bozkurt et al., 2021; Feng & Law, 2021; ZawackiRichter et al., 2019). In all these practices, Artificial intelligence deployed to improves teaching and learning at secondary school level of education in Nigeria; for effective global practices of instructions.

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What is Concept of Artificial intelligence?

John McCarthy introduced the term Artificial Intelligence in the 1950s, defining it as “the science and engineering of making intelligent machines”. Since then, the field has evolved and so has the definition of AI. Currently, there is no single universal definition of AI. This is partially due to the rapid development of the field, but also because researchers outside of computer science, in the areas of education, healthcare, philosophy, economics, and arts have taken a great interest in AI and its application. Each of these research fields has modified the term AI to its own needs and uses, and this interdisciplinary nature of AI makes it difficult to establish a consensus about what AI is.

Popenici and Kerr (2017), who define AI as “computing systems that are able to engage in human-like processes such as learning, adapting, synthesizing, self-correcting and use of data for complex processing tasks” Artificial Intelligence (AI) can be defined as a system that has been designed to interact with the world in difference ways we may think of as human and intelligent. The line of, Ample data, cheap computing and AI algorithms mean technology can learn very quickly. The transformative power of AI cuts across all sectors, including education (UNESCO, 2019). AI will change learning, teaching, and educational classrooms situation. The speed of technological change will be very fast, and it will create high level to transform educational practices, institutions, and policies." Therefore, provision of AI-based working environment promotes learning, teaching, education and curriculum development as well as policy development.

Artificial Intelligence as an Adaptive Learning Facility in Educational Classrooms at Secondary School level of Education in Nigeria

On January 1st, 1997, the International Artificial Intelligence in Education Society (AIED) was established. By hosting the International Journal of AI in Education (IJAIED) and AIED conference series, it brings researchers together. There are four main areas of AIED in institutional and administrative services, academic support services, and services that promote learning, including profiling and prediction, assessment and evaluation, adaptive systems, personalization, and intelligent tutoring systems. The application of AI is both inventive and derived. A new technology called artificial intelligence has begun to alter educational resources and curriculum organizations. The ideal educational practice in the sphere of education requires the presence of teachers. The employment of teachers, who are vital to the educational system, is altered by the development of artificial intelligence. The AI primarily employs deep learning, machine learning, and advanced analytics to track a specific person's relative speed to other people.

AI is capable of customizing the academic curriculum. With the use of AI-Based adaptive learning platform, worldwide classrooms can accommodate students who have hearing or vision impairments. Students who are ill and unable to attend class can also benefit from this. Additionally, AI aids in providing advice on how to close learning gaps. Makes learning easier and instructions effective (Pujari, 2022). AI may also be used for admissions and enrolment procedures, while its full potential it still developing. AI can aid students in their home study habits and exam readings. Future AI will be able to respond to various learning styles, the like of convergent, divergent, impulsive and flexible learning styles, among others to mentioned, but a few to achieve the objectives.

Application of AI as a Learning Partner in Educational Classroom At Secondary School level of Education

AI technologies have brought a paradigm shift in educational classrooms, creating possibilities for personalized learning, data-driven decision-making, and innovative pedagogical approaches (Oliveira, et al., 2019, Grimus, 2020). AI-based adaptive learning platforms have been implemented in various regions worldwide, showcasing their effectiveness in improving students learning, skills and experiences. Therefore, the most common AI-enabled educational applications, and one none AI-enabled application. Intelligent Tutoring Systems (ITS) are an AI application as they provide personalized and adaptive instruction to learners. ITS take on the role of a human tutor, by offering guidance, feedback, and support to learners; It does so, using AI techniques to capture learner’s strengths, weaknesses, and progress. By adapting the learning content, difficulty level, and feedback, to these learning traits of each individual user, the learning experience is then optimized.

Application of AI as a Learning Material in Educational Classroom at Secondary School level of Education in Nigeria

The integration of AI in educational classrooms has potential for optimizing administrative processes, providing instructional resources, yielding efficiency and cost-effectiveness, as evidenced by scholarly research (Klutka et al., 2018). AI-based adaptive learning platforms can also leverage various learning resources, such as interactive videos, simulations, and gamified elements, to create engaging and immersive learning experiences. AI can be used as a tool by teachers to facilitate the teaching and learning design or to support teachers' scaffolding strategies and to track students' learning progress and

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outcomes (Chounta et.al., 2021; Lindner & Romeiki 2019). The advancement of educational technology and digital platforms such as educational learning applications, Learning Management Systems (LMS) and virtual classrooms can be utilized to assist in the teaching and learning of a language more effectively. Information and Communication Technology (ICT) usage contributes to the transformation of the learning process towards a student-centered environment (Hafa, Moubtassim, 2021). Online Instructional materials that are associated with AI tools and applications; used by students and teachers such as Quizziz, Kahoot, and Google Classroom.

Challenges of AI Technology at Secondary School level of Education in Nigeria

Despite the enormous opportunities AI presents, there may also be some possible challenges. AI has the potential to be either the greatest and friendly evil for humanity. The development of AI applications in educational classrooms has new ethical concerns and risks that could help teaching and learning process. Some of the challenges include:

5. Lack of adequate access to computers and internet connection, therefore technology use is not feasible in classrooms;
6. Need for access to professional development on new technologies like AI;
7. Need for full administrative and peer support on technology integration, result by inadequate technical support;
8. Lack of an understanding of the usefulness and experience of digital technologies (Aduwa-ogiegbaen, 2014; johnson et al., 2016).

Benefits of AI Technology at Secondary School level of Education in Nigeria

AI can affect teaching and learning. AI can be used to shape the education and instructional process, through for example, digital assistants which support the teacher in teaching in the classroom. AI can undertake administrative tasks, freeing teachers for more time supporting learners. In the school context, there could also be AI-based learning data analysis (Learning Analytics), AI-based individualized learning offers (Adaptive Learning) or AI-based assessment systems (mmb Institut, 2020). despite their specific design, these applications would change learning and instructional process as well students' development.

Another impact for students in educational classroom is that the transformative power of AI promises profound changes in instructional strategy and resources. AI improves changes in initial and continuing training for teachers and students in educational environment. Therefore, the AI-based tools for teaching and learning can be used in the classroom to improve the quality of the instructional delivery. Also, AI can address certain challenges or consequences of the increased use of technology in the classroom. AI technologies are organized in schools to prepare 'learners' for an AI-based working environment.

Therefore, the learning styles and behavioral patterns of students can be analyzed by AI-based adaptive learning systems, which can then offer them content, exercises, and tests that are specifically tailored to the students' needs. Additionally, teachers can track students' development more precisely and offer targeted help as required. AI-based adaptive learning is a growingly popular option for schools and universities throughout the world due to its potential to increase student engagement and outcomes. The use of artificial intelligence (AI) tools to customize server education and training for groups of learners is referred to as server customization education.

Conclusion

AI-based Adaptive learning have the potential to revolutionize the way education is delivered, administered, and researched, leading to more efficient and effective instructional experiences for students and teachers. While the impact of AI-based adaptive learning in educational classrooms, include personalized learning, adaptive assessments, improved student engagement, enhanced administrative processes, and research capabilities, there are also certain improvement in the quality of instructional process and provision of AI-based working environment for learners. In the 21st century academic era and beyond, AI-based adaptive learning platform remains a dynamic and transformative to education; shaping the future of learning.

Recommendations

On the bases of the above discussions, the following recommendations are made:

1. AI technology often address the individual needs and learning pace of students with limited resources.
2. Enhancement of student's engagement and their academic performance
3. Changing the learning and teaching of educational classrooms situation
4. AI technology aids in the provision onto fill the learning gaps

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Assessment of Awareness on Antenatal Care Service Delivery among Pregnant Women in North-West, Nigeria

Muhammed, Murtala Jangebe¹

Email: Jangebe2013@gmail.com

Tel: 08034580231

Umar, Mubarak²

Email: mubfta@gmail.com

Tel: 07066660066

Zubairu, Fatima³

Email: fatimazubairuone@gmail.com

Tel: 08030886320

¹School of Health Technology, Tsafe, Zamfara State

²Department of Human Kinetics and Health Education, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria

³Zamfara State College of Art and Science

Abstract

The purpose of this study was to assess awareness of antenatal care service delivery among pregnant women in North-West, Nigeria. To achieve this purpose, the ex-post facto research design was adopted for the study. The population for the study comprised of pregnant women in all the seven (7) states in North-west, Nigeria within the year 2023. Estimated at one million two hundred and twenty-three thousand, five hundred and seventy-one (1,223,571). The sample size for this study consists of 768 pregnant women. The participants were selected using multi-stage sampling techniques. Close-ended questionnaire titled “awareness of antenatal care service delivery among pregnant women” with reliability index (Cronbach Alpha) of 0.859 was used to obtain responses from the respondents. Descriptive statistics of frequencies, percentages, means and standard deviation were used to describe the demographic characteristics of the respondents and to answer the research question. Hypothesis formulated was tested at 0.05 level of significance using one sample t-test. The finding revealed that the pregnant women in North-west zone, Nigeria have no significant awareness of antenatal care services ($p = 0.12$). Thus, it is concluded that pregnant women in North West zone, Nigeria have inadequate awareness on antenatal care service. On the basis of the conclusion the study further recommends that: There should be a practical demonstration of the antenatal talk by health educators to pregnant women as it relates to antenatal care services.

Keyword: awareness, antenatal, pregnant women, antenatal care service delivery.

Introduction

Antenatal care is a medical and general care that is provided to pregnant women during pregnancy and it is goal-oriented provided with the aim of meeting both psychological and medical needs of pregnant women within the context of health care delivery system. The major aim of antenatal care is to ensure that the mother reaches the end of pregnancy as healthy as, or even healthier than she was before the pregnancy (Federal Ministry of Health {FMOH}, 2014). Researches reveal that in many pregnancies there are relatively high proportion of complications and some of which are very serious and of a life-threatening nature (Tochi, *et al* 2022). Good care during pregnancy is important for the health of the mother and the development of the unborn baby. Pregnancy is a crucial time to promote healthy behaviours and parenting skills (Haruna, 2017). Good ANC links the woman and her family with the formal health system, increases the chance of using a skilled attendant at birth and contributes to good health through the life cycle. Inadequate care during this time breaks a critical link in the continuum of care, and affects both mothers and their babies. The World Health Organization (2016), recommends a minimum of eight ANC visits for every pregnant woman and to have their first contact in the first twelve weeks' gestation with subsequent contacts taking place at 20, 26, 30, 34, 36, 38 and 40 weeks of gestation.

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Nigeria is Africa's most populous country with a population of over 140 million people (National Demographic and Health Survey {NDHS}, 2017). It is reported that, there are about 31 million women of childbearing age (Abimbola et al., 2017). Maternal mortality is estimated to be more than twice as high in the rural areas (828 deaths per 100,000 live births) than in the urban areas (351 deaths per 100,000 live births) (Abimbola et al., 2017). Zonal variations abound in maternal mortality figures across Nigeria. WHO (2021), reports that maternal mortality rates (MMR) are significantly higher in Northern Nigeria compared to the Southern part of the country. The North West zones with MMR of 1,549 deaths per 100,000 live births and 1,025 deaths per 100,000 live births with a rate of about ten and six times higher than that in the South West (165 deaths per 100,000 live-births) (Adegoke et al., 2017).

North-West zone, is known for poor health care system, inadequate maternal and child health care, illiteracy and poor socio-economic status (National Demographic and Health Survey {NDHS}, 2017). United State Agency for International Development {USAID}, (2016), reported that North West zone of Nigeria like other geo-political zones in Nigeria has formulated strategies such as primary health care program, which, however, faces tremendous challenges in achieving national wide coverage on maternal and child birth care. It is observed that in some states in North West zone of Nigeria, an estimated 200,000 babies die as stillbirths during their last twelve weeks of pregnancy. It is estimated that babies who die before the onset of labour, or ante partum stillbirths, account for two-thirds of all stillbirths in some states where the mortality rate is greater than 22 per 100 births – nearly all states in Nigeria (Medical Center Health System {MCHS}, 2015).

Objectives of the study

The main purpose of this study was to assess the awareness on antenatal care service delivery among pregnant women in North-West zone, Nigeria.

Research Questions

What is the level of awareness of pregnant women on antenatal care service delivery in northwest Nigeria?

Hypotheses

There is no significant difference between awareness and antenatal care service delivery among pregnant women in North-west Nigeria.

Methodology

Ex-post facto research design was used for this study; this is also referred to as after-the-fact research design. Sharma, (2019), explained that in the context of social science research an ex-post facto investigation seeks to reveal possible relationships by observing an existing condition or state of affairs and searching back in time for plausible contributing factors. The population for this study comprised of all pregnant women in the seven (7) states of North-West zone, mount to one million two hundred and twenty-three thousand, five hundred and seventy-one (1,223,571) (National Bureau of Statistic, 2022). The sample size for the study consisted of 768 pregnant mothers drawn from the total population using multistage sampling technique. Stratified sampling technique was used to divide the zone into three strata as already done by FMOH (2021), on the basis of proximity, in which a stratum consisted of two (2) states with the exception of the 3rd stratum which consisted of three (3) States. Namely: Jigawa and Kaduna as first stratum, Kano and Katsina as second stratum, while Sokoto, Kebbi and Zamfara as third stratum. Three (3) states were selected from their various strata using simple random sampling technique. The same technique was employed in selecting senatorial zone within the selected states, local Governments areas and Heath facilities used in this study. To compute the number of respondents in each selected LGA and healthcare facility, a proportionate sampling technique was used. This technique was used to give equal chance of been selected to each respondent. Systematic sampling technique was used to select respondents from each of the health facility selected. The research instrument used for this study was a closed ended questionnaire titled: "Awareness on antenatal care service delivery among pregnant women". The questionnaire consists of two (2) sections: section A; contained three (3) statements on personal data of the respondents. Section B; contained ten (10) statements on knowledge of antenatal care service among pregnant mothers in North-West zone, Nigeria. To ascertain the reliability of the instrument used in this study, a pilot study was conducted. Two health facilities were randomly selected because they formed part of the population of the health facilities in North West zone, Nigeria. In each of these selected sampled health facilities, twenty (20) questionnaires were purposively administered to 20 pregnant women who attended two health facilities on Tuesday and Thursday. Hence, a total of 40 questionnaires were purposively administered to 40 respondents. The copies of questionnaire were retrieved on the spot and processed for reliability through Cronbach Alpha. The results revealed that reliability was 0.859, the instrument is considered reliable. Taber (2018), state that acceptable reliability of an instrument is 0.50. Descriptive statistics of frequency, percentages, mean score and standard deviation were

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used to describe the demographic characteristics and to answer the research question. Inferential statistics of one sample t-test was used to test the null hypothesis.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the level of awareness of pregnant women on antenatal care service delivery in northwest Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean Scores of Responses on knowledge of ANC Services among Pregnant women in North-West Zone, Nigeria

S/no	Statement	Mean	SD
1	I am aware of HIV screening during ANC clinic in the hospitals	2.25	1.06
2	I have good understanding of the benefits of weight measuring during ANC clinic in the hospital	2.05	1.07
3	I am aware of regular checking of blood pressure during ANC clinics	2.52	1.43
4	Respiratory rate measurement for the pregnant mothers during ANC clinic services is known by me	2.59	1.22
5	I am aware of hepatitis B virus screening during ANC clinics	2.37	1.23
6	I am aware of immunization with tetanus toxoid vaccine during ANC visit	2.56	1.21
7	I have good understanding of blood sugar level test during ANC visit	2.28	1.19
8	I am informed about blood screening for malaria during ANC visit	2.46	1.17
9	I am aware of ultrasound scanning during ANC visit	2.31	1.12
10	I am aware of urine test for protein and blood glucose during ANC visit	2.12	1.10
TOTAL		2.35	1.16

Field work (2022)

Observation of Table 1 shows that the respondents revealed that they are not knowledgeable about antenatal care services as most of the mean scores of responses were less than 2.50, except items 3, 4, and 6 where the means score of responses were 2.50 and slightly above. Know about checking of blood pressure (2.52; 1.43), respiratory rate measurement (2.59; 1.22), and immunization with tetanus toxoid vaccine (2.56; 1.21). The aggregate mean score of 2.35 indicates that pregnant mothers in North West zone of Nigeria are not knowledgeable of antenatal care services.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between awareness and antenatal care service delivery among pregnant women in North-west Nigeria.

Table 2: One sample t-test Analysis on awareness of ANC Services among Pregnant women of in North-West zone, Nigeria

Variable	Mean	Std.	Df	t-value	P-value.
awareness	2.351	1.157	9	40.553	0.12

t (9)= 1.833 P< 0.05 Significant.

The result shows the t-value of 40.553 at 9 degree of freedom (df) and a significance level of 0.12 at 0.05 level of confidence, with this result indeed supports the hypothesis which states that “pregnant women do not have significant awareness of ANC services in North West zone of Nigeria”. The hypothesis was therefore retained. Thus, there is no significant difference between awareness and antenatal care service delivery among pregnant women in North-west Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The primary purpose of this study was to assess the awareness on antenatal care service delivery among pregnant women in North-West zone, Nigeria. To achieve this purpose, it became necessary to assess the level of the awareness on antenatal care service delivery among pregnant women in North-West zone, Nigeria. The findings of this study revealed that pregnant women in North West zone of Nigeria does not have significant awareness on Antenatal care service delivery with a

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p-value of 0.12. This finding is in consonance with Gurmesa (2015), who reported that pregnant mothers are not knowledgeable of antenatal care services, it could be in realization that knowledge of pregnant mothers is a major factor in determining the extent to which antenatal care services are used. Ibrahim (2020), identified factors associated with late antenatal care attendance in selected rural and urban communities in Kebbi state, that inadequate awareness about antenatal care services resulted into 2.2 times high odds for late antenatal care attendance than women who had adequate knowledge in urban cities. The perception of no benefits derived from commencement of antenatal care early was associated with four times likelihood of late attendance in the urban city (WHO, 2017). According to Raru, Ayana, Zakaria and Merga, (2022), levels of education and knowledge were the most important predictors of antenatal care utilization. The study revealed that antenatal care utilization was relatively low in East African countries. This study also depicts that a higher level of maternal formal education significantly increases the utilization of antenatal care services, even after controlling for other socioeconomic factors. Furthermore, with respect to knowledge of ANC services, Andualalem, Hamel, Hana and Hale (2015), opined that 11.8% of the respondents did not know about antenatal care, the result was lower with El-Sherbini (2018) in Assiut General Hospital which was 25.5%. The researcher observed that this difference could be attributable to difference in population (304) and time of study in which the present population was 768 and the other reason is difference in operational definition. But their result was comparable with the result of Ibrahim (2020), 14.5% have no knowledge of antenatal care services among pregnant mothers in Nigeria and 73% of pregnant mothers in Zurmi general hospital lacked basic and essential knowledge about antenatal care. Okonofua et al., (2018), found that antenatal care nonattendance rate by pregnant women is high with about 62.1%, and a skilled delivery of 46.6% by recently delivered women at PHCs, while 25% of women delivered at home or with traditional birth attendants. There were several reasons for use and non-use of PHCs for antenatal and delivery care given by women some related to perceptions about long distances to PHCs, high costs of services and poor quality of PHC service delivery. The study also opined that the use of PHC facility was less among women who had low autonomy (OR 0.75, CI 0.57–0.99) as compared to women with higher autonomy. Additionally, Mohammed (2019) reported that 58.2% of the pregnant women had unsatisfactory knowledge about antenatal care service.

Conclusion

On the basis of the research findings, it is concluded that, there is no significant difference between awareness and antenatal care service delivery among pregnant women in North-west Nigeria.

Recommendations

The following are recommendations made as a result of the finding of the study:

1. There should be a practical demonstration of the antenatal talk by health educators to the pregnant women as this may improve their knowledge concerning antenatal care services.
2. There is need for the antenatal talk to be more of an interactive session between the nurses and the pregnant women, so that the pregnant mothers can discuss their doubts about any confusing matter and also ask questions regarding the aspects of the talk that is not clear to them.

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Assessing the Impact of Electronic Information Resources on Performance in Basic Science and Technology among Secondary School Students in Katsina State

Kabir Garba¹

Email: kabirgarba200@gmail.com

Tel: 08062196072

Musa Muhammad²

Email: musamuhammad299@gmail.com

Tel: 08068015550

¹College Library, Federal College of Education Katsina

²primary Education Studies, Federal College of Education Katsina

Abstract

This study is an assessment of electronic information resources on performance in Basic Science and Technology among secondary school students in Katsina State. 3 objectives and corresponding research questions and hypothesis guided the study. Descriptive statistics was used to answer research questions and t-test to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The population of the study consists of 618 (318 Male and 300 female) junior secondary school class three (JSSIII) students in Katsina Zonal Education Board during the 2022/2023 academic session. 253 (153 Male and 100 Female) Students constitutes the sample size of the study. Hence this was arrived at using simple random sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was a self-developed questionnaire rated on five scale Linkert. The result showed that, there is significant relation between the use of electronic information resources and performance in basic science among secondary school students in Katsina state. The study concluded that, electronic information resources in the yield positive outcome as it gives the students the opportunity to use independent learning and increase the performance in basic science. Based on this the study recommend that the government should provide and deploy adequate electronic information resources in Junior Secondary schools for effective teaching and learning of Basic Science

Keyword: Electronic Information Resources, performance, Basic Science and Technology

Introduction

Education is considered as the overall development of an individual, physically, mentally, morally, socially and economically while teaching and learning in any level of education can only be effective and efficient when adequate provision of educational infrastructure and physical facilities are made. Especially in public schools where there is increase in population. Basic science and Technology are a core subject at the junior secondary level of education (Sadi & Haruna, 2020) as specified in the National Policy on Education (2004). It is an introductory science course and a necessary background to all scientific and engineering careers. Basic science is described as a branch of knowledge that expresses the central idea of scientific integration via the use of ideas and principles. Teaching and learning of Basic science and technology has increasingly been taking advantage of electronic information resources managed by librarians, instructors or publishers. These tools are varied and may include websites, social media such as Face-book, Twitter and YouTube and communication media such as email, chat rooms, instant messaging systems, and web conferencing systems like Big Blue Button and Adobe Connect. The transition of all forms of intellectual potentials to digital, the process of digitizing printed materials, including scientific works, educational and methodological materials, periodicals and much more, becomes the most important incentive to change the format of Secondary Education in Nigeria (Ferreira, Paterson, and Hakone, 2018). (Alhabeeb, and Rowley, 2018). That is why Nigeria's basic science curriculum requires students to engage in any activities that encourage critical thinking. This is evident in the objectives of basic science curriculum (NERDC, 2004) which include to enable students to:

1. Develop interest in science and technology: with deployment of electronic information resources in teaching and learning basic science and technology the interest of students at junior secondary school level can be arose to achieve this objective
2. Acquire basic knowledge and skills in science and technology: Electronic information resources that has voice, audio, data videos is regarded as a critical tool for preparing and educating students with the required skills for the global work place

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3. Use your talents, technical knowledge, and abilities to satisfy society needs: electronic information resources can be used to achieved this objective. By using electronic information resources it will help, support, enhances students and complement existing classroom traditional practices.
4. Develop the skills necessary to pursue a career in science or technology: using electronic information resources by students at Junior secondary school level is a great opportunity for promoting students' intellectual qualities through higher order thinking, problem solving, improved communication skills and deep understanding of the learning tools and concepts to be taught necessary to pursue a career in science or technology
5. Prepare yourself for more science and technology studies: Electronic information resources plays a major role in human activities in everyday living in order to cope and adopt to the demand of the environment. With this objective it is generally agreed that students can be prepared for more science and technology studies by using electronic information resources.

To achieve the aforementioned objectives, the use of modern ICT facilities such as electronic information resources become imperative in the sense that they reduce obstruction, and capture students' attention and interests, promotes students' active preparation and improve students' ability to search learning concepts. The uses of electronic information resources according to Burk, Lyons, Noriega and Polovina (2013) are manifold and include:

1. The dissemination of common material such as course outlines, lecture notes and grades: This can be seen in the use of electronic information resources by students at secondary school level as it holds out the opportunity to revolutionaries' pedagogical methods, expand access to quality education and improve the management of education in providing material such as course outlines, lecture notes and grades and allowing students to receive primary and supplementary lecture and course materials
2. Allowing students to solve homework-type material at their own pace and receive personalized feedback: there is no doubt that, it is quite over wheeling to stress that electronic information resources simplify methods and strategies of acquisition of knowledge there by allowing students to solve problem at their own pace.
3. Rapidly fixing errors in previous communications or misconceptions about particular course material: The use of electronic information resources at junior secondary school does not only prepare students for the information age and globalization, it helps the students in fixing errors or misconceptions about particular topic under basic science and technology.
4. Coordinating the activities of the instructors, teaching assistants, laboratory coordinators and students everybody gets the same message at the same time: electronic information resources that that are connected via internet proto cold (IP) and non-IP network can be used by the instructors, teaching or laboratory technicians and students there by allowing everybody to gets the same message at the same time

Universal Service Provisional fund in its objective to promote seamless aces to online and off-line remote educational resources and adoption of smart education to increase ICT literacy among teachers and studentsl in collaboration with Nigeria Communication Commissions (NCC) built Students Knowledge Center in up to 369 public Secondary schools across the country, with the centers Equipped with computers and free internet for students to access resources on-line, but the centres are not duly put into use. The federal Ministry of Educations also partner with an Edtech private company (Skool Media) which is to provide: students' Experience Centers that will be fully equipped with Laptops and Internet to enhance Students' Research, teachers' Experience Center equip with laptops and internet for teachers to update themselves, prepare for Exams and get information on the internet and to digitalize classrooms by installing Projectors and each classes having its separate Laptop in them so that lessons can be delivered digitally.

In supplement of the above assertions, Xiao and Hu (2019), Adekunle, and Opeyemi, (2021) opined that use of electronic information resources improves the reading performance of students, especially those from a disadvantaged socio-economic background. The researchers observed that the impact of electronic information resources on students' reading performance gap caused by their socio-economic status changed from negative to positive. they consider that a more interactive and attractive digital environment, as well as the use of creative activities in teaching practices with ICT devices, could explain this positive effect of electronic information resources on reading performance among students from disadvantaged socio-economic backgrounds. Governments' attention has over the years been drawn to the issues of quality of education in Katsina state and the relevance of the curriculum to the needs of the society. So far, it has been noted that a giant stride has been made towards improving the quality of teachers, instructional resources and facilities to enhance learning. However, in spite of government efforts, there are still notable challenges in relation the adoption of ICT facilities in teaching and learning process, the challenges lie in giving out information, directives and timely release of funds in addition to low ICT capacity of the personnel. Based on these reasons the researchers were motivated to embark on a study to assess electronic information resources on performance in Basic Science and Technology among secondary school students in Katsina State

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Electronic Information resources (EIR), which include a whole range of educational materials, allow varying the forms of teaching and contribute to improving the quality of education. Omoike (2013) pointed out that electronic information resources comprise instructional materials such as audio and video cassettes, CD-ROM, television and radio broadcast as well as multimedia components such as computer and satellites. Titilope, Abobi; and Olayemi, (2022) defined Electronic resources as those materials that require computer access, whether through a personal computer, mainframe, or hand-held mobile device. It is the collective means of communication by which general public or populace is kept informed about the day-to-day happenings in the society.

Academic Performance is one of the most widely used variables to try to understand how information and communication technologies affect student learning outcomes. thus, academic performance may be difficult to measure, it is however seen in the grades obtained by students. Several authors agree that academic performance is the result of learning, prompted by the teaching activity by the teacher and produced by the student. Performance. Giunchiglia, Fausto, Zeni, Mattia, Gobbi, Elisa, Bignotti, Enrico, Bison, Ivano, (2018) defined academic performance as a standard for assessing a student learning status and usually measured with two dimensions, namely GPA (Grade Point Average) and CFU Credito Formativo University

This section reviewed some of the related literature conducted by different scholars on the impact of electronic information and academic performance and the study also reveal and accepted that electronic information sources have an impact on their work. Olajide Olabode (2016) explore the impact of usage of e-resources on the academic performance of the undergraduates of Federal University Oye-Ekiti, (FUOYE), Nigeria. This research is a survey. The population for this study includes the final year students of faculties of Social Science, Humanities and Science, Federal University Oye-Ekiti, Nigeria, of the 2015/2016 academic session. 150 students were chosen by simple random sampling. The data collected were analyzed quantitatively with the use of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS). Figures and tables were used to present the results of the findings. From the total of 150 copies of questionnaires distributed, 144 copies, representing 96%, were filled and returned. Results indicated that use of electronic resources had a positive impact on students' academic performance. Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that more emphasis should be laid on the acquisition of electronic resources so as to give room for wider and multiple access to information resources in order to meet the information needs of diverse users

Bakare, and Solomon (2022) investigated the relevance of Internet resources on the academic performance of secondary school students in Esan West LGA of Edo State of Nigeria. The questionnaire was the instrument; 500 copies were administered, 425 were retrieved and analysed. The descriptive survey research method was adopted. Findings show that students have access to the Internet. Students access the Internet to keep in touch with friend, get current information, improve their reading habits, and be exposed to global issues; the mostly used Internet resources are social media, Search Engines and Electronic Newspapers. The challenges to access to the Internet are cost and speed, lack of proper training/guidance on how to use the Internet. The use of Internet resources has improved their performance during test and examination. Nonetheless, the use of Internet resources have not helped them to learn self-study skills, develop information seeking skills, nor develop life-long learning skills The research recommends that students should be properly trained and constantly guided on the profitable use of the Internet and its resources for their academic pursuits; also mobile telecommunication companies should make Internet access cheaper, as well as faster so that students can access the Internet for their academic works.

Junfeng Li (2022). conducted a study aimed to explore the impact of the usage of electronic devices on students' academic performance using Ordinal Logistic Regression. Through the data analysis of the CFPS database, design electronic device usage, key school, perception of Internet as in dependent variables, and the academic performance is used as a dependent variable as a Ordinal Logistic model. The findings revealed that the length of the use of electronic devices has a significant negative correlation with the academic performance of students. Whether students belong to key schools and students' perception of the importance of the Internet to learning have no significant effect on academic performance. The results show that academic performance can be improved by controlling the length of time students use electronic devices

Several international studies have shown little improvement in performance attributed to the use of Electronic Information Resources, although other reviews have shown positive results in relation to certain curricular areas. In a study conducted by Mullis, (2017) it was revealing that students in schools that do not utilise electronic information resources performed lower than students in schools that utilised electronic information resources, although this correlation is difficult to interpret, since socio-economic levels and teaching methodologies are highly interrelated. Despite the increase and widespread use of electronic information resources among junior secondary school students, there are still challenges that are significantly preventing the effective access and usage of electronic information resources in secondary schools. According to Sife (2016), the challenges facing students could be lack or inadequate ICTs infrastructure in secondary schools, lack of awareness among

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the students, limited power supply, low bandwidth as well as lack or inadequate budget for adoption of technologies in secondary schools.

In a preliminary survey conducted it was found that, these challenges might be caused by lack of support from the parents, government, education managers, parents and even the students themselves. It is therefore based on these assertions the research was conducted to assess electronic information resources on performance in Basic Science and Technology among secondary school students in Katsina State

Objectives of the study:

The objectives of this study are:

1. To assess electronic information resource available for teaching and learning of Basic Science and Technology among Junior Secondary School Students in Katsina State
2. To examine performance of students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device and those expose to lecture teaching method in Katsina State
3. To examine performance of male and female students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device in Katsina state

Research Questions:

1. What type of electronic information resource are available for teaching and learning of Basic Science and Technology among Junior Secondary School Students in Katsina State?
2. What is the level performance of students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device and those expose to lecture teaching method in Katsina State?
3. Is there any difference in the performance of male and female students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device in Katsina state?

Hypotheses:

The following hypotheses were formulated tested at 0.5 level of significance

1. There is no significant difference between the mean performance score of students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device and those expose to lecture teaching method in Katsina State.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean performance score of students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device and those expose to lecture teaching method in Katsina State.

Methodology

The descriptive survey research design was adopted in this study. the population of the study consists of 618 (318 Male and 300 female) junior secondary school class three (JSSIII) students in Katsina Zonal Education Board during the 2022/2023 academic session. 253 (153 Male and 100 Female) Students constitutes the sample size of the study. Hence this was arrived at using simple random sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was a self-developed questionnaire rated on five scale likert. Research questions were answered using descriptive statistic while t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.005 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1

What type of electronic information resource are available for teaching and learning of Basic Science and Technology among Junior Secondary School Students in Katsina State?

Table 1. Available type of electronic information resources

S/N	Type of Electronic information resources	SA	A	SD	D	Decision
1	E-journals	38 (15.1%)	23 (9.1%)	129 (50.9%)	63 (24.9%)	Not available
2	E-newspapers	31 (12.3%)	43 (16.9%)	137 (54.2%)	42 (16.6%)	Not Available
3	E-magazines	109	74	22	40	Available

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4	E-research reports	(43.1%) 23	(29.3%) 10	(8.6%) 186	(15.8%) 34	Not available
5	Card readers (e-readers)	(9.0%) 119	(3.9%) 73	(73.5%) 38	(13.5%) 23	Available
6	E-graphics board	(47.1%) 157	(28.8%) 42	(15.1%) 21	(9.1%) 33	Not available
7	Multimedia (MM) Projector	(62.1%) 119	16.6% 73	(8.3%) 38	(13.1%) 23	Available
8	Computer	(47.1%) 157	(28.8%) 22	(15.1%) 41	(9.1%) 33	Available
9	Flash memories	(62.0%) 102	(8.6%) 71	(62.2%) 29	(13.0%) 42	Available
10	E- Library	(40.31%) 156	(29.3%) 34	(8.6%) 23	(16.6%) 40	Available
		(61.6%)	(13.5%)	(9.0%)	(15.8%)	

Table above present data on available type of Electronic information resources in Junior Secondary Schools in Katsina Zonal Education board. The table shows the percentage scores of the response of the types of electronic information resources available for students. From the above table, items 3,5,9,8,10, are available, while items 1,2,4,6, are not available.

Research Question 2

What is the level performance of students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device and those expose to lecture teaching method in Katsina State?

Table 1. Level of performance of students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device

S/N	level of performance of students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device	SA	A	SD	D	Decision
1	The performance of students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device is high	157 (62.1)	42 (16.6)	21 (8.3)	33 (13.1)	Positive
2	The performance of students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device is low	23 (9.1)	38 (15.1)	73 (28.8)	119 (47.1)	Negative

Table 2 above present data on level of performance of students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device and those expose to lecture teaching method in Katsina State. The result shows that the performance of students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device is high.

Research Question 3

Is there any difference in the performance of male and female students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device in Katsina state?

Table 3: Differences in the performance of male and female students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device in Katsina state

S/N	Differences in the performance of male and female students	SA	A	SD	D	Decision
1	Male students perform better that female counter part when taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device	58 (22.9)	30 (11.8)	100 (39.5)	57 (22.5)	Negative

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3	Female students perform better than male counterpart when taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device	100 (39.5)	57 (22.5)	58 (22.9)	30 (11.8)	Positive
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Table above present data on differences in the performance of male and female students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device in Katsina state. The result shows that female students perform better than male counterpart when taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device based on the percentage scores of the response.

Hypotheses testing

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the mean performance score of students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Katsina State.

Table 4: t-test showing difference between the mean performance score of students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Katsina State

	x	n	S ²	df	T-cal	T-crit	decision
Electronic information resources	2.58	86					
Students Academic Performance	2.96	169	0.38	253	1.12	1.96	Accepted

Significant at $p < 0.05$, of 2.53 critical = 1.96

Data in Table I indicates that the calculated t-test is 1.12 while the critical t-value is 1.96 at .05 level of significance. This implies that the calculated value is less than the critical value. The null hypothesis was rejected. Thus, There is significant difference between the mean performance score of students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Katsina

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between the mean performance score of students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Katsina State.

Table 5: t-test showing difference between the mean performance score of students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Katsina State

	x	n	S ²	df	T-cal	T-crit	decision
Electronic Information resources	3.85	98					
Female students' Academic Performance	2.34	157	0.62	253	3.51	1.96	Rejected

Significant at $p < 0.05$, $df = 2.53$ critical value = + 1.96

Table 2 revealed that the calculated t-test 3.51 is greater than the table value 1.98 at .05 level of confidence. The null hypothesis was rejected while the alternative hypothesis which holds that There is no significant difference between the mean performance score of students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Katsina State in Katsina Zonal Education board is thereby upheld

Discussion of Findings

Based on the result presented it showed that, E- Magazines, Card readers (e-readers), Multimedia (MM) Projector, computer, Flash memories and E-Library are among the available types of electronic information resources in secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality assurance. This corroborate with the finding of Ternenge, Tofi Simon and Kashimana, Fanafa, (2019) concluded in his study that e-journals, e-newspapers, on-line public access catalogue (OPAC), CD-Rom database, e-magazines, e-books, on-line database, e-research reports, virtual library on-line, science direct online and Ebscohost reference databases are not available in most of the secondary schools in Nigeria they were found only in higher institutions. Similarly in a study conducted by Adekunle, and Opeyemi, (2021) indicated that the most used E-learning platform really helped the students during the as it kept them busy and able to make good use of the long break and exposed them to the use of digital devices for Learning,

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Based on the result presented it was revealed that, the performance of students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device is high and female students perform better than male counterpart when taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device. This is in-line with the finding of Hu (2018) in his study he found that students in countries with higher overall levels of digital competences were more likely to achieve better academic results. Finally, the results indicated that there is no significant difference between use of electronic information resources on female students' academic performance of Junior Secondary Schools.

Conclusion

Based on the research conducted on in this study, it showed that electronic information resources give the students opportunity to use independent learning and increase performance in basic science, while retaining semantic competencies reading, reading habits and the ability to analyse textual material. It was concluded that, there is significant relation between the use of electronic information resources and students' academic performance of Junior Secondary Schools while there is no significant difference between use of electronic information resources on female students' academic performance of Junior Secondary Schools.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on findings:

1. The government should provide and deploy adequate electronic information resources in Junior Secondary schools for effective teaching and learning of Basic Science.
2. The government should embark on orientation, training and retraining of both students and teachers on how to search and use electronic information resources in the secondary schools
3. Government should make emphasis in the budget formulation to consider electronic information resources as the important educational Infrastructural facilities that should be provided in the schools for effective teaching
4. There is need for school administrators to report any damage and problem to the technicians for repair and maintenance of electronic information resources being used in in the schools.

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Assessment of Information and Communication Technology Tools on Chemistry Teaching and Learning among Secondary School Teachers in Ogbia, Bayelsa State

Akpomiemie, Voke Lilian

Email: vokelilian@gmail.com

Tel: 08032143930

Department of Science Education, Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State

Abstract

This study examined Information and Communication Technology tools on Chemistry teaching and learning among Secondary School Teachers in Ogbia, Bayelsa State". Four research questions and hypotheses guided the study. Descriptive survey research design was used. The population of the study comprises of all Chemistry teachers during the 2022/2023 academic session in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State. A sample size of 256 (Male 140 and Female 116) Chemistry teachers was obtained using Taro Yamene formula. A 4-point rating scale questionnaire was used. The instrument was validated by two experts. The split-half technique was used to test the reliability and a reliability coefficient of 0.89 for teachers, showed that the instruments are reliable. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer research questions. Hypotheses were tested using z- test at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that ICT facilities such as computer and its accessories, software packages such as Access, Excel, power point etc. were available for Chemistry teaching and learning, while projectors, multimedia devices were not available for Chemistry teaching and learning in senior secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State. It was concluded that thought, the use of ICT tools in the study area is low, it has positive and significant impact in students' performance. It was recommended amongst others that; ICT in Education should be a core course for teachers' training programme to adequately prepare teachers on how they can effectively domesticate ICT in their respective discipline while in the classroom.

Keyword: ICT Tools, Teaching, Learning, Chemistry and Teacher

Introduction

One of the notable changes that are peculiar in this 21st century also known as the information age is the dynamic and rapid growth of information Communication Technologies. Information Communication Technology (ICT) has turned the world into a global village and as the days goes by, it gained more ground (Nnaekwe & Ugwu, 2019). Before now, eventually everything was done manually but the advent of ICT has changed the perception and also increases the work speed of so many things in our society today. The growth of every society is ascertained to a degree of communication between the human standards and technical advancement. There is hardly a thing one we do in this new age without using ICT, this is a well-known fact as all human activities is speedily changing into electronic patterns of which education is not left out (Akubuilu, Nnam, & Ugo, 2021). ICT can be defined as an electronic, and communication devices connected with the social and material life of human which allows individuals to use a wide range of instructional process. ICT tools comprises of all the available equipment used for identification, generation, preservation, conservation, production, storage, packaging, processing, retrieval and dissemination of information that is not limited by time and distance (ThankGod & Innocent, 2021). Ejinwa, (2018) posit that advancement, globalization and new opportunities in education is a result of the blending and frequent use of ICT. For an improvement in works of teachers and students in this information era there is need for the implementation and integration of ICT into the teaching and learning environment as it presents more opportunities (Lawrence & Tar, 2018). The advancement of this era of information interaction and it meeting with telecommunication with the aid of computers has increases the possibility to use different technological tool in teaching and learning situation. The utilization of ICT facilities in the education system shift education from teacher-centered education to learner-centered education. Akubuilu, Nnam, & Ugo (2021).

Community and individuals are affected in various ways by ICT facilities which surrounds different area like politics, technology, economics, society for transformation globally (ThankGod & Innocent, 2021). The incorporation of information and communication technologies into our education system has bring about exceptional privileges since it has the ability to improve, communicate and bring together people from different locations, both far and near to interact and achieve learning objects in a meaningful way. The use of ICT improves the quality of education, make information accessible and also increase

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learning opportunities in different subjects. ICT as an innovative method of teaching creates an interactive learning situation facilitate improve thinking ability and make the classroom an environment for educational development. (Akubuilu, Nnam, & Ugo, 2021). ICT has capability to change the teaching and learning environment from the traditional methods to a new one by teaching, visualizing new learning methods. The use of ICT and other IT communication facilities such as computer, internet, projector in the teaching and learning of Chemistry in secondary schools is more ease and more effective. Therefore, this research work is intended to examine the impact of the use of ICT in the teaching and learning of Chemistry in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State.

(Despite the global advancement in technology, the teaching of Chemistry in Nigerian secondary schools particularly in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State has been archaic as they still adopt the old method of teaching of chalkboard and textbooks only (Ejinwa, 2018). They have not yet started using innovative strategies of teaching like use of projects, internet, computers and other ICT facilities (Ejinwa, 2018). A major setback in various classrooms of third world countries and Nigeria in particular is lack of expertise and understanding in applying and incorporating of ICT in teaching pedagogy (Lawrence & Tar, 2018). At present, various challenges such as: lack of ICT facilities, in-service training for teachers and funds from government, made the utilization of ICT in learning still quite low. Furthermore, most students lack the needed tools like android phones, laptops, personal computers (hardware), software and internet access (ThankGod & Innocent, 2021). Students perform poorly in some Chemistry concepts of which the use of the conventional strategy of teaching is lacking but when taught using ICT it has capability in meeting the requirements of new instructional strategies in teaching and learning which will in turn enhance their performance (Akubuilu, Nnam, & Ugo, 2021).

Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study was to Assess Information and Communication Technology tools for chemistry teaching and learning among Secondary School Teachers in Ogbia, Bayelsa State. Specifically, the objectives were to:

1. Determine the mean response on level of utilization of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching and learning among secondary school teachers in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State.
2. Determine the mean response on level of competence exhibited by teachers in the use of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching and learning in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State.
3. Identify the challenges in the use of ICT tools in Chemistry teaching and learning among secondary school teachers in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the mean response on availability of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching and learning among secondary school teachers in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State?
2. What is the mean response on utilization of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching and learning among secondary school teachers in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State?
3. What is the mean response on competence of secondary school teachers in the use of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching and learning in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State?
4. What is the mean response on challenges on the use of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching and learning among secondary school teachers in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female Chemistry teachers on availability of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching and learning in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female Chemistry teachers on utilization of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching and learning in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State.
3. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female Chemistry teachers on competency exhibited in the use of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching and learning in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State.
4. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female Chemistry teachers on the challenges in the use of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching and learning in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State.

Methodology

This study is descriptive research. The survey designed was used to investigate Assessment of Information and Communication Technology tools for chemistry teaching and learning among Secondary School Teachers in Ogbia, Bayelsa State. Wali (2019) survey research design is used to ascertain or investigate the current status of a problem by studying a true representative of the population. All Chemistry teachers in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State constitute the population of this study. There are total of 742 Chemistry teachers in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State. Taro Yamene formula was used to obtain a sample size of 256 Chemistry teachers, out of a population of 742 teachers. Stratified random sampling was used to select the 256 teachers.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the mean response on availability of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching and learning among secondary school teachers in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State?

Table 1: Teachers' Response on Availability of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching and learning among secondary school teachers in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State

Availability of ICT facilities for Chemistry Students	Male Chemistry Teachers' N= 140		Female Chemistry Teachers' N= 116		Decision
	Mean \bar{x}	Std. dev. δ	Mean \bar{x}	Std. dev. δ	
Computer and ICT accessories	3.01	0.83	3.15	0.87	Agree
Projectors and transparencies	2.33	0.68	2.21	0.64	Disagree
Multimedia devices	2.23	0.50	2.00	0.50	Disagree
Internet facilities	2.14	0.52	2.21	0.68	Disagree
Software packages such as Access, Excel, power point etc.	2.91	0.81	2.94	0.90	Agree
Display boards	3.02	0.82	2.70	0.90	Agree
Photocopiers	2.90	0.76	2.96	0.80	Agree
CD and flash drive	2.93	0.84	2.93	0.73	Agree
Total	2.68	0.72	2.64	0.75	

Standard reference mean $\bar{x} = 2.50$

Table 4.1 shows that mean values of 3.01, 2.91, 3.02, 2.90 and 2.93 respectively, which are greater than the standard reference mean of 2.50 indicates that male teachers were of the view that the following ICT facilities; computer and its accessories, software packages such as Access, Excel, power point, display boards, photocopiers, CD and flash drive respectively were adequately available for Chemistry students in secondary schools in Bayelsa State, while mean values of 2.33, 2.23 and 2.14 respectively, which are less than the standard reference mean of 2.50 indicates that male teachers were of the view that the following ICT facilities; projectors and transparencies, multimedia devices and internet facilities respectively were not adequately available for Chemistry students in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State. Small values of standard deviations obtained, that is; 0.83, 0.68, 0.50, 0.52, 0.81, 0.82, 0.76 and 0.84 respectively indicates that the male Chemistry teachers were homogeneous in their response. However, mean values of 3.15, 2.94, 2.70, 2.96 and 2.93 respectively, which are greater than the standard reference mean of 2.50 indicates that female teachers were of the view that the following ICT facilities; computer and its accessories, software packages such as Access, Excel, power point, display boards, photocopiers, CD and flash drive respectively were adequately available for Chemistry students in secondary schools in Bayelsa State, while mean values of 2.21, 2.00 and 2.21 respectively, which are less than the standard reference mean of 2.50 indicates that female teachers were of the view that the following ICT facilities; projectors and transparencies, multimedia devices and internet facilities respectively were not adequately available for Chemistry students in secondary schools in Ogbia

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Local Government Area, Bayelsa State. Small values of standard deviations obtained, that is; 0.83, 0.68, 0.50, 0.52, 0.81, 0.82, 0.76 and 0.84 respectively indicates that the female Chemistry teachers were homogeneous in their response.

Research Question 2

What is the mean response on utilization of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching and learning among secondary school teachers in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State?

Table 2: Teachers' Response on Utilization of ICT tools for chemistry teaching and learning among secondary school teachers in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State.

Utilization of ICT facilities for Chemistry Students	Male Chemistry Teachers' N= 140		Female Chemistry Teachers' N= 116		Decision
	Mean \bar{x}	Std. dev. δ	Mean \bar{x}	Std. dev. δ	
Computer and ICT accessories	2.95	0.78	2.82	0.88	Agree
Projectors and transparencies	2.32	0.68	2.30	0.58	Disagree
Multimedia devices	2.14	0.63	2.30	0.67	Disagree
Internet facilities	2.38	0.66	2.24	0.72	Disagree
Software packages such as Access, Excel, power point etc.	2.94	0.84	3.10	0.74	Agree
Display boards	3.03	0.86	2.74	0.83	Agree
Photocopiers	2.97	0.85	2.92	0.87	Agree
CD and flash drive	2.81	0.91	2.84	0.70	Agree
Total	2.70	0.78	2.66	0.75	

Standard reference mean $\bar{x} = 2.50$

Table 4.2 shows that mean values of 2.95, 2.94, 3.03, 2.97 and 2.81 respectively, which are greater than the standard reference mean of 2.50 indicates that male teachers were of the view that the following ICT facilities; computer and its accessories, software packages such as Access, Excel, power point, display boards, photocopiers, CD and flash drive respectively were adequately available for Chemistry students in secondary schools in Bayelsa State, while mean values of 2.32, 2.14 and 2.38 respectively, which are less than the standard reference mean of 2.50 indicates that male teachers were of the view that the following ICT facilities; projectors and transparencies, multimedia devices and internet facilities respectively were not adequately available for Chemistry students in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State. Small values of standard deviations obtained, that is; 0.78, 0.68, 0.63, 0.66, 0.84, 0.86, 0.85 and 0.91 respectively indicates that the male Chemistry teachers were homogeneous in their response. Mean values of 2.82, 3.10, 2.74, 2.92 and 2.84 respectively, which are greater than the standard reference mean of 2.50 indicates that female teachers were of the view that the following ICT facilities; computer and its accessories, software packages such as Access, Excel, power point, display boards, photocopiers, CD and flash drive respectively were adequately available for Chemistry students in secondary schools in Bayelsa State, while mean values of 2.30, 2.30 and 2.24 respectively, which are less than the standard reference mean of 2.50 indicates that female teachers were of the view that the following ICT facilities; projectors and transparencies, multimedia devices and internet facilities respectively were not adequately available for Chemistry students in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State. Small values of standard deviations obtained, that is; 0.88, 0.58, 0.67, 0.72, 0.74, 0.83, 0.87 and 0.70 respectively indicates that the female Chemistry teachers were homogeneous in their response.

Research Question 3

What is the mean response on competence of secondary school teachers in the use of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching and learning in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State?

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Table 3: Teachers' Response on the extent to which teachers exhibit competence in the use of ICT tools for chemistry teaching among Secondary School teachers in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State

Competence in the use of ICT skills in teaching Chemistry	Male Chemistry Teachers' N= 140		Female Chemistry Teachers' N= 116		Decision
	Mean \bar{x}	Std. dev. δ	Mean \bar{x}	Std. dev. δ	
Planning and presenting classroom instructions in Chemistry	2.44	0.71	2.20	0.60	Disagree
Prepare ICT- based learning environment in Chemistry	2.21	0.66	2.25	0.52	Disagree
Using ICT as a didactical tool to establish a dynamic and powerful instructional strategies in chemistry	2.37	0.70	2.27	0.65	Disagree
Using ICT to promote social competence such as developing knowledge and skills in ethical, legal, safety, humor and good manners during teaching and learning chemistry	2.36	0.61	2.30	0.66	Disagree
Total	2.35	0.67	2.26	0.61	

Standard reference mean $\bar{x} = 2.50$

Table 4.3 shows that mean values of 2.44, 2.21, 2.37 and 2.36 respectively, which are less than the standard reference mean of 2.50 indicates that male teachers were of the view that the following skills; planning and presenting classroom instructions in Chemistry, prepare ICT- based learning environment in Chemistry, using ICT as a didactical tool to establish a dynamic and powerful instructional strategies in chemistry and using ICT to promote social competence such as developing knowledge and skills in ethical, legal, safety, humor and good manners during teaching and learning chemistry respectively were lacking for teaching Chemistry students in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State. Small values of standard deviations obtained, that is; 0.71, 0.66, 0.70 and 0.61 respectively indicates that the male Chemistry teachers were homogeneous in their response. The mean values of 2.20, 2.25, 2.27 and 2.30 respectively, which are less than the standard reference mean of 2.50 indicates that female teachers were of the view that the following skills; planning and presenting classroom instructions in Chemistry, prepare ICT- based learning environment in Chemistry, using ICT as a didactical tool to establish a dynamic and powerful instructional strategies in chemistry and using ICT to promote social competence such as developing knowledge and skills in ethical, legal, safety, humor and good manners during teaching and learning chemistry respectively were lacking for teaching Chemistry students in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State. Small values of standard deviations obtained, that is; 0.60, 0.52, 0.65 and 0.66 respectively indicates that the female Chemistry teachers were homogeneous in their response.

Research Question 4: What is the mean response on challenges on the use of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching and learning among secondary school teachers in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State?

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Table 4: Teachers' Response on the Challenges in the use of ICT tools for chemistry teaching in Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State.

Challenges of Using ICT facilities for Chemistry Students	Male Chemistry Teachers' N= 140		Female Chemistry Teachers' N= 116		Decision
	Mean	Std. dev.	Mean	Std. dev.	
	\bar{x}	δ	\bar{x}	δ	
Lack of trained manpower	2.67	0.84	2.92	0.70	Agree
Lack of motivation and incentive among Chemistry teachers	2.66	0.95	3.00	0.75	Agree
Inadequate funding	2.80	0.84	2.97	0.84	Agree
Inadequate time to integrate ICT into the school timetable	3.07	0.91	2.85	0.91	Agree
Lack of regular power supply	2.81	0.92	2.81	0.86	Agree
Inadequate facility to ensure one on one hands-on training	3.17	0.83	2.78	0.80	Agree
Total	2.86	0.66	2.88	0.81	

Standard reference mean $\bar{x} = 2.50$

Table 4.4 shows that mean values of 2.67, 2.66, 2.80, 3.07, 2.81 and 3.17 respectively, which are greater than the standard reference mean of 2.50 indicates that the male teachers were of the view that the following; lack of trained manpower, lack of motivation and incentive among Chemistry teachers, inadequate funding, inadequate time to integrate ICT into the school timetable, lack of regular power supply and inadequate facility to ensure one on one hands- on training respectively were problems facing Chemistry students and teachers in the use of ICT facilities in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State. Small values of standard deviations obtained, that is; 0.84, 0.95, 0.84, 0.91, 0.92 and 0.83 respectively indicates that the male Chemistry teachers were homogeneous in their response. However, the mean values of 2.92, 3.00, 2.97, 2.85, 2.81 and 2.78 respectively, which are greater than the standard reference mean of 2.50 indicates that the female teachers were of the view that the following; lack of trained manpower, lack of motivation and incentive among Chemistry teachers, inadequate funding, inadequate time to integrate ICT into the school timetable, lack of regular power supply and inadequate facility to ensure one on one hands- on training respectively were problems facing Chemistry students and teachers in the use of ICT facilities in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State. Small values of standard deviations obtained, that is; 0.70, 0.75, 0.84, 0.91, 0.86 and 0.80 respectively indicates that the female Chemistry teachers were homogeneous in their response.

Hypothesis 1

Hypothesis 1:

There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female Chemistry teachers on availability of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching and learning in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State.

Table 5: Z-Test of Differences in the Mean Responses of Male and Female Chemistry Teachers on the Availability of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching and learning in Secondary Schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State

Group	Mean	Std. dev	N	Df	Std. error	Zcal	Z-table	Decision
Male teachers	2.68	0.72	140					
Female teachers	2.64	0.75	116	254	0.093	0.43	1.96	H0 accepted

Table 4.5 shows that the null hypothesis on Z-test of difference in the mean responses of male and female teachers on the availability of ICT facilities in teaching and learning Chemistry in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State, was accepted at 5% level of significance, where the degree of freedom (254) is at infinity (∞), because the critical

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or tabular value of Z (1.96) is greater than the calculated value of Z (0.43). This shows that male and female teachers agreed that ICT facilities are not adequately available in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female Chemistry teachers on utilization of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching and learning in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State.

Table 6: Z-Test of Differences in the Mean Responses of Male and Female Chemistry Teachers on the Utilization of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching and learning in Secondary Schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State

Group	Mean	Std. dev	N	Df	Std. error	Zcal	Ztable	Decision
Male teachers	2.70	0.78	140					
Female teachers	2.66	0.75	116	254	0.097	0.41	1.96	H0 accepted

Table 4.6 shows that the null hypothesis on Z-test of difference in the mean responses of male and female teachers on the utilization of ICT facilities in teaching and learning Chemistry in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State, was accepted at 5% level of significance, where the degree of freedom (254) is at infinity (∞), because the critical or tabular value of Z (1.96) is greater than the calculated value of Z (0.41). This shows that male and female teachers agreed that ICT facilities are not adequately utilized in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female Chemistry teachers on competency exhibited in the use of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching and learning in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State.

Table 7: Z-Test of Differences in the Mean Responses of Male and Female Chemistry Teachers on the level of competence exhibited by teachers in the use of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching in Secondary Schools Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State

Group	Mean	Std. dev	N	Df	Std. error	Zcal	Ztable	Decision
Male teachers	2.35	0.67	140					
Female teachers	2.26	0.61	116	254	0.08	1.13	1.96	H0 accepted

Table 4.7 shows that the null hypothesis on Z-test of difference in the mean responses of male and female teachers on the level of competence exhibited by teachers in the use of ICT facilities in teaching Chemistry in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State, was accepted at 5% level of significance, where the degree of freedom (254) is at infinity (∞), because the critical or tabular value of Z (1.96) is greater than the calculated value of Z (1.13). This shows that male and female teachers agreed that ICT skills are lacking for utilizing ICT facilities in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State.

Hypothesis 4

There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female Chemistry teachers on the challenges in the use of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching and learning in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State.

Table 8: Z-Test of Differences in the Mean Responses of Male and Female Chemistry Teachers on the challenges in the use of ICT tools for Chemistry teaching in Secondary Schools in Ogbia Local Government Area Bayelsa State.

Group	Mean	Std. dev	N	Df	Std. error	Zcal	Ztable	Decision
Male teachers	2.86	0.66	140					
Female teachers	2.88	0.81	116	254	0.094	0.21	1.96	H0 accepted

Table 4.8 shows that the null hypothesis on Z-test of difference in the mean responses of male and female teachers on the challenges of using ICT facilities in teaching Chemistry in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa state, was accepted at 5% level of significance, where the degree of freedom (254) is at infinity (∞), because the critical or

tabular value of Z (1.96) is greater than the calculated value of Z (0.21). This shows that male and female teachers agreed that they are confronted by problems using ICT facilities in teaching and learning Chemistry in secondary school in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State. In research question 1 and hypothesis 1, the study found out that ICT facilities such as; computer and its accessories, software packages such as Access, Excel, power point, display boards, photocopiers, CD and flash drive respectively were adequately available for Chemistry students in senior secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State, while projectors and transparencies, multimedia devices and internet facilities respectively were not adequately available for Chemistry students in secondary schools in Bayelsa State. Harrison (2002), Ilomaki and Rantanen (2007) who were of the opinion that ICT has the potential of improving student academic performance but its facilities are not adequately and readily available for use in schools. The researchers therefore are of the opinion that ICT is to be used as a method of instruction in the teaching and learning of Chemistry in the study area.

Discussion of Findings

In research question 2 and hypothesis 2, the study found out that ICT facilities such as; computer and its accessories, software packages such as Access, Excel, power point, display boards, photocopiers, CD and flash drive respectively were adequately utilized for Chemistry students in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State, while projectors and transparencies, multimedia devices and internet facilities respectively were not adequately utilized for Chemistry students in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State. Again, finding from this study reveal that the extents of the utilization of ICT in the teaching and learning of Chemistry is low, this also agrees with the work of Yusuf, Kajuru and Musa (2013) who reported that only few schools used computer in the teaching and learning of science subjects. The researchers therefore are of the opinion that teachers should employ the use of ICT in the teaching and learning of Chemistry and other science and technology related courses for the benefits of the teaching profession.

In research question 3 and hypothesis 3, the study found out that skills such as; planning and presenting classroom instructions in Chemistry, prepare ICT- based learning environment in Chemistry, using ICT as a didactical tool to establish a dynamic and powerful instructional strategies in chemistry and using ICT to promote social competence such as developing knowledge and skills in ethical, legal, safety, humor and good manners during teaching and learning chemistry respectively were lacking for teaching Chemistry students in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State.

In research question 4 and hypothesis 4, the study found out that lack of trained manpower, lack of motivation and incentive among Chemistry teachers, inadequate funding, inadequate time to integrate ICT into the school timetable, lack of regular power supply and inadequate facility to ensure one on one hands- on training respectively are the problems facing Chemistry students and teachers in the use of ICT facilities in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State. This study supports the findings of Unogu (2015), view that teachers should be encouraged to use ICT facilities in teaching some concepts in Chemistry. To achieve this, they should be enlightened on the use of ICT facilities through organized in-service trainings, workshops and seminars.

Conclusion

This study investigated on the impact of ICT facilities in teaching and learning Chemistry in Senior Secondary Schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa. From the results and findings of the study it was safe to conclude that though the use of ICT in the study area is low, it has positive and significant impact on the academic performance of students and there was no significant difference in the performance of male and female students of the study area. In the circumstance, the researchers are of the opinion that there should be improvement in the use of ICT facilities. Therefore, if schools' instructional materials, workshops and equipment, training and retraining of Chemistry teachers by experts are adequately provided and effectively utilized, it will produce great positive impact on students' achievement and teachers objectives actualized. It will enable better understanding of abstract topics taught by teachers. Teachers however are faced with constraints such as inadequate funding, lack of regular power supply, inadequate workshops and materials, lack of adequate time to integrate ICT into the school timetable, lack of motivation and incentives among Chemistry teachers.

Recommendations

The following recommendations based on the findings were made:

3. The ability to acquire the ICT devices and appendages rest squarely on what is available to the school management as fund.
4. ICT in Education should be a core course for teachers' training programme to adequately prepare teachers on how they can effectively domesticate ICT in their respective discipline while in the classroom.
5. The Federal Ministry of Works, Housing and Power should work towards stabilizing electricity supply in Nigeria.

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6. Government at the federal and state levels should provide computers and other equipment (projector and transparencies) to secondary schools for the integration of ICT into science learning and Government should empower teachers by training them in the use of ICT to teach students.

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Assessment of Knowledge, Attitude and Prevalence of Drug Abuse among Federal Colleges of Education Students in Nigeria

*Ezeaghasi, Ngozi. Eucharía¹

Email: ngoziezeaghasi@gmail.com

Tel: 08030937563

Najmuddeen, Alhassan¹

Email: muhalbg@gmail.com

Tel: 07063063335

Dalhatu, Hadiza Umar¹

Email: hudalhat9@gmail.com

Tel: 07061684730

¹ Department of Biology, School of Secondary Education, Sciences. Federal College of Education, Zaria. Nigeria.

Abstract

Drug abuse is one of the major health challenges and of a great concern to the government and also the general public. This study sought to determine the knowledge level, attitudes, prevalence, contributing factors and intervention strategies towards drug abuse among Federal Colleges of Education students in Nigeria. The research design used was descriptive cross-sectional among the NCE II Biology students. A multistage sampling technique was adopted; one Federal College of Education each was selected from the six geo political zones. A total of 1572 subjects were the sample. The study has Six research questions and hypotheses respectively. Structured questionnaire named Students' Knowledge Attitude Prevalence of Drug Abuse Questionnaire (SKAPODAQ) was used to collect data online through a kobo tool box. The questionnaire was based on Likert 5-point rating scale. Descriptive statistics of frequencies and percentage were used to analyze the Demo graph of the respondents, Mean and Standard Deviation for research questions (SPSS version-20.0) while Chi-Square statistics and Pearson Correlation was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Result of rho obtained was 0.73. The result revealed that the most of the respondents were young people (16-22) years 86.3%, male having the highest number; That NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education, Nigeria have the knowledge (4.162) and positive attitude (3.385) to the use of drugs and abuse. Majority of the students agreed that the contributing factors such as using drugs to achieve feeling to joy and happiness (33.7%), use drugs during exams (52.7 %) use medication without valid prescription (62.3%) influence the prevalence of drug abuse. The study also agreed that relationship exist among knowledge, attitude, prevalence and contributing factors to drug abuse. Therefore, recommends that more awareness should be created on the negative effects of drug abuse among students in Federal Colleges of Education, Nigeria which on the other hand will reduce the prevalence rate.

Keywords: Knowledge, Attitude, Prevalence, Drug Abuse

Introduction

Drug abuse refers to the harmful or hazardous use of psychoactive substances, including both legal and illegal drugs. It involves the use of substances such as alcohol, prescription medications, or illicit drugs in a way that leads to physical, psychological, or social harm to the individual. It is an intrinsic health behavior according to (United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, 2021) that can result in addiction health problems, impaired judgment, and negative consequences in various aspects of a person's life (Dibia., Nwagu & Odo 2020). Drug abuse is of significant concern in Developing countries, especially among students of tertiary institutions. According to UNODC (2021) about 275 million people used drugs worldwide while over 36 million people suffered from drug use disorders. Drug abuse, among the most common public health problems for both adults and adolescents, is of significant societal concern Abuhuraira., Yusuf., Muhammad., Mamman., Solomon., Umar & Muhammad, (2021).

Federal Colleges of Education is tertiary institutions that award students with a Nigerian Certificate in Education (NCE) Degree. During this period in school, students experience independence and freedom from adult and parent supervision,

form new social groups, make decisions by themselves, and balance some social engagements and life responsibilities with their academics. They also imbibe some normative values and youth culture that differ from their parental background. Most of the Federal College of Education students are in their Adolescence stage, a vital stage of life and the most transformative time in life Makanjuola., Daramola & Obembe (2007) and Alhyas., Ozaibi., Elarabi., El-Kashef., Wanigaratne & Almarzouqi (2015). These perceived norms motivate the youth to indulge in some unhealthy behaviors, such as smoking, alcohol, and drugs, that could change their perceptions, mood, cognition, and behavior (Alhyas., Ozaibi., Elarabi., El-Kashef., Wanigaratne & Almarzouqi (2015). Researchers like Herold., Boykan., Eliscu., Alcalá., & Gronkiewicz (2021) and Desmennu., Titiloye & Owoaje (2018) grouped the abused drugs as follows: stimulants, such as amphetamines and cocaine, which increase alertness and energy levels. Depressants, such as alcohol and benzodiazepines, slow down the central nervous system and induce relaxation—hallucinogens, such as LSD and psilocybin mushrooms, which alter perception and mood. Barati., Bashirian., Jormand., Babamiri., & Rezapur-Shahkolai (2022) and Umukoro., Eduviere., Ahama., Moke., Edje., Omorodion & Ovigwe (2021) said that Opioids, including prescription painkillers and heroin are highly addictive substances that create a sense of euphoria. Cannabis, also known as marijuana, is another commonly abused drug among adolescents (UNODC,2021). Several researchers have linked drug abuse with some unhealthy behaviors like depression, violence, crimes like rape, stealing, prostitution, and sex work, this create nuisance to the society (Racionero-Plaza., León., Iglesias., & Ugalde 2021). Constant uses cause serious problem and irreversible damage on individual's physical and development, a significant societal concern that affects worldwide, including students pursuing higher education Akinsefunmi, Rita, Aminat & Rufus (2016) and Onoyase, (2019). Understanding the knowledge level, attitudes, prevalence, contributing factors to drug abuse is crucial for developing targeted prevention, control and intervention strategies to address the issue effectively. It is in this context that drug abuse becomes an addiction for most adolescents in schools. Drug abuse among adolescents in schools is a complex issue that is influenced by multiple factors with the problem increasing day by day Racionero-Plaza., León., Iglesias., & Ugalde (2021). In recent years, drug abuse has become a growing problem among students in tertiary institutions with potentially detrimental consequences for their academic performance and personal well-being. Federal Colleges of Education is not left out. It was against these backdrops that the researchers sought to investigate the Knowledge Level, Attitude and Prevalence of Drug Abuse among Nigerian Certificate Education Students in Federal Colleges of Education, Nigeria. This assessment will provide insights into the existing gaps in their understanding of the risks associated with drug abuse and shed light on their prevalence, perceptions, beliefs and attitudes toward the misuse of drugs, it will offer valuable information for designing targeted interventions and also identifying the contributing factors. Unraveling these factors will help in developing comprehensive prevention strategies that will likely address the root causes of these situation among students in Federal Colleges of Education, Nigeria.

Recent studies in Nigeria and worldwide have shown that a significant percentage of drug abusers seeking treatment and rehabilitation are adolescents and students (Jyotika & Pradeep, 2017, Chetty 2018 and Nwagu., Dibia & Odo 2020). An estimation of about 275 million people worldwide are engaged in drug abuse (UNODC,2021). In Nigeria, drug abuse is prevalent among youths, many of whom are unaware of the dangers associated with drug addiction (Ofili., Ugorume., Oyibocho & Eziashi 2021 Sarkingobir & Dikko, 2020 and Uroko, 2022) with potential consequences on their academic performance and overall well-being. However, there is a lack of comprehensive understanding regarding the knowledge level, attitudes, prevalence, contributing factors, and effectiveness of prevention and intervention strategies in addressing this issue (Mayanchi, et. al., 2020). This knowledge gap hinders the development of targeted and evidence-based approaches to combat drug abuse. Therefore, there is a need to investigate the knowledge, attitudes, prevalence, contributing factors and intervention strategies for drug abuse among students in Federal Colleges of Education.

Objectives of the Study

1. Determine the knowledge level and its prevalence on drug abuse among NCE II Biology Students in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria
2. What is the attitude and prevalence of drug abuse among NCE II Biology Students in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria?
3. Do contributing factors to drug abuse influence the prevalence rate among NCE II Biology Students in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria
4. Do Intervention Strategies assessment influence the prevalence of drug abuse among NCE II Biology Students in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria.

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5. Investigate the relationship among knowledge level, attitude, prevalence and contributing factors to drug abuse among NCE II Biology Students in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria

Research Questions

5. Does knowledge level of NCE II Biology Students in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria have no significant influence on prevalence of drug abuse?
6. Does the attitude of NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria towards drug abuse have no significant influence on prevalence?
7. Do contributing factors to drug abuse influence the prevalence among NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria?
8. Do Intervention Strategies assessment influence the prevalence of drug abuse among NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria?
9. What is the relationship between the knowledge level, attitude, prevalence and contributing factors to drug abuse among NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria?

Hypotheses

1. Knowledge level of NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education have no significant influence on prevalence of drug abuse
2. Attitude of NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education towards drug abuse have no significant influence on prevalence.
3. Contributing factors to drug abuse have no significant influence on the prevalence among NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education
4. Intervention Strategies Assessment have no significance influence on the prevalence of among NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education
5. There is no significant relationship among knowledge level, attitude, prevalence and contributing factors to drug abuse among NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education.

Methodology

The research design was a descriptive survey which was carried out for a period of six months (July to Dec 2023). All NCE II Biology students of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria with a total of 4912 students that registered in 2022/2023 Academic Session were the population. A multistage sampling technique was adopted; one Federal College of Education each was selected from the six geo political zones. One thousand five hundred and seventy-two 1572 (943 Male and 629 Female) students were sampled using a simple random sampling technique. Table 1 presented the Sample Study.

Table 1: Sample of the Study

S/N	Colleges of Education	Male	Female	Total
1	Adeyemi College of Education	67	45	112
2	FCE EHA-Amufu	65	43	108
3	FCE Obudu	88	58	146
4	FCE Okene	77	51	128
5	FCE Yola	159	107	266
6	FCE Zaria	487	325	812
Total		943	629	1572

Source: Field Survey (2023)

The research Instrument for the study is Students Knowledge, Attitude and Prevalence of Drug Abuse Questionnaire (SKAPODAQ) which was adapted and developed. The questionnaire comprised of six sections; (1) Demographic Information (2) knowledge Assessment (3) Attitude Assessment (4) Prevalence of Drug abuse (5) Contributing Factors Assessment and (6) Intervention Effectiveness assessment. The questionnaire contained 60 items to reflect on the overall towards Knowledge, Attitude Prevalence, Contributing Factors, Intervention Effectiveness of Drug Abuse among NCE II Biology Students of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria. The questionnaire was based on Likert 5-point rating scale.

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The rating of the 5-point Likert scale of Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A) Undecided (UD) Disagreed (D) and Strongly Disagreed (SD) Scored 5,4321 for positive statement and reverse order for negative statements. The data was collected online using Students Knowledge level, Attitude Prevalence of Drug Abuse Questionnaire (SKAPODAQ) through a kobo tool box. Data was analyzed with statistical software (SPSS version-20.0). Descriptive statistics of frequencies and percentage were used for Demography of the respondents. Mean and Standard Deviation was used to answer the research questions while Chi-Square statistics and Pearson Correlation was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The results were presented in form of tables. The data was analyzed at the data processing unit of Iya Abubakar Computer Centre, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. The Instrument, Students Knowledge Attitude Prevalence of Drug Abuse Questionnaire (SKAPODAQ) was validated by three experts with qualification of PhD and minimum rank of Senior lecturers in the Department of Psychology, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. Pilot study was carried out to a group of two hundred and fifty (250) students in the Department of Biology, Federal College of Education Katsina, Katsina State for reliability. This college was part of the population but not sampled. The Method of analysis used was Spearman Rank Order Correlation. Result of rho obtained was 0.73 which made the instrument reliable for the study. The researchers administered the questionnaire for five weeks with the help of research assistance in the department.

Table 2: Demographic Data of the Respondents

	Frequency	Percentage	Mean	Standard Deviation
Gender			1.40	0.490
Male	943	60		
Female	629	40		
Age			1.16	0.446
16-22	1356	86.3		
23-26	155	9.9		
27+	49	3.1		
Socio Economic Status			1.33	0.535
Low	1096	69.7		
Middle	426	27.1		
High	50	3.2		
Total	1572	100	1.29	0.49

Source: Field Survey, 2023

This study had 1572 respondents, 943 (60%) were males, 629 (40%) were females, 1356 (86.3%) were within the ages of 16-22 years, 155 (9.9%) were within the ages of 23-26 years, 49(3.1%) were within the ages of 27 and above. The socio – economic status, 1096 (69.7%) were Low, 426(27.1%) middle, 50 (3.2%) high. The result revealed that the majority of the respondents were young people (16-22) years 86.3%, male having the highest number.

Research Question 1

Does Knowledge level of NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria have significant influence on prevalence of drug abuse?

Table 3: Summary of Mean and standard deviation on the knowledge level of NCE II biology students in Nigerian Colleges of Education.

S/N	Variables	SA		A		UN		D		SD		Mean	STD
		F.	%	F.	%	F.	%	F.	%	F.	%		
1	Drug abuse refers to use of illegal substances only	846	53.8	449	28.6	22	1.4	196	12.5	59	3.8	4.16	1.168
2	Mixing alcohol with certain medications can be	801	51.0	469	29.8	22	1.4	221	14.1	59	3.8	4.10	1.189

	dangerous and potentially life-threatening												
3	Drug addiction is a chronic disease that requires long-term treatment and support	803	51.1	482	30.7	31	2.0	31	2.0	197	12.5	4.13	1.164
4	Using Prescription drugs without a doctor's supervision is safe and poses no risks	831	52.9	464	29.5	22	1.4	196	12.5	59	3.8	4.15	1.165
5	Seeking professional help, such as counselling or rehabilitation, is an effective way to overcome drug addiction	844	53.7	453	28.8	20	1.3	196	12.5	59	3.8	4.16	1.166
6	Impaired judgement and decision making is a potential consequence of drug abuse	843	53.6	453	28.8	21	1.3	196	12.5	59	3.8	4.16	1.167
7	Physical dependence is a potential consequence of drug abuse	846	53.8	450	28.6	22	1.4	195	12.4	59	3.8	4.16	1.166
8	Improved academic performance is a potential consequence of drug abuse	846	53.8	455	28.9	21	1.3	191	12.2	59	3.8	4.17	1.161
9	Mental Health problem is a potential consequence of drug abuse	846	53.8	451	28.7	20	1.3	196	12.5	59	3.8	4.16	1.167
10	Sudden weight loss or gain is a sign or symptom of drug abuse	846	53.8	457	29.1	21	1.3	189	12.0	59	3.8	4.17	1.158
11	Increased social withdrawal is a sign or symptom of drug abuse	846	53.8	459	29.2	20	1.3	188	12.0	59	3.8	4.17	1.157
12	Difficulty concentrating is a sign or symptom of drug abuse	840	53.4	472	30	21	1.3	180	11.5	59	3.8	4.18	1.145
13	Healthy copying skills is an example of a risk factor for drug abuse	846	53.8	469	29.8	20	1.3	178	11.3	59	3.8	4.19	1.144
14	Stable family relationship is an example of a risk factor for drug abuse	839	53.4	488	31.0	20	1.3	166	10.6	59	3.8	4.20	1.126
15	What is the recommended course of action if you suspect a fellow student is struggling	846	53.8	463	29.5	22	1.4	182	11.6	59	3.8	4.18	1.150
	Aggregated Mean											4.162	1.159

Source: Field Survey, 2023

From the aggregated mean (4.162) and a standard deviation of 1.159, the decision mean is 2.50. The aggregated mean (4.162) of knowledge level of students is significantly above 2.50 which is the decision mean. The result means that majority of the respondents agreed that knowledge level of NCE II Biology students have significant influence on prevalence of drug abuse. This indicates that the students have a positive knowledge on drug abuse.

Research Question 2

Assessment of Knowledge, Attitude ... (Ezeaghasi, et. al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10654693>

Does the attitude of NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria towards drug abuse have significant influence on prevalence? To answer the research question frequency count, percentage of the students' response of aggregated Mean and Standard deviation were calculated and summary presented in table 4.

Table 4: Summary of Mean and standard deviation on the attitude level of NCE II biology students in Federal Colleges of Education.

S/N	Variables	SA		A		UN		D		SD		Mean	STD..
		F.	%	F.	%	F.	%	F.	%	F.	%		
1	I am concerned about the rate of drug abuse among NCE Students	15	1.0	167	10.6	1076	68.4	205	13.0	109	6.9	2.86	0.729
2	Drug abuse is a significant problem that needs to be addressed among NCE students	756	48.1	171	10.9	526	33.5	83	5.3	36	2.3	3.97	1.110
3	I am likely to engage in drug abuse in the future	93	5.9	14	0.9	2	0.1	21	1.3	1442	91.7	1.28	0.984
4	I find drug abuse behavior acceptable among my peers	2	0.1	152	9.7	361	23.0	919	58.5	138	8.8	2.34	0.775
5	I believe drug abuse prevention and intervention programs are effective in raising awareness and promoting a drug-free environment among NCE students	772	49.1	588	37.4	48	3.1	128	8.1	36	2.3	4.23	1.001
6	I am comfortable discussing drug abuse-related topics with my peers	387	24.6	748	47.6	191	12.2	187	11.9	59	3.8	3.77	1.063
7	It is important for NCE students to seek help or support if they are struggling with drugs abuse	613	39.0	661	42.0	109	6.9	140	8.9	49	3.1	4.05	1.046
8	Media and popular culture influence promoting drug abuse among NCE students	758	48.2	680	43.3	90	5.7	19	1.2	25	1.6	4.35	0.779
9	I am likely to intervene if I witness a fellow NCE student engaging in drug abuse	836	53.2	311	19.8	277	17.6	48	3.1	100	6.4	4.10	1.180
10	I am aware of the resources and support available on campus for NCE students struggling with drug abuse	846	53.8	417	26.5	155	9.9	110	7.0	44	2.8	4.22	1.060
11	I am happy with drug abuse because it symbolizes manhood	28	1.8	33	2.1	2	0.1	21	1.3	1488	94.7	1.15	0.686
12	I do not like drug abuse because it interferes with sports and social activities	965	61.4	369	23.5	14	0.9	188	12.0	36	2.3	4.30	1.104

Assessment of Knowledge, Attitude ... (Ezeaghasi, et. al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10654693>

Aggregated Mean	3.385	0.959
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Source: Field Survey, 2023.

The aggregated mean (3.385) and standard deviation of 0.959, It shows that majority of the students agreed that attitude of NCE II Biology students towards drug abuse have significant influence on prevalence of drug abuse. The table showed that majority of the students strongly agreed that effective raising awareness on Drug abuse will have significant effect on addressing the problem.

Research Question 3:

Do contributing factors Influence the prevalence of drug abuse among NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria? To answer this research, question the frequency count, percentage of the students' response of aggregated Mean and Standard deviation were calculated and summary presented in table 5.

Table 5: Summary of Mean and standard deviation on Contributing Factors to Drug Abuse

S/N	Variables	SA		A		UN		D		SD		Mean	STD. Dev.
		F.	%	F.	%	F.	%	F.	%	F.	%		
1	I have used illicit drugs (e.g Marijuana, cocaine, heroin) in my lifetime	157	10.0	211	13.4	73	4.6	340	21.6	791	50.3	2.11	1.405
2	I frequently use illicit drugs in the past year	221	14.1	175	11.1	192	12.2	925	58.8	559	3.8	2.73	1.157
3	I use medications without valid prescription	157	10.0	1111	70.7	201	12.8	94	6.0	9	0.6	3.84	0.701
4	I frequently make use of medications without valid prescription by doctors	980	62.3	419	26.7	8	0.5	128	8.1	37	2.4	4.38	1.009
5	I use drugs to improve my memory during examination	608	38.7	445	28.3	264	16.8	196	12.5	59	3.8	3.42	1.027
6	I have engaged in binge drinking (consuming a large amount of alcohol in a short period)	201	12.8	256	16.3	8	0.5	1071	68.1	36	2.3	2.69	1.163
7	I have used tobacco products (e.g cigarettes, e-cigarettes, smokeless tobacco) in the past year	264	16.8	275	17.5	21	1.3	196	12.5	816	51.9	2.35	1.620
8	I often use drugs during examination	828	52.7	275	17.5	256	16.3	177	11.3	36	2.5	3.34	0.956
9	I make use of injections to take drugs	264	16.8	275	17.5	8	0.5	980	62.3	45	2.9	2.83	1.248
10	I use drugs to achieve feelings of joy and happiness	529	33.7	449	28.6	339	21.6	196	12.5	59	3.8	3.52	1.075
Aggregated Mean											3.077	1.142	

Source; Field Survey, 2023

From the responses, the aggregated mean (3.077) and standard deviation (1.142). The students strongly agreed that contributing factors to Drug Abuse Influence the Prevalence among NCE II Biology Students of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria. From the table majority of the students strongly agreed that they use drugs without valid prescription from doctors, during examinations to improve memory and also to achieve feelings of joy and happiness (Muhammad, 2021).

Assessment of Knowledge, Attitude ... (Ezeaghasi, et. al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10654693>

Research Question 4:

Do intervention strategies assessment influence the prevalence of drug abuse among NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria? To answer the research question frequency count, percentage of the students' response of aggregated Mean and Standard deviation were calculated and summary presented in table 6.

Table 6: Summary of Mean and standard deviation on Intervention Strategies Assessment to Drug Abuse

S/N	Variables	SA		A		UN		D		SD		Mean	STD. Dev.
		F.	%	F.	%	F.	%	F.	%	F.	%		
1	Peer Pressure is influential in encouraging drug abuse among NCE students	780	49.6	515	32.8	22	1.4	196	12.5	59	3.8	4.12	1.155
2	I believe that stress and academic pressure contribute to drug abuse among NCE students to a great extent	718	45.7	577	36.7	22	1.4	196	12.5	59	3.8	4.08	1.141
3	Family background is contributory to NCE students engaging in drug abuse	741	47.1	554	35.2	22	1.4	196	12.5	59	3.8	4.10	1.146
4	Poverty is a contributing factor to drug abuse among NCE students	846	53.8	449	28.6	22	1.4	196	12.5	59	3.8	4.16	1.168
5	Lack of awareness about the risks of drug abuse plays a significant role in the prevalence of drug abuse among NCE students	846	53.8	449	28.6	22	1.4	196	12.5	59	3.8	4.16	1.168
6	Media and popular culture promotes drug abuse among NCE students	846	53.8	449	28.6	22	1.4	196	12.5	59	3.8	4.16	1.168
7	Early aggressive behaviors contributes to drug abuse among NCE Students	846	53.8	449	28.6	22	1.4	196	12.5	59	3.8	4.16	1.168
8	Lack of parental supervision adds to drug abuse among NCE students	846	53.8	449	28.6	22	1.4	196	12.5	59	3.8	4.16	1.168
9	Educational campaigns and prevention programs helps in reducing drug abuse among NCE students	846	53.8	449	28.6	22	1.4	196	12.5	59	3.8	4.16	1.168
10	Mental health disorders contributes to drug abuse among NCE students	846	53.8	449	28.6	22	1.4	196	12.5	59	3.8	4.16	1.168
Aggregated Mean											4.142	1.162	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

The aggregated mean (4.142) and standard deviation (1.162). The students strongly agreed that Intervention Strategies Assessment Influence the Prevalence of Drug Abuse among NCE II Biology students of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria. They agreed that Poverty, Lack of parental supervision, Early aggressive behaviors and Lack of awareness about the risks of drug abuse plays a significant role in the prevalence of drug abuse (Umukoro., Eduviere., Ahama., Moke., Edje., Omorodion & Ovigie 2021)

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Research Question 5:

What is the relationship between knowledge level, attitude, prevalence and contributing factors to drug abuse among NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education, Nigeria? To answer the research question, frequency count, percentage of the students' response of aggregated Mean and Standard deviation were calculated and summary presented in table 7.

Table 7: Summary of Mean and standard deviation on the relationship between knowledge level, attitude, prevalence and contributing factors to drug abuse among NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education.

S/N	Variables	SA		A		UN		D		SD		Mean	STD. Dev.
		F.	%	F.	%	F.	%	F.	%	F.	%		
1	I am aware of drug abuse prevention and intervention programs provided by the college	844	53.7	466	29.6	22	1.4	196	12.5	44	2.8	4.19	1.125
2	The prevention and intervention programs are aware of its effectiveness	829	52.7	497	31.6	22	1.4	165	10.5	59	3.8	4.19	1.124
3	I have personally participated in drug abuse prevention or intervention programs offered by the college	846	53.8	471	30.0	22	1.4	174	11.1	59	3.8	4.19	1.139
4	Psychosocial interventions can effectively help with drug disorders	846	53.8	463	29.5	22	1.4	182	11.6	59	3.8	4.18	1.150
5	Short-term interventions can reduce alcohol use or related problems for adolescents and young adults	824	52.4	487	31.0	22	1.4	180	11.5	59	3.8	4.17	1.143
6	Juvenile drug courts do not have an effect on drug and alcohol offense recidivism of future drug use	844	53.7	464	29.5	22	1.4	183	11.6	59	3.8	4.18	1.151
7	Drug abuse prevention and intervention resources on the college campus is very accessible	816	51.9	493	31.4	20	1.3	184	11.7	59	3.8	4.16	1.146
Aggregated Mean											4.180	1.139	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

From the responses, the aggregated mean (4.180) and standard deviation (1.139) strongly agreed that there is relationship among knowledge level, attitude, prevalence and contributing factors to drug abuse among NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education, Nigeria. Majority of the students are aware of prevention and intervention programs provided by the colleges and that Psychosocial interventions can effectively help with drug disorders.

Hypothesis 1:

Knowledge Level of NCE II Biology Students in Federal Colleges of Education have no Significant Influence on Prevalence of Drug Abuse. Chi-square test was used to analyze the data collected and summary presented in table 8.

Table 8: Summary of chi-square test on the Knowledge Level of NCE II Biology Students in Federal Colleges of Education.

Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)

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Pearson Chi-Square	6111.265 ^a	340	.000
Likelihood Ratio	3037.121	340	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	336.010	1	<.000
N of Valid Cases	1572		

a. 333 cells (88.1%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .00.

From the table above, the knowledge of NCE students in Federal College of Education have significant influence on the prevalence of drug abuse at ($p < 0.05$). The p-value of $< .000$ is less than the 0.05 level of significance, suggesting that there is a statistically significant difference. Based on the result, the null hypothesis which stated that Knowledge level of NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigerian have no significant influence on Prevalence of Drug Abuse is therefore rejected implying that knowledge level influence prevalence of drug abuse among the students.

Hypothesis 2:

Attitude of NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education, Nigeria towards drug abuse have no significant influence on prevalence. Chi-square test was used to analyze the data collected and summary presented in table 9.

Table 9: Summary of chi-square test on the attitude level of NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education, Nigeria towards drug abuse and prevalence.

	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	9958.003 ^a	560	.000
Likelihood Ratio	4627.362	560	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	285.448	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	1572		

a. 535 cells (87.8%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .00.

From the table above, the attitude of NCE students in Nigerian College of Education have significant influence on the prevalence of drug abuse ($p < 0.05$). The hypothesis was carried out in order to test whether attitude of NCE students towards drug abuse influence prevalence of drug abuse. Based on the result, the null hypothesis which stated that Attitude of NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education towards drug abuse have no significant influence on prevalence of drug abuse is therefore rejected implying that attitude towards drug abuse influence prevalence of drug abuse among the students.

Hypothesis 3:

Contributing factors to drug abuse have no significant influence on the prevalence among NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education. Chi-square test was used to analyze the data collected and summary presented in table 10.

Table 10 Summary of chi-square test on the Contributing factors to drug abuse and prevalence among NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education?

	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	5447.220 ^a	120	.000
Likelihood Ratio	3254.319	120	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	352.474	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	1572		

a. 98 cells (66.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .01.

From the table above, the Contributing factors to drug abuse have significant influence on the prevalence of drug abuse among NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education ($p < 0.05$). The hypothesis was carried out in order to find out if the identified contributing factors to Drug Abuse Influence Prevalence of Drug Abuse among NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria. Based on the result, the null hypothesis which stated that Contributing

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factors to drug abuse have no significant influence on the prevalence of drug abuse among NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education. The significance value is 0.00 (i.e., $p = 0.00$), below 0.05. This is because the p -value of 0.00 is substantially lower than the threshold value of 0.05. then the null hypothesis is rejected implying that identified contributing factors to drug abuse influence prevalence of drug abuse.

Hypothesis 4:

Intervention strategies assessment have no significant influence on the prevalence of drug abuse among NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education. Chi-square test was used to analyze the data collected and summary presented in table 11.

Table 11: Summary of Chi-square test on Intervention Strategies Assessment on the prevalence of drug abuse among NCEII Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education, Nigeria.?

	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	6262.129 ^a	280	.000
Likelihood Ratio	3003.468	280	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	335.727	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	1572		

a. 275 cells (87.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .00.

From the result obtained, Intervention Strategies Assessment have significant influence on the prevalence of drug abuse among the students at ($p < 0.05$). The hypothesis was carried out in order to find out whether Intervention Strategies Assessment Influence Prevalence of Drug Abuse. The significance value is 0.00 (i.e., $p = 0.00$), below 0.05. This is because the p -value of 0.00 is substantially lower than the threshold value of 0.05. Based on the result, the null is therefore rejected implying that Intervention Strategies Assessment Significantly Influence Prevalence of Drug Abuse among the students.

Hypothesis 5:

There is no significant relationship among Knowledge Level, Attitude, Prevalence and Contributing Factors to Drug Abuse among NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education, Nigeria. Pearson Moment Correlation test was used to analyze the data collected and summary presented in table 12.

Table 12: Summary of Pearson Moment Correlation test on the relationship between Knowledge Level, Attitude, Prevalence and Contributing Factors to Drug Abuse among NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education, Nigeria.

		Knowledge	Attitude	Prevalence	Contributing
Knowledge	Pearson Correlation	1	.962**	.462**	.997**
	Sig. (2-Tailed)		.000	.000	.000
	N	1572	1572	1572	1572
Attitude	Pearson Correlation	.962**	1	.426**	.960**
	Sig. (2-Tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	1572	1572	1572	1572
Prevalence	Pearson Correlation	.462**	.426**	1	.474**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	1572	1572	1572	1572

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Contributing factor	Pearson Correlation	.997**	.960**	.474**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	1572	1572	1572	1572

There is a strong positive relationship among knowledge level, attitude, prevalence and contributing factors to drug abuse among NCE II Biology students and is significant at ($p < 0.05$). The hypothesis was carried out in order to find out whether relationship exists among knowledge level, attitude, prevalence of drug abuse and contributing factors to drug abuse among students. The Pearson Correlation was used to analyze the data as presented in Table 11 at $p \leq 0.05$. The significance value is 0.00 (i.e., $p = 0.00$), below 0.05. This is because the p-value of 0.00 is lower than the threshold value of 0.05.

Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship among knowledge level, attitude, prevalence and contributing factors to drug abuse among NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education is rejected.

Discussion of Findings

This study had 1572 respondents, 943 (60%) were males, 629 (40%) were females, 1356 (86.3%) were within the ages of 16-22 years, 155 (9.9%) were within the ages of 23-26 years, 49(3.1%) were within the ages of 27 and above. The majority of the respondent falls within the age range of 16-22 years and male student having the higher proportion. The study is in line with the works of Adeyemo, Okpala & Ohaeri (2016), Ofili, Ugorume, Oyibocha, Eziashi (2021) and Abuhuraira., Yusuf., Muhammad., Mamman., Solomon., Umar & Muhammad, (2021), who agreed that drug abusers are within the above range and majority are male.

The findings of this study revealed that NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education, Nigeria were knowledgeable and had positive attitude to the use drugs and abuse. The result revealed knowledge level (4.162) and attitude (3.385) have significant influence at $p \leq 0.05$ on the prevalence, this findings tallies with the study of Adibe ,Anene- Okeke, Igboeli & Chibueze (2022) on knowledge ,attitude and prevalence of drug abuse among the students. Majority of the students agreed that the contributing factors such as using drugs to achieve feeling to joy and happiness (33.7%) often use drugs during exams (52.7 %) frequently use medication without valid prescription (62.3%) influence the prevalence of drug abuse, this correlates with studies conducted by Adeyemo, Okpala & Ohaeri (2016) that Most students abuse drugs as a result of poor teacher/parental upbringing and also the influence of peer pressure. the null hypothesis which stated that Contributing factors to drug abuse have no significant influence on the prevalence of drug abuse was rejected at $p \leq 0.05$ level of significance implying that identified contributing factors to drug abuse influence prevalence rate. The study also said that Intervention Strategies Assessment Influence the Prevalence of Drug Abuse. The result of the finding concurs with that of Akinsefunmi, Rita, Aminat & Rufus (2016) that Intervention Strategies Assessment Influence the Prevalence of Drug Abuse. Finally, the study strongly agreed that there is relationship among knowledge level, attitude, prevalence and contributing factors to drug abuse.

Conclusion

The study showed that the students in Federal Colleges of Education, Nigeria had adequate knowledge and positive attitude towards drug abuse which influence the prevalence among NCE II Biology students. Contributing factors (feelings of joy and improve memory during examination) influence prevalence of drug abuse. Intervention strategies assessment (lack of awareness, peer pressure influence and lack of parental supervision) significantly influence prevalence of drug abuse. Finally, there is Significant relationship among knowledge level, attitude, prevalence, contributing factors and Intervention strategies assessment to drug abuse among NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education, Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this work, we recommend that more awareness should be created on the effects of drug abuse among students of Federal Colleges of Education, Nigeria which on the other hand will reduce the prevalence rate. The study also recommends that drug abuse information that addresses social norms and education should be included in the college of education curriculum as a general study for the students as these may have protective outcome.

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Assessment of Mathematics Learning on Entrepreneurial Skills Development among Secondary School Students in Kontagora Local Government Area, Niger State

Awoyale, Olusegun¹

Email: awoyaleolusegun@gmail.com

Tel: 08039092004

Niyi, Olorunsola Oriola¹

Email: niyisola@gmail.com

Tel: 08037583903

¹Department of Mathematics, Federal College of Education, Kontagora, Niger State, Nigeria.

Abstract:

This paper discussed the assessment of mathematics learning on entrepreneurial skill development among secondary school students in Kontagora. The study revealed the importance of mathematics education in skills acquisition for entrepreneurial development. The research questions such as what is the mean response of students on importance of learning mathematics for entrepreneurial development and what is the mean response of students' perceptions on relevance of mathematics for entrepreneurial development for economic diversification and poverty reduction were developed. The hypotheses the mean response of students on importance of learning mathematics for entrepreneurial development is not significantly high. There is no significant difference in the mean response of students' perceptions in public and private schools on mathematics skills acquisition for economic diversification and poverty reduction. A survey designed was adopted for the study. The population of the study was students in Kontagora Local Government Area, Niger State. A random sampling technique was used to obtain the sampled used for the work. The sample consists of 100 students. Basic Mathematics Skills Questionnaire (BMSQ) was used for data collection. The mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while the research hypotheses were tested using t- test at 0.05 level of significant. The findings of the study show that the students agreed that mathematics provides basic skills for entrepreneurship development which in turn promotes economic development and reduce poverty. Recommendation such as the entrepreneurship education should be encouraged at all level of education among others is suggested.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, Mathematics, Skills.

Introduction

In Nigeria today, unemployment has become a daily challenge. Nigeria is now facing one of the greatest threats to her existence as a nation, because of high level of unemployment, especially among the youths. This has led to poverty, banditry, kidnapping, and unrest among the unemployed people. Poverty is a global issue for both developed and underdeveloped countries. Poverty takes different forms. It can be in form of both income and non-income dimensions. To some people, poverty is a state of lacking the human basic needs such as adequate nutritious food, clothing, housing, clean water and health services, glaringly unemployment leads to poverty. In Nigeria unemployment is increasing every day. It is pertinent to know that Nigeria at 63 years of independence is still facing the problem of unemployment. Among other factors, this can be attributed to lack of basic skills in learners which could help them to venture in to entrepreneurship when they pass out from school. Also majority of the graduates from tertiary institutions who are job seekers are forced to venture into frauds of any kind. The era of depending on government for job is almost eroded, as government alone could not cater for job creation. There is no doubt that our graduates may have employment opportunities if they are adequately provided with entrepreneurial education (Olaniyan & Ezekiel, 2019). From the aforementioned there is a need to close the gap through skills acquisition because without entrepreneurial skills youth development would be hampered and this in turn would lead to poverty. Since there is population explosion, there is need to provide room for students' self-reliance and this can be done through entrepreneurship education. When students have sufficient knowledge in entrepreneurship education, it will help them to be self-employed later in future and contributes meaningfully to the society.

Mathematics provides fundamental skills for societal transformations. Today, mathematics is the language and key to every days' activities in science, technology, commerce and even art (Sadi & Haruna, 2020). Mathematics is a powerful tool

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for technological development. It solves security, poverty problems and provides necessary skills for economic diversification. Mathematics as a tool, its knowledge and skills are bedrock of all societal transformation and transfer of ideas into reality (Abubakar, Wokoma & Afebuame, 2012). Also, Malik and Salman (2018) stated that mathematics is a core subject which serves as fundamental for pupils' level of thinking, skill development and problem solving. It is interesting to know that the advancement in the areas of science and technology are indebted to mathematics to a great extent. The knowledge of mathematics is fundamental in addressing the critical issues of security problems, poverty alleviation and economic transformation. Mathematics is a core subject which serves as fundamental for learners' level of thinking, skill development and problem solving, which are fundamental for future task. It is interesting to know that the advancement in the areas of science and technology are indebted to mathematics to a great extent.

Mathematics Education is the practice of teaching and learning mathematics along with problem solving techniques and issues relating to curriculum (Ugboduma & Alio, 2014). The role of mathematics education in a nation's development cannot be over emphasized. Mathematics education improves the cognitive development of learners, which in turns gives room for reasoning, analytical and problem -solving skills acquisitions which are fundamental in the labour market and entrepreneurship development. Mathematics education provides skills that are applicable in all facets of life. According to Omole (2017) and Federal Ministry of Education. (2007), at basic level the following topics are taught: number and numeration, measurement, basic operation, geometry, algebraic processes and everyday statistics. These help to achieve objectives of teaching mathematics at this level. It includes to:

1. Acquire mathematical literacy necessary to function in an informative age.
2. Cultivate the understanding and application of mathematical skills and concepts necessary to thrive in an ever-changing technological world and
3. Develop essential elements of problem solving, communication, reasoning and connection within their study of mathematics.

Entrepreneurship Education is that aspect of education which equips an individual with the mind-set to undertake the risk of venturing into something new by applying knowledge and skill acquisition in schools (Omokaro, 2019). Dianda and Azyme (2020) says that entrepreneurship is a part of business life that contributes towards successful organization. The authors said further that business is healthy when there is entrepreneurial skills and management are adopted for changing and learning. According to Lawal et al, (2023), entrepreneurship education is seeing as an aspect of education that equips an individual with the mindset to undertake the risk of venturing into something new by applying knowledge and skills acquired in school. Entrepreneurship can be described as means of equipping the individual through skills acquisition in different vocational trades to harness investment opportunity and promote self-employment. Furthermore, entrepreneurship can be described as a process of creating something new, in different ways through the skills acquisitions for taking risk for the purpose of making profit and adding value to life. Entrepreneurship is an integral part of industrial growth, which is a backbone of any nation's development. Entrepreneurship education builds in a learner the necessary skills for self –reliance and society development. Adeagbo (2018) said that the students had positive attitude towards entrepreneurship and they were willing to be self-employed or become entrepreneur after graduation. According to Fada et al (2017), entrepreneurship education prepares students to establish career in entrepreneurship.

A nation where entrepreneurship is accorded recognition such a country will have very low unemployment rate and poverty reduction. Mathematics is a creative discipline which can be described as a huge body of knowledge which is essential for the development of entrepreneurship skills, because everywhere we go, everything we do or propose to do, either structures of mathematics or its applications play a vital role (Aliyu et al. 2017). In a related development, Adegoke (2013) stated that students develop numeracy, reasoning, thinking skills and problems solving skills through the learning and application of Mathematics. The authors added that the importance of mathematics is not limited to every science and technology but also in every living and the work place. Also, Ezech and Uqwanyyi (2013) captured a huge of career opportunities in banking, engineering, architecture, information technology, accountancy that heavily rely on mathematics principle that could generate entrepreneurship opportunities.

The philosophy of Nigeria education and the philosophy of mathematics education both aim at developing skills, competence and knowledge that could propel every individual in to entrepreneurship activities (Olaniyan & Ezekiel, 2019). The teachers play a major role in making this philosophy comes to reality. Effective teaching of mathematics must be the concern of all stakeholders to provide the prerequisite skills for the entrepreneurship activities to triumph. The situation of unemployment in the world today call for attention of all stakeholders. Every year, fresh graduates are released to job market without acquiring necessary entrepreneurial skills that can help them to live on their own and contribute to the development of

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their community. To curb this trend and to minimize overdependence on white collar job, entrepreneurship development must continue to give priority to at all level of education in the country. Therefore, this paper examines the role of teaching mathematics in the development of entrepreneurial skills among secondary school students,

Objective of the Study

The purpose of this study is to investigate senior secondary school students' perceptions on learning mathematics for entrepreneurship development. Specifically, the study sought to investigate the following:

1. To know students' perceptions on importance of mathematics in entrepreneurial development;
2. To compare male and female students' perceptions on importance of mathematics for entrepreneurial development;
3. To examine students' perceptions of relevance of mathematics based on intention to work after school;
4. To determine the basic mathematics skills relevant for the development of entrepreneurial skills.

Research Questions

1. What is the mean response of students on importance of learning mathematics for skills acquisitions for entrepreneurial development?
2. What is the mean response of students on relevance of mathematics for entrepreneurial development for economic diversification and poverty reduction?
3. What is the mean response of male and female students on relevance of mathematics for entrepreneurial development?

Hypotheses

1. H_{O1} . The mean response of students on importance of mathematics learning for entrepreneurial development is not significantly high.
2. H_{O2} . There is no significant difference in the mean response of students on importance of mathematics learning in public and private schools on skills acquisition for economic diversification and poverty reduction.
3. H_{O3} . There is no significant difference in the mean response of male and female students on importance of learning mathematics for entrepreneurial development.

Methodology

A descriptive survey research design was used to carry out the study. The population of the study was students in the secondary schools in Kontagora Local Government Area, the sample consists of 100 students drawn from SS2 and SS3 secondary schools in Kontagora Local Government Area, Niger state. Both private and secondary school students were used. The first section of the questionnaire was used to elicit general information on age, gender and type of schools. The second section consists of a checklist of basic mathematics skills questionnaire. The research instruments designed for data collection was a 16-items Basic Mathematics Skills Questionnaire (BMSQ) constructed by the researcher on a four -point scale of Very High (VH), High (H), Low (L), Very Low (VL) representing 4,3 ,2 and 1 respectively. The questionnaire was given to two mathematics teachers for validation. The questionnaire was administered with the help of teachers in the selected schools. The mean and standard deviation and t-test were employed with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version for data analysis.

Result

Research Question 1

What is the mean response of students on importance of learning mathematics for skills acquisitions for entrepreneurial development

Table 1. Mean response of importance of mathematics education in the development of entrepreneurial skills acquisition.

S/N	Items description	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
1	The use of mathematical skills can lead to acquisition of creative entrepreneurship skills	3.53	24.67	Accepted
2	With the help of mathematical skills, entrepreneurs are able to diversify their knowledge in their enterprises.	3.56	25.89	Accepted
3	Mathematical skills acquisition help me in everyday situations.	3.13	15.20	Accepted

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4	It helps in estimation and approximation, that is, in estimating quantity, length, distance.	3.70	31.61	Accepted
5	The knowledge of mathematics operations can provide growth in business.	3.58	25.99	Accepted
6	I understand that a good knowledge of mathematics can help an entrepreneur to analysis gains and loss in business.	3.76	32.34	Accepted
7	The mathematical skills help in reading, interpreting, constructing tables, charts and graphs.	3.40	23.22	Rejected
8	Mathematical skills help in computer literacy.	3.02	15.33	Accepted
9	The knowledge of mathematics help students to see the relationship between mathematics and business.	3.49	23.44	Accepted
10	The knowledge of mathematics is good for predictions for future events in businesses.	3.10	15.02	Accepted
11	A good knowledge of mathematics helps entrepreneurs In planning for poverty reduction.	3.22	17.33	Accepted
12	A good knowledge of mathematics helps entrepreneurs in planning for economic growth.	3.22	18.16	Accepted
13	It helps in planning for job creations	3.18	16.58	Accepted
14	The knowledge of mathematics helps entrepreneurs in planning for employment.	3.22	18.16	Accepted
15	The mathematical skills help entrepreneurs in planning for infrastructural development.	3.19	20.89	Accepted
16	A good knowledge of mathematics helps entrepreneurs to reduce hunger in the land.	2.64	7.77	Accepted
Total Mean Weight Average/Cluster Mean		3.31	20.72	Accepted

Table 1 shows that the mean of each items ranges from 2.64 to 3.76 are greater than 2.5 the cutoff point. Moreover, the cluster means of 3.42 was found to be above the cut-off point of 2.5. This implies that the respondents (students) perception on learning mathematics for skills acquisition for entrepreneurial development is affirmative.

Research Question 2

What is the mean response of students on the relevance of mathematics for entrepreneurial skills acquisition for economic diversification and poverty reduction?

Table 2. Mean responses on extent to which mathematics enhances entrepreneurial skills.

S/N	Items description	Private		Public		Decision
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
11	A good knowledge of mathematics helps entrepreneurs to diversify their enterprises to reduce poverty.	3.14	3.33	3.30	8.60	Accepted
12	With the help of mathematics skills, entrepreneurs are able to diversify their knowledge in their business for economic growth.	3.08	3.40	3.22	9.35	Accepted
13	It helps entrepreneurs to diversify their knowledge in their business for job creations	3.12	3.25	3.23	8.49	Accepted
14	The knowledge of mathematics helps entrepreneurs in planning for employment.	3.14	3.33	3.35	9.42	Accepted
15	The mathematical skills help entrepreneurs in planning for infrastructural development.	3.16	3.18	3.09	9.06	Accepted
16	A good knowledge of mathematics helps entrepreneurs to diversify their knowledge in their business to reduce hunger in the land.	2.46	2.88	2.52	6.48	Accepted
Total Mean Weight Average/Cluster Mean		3.02	11.58	3.12	10.39	Accepted

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Based on the data presented in table 2, it was evident that all the 11-16 items were rated above 2.5

The grand mean for public school is 3.34 while that of private school is 3.33 meaning that the respondents agreed positively that mathematics skill acquisition boost entrepreneurial development. This also implies that there was no difference between the students' view in public school and that of their private school counterparts towards relevance of mathematics entrepreneurial skills acquisition.

Research Question 3.

What is the mean response of male and female students on relevance of mathematics skills acquisition for entrepreneurial development?

Table 3: Mean rating on how mathematics education provides entrepreneurial skills acquisition.

S/N	Items description	Male		Female		Decision
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
1	The use of mathematical skills can lead to acquisition of creative entrepreneurship skills	3.57	12.68	3.58	13.07	Accepted
2	With the help of mathematical skills, entrepreneurs are able to diversify their knowledge in their enterprises.	3.71	11.81	3.51	12.20	Accepted
3	Mathematical skills acquisition helps me in everyday situations.	3.33	9.71	3.38	10.44	Accepted
4	It helps in estimation and approximation, that is, in estimating quantity, length, distance.	3.80	17.95	3.71	12.04	Accepted
5	The knowledge of mathematics operations can provide growth in business.	3.40	11.93	3.67	14.43	Accepted
6	I understand that a good knowledge of mathematics can help an entrepreneur to analysis gains and loss in business.	3.91	19.92	3.78	16.52	Accepted
7	The mathematical skills help in reading, interpreting, constructing tables, charts and graphs.	3.27	13.35	3.33	10.31	Rejected
8	Mathematical skills help in computer literacy.	2.93	8.74	2.92	6.93	Accepted
9	The knowledge of mathematics help students to see the relationship between mathematics and business.	3.39	12.50	3.53	12.42	Accepted
10	The knowledge of mathematics is good for predictions for future events in businesses.	3.47	11.84	3.11	8.06	Accepted
11	A good knowledge of mathematics helps entrepreneurs In planning for poverty reduction.	3.13	7.63	3.30	9.20	Accepted
12	A good knowledge of mathematics helps entrepreneurs in planning for economic growth.	3.40	11.93	3.22	10.24	Accepted
13	It helps in planning for job creations	3.07	9.20	3.23	9.20	Accepted
14	The knowledge of mathematics helps entrepreneurs in planning for employment.	3.11	9.00	3.35	10.80	Accepted
15	The mathematical skills help entrepreneurs in planning for infrastructural development.	3.17	10.75	3.09	9.81	Accepted
16	A good knowledge of mathematics helps entrepreneurs to reduce hunger in the land.	2.54	5.07	2.52	4.55	Accepted
Total Mean Weight Average/Cluster Mean		3.33	11.50	10.64	3.33	Accepted

Table three indicates that the grand mean for male students is 3.33 while that female is also 3.33. The difference in grand mean is zero. This implies that there was no difference between the male and female students' perception towards relevance of mathematics for entrepreneurial development.

Hypotheses Testing

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HO₁: The mean response of students on importance of mathematics learning for entrepreneurial development is not significantly high.

Table 4: t- test of students’ response on mathematics education for skills acquisition for entrepreneurial development.

Description	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Agreed	70	3.035	10.39	88	2.001	1.987	NS
Disagreed	20	0.279	10.52				

Table 4 revealed that t-calculated is greater than the t-critical. Thus, the Null Hypothesis I (H₀₁) at P<0.05 which stated that “The students’ perception on learning mathematics for entrepreneurial development is not significantly high” was rejected. However, the mean perception of students’ affirmation of 3.035 was found to be significantly greater than the mean of students’ perception depicting disapproval is 0.279. This implies that the students’ perception on learning mathematics for entrepreneurial development is high.

HO₂: There is no significant difference in the mean response of students on importance of learning mathematics in public and private schools on skills acquisition for economic diversification and poverty reduction.

Table 5 showing t- test of students’ response on importance of mathematics skills acquisition for entrepreneurial development based on school - type

Variable	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Public School	40	3.34	10.39	88	0.0259	1.987	NS
Private School	50	3.28	11.58				

In table 5, t-calculated of 0.00259 is less than t-critical of 1.987. Hence, Hypothesis II (H₀₂) which states that “there is no significant difference between the students’ perceptions in public and private schools on learning mathematics for entrepreneurial development” was accepted. However, the mean perception of public-school students of 3.34 was found to be greater than the mean of private school students’ perception of 3.28. They both agree that skills acquisition plays important role in grow of economy and poverty reduction.

HO₃: There is no significant difference in the mean response of male and female students on importance of mathematics learning for entrepreneurial development.

Table 6: t- test of male and female students’ perceptions on mathematics skills acquisition for entrepreneurial development

Gender	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Male	46	3.33	11.50	88	0.001	1.987	NS
Female	44	3.31	10.64				

In table 6, t-calculated of 0.001 is less than t-critical of 1.987. Hence, Hypothesis III (H₀₃) which states that “there is no significant difference in male and female students’ perception on learning mathematics for entrepreneurial development” was accepted. This shows that there is no gender difference in their perceptions.

Discussion of Findings

Data represented in table one shows that the students agreed that mathematics provides necessary skills acquisition for entrepreneurial development. They agreed that mathematics skills acquisition help them in daily activities. Also, the grand mean of 3.42 obtained shows that the respondent agrees to the items such as that the knowledge of mathematics helps in analyzing of profit made, reading, interpreting, constructing tables, diversifying of enterprises among others to venture into entrepreneurial career choice. The finding from the study in research question 2 revealed that there was no significant difference in the students’ perception in public and that of private schools’ counterparts towards relevance of mathematics for entrepreneurial development. They both agreed that mathematics plays major roles in skills acquisition for entrepreneurial development. This implies that the application of skills acquisition by entrepreneurs helps to diversify their knowledge in their business for economic growth, poverty reduction, creation of jobs among others. Entrepreneurship will boost their carrier choice as entrepreneurs which help them to solve their problems and the society. The finding was supported by Adeagbo (2018) who said that the students had positive attitude towards entrepreneurship and they were willing to be self-employed or become

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entrepreneur after graduation. Also, the study is supported by Fada et al (2017) which agreed that entrepreneurship education prepares students to establish career in entrepreneurship, Also Lawal et al (2023) agreed with the result, by saying that the *entrepreneurship education provides an experiential training for students which allow them to apply the skills acquired to establish career in entrepreneurship.*

The finding from the study in research question 3 indicated that there was no gender difference in students' perception towards relevance of mathematics for entrepreneurial development. They all viewed that mathematics skills are useful for entrepreneurial development. The result of hypotheses revealed that the students' perception on learning mathematics for entrepreneurial development is high. Also, it showed that the students were of the opinion that there is application of mathematics skills acquisition in the lives of entrepreneurs, which gives room for diversification in business endeavors.

Conclusion

It must be noted that all educational objectives are stated by the philosophy of a particular country in question. Therefore, objectives of teacher education are based on the philosophy of education in Nigeria. It is also observed that development is far from a nation that did not encourage quality entrepreneurship education, because products of such educational system cannot contribute greatly to the development of the society. Based on the findings, the students' perception on mathematical skills acquisition for entrepreneurial development is encouraging. Thus, the study concludes that the students were willing to learn mathematics for necessary skills acquisition to become entrepreneurs after their study in school, as the knowledge acquired from entrepreneurship would equip them with necessary skills and knowledge to become successful business persons and makes them to be self-reliance.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made

1. The entrepreneurship education should be encouraged at all level of education
2. All stakeholders should provide enabling environments for mathematics teachers to improve mathematics education in Nigeria.
3. Students should be encouraged to show positive attitude towards the learning of mathematics

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Assessment of National Security and Female Inclusivity: Challenges for Nigerian Peacekeepers

Ekuerhare, Sylvia Efe

Email: efe_sylvia@yahoo.com

Tel: 08023282224

Directorate of General Studies, Federal University of Petroleum Resources, Effurun, Delta State. Nigeria

Abstract

The study examined assessment of national security and female inclusivity: challenges for Nigerian peacekeepers. The study adopts the mixed studies systematic review by deployed study that adopted different research design method such as quantitative, qualitative, review among others between years 2000 and 2021. The population, intervention, comparison, outcome and study (PICOS) framework were used to inform the search strategy and initial searches were conducted on the initiation of search process which commenced on February 12, 2021 and also repeated on December 06, 2021 so as to cover up for gaps of relevant resources especially during the course of the writing of and reviewing the study. The search phase identified 86 papers; only 6 papers were eventually considered through abstract analysis. The findings of the study revealed that for effective and sustainable national security to be achieved by the Nigeria peacemakers which include the Nigerian Army, Nigeria Police Force, Military Joint Task Forces, the Nigerian Security and Civil Defence Corps, Nigerian Prisons Service, among others, there is need for the inclusion of gender relation to better involve female personnel in national security matters. Hence, attaining sustainable development and national security would be a mirage in Nigeria and the various efforts to achieve sustainable national security would be futile like was achieved in the past strategies. To this end, this study recommended that the proportion of women intake in the various Nigeria Force recruit should be increased so as to give room for a majority of women in the society to contribute and play their role in ensuring national security.

Keywords: Gender, Security, Challenges, Nigeria, Peacekeeping

Introduction

Security issues have been common phenomena at the local, national, regional and global levels hence, in trying to maintain peace and harmony in the society, stakeholders such as governments, policy makers, international organizations, security agents, among others have tried to ensure effective security. Hence, every nation ensures security from terrorism, crime, economic, political, homeland, energy, environment, food, and cyber related issues hence national security (Holmes, 2015). The concept of security has been noted to be a very complex issue hence, several definitions have been provided to it but the concept definition should cut across several of the arms of the nation which include human, economic energy, environment, food, and cyber related issues. For example, Osisanya (2022) noted that national security is the ability of a state to provide protection and defend its citizens. National security could also be defined as the security and defence of a sovereign state which also includes the citizens, economy, and institutions, which is regarded as a duty of government. It is also defined as the requirement to maintain the survival of the state by using powers which cuts across the economic, diplomacy, projection and political powers (Science Daily, 2022). According to Paleri (2008); Orhero (2020) and Uzodimma (2020), national security is the capability of a nation to overcome the multi-dimensional threats to the apparent well-being of its people and its survival as a nation-state at any given time, by balancing all instruments of state policy through governance and is extendable to global security by variables external to it. National security has two facets and include the external and internal (Paeri, 2008; Uzodimma, 2020). The external security involves the security challenges that originate from outside while those generated within the nation are termed internal security issues. Tackling these two forms of security are germane to national development.

In Nigeria, national security is a major challenge (Epron, 2018; Nwagboso, 2018). Despite the fact that Nigeria has the biggest economy in Africa and among the biggest in the world, security challenges have been a major problem affecting the nation's economy and there have been no clear-cut policies in place to address this high level of security problems in the nation. There are several incidences of insecurity issue in ritual killings, religious and political killing, cyber-crimes, car theft, carjacking, advanced free fraud, drug trafficking, human trafficking, terror-attacks by Islamic extremists in Jos and the North East, frequent clashes between farmers and herdsmen in the North-Central among others. Consequently, these security challenges have posed elastic threats to the nation's corporate existence and also undermined the quest for solidarity and unity in diversity in Nigeria (Nwagboso, 2018; Epron, 2019). Olufemi (2015) and Epron (2019) noted that several efforts have been

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put in place to manage Nigeria security issues by the government to curb this menace, but to no avail. Among such efforts are the deployments of several Nigerian security agencies who are made to ensure peace in the society such as the Nigerian Army, Nigeria Police Force, Military Joint Task Forces, the Nigerian Security and Civil Defence Corps, Nigerian Prisons Service, among others to tackle these recurring security challenges (Momodu, 2019; Yake, 2019; Johnson, 2019; Owonikoko & Ashindorbe, 2019).

Also, several factors were responsible for the national security challenge such as poor system of governance, concession of political power to certain ethnic and religious group, religious fanaticism, injustice, weak judicial system, nepotism, bribery and corruption, wrong use of resources, unemployment and poverty, among others (Usman & Mathew, 2014). Also, according to Jacoby (2018), another important factor that could influence national security is gender relations. Gender relations is the social relationships and power distribution between men and women in both the society which include in the private (personal) and public spheres (UNDP RBEC, 2007; Orhero, 2020). It spelt out how people tend to interact with others and how others relate to them, depending on their attributed gender in connection within the cultural context in which they develop. Hence, it intersects with all other influences on social relations which are age, ethnicity, race, religion, among others to determine the position and identity of people in a social group. Therefore, gender relations are approached as a social construct hence can be transformed over time to become more equitable. Nearly every dimension of national security such as human, economic, energy, environment, food and cyber related issues (Holmes, 2015; Osisanya, 2022) is attached to the level of empowerment given to women (Navone, 2021). It was affirmed that for every suppression of the women in any society or nation, there is twice the chance of being a fragile state with 50% increased chance of becoming an unstable and violent society and one and half times the chance of experiencing terrorism (Navone, 2021). However, several communities such as the Nigeria society fail to understand gender relations issues and its connection to national security. The Nigerian force has more than 223,000 active personnel, and is one of the largest uniformed combat services in Africa, the fourth-most powerful military in Africa, and was ranked the 35th at the international level (Global Firepower, 2022). Not much is known about the population of female in the Nigerian army force.

However, Madobi (2022) noted that sustainable national security is not possible without the involvement of women. Hence, with growing evidences of gender issues in the communities of Nigeria (Omiunu, 2014), it is highly important to draw attention to the fact that ensuring complete and sustainable national security may be a challenge. The gender equality bill which was introduced in the Nigerian senate was given little or no publicity (Wole-Abu, 2018). But the Nigerian Armed forces have not recognise women as a major segment of the population or forces to contribute to the defence and security of the nation in order to ensure sustainable national security in Nigeria (Alaga, 2011; Ozemoya, 2017). According to Egbefo and Salihu (2014) and Obi (2015), a society without security threat is a dead society because it has been known as the reality of human existence and hence an important way to understand social behavior of a society. Also, the experience of women with regards to security issues remain an important subject for studies and on gendered relations but there is still a concentration of its effect to addressing security issues towards national transformation (Tickner 1995; Niethamme, 2020). Hence, several theorists contend that the “institution of war could be closely related to gender (Francis 2004). Therefore, there is need to examine the link between gender relations and national security with focus on the challenges among the Nigerian peacekeepers.

The concept of national security has been a very difficult issue at the local, national, regional and global levels (Egbefo and Salihu, 2014; Orhero, 2020) and has long been a major concern and attracted attention in various studies and countries (Habtamu, 2013; Orhero, 2020). Generally, two major sources of insecurity exist and include: remote factors, and immediate and proximate factors (Achumba, Ighomeroho and Akpor-Robaro, 2013; Nigeria – South Africa Chamber of Commerce (NSACC), 2023). Examples of remote factors include the lack of institutional capacity which has resulted to government failure; persistent material inequalities and unfair treatment in the society; ethno-religious conflicts; public and government conflicts; weak security system; loss of socio-cultural and shared value system; among others. Examples of immediate and proximate factors include porous borders; rural/urban drift; social irresponsibility of companies; unemployment/poverty; terrorism; among others. National insecurity is a major issue in Nigeria fuelled by the increased crime rate and terrorists attacks in different parts of the country, leaving unpalatable consequences for the nation’s economy and its growth (Ewetan and Urhie, 2014; Obi, 2015). Nwagboso (2018) noted that such threats and challenges could distort the socio-political and economic balance of the nation.

Ensuring and effective national security is not possible without the involvement of women in the national security peacekeepers such as the (Madobi (2022) which are the Nigerian Army, Nigeria Police Force, Military Joint Task Forces, the Nigerian Security and Civil Defence Corps, Nigerian Prisons Service, among others (Momodu, 2019; Yake, 2019; Johnson, 2019; Owonikoko & Ashindorbe, 2019). But Ozemoya (2017) affirmed that among the peacemakers in Nigeria, the place of

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women as a major segment of the population or forces to contribute to the defence and security of the nation in order to ensure sustainable national security in Nigeria is underestimated. In addition, even in the society, there are growing evidences of gender discrimination issues (Omiunu, 2014). Moreover, the gender equality bill was introduced in the Nigerian senate but was given little or no publicity (Wole-Abu, 2018). This could challenge the tendency to ensure complete and sustainable national security because according to Madobi (2022), national security can't be attained without women involvement in the national security peacekeepers. Moreover, studies on national security especially in Africa, Nigeria inclusive, have focused on providing explanations for the deterioration of national security and tend to focus on the causes with interest drawn to contradictions of globalization and identity-based struggles for control of power and resources, simultaneous economic and also the national political reforms, flawed democratization, the declining state capacities and also the diminishing resources and proliferation of small arms (Hendricks, 2011; Nigeria – South Africa Chamber of Commerce (NSACC), 2023; Orhero, 2020). Much of these studies do not consider gender related issues such as the gender relations as a specific factor that could influence national security. Therefore, there is need to examine the link between gender relations and national security with focus on the challenges among the Nigerian peacekeepers.

Methodology

The study adopts a mixed studies systematic review with focus on the research objective of the study. The mixed studies systematic review focuses on the use of several studies that deployed different research design method such as quantitative, qualitative, review, among others due to the lack of studies that focus on this study. Systematic review is branch of review design that focuses on the deployment of systematic methods to collect and appraise data and information obtained from secondary sources such as databases of publishers, television websites, and other publications. It is designed to enumerate and provide a complete and exhaustive summary of current evidence (Giang et al., 2019). In addition, the major search engines used to search for materials are the google scholar and the google search engines. Also, the Cochrane reviews style was deployed for the reviewing of the literature as stated by Sieving (2007) and Chapman (2014). Also, the PICOS framework was used to inform the search strategy (Huang et al., 2006). The PICOS acronym represents (Richardson,1995): P –Problem or Population; I – Intervention; C – Comparison, control or comparator; O – Outcome(s); S - Study type (e.g. randomized controlled trial, cohort study, etc.). With regards to this study, the PICOS framework used is presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1. PICOS

	Inclusion	Exclusion	Search terms
Population	Gender issues in national security	Other national issues	Gender relations and National Security: Challenges for the Nigerian Peacekeepers
Intervention	None	None	None
Comparator	None	None	None
Outcome	National Security		National Security in Nigeria Role of peace makers Women peace makers
Study type	Mixed studies systematic review	None	Mixed studies systematic review

The initiation of searching process commenced February 12, 2021 and this was also repeated on December 06, 2021 so as to obtain wide elastic relevant resources that have not been previously covered in the previous date especially in the process of writing of and also reviewing the paper. Mixed studies were all considered and adopted in this study and materials deployed include those within the years 2000 and 2021. Also, the PRISMA Flow Diagram for the study search is provided in Figure 1 below:

Figure 1: The PRISMA Flow Diagram for the Study

Source: The Author

To ensure effective materials appraisal in this study, several components were inculcated such as the evaluation of the appropriateness of the study design that was used in the study, the methodological features of such design, the author of the article; sources of the articles, among others. Moreover, to further synthesize the information retrieved, data extraction was deployed but this was revolved around the research objective and questions of the study as stated by Frederiksen (2017).

Results and Discussion

The study focused on examining gender relations and national security: challenges for the Nigeria peacekeepers, and the results and discussions were provided. The search phase identified 86 papers; only 6 papers were eventually considered through abstract analysis. The analyses of these papers are presented below. The United Nations (2022), in trying to ensure the attainment of Goal 5 which is achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls, revealed that in certain geographical locations such as Nigeria, the discriminatory laws and social norms remained pervasive as women in the society which could also include those involved in peacemaking are underrepresented. Although, it also noted that certain progress to this effect has been made in the last decades as more women are serving in parliament and positions of leadership, and certain laws are subjected to reformation to ensure gender equality which could cut across the peacemakers of the national security in Nigeria. In other sectors of the economy, women have play disproportionate roles as healthcare workers, careers at home and a large percentage of women work in the formal and informal economy, which tend to contribute to national development in the long run. Hence, they could also be of major significance in ensuring national security. This concurs with the findings of Jacoby (2018), that gender relations hold a prominent place in ensuring national security. Ozemoya (2017) wrote about gender equality

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in Nigeria: implications of the national defense policy, as noted that despite the roles of great women in the Nigerian society such as the Queen Amina of Zaria, Queen Idia of the Benin Kingdom, among others, the Nigerian military does not include female intake in the regular combatant cadet. Only the Regular Combatant Commission are allowed to enhance career growth and are provided the opportunity to head in any of the Nigerian services up to the rank of the Chief of Defense Staff. Hence, because women are not allowed in the intake in the regular combatant cadet, women may not be able to move on career path and may not have the opportunity to head any of Nigerian services and cannot move to the rank of the Chief of Defense Staff. Moreover, underestimating the role of women in advancing national interests such as national security could affect development. Hence, gender equality should govern not only the ranks of the defense service but also the philosophy of advancement in true equality and equity in Nigeria. This concurs with the works of Alaga (2011) and Ozemoya (2017) that the Nigerian Armed forces have failed to recognize women as a major force to contribute to the defence and security of the nation.

Alaga (2011) examined gender and security policy in West Africa, and found that threats to security in West Africa are largely intra state in nature and rendering the State and military centered security almost irrelevant. The study revealed that there is a gender aspect to national security which demands the analyses of gender dimensions with regards to national security challenges. Also, the military and the entire security sector which include the Nigerian Army, Nigeria Police Force, Military Joint Task Forces, the Nigerian Security and Civil Defence Corps, Nigerian Prisons Service, among others as stated by Momodu (2019); Yake (2019); Johnson (2019); Owonikoko and Ashindorbe (2019), among others should put into consideration gender related approach to better deliver accountable security to the citizens and the state.

Oluremi (2021) examined women, peace and security in Nigeria through the domestic and international legal framework, and revealed that the issue related to national security is a global phenomenon due to its strategic importance to the national progress hence, no nation dire treat national security with levity. Despite the place of national development at the global level and the position women hold, also at the global level, women have not been given the full and equal opportunity in ensuring peace building in Nigeria due to several factors such as discrimination, patriarchy, culture, lack of legal framework, and others. The study of Oluremi (2021) revealed that women are powerful agents for peace and security in various societies and the nation at large and have the capability to engage in various areas of the nation for peace coalition. Therefore, there is the need for the adoption of gender perspective to peace building and involvement of women, towards imbuing them in the national security plans and strategies towards ensuring better security outcome in the nation.

The need to reconsider gender relations in national security is hinged on the fact that women are targeted and vulnerability and at the same time have strengths made women to be included in conflict prevention, peacemaking and building. The study also revealed that women have in the past acted as peace builder in major civil/uncivil war. Women support war efforts in multiple ways such as: they resist and fight, are not neutral bystanders during conflict. The study also revealed that integrating gender issues into the security sector is a major phenomenon at the formulation of peace agreements, participatory national dialogues and constitutional and electoral reform processes hence, the need to tackle the persistence of gender biases, the lack of educational and training opportunities for women, lack of a quota system for women, influence of cultural attitudes that have worked against women deployment in ensuring peacekeeping, women-unfriendly equipment and uniform design and living quarters, lack of role models, among others. Hence, with the high number of active force personnel in Nigeria, and the fourth-most powerful military in Africa, and the 35th at the international level as stated by Global Firepower (2022), not given priority to women in the national security plan and strategy may lead to gender bias and also may not ensure sustainable national security as stated by Madobi (2022) coupled with the growing evidences of gender issues in the Nigerian society as stated by Omiunu (2014). Hence, this justifies the assertion of Wole-Abu (2018) that the gender equality bill introduced in the Nigerian senate was given little or no publicity.

Idike, Okeke, Okorie, Ogba & Ugodulunwa (2020) examined gender, democracy, and national development in Nigeria, and revealed that national development has been stunted in Nigeria because of gender related issue particularly the unequal gender representation across the nation and in several of the Armed Forces arms of the nation. Also, their result revealed that the existing male-prone gender representation in Nigeria have only led to increasing in poverty and underdevelopment. To this end, Nigerian women could use powers inherent hence, should be included in the various arms of the nation's economy, particularly in the security issues of the nation. The result revealed that gender approach to security denotes that security must be connected to empowerment hence, women empowerment and involvement in the national security becomes germane. This also bolsters the findings of Jacoby (2018) and Navone(2021), that gender relations holds a prominent place in ensuring national security. Hence, the Nigeria peacemakers which include the Nigerian Army, Nigeria Police Force, Military Joint Task Forces, the Nigerian Security and Civil Defence Corps, Nigerian Prisons Service, among others as stated by Momodu (2019); Yake

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(2019); Johnson (2019); Owonikoko and Ashindorbe (2019), among others should inculcate gender relations in achieving national security.

Conclusion

In conclusion, for effective and sustainable national security to be achieved by the Nigeria peacemakers which include the Nigerian Army, Nigeria Police Force, Military Joint Task Forces, the Nigerian Security and Civil Defence Corps, Nigerian Prisons Service, among others, there is need for the inclusion of gender relation to involve females; hence, attaining sustainable development and national security would be a mirage in Nigeria and the various efforts to achieve sustainable national security would be fruitless like was achieved in the past strategies.

Recommendations

1. The proportion of women intake in the various Nigeria Force recruit should be increased so as to give room for a majority of women in the society to contribute and play their role in ensuring national security.
2. Women should also be inculcated into the regular combatant cadet intake so as to also have the opportunity for career growth and development towards been able to obtain the Chief of Defense Staff to be able to contribute their quota to national security.
3. Also, there is need for other women empowerment and social restructuring for women to be involved in the national security of Nigeria.
4. Also, there should be need for providing other measures such as short service opportunity and other courses that could also empower women in the Nigerian Force to be able to contribute and play their role in ensuring national security.

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Assessment of Peer Influence on Predisposition to Examination Misconduct among Tertiary Institution Students in Cross River State, Nigeria

Onah, Peter Ogbaji¹

Email: ogbajipetex@gmail.com

Tel: 07034512139

Akanimoh, Martha Edu¹

Email: markanimoh@gmail.com

Tel: 08063924227

Ndome, Linda Esse²

Email: Ndomelinda2017@gmail.com

Tel: 08119823425

¹Department of Educational Foundations, University of Calabar

²Department of Guidance and Counseling, University of Calabar

Abstract

The Study aimed at examining Assessment of Peer Influence on Predisposition to examination misconduct among tertiary institution students in Cross River State, Nigeria. Research questions were raised and corresponding hypotheses tested at .05 level of significance. The research design adopted for this study was an ex-post facto research design and the population of this study comprised 35,500 (21,589 Males and 13,911 Females) final-year students in all tertiary institutions in Cross River State, during the 2022/2023 academic session. The sample of this study consists of 2,439 (1,079 Males and 1,360 Females) final year students which represents 7% of the total population selected from five tertiary institutions in Cross River State. The instrument used for data collection was "Assessment of Peer Influence on Predisposition to Examination Misconduct Questionnaire (APIPEMQ). Cronbach Alpha reliability test was used to test scores from the questionnaire. The questionnaire was administered once to the respondents after which the coefficient of internal consistency was estimated and the reliability index was 82. Accordingly, which shows that the instrument was reliable for data collection. descriptive statistics was employed to answer the research questions while the hypotheses were tested using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) at .05 level of significance. Findings revealed that Peer assessment does significantly influence students' examination misconduct. It concludes that stake holders in the academic environment are expected to encourage the students to shun all manners of misconduct, amongst others. The researchers recommended among others that, the school management should as a matter of urgency restrict negative peer associations in schools by enacting laws to prevent students from engaging in any form of examination misconduct.

Keywords: Peer association, Predisposition, Examination misconduct, Tertiary institution

Introduction

Education at any level is geared towards an instructional system that deals with teaching, learning and evaluation in a defined environment. The Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013) defined tertiary education as post-secondary education that is offered in universities, polytechnics and colleges of technology. Education is important in the development and improvement of skills. It helps in improving the living standard and condition of the people. According to Morrison et al in Onah, Eteng & Adie (2021) education is the process through which the ideals and worthwhile values of society are systematically passed on from the generation to another to ensure socio-cultural transformation and advancement of man and his environment. That is education makes one a responsible and respectful citizen. Through education, people are enabled to develop their knowledge and skills, adopt new behaviour and be able to survive in the society. The quality of examination refers to the systematic monitoring and evaluation of the various aspects of the programme to maximize the possibility of achieving programme goals. The quality of these goals is measured through tests and examinations Asim (2017). For examinations to be valid, reliable and useable as a potent instrument for judgment of knowledge, every student must be devoid of all forms of malpractices (Haruna,

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et. al., 2023). This is to ensure that whatever grades or certificates a learner is given is a true reflection of the attributes possessed by such a student.

Examination remains the best tool for objective assessment and evaluation of what learners have acquired after a period of schooling. Thus, any compromising action or inaction poses a great danger to the validity, reliability and authenticity of examination results and certificates. Unfortunately, the process of assessment in schools in Nigeria is being marred by the phenomenon of examination misconduct that has become endemic in the educational system. Examination misconduct according to Onyibe *et al.* (2015) manifests in different forms, such as, ‘blocking’, ‘cooperation’, ‘sorting’, ‘cheating’, ‘sexual gratification’ and others. Some other schemes employed by the learners are; impersonation, exchange of answer scripts, fabrication of results, plagiarizing, misrepresentation of identity, tampering with works of others, and unethical use of academic resources. Evidences abound of increasing involvement in examination misconduct behaviour by students. For instance, in 2019, the Federal Ministry of Education blacklisted 316 secondary schools across the nation for their involvement in examination misconduct (Adedigba, 2019). Also, in the May / June 2021 West African Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (WASSCE) in Nigeria, it was reported that out of 1,590,173 candidates, 180, 205 candidate’s results were withheld over examination misconduct (Ogwo, 2022). Examination misconduct has been seen as a serious problem facing the educational system in contemporary.

Examination misconduct is anything done by examination candidates that is likely to render the assessment in education useless. Onyibe *et al.* (2015), posited that examination misconduct as all aspect of dishonesty or illegal deeds or actions that are carried out by students either personally or using other people like security officers, invigilators, parents, teachers either earlier, during or at the end of examination so as to obtain unmerited grade or marks. Animasahum and Ogunniran (2014) described it as an act that contravenes the rules and regulations of a particular period of time. This implies that it is any activity or activities carried out by students during an examination such that are likely to change the result of the assessment. There are various factors that can be said to be responsible for examination malpractice in our schools. According to Afuge (2015) general moral decadence and the high premium placed on achievement and certificates by Nigerians have in recent times spawned examination fraud. The general overdependence on educational certification as a measure of one’s knowledge and competence has led to a mad rush by most people for educational certificates. In a bid to acquire such certificates, many have resorted to unethical practices just to acquire the certificates at all costs. According to Salvador (2020), a peer is a person who is equal to another in ability, qualification, age, background and social status. That is to say, a peer is a person who belongs to the same age group or social group. Oloshola (2016), see peer group as important socialization agent. For them participating in peer group activities are a primary stage of development and adolescent identities are often closely associated with that of their peers Furo (2015), indicate that peer pressure refers to the way people of the same social group act or believe to influence one another often in negative ways. Peer group pressure is something everybody has to deal with at some time in life because how successfully one handles peer pressure depends so greatly on the individual’s self-concept and position in the world (Ogunbiade and Ajayi, 2018). Irouje (2015) and Okories (2018) emphasized that peer pressure has a much more impact on adolescents’ behaviour than any other factor. They further observed that adolescent interaction with their peers is direct and much more powerful than the influence of counselors, teachers and other authority figures. The teenagers spend much of their working hours with peers than with family members. Okories (2018), Irouje (2015) noted that peer pressure has both negative and positive impacts on the attitude of adolescents towards examination malpractice. The growing menace of examination malpractice in our schools is becoming a worrisome and disturbing phenomenon. The author correctly noted that peer pressure has environmental factors capable of influencing student attitudes towards examination malpractice positively or negatively. Okories (2018) noted that research such as peer cluster theory has shown that peer pressure has a much greater impact on adolescent behaviour than any other factor. The author added that peer influence can increase students’ tendency to involvement in examination misconduct.

Aquibiade and Ajayi (2018), investigated test anxiety and peer influence on secondary school students’ involvement in examination malpractices. The study was carried out in Lagos metropolis. The population for the study consists of secondary school students in education district II in Lagos State. The study adopted ex-post-facto design and made use of a sample of 250 students randomly selected from five senior secondary school in the area of the study. Research instrument titled “Test anxiety and peer influence on secondary school students’ involvement in Examination Malpractices Questionnaire (EMQ)” was used for data collection. Three hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance. Data collected were analyzed using one and two-way analysis of variance statistics. The study’s finding revealed that high test anxiety and high peer influence resulted in high involvement in examination malpractices among secondary school students. It was also found that test anxiety and peer influence jointly determine involvement in examination malpractice among the student. It was recommended that student

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should invest sufficient time to their studies and engage in group discussion for effective learning and multiple streams of ideas. Student should avoid keeping bad and unprofitable association so that they will not be laved into examination malpractices. They should associate with people of integrity who will positively influence their value systems and behaviors. This study employed an ex-post-facto to design as opposed to the cross-sectional design employed in the present study.

Also, Okorodudu (2015) conducted a study on peer pressure and socio-economic status as influence on students' attitude to examination malpractice in Nigeria. The questionnaire was used to elicit the right responses on peer pressures and students' attitude toward examination malpractice, using simple regression statistics on the data collected from a sample of 1000 junior secondary two students. The outcome of the study revealed a strong relationship between peer pressure and students' attitude examination behavior. Anierobi *et al.* (2018) studied peer influence and secondary school students' attitude towards examination malpractice in Anambra State. Two research questions and two hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance guided the study. The correlation survey design was adopted for the study. The participants were selected through simple random sampling. A total of 1300 SS2 students from the population of 8,978 SS2 students in the 174 co-educational public secondary schools in Anambra State made up the sample for the study. Three sets of questionnaires titled "Self-Esteem Scale (SES)", "Peer Influence Scale (PIS)" and "Attitude towards Examination Malpractice Scale (ATEMS)" were used for data collection. The instruments were validated by three experts and the reliability of the ATEMS and PIS were ascertained using Cronbach alpha and they yielded Cronbach alpha coefficients of 0.85 and 0.76 respectively while the SES yielded 0.74 in the Nigerian secondary school setting. Data were analyzed and hypotheses were tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. The findings showed that peer influence has a negative correlation with students' attitudes towards examination malpractice. Self-esteem has a positive correlation with students' attitude toward examination malpractice. Based on the findings it was concluded that students' have a negative attitude towards examination malpractice based on peer influence. It was recommended among others that students should be encouraged to have a positive sense of worth about themselves and also be enlightened on the strategies of avoiding and or coping with negative peer influence to shun examination malpractice.

Examination misconduct has become one among the cankerworms which has eaten so deep into the fabric of examinations in Nigeria (Ogwo 2022). In tertiary institutions in Cross Rivers State, different forms of examination misconduct persist, which include cheating in examination, stealing of examination papers, impersonation, disturbances during examinations, giraffing, obstruction of supervisors, forgery of results, bribery, substitution for answer sheets, use of coded sign languages, submission of fake passport photograph, improper completion of entry forms among others. students' behaviours during examination in tertiary institutions in Cross Rivers State tend to be so worrisome, showing that they have difficulty in conforming to established norms of behavior (Ekott and Ijeoma 2018). For instance, in 2021/2022 academic session, the researcher had a personal encounter with some final year students who were caught with parts of text books and browsing their phones in the examination hall. When the invigilator confronted them, the culprit started harassing the invigilator. Then the researcher began to wonder why such behaviour could prevail among students in tertiary institution. Could it be as a result of peer's association, family structure, social media, parental encouragement, parental educational level, gender or religious background or any other things?

Many students have lost their morals and confidence in their intellectual ability due to the fact that their mindset is that of involving in examination misconduct for success (Ekott and Ijeoma 2018). Though the Federal Government on its part has promulgated decrees, enacted laws, organized workshops and seminars and some authors have also raised alarms on this menace, examination fraud still persists (Onah Et al 2021). Few studies might have been conducted on this topic but probably not in Cross River State; and some variables of the school used in this work seem to be untouched. It was based on these observable problems and the existing gap that the researcher was interested to conduct a study aimed at examining the influence of social variables on students' predisposition to examination misconduct tendencies in tertiary institutions in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to assess peer influence on predisposition to examination miss conduct among tertiary institution students in Cross River State, Nigeria. Specifically, this study intends to:

To access the extent of peer influence on predisposition to examination misconduct among tertiary institution students in Cross River State.

Hypothesis

The following hypothesis was formulated and tested at .05 level of significance.

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There is no significant difference between mean response scores of Peer influence on predisposition to examination misconduct among tertiary institution students in Cross River State, Nigeria

Methodology

The research design adopted for this study is ex-post facto design and the population of this study comprised 35,500 (21,589 Males and 13,911 Females) final year students in all the tertiary institution in Cross River State. The sample of this study consist of 2,439 (1,079 Males and 1,360 Females) respondents which represents 7% of the total population selected from five tertiary institutions in Cross River State. The researcher made instruments, “Peer Association and Students Predisposition to Examination Misconduct Questionnaire (PASPEMQ)” were used for data collected. The face validity of the instruments was carried out by two experts. The instruments were modified after due scrutiny from the experts for face validity. The reliability co-efficient of the Peer Association and Students Predisposition to Examination Misconduct Questionnaire were ascertained using the Cronbach Alpha Reliability Co-efficient. The instrument was administered through the permission of the lecturers to the students in the lecture halls by the researcher with the help of trained research assistants. A letter of introduction from the Department was presented to authorities in the various tertiary institutions to seek permission to conduct the study. The letter contains information about the researcher and the aim of the visit for proper understanding and maximum cooperation before questionnaires are given to respondents. Caution was taken to explain the instructions on how to complete the items on the questionnaires. The instrument was retrieved immediately after completion to prevent attrition, but 5 items were missing in the process, hence, the questionnaire instrument were reduced to 2,434. In analyzing the data, descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) were employed to answer the research questions and the One-way analysis of variance ANOVA were used to test the hypotheses at .05 level of significance.

Result

Hypothesis 1

To test this hypothesis, one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was applied with peer association as factor and examination misconduct as the dependent variable. The F-ratio test was used to test for the significance of the main influence, while Fishers’ least significant Difference (LSD) test was used as post hoc test. The results are presented in Table 4.

Table 3: One-Way ANOVA of the Influence of Peer Assessment on Examination Misconduct

Sources of variation	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-vale	p-value
Between Groups	3149.026	2	1574.513	85.379	.000
Within Groups	44831.021	2431	18.441		
Total	47980.046	2433			

*p<.05 Source: Field Data (2023)

The results in Table 4.3 show that the P-value (.000) associated with the computed F-value (85.374) is less than .05. As such, the null hypothesis was rejected. This means that Peer association does significantly influence students to examination misconduct tendencies in tertiary institutions. To locate the pair of group mean values that accounted for the observed significant results, Fishers Least Significant Difference (LSD) was applied. The results are presented in Table 2.

Table 4: LSD pairwise, Comparison of Peer Association on Examination Misconduct

Peer association	Examination misconduct	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	p-values	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
High	Moderate	.05758	.23286	.805	-.3990	.5142
	Low	2.32633*	.21802	.000	1.8988	2.7538
Moderate	High	-.05758	.23286	.805	-.5142	.3990
	Low	2.26875*	.20392	.000	1.8689	2.6686
Low	High	-2.32633*	.21802	.000	-2.7538	-1.8988
	Moderate	-2.26875*	.20392	.000	-2.6686	-1.8689

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level. Source: Field Data (2023)

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The results in Table 3 show that the p-values for the categories of high and low (.000), moderate and low, (.000), low and high (.000) and low and moderate (.000) associated with the computed mean differences (MD) ($2.32633 \leq MD \leq 2.26875$ $MD \leq -2.32633$ and $MD \leq -2.26875$) are less than .05. This means that the pair of high and low, moderate and low, low and high and low and moderate paired comparisons are significant.

Discussion of Findings

Peer influence was measured using the same number of items and response options. Therefore, their descriptive statistics can be validly compared. From the Table, by peer association, the means score obtained by high ($\bar{x} = 16.3377$) is higher while those of low ($\bar{x} 14.0114$) had the least. to examination misconduct in tertiary institutions. It has been established that the level of peer association is a strong factor to students' attitude towards examination misconduct. Most adolescents are highly influenced by their peers, if the adolescents excerpt negative influence, it is bound to affect the overall life style of the students. The finding is in line with the study of Aguibiade and Ajayi (2018) which reveal that peer association positively influence the academic performance and cheating tendency of in-school adolescents. The gap in this study was that only two research questions and hypotheses were used with a standardized instrument. The present study has bridged the lapses in the study by answering one research questions and testing one (1) corresponding null hypotheses. In the same vein, Okorodudu (2015) study revealed a strong relationship between peer pressure and students' attitude examination behaviour. In accordance with the present study, Anierobi, *et al.* (2018) findings which showed that peer influence has a negative correlation with students' attitudes towards examination malpractice. Self-esteem has a positive correlation with students' attitude toward examination malpractice.

Conclusion

The issue of examination misconduct has been in the education sector for too long. It should be confronted from all channels as a menace that has almost completely destroyed the education sector. University education is meant to the learning process for human capital development and where that is not efficiently achieved due to examination misconduct, the products of such a learning process will not be efficient in their various specialized areas. Some Universities are very strict on the issues of examination misconduct but others are weak. Consequently, this is a weak up call for the University Vice Chancellors, Deans of faculties, Head of Departments, Lecturers and all those who can make a difference to be seriously involved in fight against examination misconduct by considering the future impact of this menace on graduate students. Stake holders in the academic environment are expected to encouraging the students to shun all manners of misconduct, the government, parents, churches etc. may need to play major complementary role. Having established the significance of social variables on examination misconduct behavior, it is worth the while to conclude this study by stating that examination misconduct seems to loom larger in recent times and since high values have been attached to academic success, higher price has also been attached examination misconduct which only the high can buy.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. School management should as a matter of urgency restrict negative peer associations in schools by enacting laws to prevent students from engaging in any form of examination misconduct.
2. The school management should offer students with effective orientation exercises of ethical behaviours with emphasis on examination misconduct.
3. Parents at home should endeavor to teach good morals to their children thus, parents should encourage their children to develop an attitude of diligence and not believe that unethical conduct such as bribing a lecturer (gratifications) could money solve all problems.
4. The school counsellor should counsel students on proper study habits for academic excellence in examination. Government in collaboration with non-governmental organization (NGOs) should create an orientation campaign for all stakeholders in the academic environment on the dangers of over-reliance on certification. One of the major dangers in our educational system is over emphasis on certificates. This has made all students dwell strongly on using any possible means of passing the examination.

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Assessment of Perception and Attitude on English Studies Curriculum among Junior Secondary School Teachers in Ibadan South-West Local Government, Oyo State

Ajagbe, Iyabode Mofoluwake¹

Email: folukehinmowo@gmail.com

Tel: 08059396073

Olatunji, Sheriff Olamide²

Email: olatunjisheriff07@gmail.com

Tel: 07034593781

¹Department of Arts and Social Sciences Education, University of Ibadan

²Department of Arts and Social Sciences Education, National Open University of Nigeria, Abuja

Abstract

The study investigated assessment of perception and attitude on English Studies curriculum among junior secondary school teachers in Ibadan South-West Local Government, Oyo State. The study adopted the survey research design. Population of the study consists of all junior secondary school teachers in public junior secondary schools in Ibadan South-West Local Government Area, Oyo State during the 2021/2022 academic session. Forty (17 Male and 23 Female) teachers constitute the sample size of the study. The sample size was selected using multi-stage sampling technique. Two research instruments were used for data collection: Teachers' Perception of English Studies Curriculum Questionnaire ($r=.76$) and Questionnaire on Teachers' Attitude to English Studies Curriculum ($r=.80$). Data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics of percentage, mean, standard deviation and inferential statistics of t-test. Findings of the study that there was a weighted mean of 2.84, which is greater than the threshold set at 2.50 and a weighted mean of 1.77, which is lower than the threshold set at 2.50. Also, there was a significant difference in the mean response scores of perceptions on English Studies curriculum among junior secondary school male and female teachers. So, the null hypothesis was accepted. There was no significant difference in the mean response scores of attitudes on English Studies Curriculum among Junior Secondary School male and female teachers. So, the null hypothesis was rejected. It could be concluded that the study has provided a better understanding of perception and attitude on English Studies curriculum among Junior Secondary School teachers in Ibadan South-West Local Government, Oyo State. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that government should do everything possible to educate teachers of English Studies on reasons for English Studies Curriculum at Junior Secondary School level.

Keywords: Teacher's perception, attitude, English Studies, curriculum

Introduction

The objectives of the English studies curriculum are to broaden the language competencies students have developed through Basic Education, so that they are able to use English with increasing level of proficiency for personal and intellectual development, effective social interaction, further study, vocational training, work and pleasure. To enable learners further develop their interest and confidence in using English as their understanding and mastery of the English language grows. To enable learners further broaden their knowledge, understanding and experience of various cultures in which English is used. After independence, English language was taught as a subject from primary school level through secondary to higher education. Literature in English was studied as a discipline and only introduced at senior secondary school level until the introduction of the 9-3-4 system of education which brought radical changes in the educational structure, the curriculum and in the teaching approach. Consequently, English language now become English Studies (Ajagbe, 2020).

The English Studies curriculum contents are harnessed to enable pupils learn, internalise and use what has been learnt for solving real life problems. While the primary school pupils are exposed only to English language skills (listening, speaking, reading and writing), the junior secondary school are exposed to English language and Literature genres (Saidu & Haruna, 2020). This is meant to expose the students to a wide range of English language and literary skills that should enhance their communicative skills. With this curriculum, it is believed that students will not only be competent users of English language but teaching and learning will be entertaining and interesting to them. For effective implementation of this curriculum, learners'

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active participation during lessons through different activities, teaching styles and all-round assessment tools, have been suggested in the curriculum (Ajagbe, 2020).

Due to the importance attached to the English language in education, the Nigerian educational planners in Nigeria joined the two subjects into one for students to be exposed to a wide range of English language and literary skills that should enhance their communicative skills. The Junior Secondary School Curriculum states that English language is offered together with literature. Thus, in the National Curriculum for English language in the Junior Secondary School, the two subjects have been fused into one named “English Studies”. The integrated English teaching approach is part of the movement towards communicative language teaching (Lawal, 2019). Lambo, while commending the efforts behind the integrative English curriculum at the Junior Secondary School (JSS) level, stresses the need for effective implementation. Lambo suggests the need for periodic orientation or re-training of both teachers and supervisors in Junior Secondary Schools, in view of the fact that integrative teaching of English at the JSS level is innovative.

Magoma (2015) asserts that teachers of English felt that the content of English was too much and they felt burdened by the work they had to cover. Therefore, they advocated for the separation of English and literature. The implication is that the content to be covered dictates the methodologies to be used in teaching process. Sadeghi (2007) argues in favour of integration. Sadeghi states that literature should be a powerful tool in the hands of any teacher of English as a second or foreign language especially because language learning including literature is above all educational undertaking. Language and literature is interrelated entities, with teachers as users of literature rather than teachers of it. Secondary education syllabus states that through exposure to literature, the learner will improve their language skills. They will not only enrich their vocabulary but also learn to use language in variety of ways.

Despite the important nature of the revised English Studies curriculum which is to improve students’ reading ability and communicative competence, the performance of the junior secondary students is not satisfactory. Ajagbe (2020) maintains that the integration of the two subjects implies that the English language teachers in the JSS are now saddled with responsibility of teaching the new subject (English Studies), which consists of English language and Literature-in-English. Ajagbe asserts that the new arrangement is rocked with a number of problems. The teachers are faced with the problem of balancing the time allocation for the two aspects of the new subject at the junior secondary school level. Teachers at this level of education, do not normally give enough attention to the literature aspect of the subject in the class as many of them do not even know the rationale for merging the two subjects. As part of the problem affecting the implementation of English Studies curriculum is poor perception of teachers and poor attitude of teachers to the curriculum.

As a way of addressing causes of the problem, scholars have carried out studies on teacher factors and students’ learning outcomes in English Studies (Lawal, 2019), challenges and innovations in the teaching of English Studies (Ewetan and Ewetan, 2015) and teacher perception of curriculum objectives and learning experience as correlates of achievement in English Studies among junior secondary students in Ibadan, Nigeria (Adedigba and Fakeye, 2020). These studies came up with good contributions but with little emphasis on teacher’s perception of and attitude to English Studies Curriculum at junior secondary schools especially in Ibadan. The perception of teachers on English studies curriculum is very important for the purpose of engaging students in the best way and promotes quality teaching.

Williams (2016) views perception as a way to recognise and interpret information we gathered through our senses. This also includes how we respond to certain situations with the given information. Williams also asserts that besides the collection of information, perception involves active participation of higher cognitive functions responsible for constructing and interpreting ideas. Perception, as noted by Schacter, Gilbert and Wegner (2011), is the organisation, identification and interpretation of sensory information in order to represent and understand the environment. It is the way something is regarded, understood or interpreted. Romanov (2011) stated that perception includes senses, feelings, ideas, thought and theories. Therefore, perception is personally based on selection, organization and interpretation of the stimuli. Teachers’ perceptions have enormous effect on the successful implementation of quality education in schools, quality of teaching and quality of learning. Within any single subject areas, teachers’ perception will influence a range of teaching skills, styles, models and approaches that comprise a teaching repertoire and this will provide a clear framework for describing the teaching activities.

Attitude of English Studies teachers to English Studies curriculum depicts their positive or negative reaction towards the implementation of the curriculum. Attitude can be formed from an individual’s past or present and that it can be positive or negative evaluation of a people, objects, events, activities and idea about anything in the environment (Obiegbo, 2016). It is one’s feelings, thoughts and predisposition to believe in some particular manner towards some aspects of one’s environment. Attitude can be formed from an individual’s past or present and that it can be positive or negative evaluation of a people, objects, events, activities and idea about anything in the environment.

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English Studies curriculum at junior secondary schools comprises English language and Literature-in-English. It is also expected that with this merging, students' reading ability and communicative competence will improve and students will be empowered to use English language effectively after their completion of the Junior Secondary School. Despite the important nature of the revised English studies curriculum, the objectives of the curriculum are hardly met as evident in junior secondary school students' performance in English Studies. Studies have shown that the objectives of the curriculum were not met because of teachers' negative perception and negative attitude to English Studies curriculum. Efforts to address this problem have made researchers and scholars to investigate teacher factors and students' learning outcomes in English Studies, challenges and innovations in the teaching of English Studies and evaluation of junior secondary school English language curriculum. All these studies came up with good insights to the teaching and learning of English Studies at the junior secondary school level but with little emphasis on assessment of perception and attitude on English Studies curriculum among junior secondary school teachers especially in Ibadan. Perception and attitude of teachers on English studies curriculum are very important for the purpose of engaging students in the best way and promotes quality teaching of English Studies. Therefore, this study investigated assessment of perception and attitude on English Studies curriculum among junior secondary school teachers in Ibadan South-West Local Government, Oyo State.

Objectives of the Study

This study was carried to determine:

1. The mean response score of perceptions on English Studies curriculum among junior secondary school teachers in Ibadan South-west Local Government, Oyo State
2. The mean response score of attitudes on English Studies curriculum among junior secondary school teachers in Ibadan South-west Local Government, Oyo State
3. The significant difference between mean response scores of perceptions on English Studies curriculum among junior secondary school male and female teachers in Ibadan South-west Local Government, Oyo State
4. The significant difference between mean response scores of Attitudes on English Studies Curriculum among Junior Secondary School male and female Teachers in Ibadan South-west Local Government, Oyo State

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the mean response score of perceptions on English Studies curriculum among Junior Secondary School teachers in Ibadan South-west Local Government, Oyo State?
2. What is the mean response score of attitudes on English Studies curriculum among Junior Secondary School teachers in Ibadan South-west Local Government, Oyo State?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between mean response scores of perceptions on English Studies curriculum among Junior Secondary School male and female teachers in Ibadan South-west Local Government, Oyo State
2. There is no significant difference between mean response scores of Attitudes on English Studies Curriculum among Junior Secondary School male and female teachers in Ibadan South-west Local Government, Oyo State?

Methodology

The study adopted the survey research design. Population of the study consists of all Junior Secondary School teachers in public Junior Secondary Schools in Ibadan South-West Local Government Area, Oyo State during the 2021/2022 academic session. Forty (17 Male and 23 Female) teachers constitute the sample size of the study. The sample size was selected using multi-stage sampling technique. Twenty (20) public junior secondary schools were randomly selected from 36 public secondary schools in Ibadan South West Local Government Area of Oyo State. Simple random sampling technique was used to select two English Studies teachers from each school making a total of 40 teachers (17 Male and 23 Female). Two research instruments were used for data collection. They are: Teachers' Perception of English Studies Curriculum Questionnaire ($r=.76$) and Questionnaire on Teachers' Attitude to English Studies Curriculum ($r=.80$). Data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics of percentage, mean, standard deviation and inferential statistics of t-test.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the mean response score of perceptions on English Studies curriculum among junior secondary school teachers in Ibadan South-west Local Government, Oyo State?

Table 1: The mean response score of perceptions on English Studies curriculum

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	StD
1	English Studies curriculum promotes learning of English language and literature	16 (41%)	10 (25.6%)	2 (5.1%)	11 (28.2%)	2.79	1.26
2	English Studies curriculum makes teachers to be hardworking	18 (46.2%)	10 (25.6%)	6 (15.4%)	5 (12.8%)	3.05	1.07
3	English studies curriculum makes teachers to have good attitude towards the teaching of literature	20 (51.3%)	5 (12.8%)	10 (25.6%)	4 (10.3%)	3.05	1.09
4	English Studies curriculum increases students' interest in English Studies	17 (43.6%)	12 (30.8%)	4 (10.3%)	6 (15.4%)	3.02	1.08
5	English Studies curriculum stimulates students' ability to think very fast.	18 (46.2%)	12 (30.8%)	3 (7.7%)	6 (15.4%)	3.07	1.08
6	English Studies curriculum is not objective	10 (27%)	6 (16.2%)	3 (8.1%)	18 (48.6%)	2.21	1.31
7	English Studies curriculum changes teachers' attitude towards teaching English	16 (41%)	5 (12.8%)	9 (23.1%)	9 (23.1%)	2.71	1.23
8	English Studies curriculum makes students learn new vocabularies from literary terms	24 (63.2%)	1 (2.6%)	6 (15.8%)	7 (18.4%)	3.10	1.24
9	Teaching English Studies curriculum can be a challenging activity	17 (44.7%)	8 (21.1%)	8 (21.1%)	5 (13.2%)	2.97	1.10
10	English studies curriculum facilitates the development of students' competence in writing	13 (33.3%)	12 (30.8%)	2 (5.1%)	12 (30.8%)	2.66	1.24
11	English studies curriculum does not develop students' speaking ability	18 (46.2%)	8 (20.5%)	4 (10.3%)	9 (23.1%)	2.89	1.23
12	Teaching English Studies curriculum makes students to be passive recipient of knowledge	23 (59%)	6 (15.4%)	1 (2.6%)	9 (23.1%)	3.10	1.25
13	Teaching contents of English Studies curriculum makes students to have positive attitude towards learning English.	17 (43.6%)	7 (17.9%)	8 (20.5%)	7 (17.9%)	2.87	1.17
14	English Studies curriculum changes teachers' wrong impression about teaching of English language	15 (38.5%)	3 (7.7%)	8 (20.5%)	13 (33.3%)	2.51	1.31
15	English studies curriculum makes students to reflect on what they learnt	14 (35.9%)	12 (30.8%)	8 (20.5%)	5 (12.5%)	2.89	1.04
16	Teaching contents of English Studies curriculum makes students attend English Studies classroom regularly	19 (50%)	1 (2.6%)	11 (28.9%)	7 (18.4%)	2.84	1.24
17	Teaching contents of English Studies curriculum makes students to enjoy reading literary texts	13 (33.3%)	4 (10.3%)	11 (28.2%)	11 (28.2%)	2.48	1.23
18	Contents of English studies curriculum are not easy to teach	17 (45.9%)	6 (16.2%)	3 (8.1%)	11 (29.7%)	2.78	1.31
19	English Studies curriculum fosters learning	21 (53.8%)	5 (12.8%)	6 (15.4%)	7 (17.9%)	3.02	1.20
20	Teaching contents of English Studies curriculum makes students to be eager to learn.	20 (54.1%)	2 (5.4%)	4 (10.8%)	11 (29.7%)	2.83	1.36

Weighted Mean = 2.84; Threshold = 2.50

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Data collected by the researchers (2021)

Table 1 shows the perception of teachers about English Studies curriculum. The result indicates a weighted mean of 2.84, which is greater than the threshold set at 2.50. This implies that the selected teachers had a positive perception about the English studies curriculum. Out of the 20 items used, 11 items contributed to this positive perception because their means are greater than the weighted mean. The items are item 2 – English Studies curriculum is important for students’ performance in English Studies (mean = 3.05), item 3 – English Studies curriculum makes students to participate actively in English Studies instruction (mean = 3.05), item 4 – English Studies curriculum increases students’ interest in English Studies (mean = 3.02), item 5 – English Studies enables students’ to learn very fast (mean = 3.07), item 8 – English Studies curriculum makes students’ learn new vocabularies from literary terms (mean =3.10), item 9 – English Studies curriculum stimulates students’ ability to think very fast (mean =2.97), item 11 – English studies curriculum does not develop students’ speaking ability (mean = 2.89), item 12 – English studies curriculum makes students acquire a wide range of ideas about their work in English language (mean = 3.10), item 13 – English studies curriculum enable students to become more aware of their strengths (mean = 2.87), item 15 – English studies curriculum makes students to reflect (mean = 2.89), item 19 – The literature in English aspect of the English studies curriculum makes students perform poorly in the subject (mean =3.02). This implies that the selected teachers had a positive perception of the English studies curriculum.

Research Question 2

What is the mean response score of attitudes on English Studies curriculum among junior secondary school teachers in Ibadan South-west Local Government, Oyo State?

Table 2: The mean response score of attitudes on English Studies curriculum

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	StD
1	I have poor attitude to the teaching of English Studies	1 (2.5%)	-	2 (5.0%)	37 (92.5%)	1.12	.515
2	I do not enjoy the teaching of English Studies curriculum	1 (2.5%)	-	8 (20.0%)	31 (77.5%)	1.25	.493
3	I teach English Studies curriculum with interest	1 (2.5%)	1 (2.5%)	26 (65.0%)	12 (30.0%)	1.77	.619
4	I am afraid to teach contents of English Studies curriculum	1 (2.5%)	-	20 (50.0%)	19 (47.5%)	1.57	.635
5	I am not encouraged to teach contents of English Studies curriculum	2 (5.1%)	3 (7.7%)	19 (48.7%)	15 (38.5%)	1.79	.800
6	I hate English Studies curriculum	-	2 (5%)	2 (30%)	26 (65%)	1.40	.590
7	I like teaching English Studies curriculum	1 (2.5%)	4 (10%)	14 (35%)	21 (52.5%)	1.62	.774
8	If I have my way, I will not teach the literature aspect of the curriculum	8 (20%)	7 (17.5%)	17 (42.5%)	8 (20%)	2.37	1.03
9	Teaching English Studies curriculum can be a boring activity	5 (12.5%)	7 (17.5%)	14 (35%)	14 (35%)	2.07	1.02
10	Teachers treat teaching of English Studies curriculum as an extra burden	1 (2.5%)	-	-	39 (97.5%)	1.07	.474
11	I am not comfortable teaching contents of English Studies curriculum	-	1 (2.5%)	13 (32.5%)	26 (65%)	1.37	.540
12	I always enjoy teaching the English aspect of the curriculum	7 (17.5%)	1 (2.5%)	18 (45%)	14 (35%)	2.02	1.04
13	I always enjoy teaching the Literature aspect of the curriculum	1 (2.5%)	3 (7.5%)	20 (50%)	16 (40%)	1.72	.715
14	Teaching contents of English Studies curriculum makes students to pay rapt attention in class	3 (7.5%)	1 (2.5%)	19 (47.5%)	17 (42.5%)	1.75	.839
15	I find English Studies curriculum too abstract to teach	2 (5%)	2 (5%)	9 (22.5%)	27 (67.5%)	1.47	.816
16	I have good impression about English Studies curriculum	5 (12.5%)	6 (15%)	11 (27.5%)	18 (45%)	1.95	1.06

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17	I do not see good reason for merging the two subjects	4 (10%)	5 (12.5%)	15 (37.5%)	16 (40%)	1.92	.971
18	I teach English Studies curriculum for students to pass only.	3 (7.7%)	7 (17.9%)	18 (46.2%)	11 (27.5%)	2.05	.887
19	Teaching contents of English Studies curriculum is a waste of time	8 (20%)	3 (7.5%)	8 (20%)	21 (52.5%)	1.95	1.19
20	I see the teaching of English Studies curriculum to be challenging.	23 (57.5%)	7 (17.5%)	6 (15%)	4 (10%)	3.22	1.04

Weighted Mean = 1.77; Threshold = 2.50

Data collected by the researchers (2021)

Table 2 shows the attitude of teachers to English Studies curriculum. The result indicates a weighted mean of 1.77, which is lower than the threshold set at 2.50. This implies that the selected teachers had negative attitude to the English studies curriculum. Out of the 20 items used, 10 items contributed to this negative attitude because their means are lower than the weighted mean. The items are item 1 – English studies curriculum makes teachers to have poor attitude to the teaching of English Studies (mean =1.12), item 2 – English Studies curriculum makes teachers to be hardworking (mean = 1.25), item 4 – English Studies curriculum changes teachers’ attitude towards teaching English (mean = 1.57), item 6 – I hate English Studies curriculum because it is difficult to teach to the students (mean = 1.40), item 7 – I don’t like English Studies curriculum because it is not useful in real life context (mean = 1.62), item 10 – Teachers treat teaching of English Studies curriculum as an extra burden (mean = 1.07), item 11 – Teachers do not teach the literature aspect of the English Studies curriculum (mean = 1.37), item 13 – Teaching English Studies curriculum makes students to be passive recipient of knowledge (mean = 1.72), item 14 – Teaching contents of English Studies curriculum makes students to pay rapt attention in class (mean = 1.75), item 15 – I find English Studies curriculum too abstract to teach (mean =1.47). In conclusion, the result implies that the selected teachers had poor attitude to English studies curriculum.

Testing the Null Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between mean response scores of perceptions on English Studies curriculum among junior secondary school male and female teachers in Ibadan South-west Local Government, Oyo State

Table 3: Summary of t-test Analysis of the difference in mean response scores of perceptions on English Studies curriculum among junior secondary school male and female teachers

Variables			95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Remarks
	Mean	N	Std. Dev.	Mean Difference	Lower	Upper				
Male	50.06	15	16.39	-10.14	-19.35	-.926	-2.23	37	.032	Sig.
Female	60.20	24	11.97							

Data collected by the researchers (2021)

Table 3 shows the difference in the mean response scores of perceptions on English Studies curriculum among junior secondary school male and female teachers using the independent sample t-test analysis. The result indicates that there is a significant difference in the mean response scores of perceptions on English Studies curriculum among junior secondary school male and female teachers ($t_{(37)} = -2.23$; $p = .032 < .05$), with the female teachers (mean = 60.20) having a greater mean score than their male counterparts (mean = 50.06). So, the null hypothesis was accepted.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between mean response scores of Attitudes on English Studies Curriculum among Junior Secondary School male and female teachers in Ibadan South-west Local Government, Oyo State?

Assessment of Perception and Attitude ... (Ajagbe & Olatunji, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10666893>

Table 4: Summary of t-test Analysis of the difference in mean response scores of attitudes on English Studies Curriculum among Junior Secondary School male and female teachers

Variables					95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Remarks
	Mean	N	Std. Dev.	Mean Difference	Lower	Upper				
Male	35.53	15	5.85	.408	-2.93	3.74	.248	37	.806	Not Sig.
Female	35.12	24	4.41							

Data collected by the researchers (2021)

Table 4 shows the difference in the difference in mean response scores of Attitudes on English Studies Curriculum among Junior Secondary School male and female teachers using the independent sample t-test analysis. The result indicates that there is no significant difference in in mean response scores of attitudes on English Studies Curriculum among Junior Secondary School male and female teachers ($t_{(37)} = .248$; $p = .806 > .05$). So, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Discussion of Findings

Table 1 revealed that there was positive perception of teachers about English Studies Curriculum. The finding of this study is in line with Okunrila (2018) and Adegoke (2018) who found in their different studies that teachers had positive and good perception of the curriculum objectives of basic science and technology and French. The finding is contrary to Lawal (2019) who found that there was no significant relationship between teaching style and students' achievement in English Studies. Table 2 revealed that teachers had negative attitude to English Studies curriculum. This finding is in line with Waseka, Simatwa and Okwach (2016) who found that teacher's attitude has nothing to do with English Studies curriculum. This is contrary to the study of Adedigba and Fakeye (2020) who revealed that teachers' attitude and behaviour are very important to English Studies curriculum. Table 3 revealed that there was a significant difference in the mean response scores of perceptions on English Studies curriculum among junior secondary school male and female teachers. This finding is in line with Adegoke (2018) who found that there was a significant difference in the mean response scores of perceptions on French curriculum among junior secondary school male and female teachers. This is contrary to the finding of Lawal (2019) who found that there was a significant difference in the mean response scores of perceptions on English Studies curriculum among junior secondary school male and female teachers. Table 4 revealed that there was no significant difference in mean response scores of attitudes on English Studies Curriculum among Junior Secondary School male and female teachers. This finding is in line Waseka, Simatwa and Okwach (2016) who revealed that gender had no influence on teacher's attitude to curriculum implementation. This is against the finding of Lawal (2019) who revealed that gender had important influence on teacher's attitude influence to the implementation of the curriculum.

Conclusion

The study has shown that English Studies Curriculum could be enhanced by teacher's perception of and attitude to English Studies Curriculum. Based on the findings, this study has provided a better understanding of perception and attitude on English Studies curriculum among Junior Secondary School teachers in Ibadan South-West Local Government, Oyo State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that:

1. relevant educational bodies and stakeholders should ensure that teachers of English Studies have positive perception and attitude to English Studies Curriculum.
2. government should do everything possible to educate teachers of English Studies on the reasons for English Studies curriculum at Junior Secondary School level which comprises English language and Literature-in-English.
3. teachers should be involved in the design of English Studies curriculum for them to have positive perception and attitude towards it.
4. the Teaching Service Commission (TESCOM) and other educational bodies should organise seminars, workshops and other in-service trainings for English Studies teachers on importance of English Studies curriculum at the Junior Secondary School level.

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Assessment of Psychological Approach in Managing Industrial Disputes at University System of Education among Parents in Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara State

Ajayi, Beatrice Tayo

Department of Educational Psychology and Counselling,
Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo, Ondo State, Nigeria

Email: drtayocyajayi@yahoo.com

Tel: +234 8035727363

Abstract

This study investigated parents' opinion on the relevance and evident application of psychological concepts and principles in managing industrial disputes at Nigerian university system of education by the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) and the Federal government. This study adopts the descriptive survey research design. All working-class parents in Ilorin metropolis of Kwara State having children as undergraduates at Nigerian public universities during the 2021/2022 academic session form the population for the study. Sample consists of 400 parents (206 male and 194 female) undergraduate sandwich students of Kwara State College of Education, Ilorin selected using purposive random sampling technique. Respondents were workers at federal, state, and privately-owned establishments in Ilorin metropolis, Kwara State. One research question and three null hypotheses guided this study. The Psychological Approach in Managing Industrial Disputes at University System of Education (PAMIDUSEQ) developed by the researcher was used for data collection. The validity of the instrument was ascertained by two specialists in the field of educational psychology and measurement and evaluation respectively, of educational psychology and Counselling department, Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo. The reliability coefficient of 0.78 obtained through test-retest exercise determined the reliability of the instrument. Research question was answered using descriptive statistic of mean score while the t-test and ANNOVA statistics were used for data analysis at 0.05 level of significance. Result among others revealed parents' expressed relevance of psychological concepts and principles in managing industrial disputes at university system of education though its application by ASUU and federal government was not obvious. The study recommends need for university management, ASUU and federal government to incorporate psychological concepts involving positive incentives and actions of responsiveness having potential to address fundamental needs and fears of ASUU rather than threat or victimization approach.

Keywords: Psychological Approach, Industrial Dispute, Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU), Federal Government

Introduction

Industrial dispute has come to be regarded as one of the most visible perennial problems of significance in Nigerian university campuses. The educational system in Nigeria has witnessed an unprecedented industrial unrest and official assaults than other social institutions over the last thirty years (Adesulu, 2013). Nationwide strike actions frequently embarked upon by the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) are unduly prolonged with the end of a dispute catalysing onset of another. The depressive consequences of the incessant and intractable industrial dispute have been profoundly felt on homes, schools, and organisations. The typically prolonged ASSU strikes are not only demanding but stressful, painful, exhausting, and costly in human terms and on the quality of Nigerian graduates due to time loss. Its psychological effect on the part of students who must stay idle at home, lamenting their woes and causing irritation to parents cannot be overemphasised (Osagiobare et al., 2019). Consequently, the strategic position of university in the nation's hierarchy of priorities, its roles as veritable machine for development, knowledge and value provider, brain box of a country, the fountain for intellectualism and the most appropriate ground for incubation of tomorrow leaders appear being obviously challenged.

Conflict stems from pluralism and respect for diversity and is psychologically and socially healthy in providing conditions for social changes and democracy (Kelman, 2008). Different from the general conception, conflict is also inevitable as human relationship issues are at its root (Kelman, 2008 & ghaffar, 2008). When a group is faced with non-fulfillment of basic physiological needs including physical safety, physical wellbeing, identity, recognition, autonomy, self-esteem, and sense of justice however, conflict is likely inevitable. Conflict, though considered as normal, anticipated, and a reflection of staff and employers' incompatibility of interests, goals or values with each other (Johansen, 2012 & Henry, 2009) can be required to defy people to perform and stimulate progress (Hotepo et al., 2010) and to attain optimum organizational effectiveness (Obi et

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al., 2015), can be unhealthy. Additionally, unresolved conflict can be highly demanding, stressful, exhausting, and costly both in human and material terms but if managed effectively, can facilitate progress and development among groups.

Industrial dispute ensues as a disagreement among people, institutions, groups, communities and nations, through which the parties involved perceive threat to their needs, interest or concerns (Ghaffar, 2008; Hotepo et al, 2010; Johansen 2012, when they perceive that they are getting less than their fair share or that equity has not prevailed on issues that affect their interest and that participating parties in industrial relations are unable to reach peaceful agreements as it affects job rules and conditions of job generally (Henry 2009). The Nigerian labour market has witnessed several unresolved industrial conflicts designated as inevitable, normal, anticipated and not necessarily dysfunction but suggestive of strained industrial relations between the academic staff and the Federal Government of Nigeria.

The incessant industrial disputes in Nigerian university system dates to over thirty years and has continue to be a factor in academic life to the extent that predictive phenomenon has it that students would spend some months at home for a given academic session. The wastage of years meant for investment into academic activities is a huge setback rendering impossible timely course completion. Going by record of ASUU strike in year duration, Universities were closed for; 2 months in 1981 2months in 1988, 3 months in 1992 and 4months in 1993 (Osagiobare et al.,2019) Universities were closed 6 months in 1996, 3 months in1999, 6 months in 2001and 6 months in 2003(Uzor et al., 2020). Universities were also closed for 4 months in 2008, 5 months in 2009, 1 month in 2011, 5 months in 2013, 35 days in 2017, 95 days in 2018 and 9 months in 2020 (Uzor et al., 2020). Cumulatively, students at Nigerian Universities have spent over 2 years observing different strike actions. The huge wastage of years meant for investment into academic activities at universities is obviously doing the country's education no good and requires effective conflict management approach that limits the negative effects of conflict while increasing its positive aspects and improve group outcome or performance (Dontigney, 2018).

This study proposes relevance of psychological concepts and principles in managing industrial disputes at Nigerian university system of education to facilitate progress and development among groups. As postulated by Kelman (2008), painfully and frustratingly perceived rights' denial is a stimulus which ordinarily breeds discontent with unmet expectation. It consequently gives room for frustration, discontent, uprising and protest (Aluede et al., (2004). The theory of relative deprivation to social psychologists therefore is a gap between what people get (value capability, such as social status, welfare) and what they perceive they should (value expectations). This theory explains that once people's standard of living has started to improve, their level of expectation rises. If improvement in actual conditions drops, the urge to revolt emerges (Aluede et al., 2004). Denied human expectations, interests, needs, concerns, aspirations, and positions can be so intensely felt that it can degenerate with little catalysis into frustration, mass demonstration, violence and political instability. The theory of relative deprivation thus seems to account for welfare problems which also explain the causality of industrial dispute in the Nigerian university system. ASUU strikes are triggered partly by perceived deprivation of needs, rights, interests, and concern that borders on their work and welfare (Henry, 2009 & Dontigney, 2018). Some suggested psychological concepts and principles considered effective in managing industrial disputes are stated below:

Collaborating is one of the underlying principles that underscore successful conflict resolutions (Uzor et al.,2020). It fundamentally involves teamwork and cooperation in helping everyone or both parties achieve their goals while also maintaining relationships. It is a win- win resolution as each party is involved in search for the best solution to the conflict in a constructive manner considering the needs, desires, feelings and expressing the concern of each party. Its process of working through differences will lead to creative solutions that will satisfy both parties' concerns. It is used when there is a high level of trust and when you want others to have ownership of solutions. It is also used when the people involved are willing to change their thinking as more information is found and new options are suggested (Dontigney, 2018).

Accommodating strategy essentially entails giving the opposite side what it wants (Dontigney, 2018). I lose, you win approach fundamentally involves working towards a common purpose as more important than any other concerns, it occurs when one of the parties wishes to keep the peace or perceives the issue as minor. It helps to appease others by downplaying conflict, thus protecting relationships. This approach is used when an issue is less important to one party than it is to the other. It is used when you realise the wrong when you know you cannot win and when harmony is extremely important (Dontigney, 2018).

Compromising: This approach of 'I bend you bend' is on the fundamental premise of winning something while losing a little bit. The strategic philosophy is to place both ends against the middle in attempting to serve the "common good" while ensuring each team can maintain each of their original position. There is concern for outcome as well as relationship. Both parties try to reach an agreement that will give both some of what they want that will have no side effect on their relationship (Dontigney, 2018).

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Forcing is a win –lose resolution. The concern for the outcome here is high and requires the use of authority by the forcing individual. The use of the strategy is firm, not willing to give ground, intent of pursuing his goals. When both parties use this strategy, considerable hostility is likely because each is trying to gain the upper hand. This approach builds up resentment and hostility. Only one group will be happy about it (Dontigney, 2018).

Avoiding strategy seeks to put off conflict indefinitely by delaying or ignoring the conflict, the avoider hopes the problem resolves itself without a confrontation. In some cases, avoiding can serve as a profitable conflict management strategy such as the dismissal of a popular but unproductive employee. The hiring of a more productive replacement for the position soothes much of the conflict. However, those who actively avoid conflict frequently have low esteem or hold apposition of low power (Dontigney, 2018).

Psychological attitude of human respect according to Kelman, (2008) is the first approach for treating human relation issue. The principle of intergroup cooperation explains that animosity between groups subside when they engage in a joint activity to achieve mutually shared goals. Psychological principles and concepts of inter-group cooperation, persuasion, and mutual respect to achieve mutually shared goals is of high relevance for identifying real problems and addressing them. Solutions will only be found when the real problem is addressed (Shamir,2013). However, peoples’ personal perceptions, past experiences and expectations manifested in rational or irrational decisions influence the outcome of such negotiations at negotiation tables. The mediation process for instance involves interaction of various kinds during which emotion can affect the judgment of the parties like strong feeling resulting in irrational decisions that are counterproductive and even harmful to the parties (Shamir, 2013). This probably might have formed the bedrock of failed past negotiations for which strike actions had been recurrent at Nigerian universities.

Industrial disputes at Nigerian University system of education remain incessant and persistent over decades despite its numerous negative outcomes of distorted academic calendar, heavy losses of resources and even human life. The difficulty of stake holders of university education to deal promptly with industrial dispute, stem it down and prevent its escalation suggests that effective management of industrial disputes in Nigerian system remains a tussle. Unduly prolonged strike actions in the Nigerian university system not only threatens the ideals of the institution but pose great challenges to its strategic positions in the nation’s hierarchy of priorities and roles as a veritable machine for development, fountain of intellectualism, knowledge, value provider and the most appropriate ground for the incubation of leaders of tomorrow (Akinwale et al., 2023).

The sources of discontent for ASUU crisis in Nigerian University system are in exhaustive. They point to the unresolved deep –seated problems that underlie the ASUU-Federal Government conflict, the authoritarian attitudes of the government and university management towards labour issues, corruption in all segments of the society and maladministration (Solaja,2015). Other problems include mismanagement of public utilities and fund, unmotivated workforce, poor policy execution, underfunding of social services which to ASUU have led to a combination of decline in facilities, dilapidation of existing but often outdated infrastructure as well as fundamental decay in the university system (Solaja, 2015 & Akinwale, 2023). The signs of collapse began to show in the 1980’s and became evident in the 1990’s in the form of acute shortage of research and learning facilities (buildings, technology tools, laboratories, science, and engineering equipments, lecture theaters, digital libraries, constant electricity supply) for both staff and students (Enakoko,2013). Some engineering workshops operate under zinc sheds and trees. Due to lack of reagents and tools to conduct experiments, many science-based facilities are running what is referred to as ‘Dry Lab’ (Adesulu, 2013). Whereas ASUU regards the economy of the country as quite buoyant to provide required facilities for universities, past governments’ preference to spend money on frivolous things and use cosmetic solutions to handle strike actions is perceived to account for the present deterioration state. The failure of the Federal government to implement duly signed agreement by the government and ASUU since 1992 is claimed by ASUU as a basis for intensive context of repeated national strike.

Parents and students who are often worse hit by effects of strike actions are often persistent in their call to both the federal government and ASUU for prompt resolution of disputes rather than engaging the use of irrelevant and ineffective accusations that are incapable of removing outstanding barriers that have been hindering favourable resolution of disputes over years. While the union insist that the Federal government must honour the 2009 agreement by providing the funds according to the timetable and conditions both parties set (Enakoko,2013), Nigerians also clamour for use of more relevant protest approach order than strike actions now less popular as it once seemed in the 20th century by ASUU (Adesulu , 2013).

Human relationships are found at the root of disputes. Therefore, imperative, and helpful is the application of psychological concepts and principles that foster favourable relationships and removal of barriers to manage of industrial dispute in the university system. Previous research on industrial disputes have focused on nature and causes of conflict in schools (Ghaffar,2008) and causes of industrial disputes in Nigerian university system as well (Hotepo et al., 2010). Studies

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are however rare in the literature on the psychological approach in managing industrial dispute at the Nigerian university system. This is the gap which the present study seeks to fill.

Objectives of the Study

The objective of this study was to:

1. Assess the relevance of psychological approach in managing industrial disputes at the Nigerian university system of education.
2. Determine the respondents' opinion on application of psychological approach in managing industrial disputes at the Nigerian university system of education by university management, ASUU, and the federal government.

Research Question

The following research question was answered in this study:

1. Do parents' mean score response indicate the relevance of psychological approach in managing industrial disputes at Nigerian university system of education?

Hypotheses

1. Parents do not differ significantly in their opinion on application of psychological approach in managing industrial disputes at university system of education by university management based on the number of their children affected by the strike.
2. There is no significant gender difference in parents' opinion on application of psychological approach by ASUU in managing industrial disputes at the Nigerian university system of education.
3. There is no significant difference in parents' opinion on application of psychological approach in managing industrial disputes at Nigerian university system of education based on marital status type.

Methodology

Descriptive survey was adopted for this study. The population of this study consists of all working-class parents in Ilorin metropolis, Kwara State who have children studying in Nigerian public universities at the time of conducting the study. Sample size consists of 400 (206 (51.5%) male and 194 (48.5%) female) working class parents in Ilorin metropolis, Kwara State, Nigeria. Their marital status reveals 218 (54.5%) parents living with spouses, 148 (37.0%) single parents and 34 (8.5%) widowed. Parents with a single child affected in the unrest are 281 (70.3%) and those having two children and above affected in the unrest, 119(29.8%). Parents type of occupation reveals that 289(72.3%) are civil servants and 111(27.8%), privately employed. Type of children's university proprietorship reveals 176(44.0%) federal government, 132 (33.0%) state and 92 (23.0%) private type.

The researchers' designed instrument titled "Psychological Approach in Managing Industrial Disputes at University System of Education Questionnaire" (PAMIDUSEQ) was used for data collection. Construction of items of the instrument was based on the reviewed literature, media information and personal experience on patterns employed for handling ASUU strike by ASUU and the federal government of Nigeria. The instruments' section A of the four-point modified Renis Likert Type 18 items questionnaire solicited for information on biodata of respondents, while section B contained items on psychological approaches for managing industrial disputes in Nigerian universities. The instrument's items were scored weighing from four (4) for Strongly Agree (SA) to 1 for strongly Disagree (SD). In decision making, an item was considered positive if the mean score reaches 2.5 and above. The (PAMIDUSEQ) was face and content validated by two experts in Educational Psychology and Counseling department, Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo, Ondo State, Nigeria.

Administration of the instrument was personally conducted by the study researchers with the help of two trained research assistants on randomly selected respondents at workplaces. A total of 430 copies of the instrument were administered after which the completed copies of the instrument were collected within one hour. Out of the four hundred and thirty copies of the questionnaire administered, 400 adequately completed ones were used for analysis in this study.

Results

Research Question 1

Do parents' mean score response indicate the relevance of psychological approach in managing industrial disputes at Nigerian university system of education?

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Table 1: Mean score on the relevance of psychological approach in managing industrial disputes at Nigerian university system of education.

.S/N	ITEMS	N	Mean	SD	Decision
1	PREVENTING: Taking time to obtain information that can lead to dispute and using it to change decisions that forestall strike action.	400	3.33	.884	Accepted
2	Developing dispute prevention measures and best solutions in constructive manner considering groups' needs, interest and feelings	400	3.39	.748	Accepted
3	Accepting to work through differences with high level of trust to find a win-win-solution to the problem	400	3.4	.716	Accepted
4	COLLABORATING: Using mediation approach that establishes a cooperative problem-solving result	400	3.40	.788	Accepted
5	COLLABORATING: Putting in place teamwork, mediation approaches that address the fundamental fears of the other party	400	3.29	.773	Accepted
6	COLLABORATING: Directing negotiation towards conflict resolution that will satisfy the concern of both parties.	400	3.36	.794	Accepted
7	FORCING: Displaying firm resistance and lack of willingness by forcing authority to give ground for the other group	400	2.12	.77	Rejected
8	FORCING: Pursuing own group's viewpoint at the expense of another group	400	2.04	.76	Rejected
9	FORCING: Pursuing one's party's goals to gain upper hand despite resistance from the other group	400	1.26	.73	Rejected
10	COMPROMISING: Working on each party's problems to the extent that both give up something of lesser importance	400	3.28	.89	Rejected
11	COMPROMISING: Engaging in dialogue in meaningful ways until both parties have attained mutually satisfactory solutions that will give some of what they want.	400	3.28	.87	Rejected
12	COMPROMISING: Focusing on expectant and mutually acceptable solutions to each other's' problems	400	3.21	.96	Accepted
13	ACCOMODATING: Employing responsiveness to the other party's concerns and needs rather than prioritizing one's party's goals.	400	3.11	.92	Accepted
14	ACCOMODATING: Creating a favorable environment for negotiating.	400	3.44	.74	Accepted
15	ACCOMODATING: Creating a trust environment that offers other party's earlier agreed promises	400	3.30	.84	Accepted
16	ACCOMODATING: Making available confidence building measures	400	3.29	.86	Accepted
17	AVOIDING: Ignoring dispute rather than address the fundamental fears of the other party	400	1.27	.78	Rejected
18	AVOIDING Delaying response to dispute rather than settlement hoping the problem resolves itself.	400	2.20	.795	Rejected

Source: Field survey, 2022

Table 1 reveals eighteen listed conflict resolution measures to which respondents were to indicate the degree of relevance of each to managing industrial disputes in Nigerian universities. Results reveal parent's expressed relevance of psychological approach to management of industrial disputes in Nigeria universities except for the measure of forcing and avoiding as indicated in low mean scores below 2.5. The most accepted as relevant measures of high mean scores above 2.5 being: creating a favorable environment for negotiating and implementing such agreement, next is finding out the history of the conflict and the other identifying attempts already made to solve the problem.

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Hypothesis 1:

Parents do not differ significantly in their opinion on application of psychological approach in managing industrial disputes at university system of education by university management based on the number of their children affected by the strike.

Table 2: T-test analysis of difference in parents’ opinion on evident use of psychological approach in managing industrial disputes at Nigerian universities system of education by university management based on the number of children affected.

Children Affected by industrial action	N	X	SD	DF	t.cal.	t.val.	decision
One Child	281	59.32	5.62	398	-.752	1.97	NS
Two Children and above	119	59.76	5.00				

Source: Field survey, 2022

Results on table 2 reveals t calculated value $-.756$, degree of freedom 398 at .05 level of significance. Since the calculated value $-.756$ is less than the critical table value 1.97, the research hypothesis is accepted, which means there is no significant difference in the opinion of parents on the relevance of psychological approach for handling industrial dispute by university management in Nigerian universities based on the number of children affected by the strike.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant gender difference in parents’ opinion on application of psychological approach by ASUU in managing industrial disputes at the university system of education.

Table 3: T-test analysis on application of psychological approach in managing industrial disputes at Nigerian university system of education based on gender

Gender	N	X	SD	DF	t.cal.	t.val.	Decision
Male	206	59.50	5.74	398	-.226	1.97	N.S
Female	196	59.39	5.12				

Source: Field survey,2022.

Result on the table 3 reveals t calculated value, $-.226$, degree of freedom 398 at .05 level of significance. Since the calculated t-value $-.226$ is less than the critical table value 1.97, the null hypothesis was accepted, which means, there is no significant difference in the opinion of male and female parents on evident use of psychological approach for managing industrial disputes in Nigerian universities by ASUU, the labor union.

Hypothesis 3:

There is no significant difference in parents’ opinion on application of psychological approach in managing industrial disputes at Nigerian university system of education based on marital status type.

Table 4: Analysis of variance on parents’ opinion on application of psychological approach in managing industrial disputes at Nigerian university system of education by the federal government based on marital status type.

Source of Variance	SS	DF	MS	Cal.F ratio	Critical F ratio.	Decision
Between Groups	47.229	2	23.614	.797	3.00	A
Within Groups	11767.771	397	29.642			
Total	118115.000	399				

Source: Field survey,2022.

Table 4 indicates the one-way Analysis of variance (ANNOVA) value of $.797$, DF 399 with $P=.452$. Since the calculated F-ratio is lower than critical F ratio 3.00 at .05 level significance, the hypothesis was accepted. This means that there is no significant difference in the opinion of parents on the relevance of psychological approach for managing industrial disputes in Nigerian universities by the federal government, based on type of marital status.

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Discussion of Findings

Responses to the only research question of this study reveal the relevance of psychological approaches of preventing, collaborating, compromising, and accommodating to industrial disputes management in the university system but that forcing and avoiding approaches are not. Findings agree with earlier researchers of Johansen (2012) that conflict management behaviours are partially situated and that the approach for managing conflict is chosen to match the situation at hand. Result is therefore in line with researchers' advocacy for shift in labour's use of strike actions for managing industrial dispute and federal government use of more effective approach of collaboration to curb outbreak and resolve industrial disputes in an efficient manner that could result in improved quality staff morale (Ajayi, 2020 & Johansen, 2012).

Result also reveals no significant difference in parents' opinion on evident application of psychological approach for management of industrial dispute by universities management based on the number of their children that are affected by industrial disputes. The finding agrees with that of Iredia (2013) that most people, including parents wish that university managers could reduce frustrations in their campuses by identifying with the needs of both staff and students, rather than threat. Also related is Iredia's (2013) finding that industrial disputes in Nigerian universities, being the result of administrators' inability to recognise conflict, view conflicts' constructive as well as destructive potential, learn how to manage conflict and apply conflict management strategies in practical way. Enakoko (2013) therefore advocated a more judicious use of internally generated revenue collected yearly by university managers for possible positive impacts on the overcrowded facilities in Nigerian universities hence its tendency to prevent strike outbreak. It is glaring therefore that irrespective of the number of children of a parent affected by industrial dispute parents feel grossed alike being those that mostly bear the brunt of industrial disputes as their children sit idle at home, with tendency of them getting involved in anti-social vices.

Result reveals no significant difference in the opinion of male and female parents on evident use of psychological approach for handling industrial dispute in Nigerian universities by ASUU. This result agrees with Adesulu (2013) findings on parent's opinion of absence of definite actions to end strikes in Nigerian universities by ASSU and Federal government with students at the receiving end. The result however disagrees with that of Adesulu (2013) that strike, the means of protest by ASUU is no longer popular as it once seemed in the 20th century and calls for review.

Result also reveals no significant difference in respondents' opinion on evident use of psychological approach for handling industrial disputes in Nigerian universities based on type of marital status. The result agrees with that of Adesulu (2013) and Hetepo et al (2010) that the inability of Nigerian universities to successfully attain and achieve the set goals and objectives is the result of poorly managed industrial disputes by the federal government. Result also agrees with that of Enakoko (2013) and (Akinwale et al., 2023) that fertile ground for onset and escalation of strike actions is provided by governments' avoidance and non-responsiveness to financial needs and desire of Nigerian universities.

Conclusion

Educators are quick to advocate replacement of a seemingly ineffective method of industrial dispute for a more effective one. The view very much lends credence to the passionate appeal for university management, labour union and federal government for shift in their regular strike approaches to manage industrial dispute to enable smooth running of school calendar, incentives, and more positive results order than mere promises. Relevance of psychological approach to industrial dispute management in Nigerian universities is established by respondents of this study, its use however for positive results was not evidently ascertained.

Recommendations

1. University management, labour union and the federal government should endeavor to employ psychological strategies of preventing, accommodating, collaborating and compromising that involve positive incentives and actions of responsiveness in addressing fundamentals needs and fears of the other party through positive steps and not threats,
2. University management, labour union and the federal government need to engage in dialogues that address conflict management behaviour as a first step in creating a healthy work environment. The prevalent use of avoidance of avoidance by university management as conflict management strategy prevents proper address of the root of problems.
3. Arrangement ought to be in place for educating and training of university staff, their management and undergraduate business programmes in conflict management strategies. This can go a long way to prevent, address and effectively resolve conflict. Providing more conflict management training in an undergraduate business programme could help raise the

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emotional intelligence of future managers so they are more likely able to use problem-solving skills instead of trying to bargain.

4. Because conflicts are part of human interactions and nature, university management, ASSU and federal government should employ psychological approach to resolve and manage industrial disputes as they arise before escalating to unmanageable level.

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Assessment of School Facilities on Basic Science Teaching among Secondary School Teachers in Abuja, Nigeria

Owolabi, Josiah¹

Email: joowolabi@noun.edu.ng

Tel: +2348150762756

Oni, Leah Olubunmi¹

Email: ooni@noun.edu.ng

Tel: +2348131392355

¹National Open University of Nigeria

Abstract

The descriptive survey research design was adopted for this study. The study focused on assessment of school facilities on Basic Science teaching among secondary school teachers in Abuja, Nigeria. The population of the study consists of all Basic Science Teachers in both public and private secondary schools in Abuja, during the 2022/2023 academic session. The sample size consists of 174 (94 urban and 80 rural) teachers selected using multistage sampling technique. Three research questions and one hypothesis were raised. Two instruments titled: School Facilities Functionality Inventory Scale (SFFIS) and School Facilities Adequacy Inventory Scale (SFAIS) with reliabilities coefficient value of 0.787 and 0.902 were used respectively. The draft instruments were subjected to validation process as three experts were involved in the validation of the instruments. Descriptive statistics was used to answer the research questions and independent sample t-test to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. Findings, showed that the level of availability of school facilities was high, functionality is poor, while adequacy is low. However, there is no significant difference in the influence of school facilities on basic science learning between rural and urban areas. It is therefore recommended that all hands are to be on deck in ensuring functionality adequacy of school facilities for basic science learning in both rural and urban schools.

Keywords: Assessment, School facilities, Basic science learning, Influence, Teachers

Introduction

Qualitative science education entails the provision of relevant school amenities that would garner its processes for effective service delivery. According to Mbaegbu, Unamma, Okorie, Ohuakanwa, Odupute, & Akpelu (2021), the poor performance in basic science resulted from remarkable lack of well-organized human resources, instructional materials and facilities in teaching and learning of basic science at the basic secondary education level. Availability of educational resources for teaching Basic Science in Junior secondary schools is seen as a life wire of the instructional process for successful learning outcomes of students. (Oni & Owolabi, 2021) The school facility consists of not only the physical structure and the varieties of building systems, such as mechanical, plumbing, electrical and power, telecommunications, security, and fire suppression systems. The facility also includes furnishings, materials and supplies, equipment and information technology as well as various aspects of the building grounds, namely, athletic fields, playgrounds, areas for outdoor learning, and vehicular access and parking. They are therefore, the physical and human resources that are used in the school in order to forestall effective teaching and learning.

Rufai, Umar and Idris (2013) as cited in Umar & Samuel (2019), asserted that students have low performance when they are not having access to standard facilities such as school library, laboratory and instructional equipment in the classrooms. An effective school facility is responsive to the changing programmes of educational delivery and at a minimum, should provide a physical environment that is comfortable, safe, secure, accessible, well illuminated, well ventilated, and aesthetically pleasing. A school without facilities may not be able to achieve the required goals and objectives of the educational system. This leads to a negative effect on students' academic performance. The school facility is much more than a passive container of the educational process: it is, rather an integral component of the conditions of learning. School facilities provide a real classroom experience for the learners and make teaching and learning process more interesting. The layout and design of a facility contributes to the place experience of students, educators, and community members.

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When facilities are available and skillfully utilizes, they influence learning and make it more meaningful. Gede and Tari (2011) as cited in Umar & Samuel (2019) noted that availability of resources in a school boost the morale of both teachers and learners towards effective delivery of lesson and one major factor contributing to academic performance in the schools' system. Depending on the quality of its design and management, the facility can contribute to a sense of ownership, safety and security, personalization and control, privacy as well as sociality, and spaciousness or crowdedness. In order to achieve good academic quality, these factors are pointed out as they relate to school facilities.

Practical lessons cannot be organized for science students in schools without science laboratories, or in schools with science laboratories but without the relevant materials and equipment. The only option for students in such schools who may wish to sit for science subjects in external examinations is the Alternative to Science's paper, whether or not the school building is adequately planned to accommodate the educational programme, it affects the life and activities that go on within it. The importance of school facilities has been highlighted by many educational administrators and planners. The importance attached to it as a vehicle for effective teaching and learning cannot be over emphasized (Saiyida in Sidhu, 2012), the importance of school plant was quoted thus: A school or a college is a vital and life-giving environment to the extent that it brings into the life of its students an abiding love and appreciation for all that is best and most significant in national and human life. Also, Oni (2020) claimed that the inadequacy of physical and material resources in schools is a major factor responsible for learning outcome of students. She further explained that schools that do not have adequate facilities such as workshops, laboratories, classrooms, teaching and learning materials are unlikely to post good results.

Saiyida in Sidhu (2012) asserts that as school heads and their academic staff plan and think together about the present and future needs of school facilities as vital factor that can contribute to the enrolment of students in the school. He further observes that through adequate planning of school facilities, they can determine the type of instructional materials teachers 'would need for effective instructions and whether the available classrooms are adequate for the anticipated number of students. Mgbodile (2000) cited in Osaigbovo & Osaigbovo (2021), stressing the need for school facilities, observed that the physical appearance and general condition of school physical facilities are the striking basis upon which many parents and friends of any educational institutions may make their initial judgments about the quality of what goes on in the school. In short, the physical facilities play a major role in determining the type of relationship between the school and the community. This is because parents and pupils make their judgments and take their decisions on whether to associate themselves with a particular school after a careful evaluation and consideration of the facilities in the school.

Ani (2007) cited in Osaigbovo & Osaigbovo (2021), while supporting the above statement, opined that if the quality and quantity of physical facilities attracts the admiration of a parent, the conviction of the parent will be that since the quality and quantity of facilities is of such level, the quality of the staff and school programme will be of high standard. Therefore, to attract the admiration and acceptance from the community, there is need for a well-planned school physical facilities and equipment. Assessment study on the availability and influence of school facilities, has being overlooked in the educational research in the basic education subsection. Therefore, this study sought to investigate assessment of school facilities on Basic Science teaching among secondary school teachers in Abuja, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

The main purpose of this study is to ascertain the degree of availability of school facilities and their influence on basic science learning, in two Area Councils (AMAC and Kuje) of FCT Abuja, Nigeria. The specific objectives are:

1. To ascertain the level of availability of school facilities used for basic science learning among secondary school Teachers in Abuja Area Councils.
10. To determine the level of functionality of school facilities used for basic science learning among secondary school Teachers in Abuja Area Councils.
- To investigate the adequacy of school facilities used for basic science learning among secondary school Teachers in Abuja Area Councils.
- To determine the influence of school facilities on basic science learning in rural and urban areas among secondary school Teachers in Abuja Area Councils.

Research questions

The following research question was raised in this study:

1. To what extent are school facilities for learning basic science available among secondary school Teachers in Abuja Area Councils in the sampled schools?

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2. To what extent are school facilities for basic science learning functional among secondary school Teachers in Abuja Area Councils. in the sampled schools?
3. To what extent are school facilities resources for basic science learning adequate among secondary school Teachers in Abuja Area Councils. in the sampled schools?

Hypothesis

1. There is no significant difference of school facilities on basic science learning between Secondary School Teachers in Rural and Urban Areas

Methodology

This study was designed to assess availability, functionality and adequacy of school facilities and their influence on basic science learning. The study used adopted descriptive survey research design method. The population of the study comprised of basic science teachers in private and public owned primary and secondary schools during the 2022/2023 academic session in Abuja Municipal Area Council (AMAC) and Kuje area councils. The population was stratified into the two councils and then participants were purposively selected based on availability and willingness to participate in the study. A total of 174 (94 urban and 80 rural) basic science teachers in the selected two area councils (AMAC and Kuje) participated in the study. Two instruments titled: School Facilities Functionality Inventory Scale (SFFIS) and School Facilities Adequacy Inventory Scale (SFAIS) with reliabilities coefficient value of 0.787 and 0.902 were used respectively. The draft instruments were subjected to validation process as three experts were involved in the validation of the instruments. Descriptive statistics was used to answer the research questions and independent sample t-test to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1

To what extent are school facilities for learning basic science available among secondary school Teachers in Abuja Area Councils in the sampled schools?

Table 1: Availability of School Facilities for Learning Basic Science (N = 174)

S/N	ITEMS	AVAILABILITY				TOTAL	PERCENTAGE
		Yes		No			
		Frequency	%	Frequency	%		
1.	Basic Science Laboratory	11.9	68.4	55	31.6	174	100
2.	Adequate Furniture	142	81.6	32	18.4	174	100
3.	Well Ventilated Classrooms	152	87.4	22	12.6	174	100
4.	Dust Bins	146	83.9	28	16.2	174	100
5.	Well Equipped Library	108	62.1	66	37.9	174	100
6.	Basic science garden	70	40.2	104	59.8	174	100
7.	Computer laboratory	132	75.9	42	24.1	174	100
8.	Lightening/Electricity	135	77.6	39	22.4	174	100
9.	Toiletries	140	80.5	34	19.5	174	100
10.	Refrigerator	84	48.3	90	51.7	174	100

Table 1, above shows the extent to which school facilities for teaching basic sciences are available in the sampled schools. The result showed that in majority of the schools, eight (8) the ten (10) facilities were available. This is shown by the percentage of schools that claimed the eight facilities were available. Therefore, the following school facilities were available; basic science laboratory, adequate furniture, well-ventilated classrooms, dust bins, well equipped library, computer laboratory, lightening/electricity, toiletries. The following two facilities were however absent in majority of the schools sampled for the study; basic science garden and refrigerator.

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Research Question 2

To what extent are school facilities for basic science learning functional among secondary school Teachers in Abuja Area Councils. in the sampled schools?

Table 2: Functionality of School Facilities for learning Basic Science (N = 174).

S/N	ITEMS	FUNCTIONALITY						Total	%
		Poor		Fair		Very Okay			
		No	%	No	%	No	%		
1.	Basic science Laboratory	64	37.0	69	39.7	40	23.1	174	100
2.	Adequate furniture	28	16.1	83	47.7	63	36.2	174	100
3.	Well-ventilated classrooms	25	14.4	70	40.2	79	45.4	174	100
4.	Dust bins	28	16.1	79	45.4	67	38.5	174	100
5.	Well-equipped library	59	33.9	76	43.7	39	22.4	174	100
6.	Basic science garden	79	45.4	66	38.2	28	16.2	174	100
7.	Computer laboratory	48	27.6	81	46.6	45	25.9	174	100
8.	Lightening/ Electricity	49	28.2	51	29.3	74	42.5	174	100
9.	Toiletries	46	26.4	65	37.4	63	36.2	174	100
10.	Refrigerator	100	57.5	41	23.6	33	19.0	174	100

Table 2 above also showed the level of functionality of the school facilities for teaching basic sciences in the sampled schools. The functionality of the items was generally poor. For instance, it is only two of the facilities (Well ventilated classrooms and Lightening/ Electricity) that were very okay in more than 40% of the schools sampled. Five of the school facilities (Adequate Furniture, Well Ventilated Classrooms, Dust bins, Well Equipped Library and Computer Laboratory) were fair in more than 40% of the schools sampled. Two of the school facilities (Basic science garden and Refrigerator) were poor in more than 40% of the schools sampled. Therefore, the analysis result showed a poor functionality of the available equipment.

Research Question 3

To what extent are school facilities resources for basic science learning adequate among secondary school Teachers in Abuja Area Councils. in the sampled schools?

Table 3: Adequacy of School Facilities for Learning Basic Science (N = 174).

S/N	ITEMS	ADEQUACY						Total	%
		Not Adequate		Somewhat Adequate		Very Adequate			
		No	%	No	%	No	%		
1.	Basic science Laboratory	73	42.0	65	37.4	36	20.7	174	100
2.	Adequate furniture	47	27.0	74	42.5	53	30.5	174	100
3.	Well-ventilated classrooms	44	25.3	63	36.2	67	38.5	174	100
4.	Dust bins	38	21.8	75	43.1	61	35.1	174	100
5.	Well-equipped library	74	42.5	64	36.8	36	20.7	174	100
6.	Basic science garden	94	54.0	54	31.0	26	14.9	174	100
7.	Computer laboratory	62	35.6	70	40.2	42	24.1	174	100
8.	Lightening/ Electricity	60	34.5	45	25.9	69	39.7	174	100
9.	Toiletries	62	35.6	49	28.2	63	36.2	174	100
10.	Refrigerator	98	56.3	46	26.4	30	17.2	174	100

Table 3 above showed the level of adequacy of the school facilities for teaching basic sciences in the sampled schools. The adequacy of the facilities was generally below average. For instance, none of the school facilities was found adequate in more than 40% of the schools sampled. Three of the school facilities (furniture, dust bins and computer laboratory) were

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somewhat adequate in more than 40% of the schools sampled. Therefore, the analysis result showed that generally, the school facilities for basic science teaching were not very adequate.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference of school facilities on basic science learning between Secondary School Teachers in Rural and Urban Areas

Table 4: T-Test Analysis of Influence of school facilities on basic science learning in rural and urban areas.

LOCATION	N	MEAN	STD. DEVIATION	T	D.F.	SIG.(2TAILED)	REMARK
Urban	94	47.7204	6.74435	1.141	171	.255	NS
Rural	80	46.5125	7.16531				

Table 4 presents the t-test comparison of influence of school facilities on basic science learning in rural and urban areas. The t-test comparison showed that the difference in rural and urban influence of school facilities on basic science learning was not statistically significant. This is evident from the sig-2 tailed values that is greater than the 0.05 benchmark. Since any t-test comparison of means of two groups which is greater than the 0.05 benchmark signifies insignificant difference in influence of the two groups (urban and rural areas), it therefore follows that the difference is not statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that There is no significant difference of school facilities on basic science learning between Secondary School Teachers in Rural and Urban Areas is accepted. The values of the mean influence of urban and rural areas however showed that the influence of urban area is higher than that of their rural areas. Since the difference is not statistically significant, it cannot be generalised; it must have occurred due to sampling error.

Discussions of findings

The findings of this study, showed that the level of availability of most school facilities for basic science learning is high to a great extent. Few of the school facilities, however, were not available in most of the studied schools. The variation in the level of availability across schools may not be unconnected with the fact that the schools are owned by bodies that differ in financial capability as well as focus and passion. While some of the owners are buoyant financially, some are not. Also, while some are passionate about availability of school facilities, some may not. The finding contradicts Tekalign (2016), who in a study on science laboratory equipment in the teaching of science subjects revealed that, 33.33% of the high schools under study did not have science laboratories. The unavailability and inadequacy of science laboratory resources in the schools makes it difficult for teachers and students to cover some areas that require practical activities, and this obviously is bound to be a contributory factor to non-achievement of curriculum objectives.

The next finding showed that to a large extent there is poor functionality of available school facility equipment in basic science learning. This may be as a result of inadequate maintenance of school facilities. This result agrees with Musa (2014) who studied the evaluation of availability and maintenance of school facilities and reported that some of the facilities were inadequate, while some are not available at all. The ones available were not maintained and were only used occasionally which leads to poor functioning. It was basically revealed that, what was indicated as available by the respondents were mainly dilapidated structures and facilities begging for maintenance. Asiyai (2012), also reported that the maintenance carried out on school facilities were inadequate on majority of the facilities. The factors encouraging school facilities deprecation included excess pressure on available facilities and delayed maintenance amongst others.

Another finding also showed that generally, the school facility for basic science learning were not very adequate. Paucity of funds and economic hardship can be a possible explanation for the finding. This result is in agreement with Education Insight (2005) that discovered that inadequacy of facilities such as laboratory equipment pose a big challenge in many schools.

The test of hypothesis showed that the difference in the influence of school facilities in urban area is not significantly different from that of the rural areas. The possible reason could be a result of the impact of governments' intervention in the promotion of learning of sciences in schools.

Conclusion

The findings of the study revealed that degree of availability of school facilities for teaching and learning of basic science was high while functionality and adequacy were poor. Also, the differences in the effect of school facilities on basic science learning in urban and rural areas is not statistically significant and therefore not generalizable.

Recommendation

In line with the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

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1. More funds should be injected into the basic school system for the purpose of procuring more school facilities for teaching and learning of basic sciences.
2. The quality assurance section in the ministry of education should lay more emphasis on availability, functionalities and adequacy of school facilities that aid teaching and learning of basic science in their routine monitoring activities of both public and private basic schools.
3. School administrators should ensure availability, functionality and adequacy of school facilities for teaching and learning of basic science.
4. Curriculum planners, developers and designers should endeavour to include in the curriculum, activities that will enhance the use of school facilities in the teaching and learning of basic science.

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Assessment of the Influence of small-scale Business on Academic Performance of Middle school Female Students in Takeita City, Zinder, Niger Republic

Ousseini Kaka, Adamou¹

Email: adamoukaka15@gmail.com

Tel: +22796071714

Ousseini Kaka, Maman Rabiou²

Email: maman.rabiou@gmail.com

Tel: +41775058598

¹Collège d'enseignement Secondaire de Tirmini, Zinder, Niger Republic.

²SWISS UMEF University, Geneva.

Abstract

The purpose of this study is to assess the influence of small-scale business on academic performance among middle school female students in Takeita City, Zinder, Niger Republic. A quantitative approach through an explanatory research design is used to conduct this study. The Population of the study consists of all middle school class two students during the 2022/2023 academic session in Takieta City, Zinder, Niger Republic. A sample size of 100 female students were selected using multi-stage sampling technique. The data were collected through a questionnaire and the results indicate that girls who daily engage themselves in Small Scale Business and devote much time in these activities are negatively influenced in their academic activities (school attendance, lesson review, homework, etc.). Although the social role that the small-scale business plays, it is undeniable that it constitutes an influencing factor which can leads the female students to dropout. That's why it is recommended to female students who practice that activity, to plan their time and respect this planning and to parents in order to control the practice of the extracurricular activities of their daughter. Parents must also ensure and place a particular emphasis on the follow up of the schooling of their daughter.

Keywords: Small Scale Business, Female Students, Academic Performance.

Introduction

Education plays a key role in the development of a country, so it would be fallacious to think about a development worthy of its name without it. Indeed, the objective set by UNESCO (1990 as cited in Abdou, 2020, p.12) during the world conference on education in Jomtien (Thailand) on Education For All (EFA) to which Niger subscribed in 2000, caused the swelling of the school population and a massive transition from primary to lower secondary education. Regarding the importance of education in the development of each country, Niger Republic has placed a particular emphasis on the development of education since its accession to independence. Thus, to improve this education system, several reflections have been carried out in order to meet the aspirations of the population of Niger, which must participate fully in its economic and socio-cultural development. In 1998, Niger adopted a law (LOSEN) which carried the orientation of the educational system of Niger (Law n°98-12 of June 1st 1998). This law was materialized by the elaboration of a decennial program for the development of education (PDDE) for the period of 2003-2013. Indeed, this law promoted the expansion of secondary school enrollment while creating an imbalance between needs and available means. Despite all the efforts made, the educational system of Niger republic is still confronted with gender disparities. The schooling and the academic success of the young girls, is far behind those of the boys. Those disparities are for the most parts, related to socio-cultural and economic factors. Many studies (Roufai, 2011; Quenum, 2011 ; Zah, 2013) particularly supported the idea that traditional status of the girl/woman, the economic situation of the parents, the domestic work, the small scale business, the forced and early marriage, the undesired pregnancy constitute some causes of these gender inequalities in terms of access, performance and school completion. Considering the importance of girls' education, this study focuses on assessing the Small-Scale Business on Academic Performance among Middle School Female students in Takeita City, Zinder, Niger Republic.

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This article focuses on the academic performance of girls, which falls within the field of social science studies and several methodological approaches. Study carried out by Jacques HALLAK (1981) revealed that factors like social factor, geographical factor and environmental factor constitute the main factors of school success. The family environment has a direct influence on the academic performance of students. It's also shown that students from privileged backgrounds, given their social conditions, obtain more good school results than those from disadvantaged parents, Abdou (2020, p.48). ZAH (2013), found that the school failure of the students can be justified by the socio-economic status of their parents. Other studies (UNICEF, 1990; Daniel, 2014; Johannes, 2018) revealed the influence of school environment, culture, and peers on the academic performance of girls. It is asked in the schooling of girls the reasons of the poor school attendance of girls in these terms: how to explain that there are traditionally so few girls in schools in Niger? The desire of mothers to keep their daughters by their side, early marriage encouraged by the culture, fear of the influence of the modern school on children by parents and the unfavorable perception of school that girls have due to failures perpetrated by many students are the reasons of the poor school attendance of girls mentioned UNICEF (1990). The solution to this scourge in UNICEF's approach is to raise public awareness of the benefits of educating their daughters as well as the success of some of them at all school levels.

According to World Bank (2018, p.26) "In the global context, young girls' education, lagging behind that of boys, remains the major concern of the international community in general, and that of Africa in particular". Among the problems that affect the educational system and secondary education in African societies appears the poor academic performance of girls (Abdou, 2020 p.17). The extracurricular activities of girls are becoming more and more intensive and are affecting their academic performance as supported by the study carried by Koura (2001) and Roufai (2011). Despite the multiple efforts that educational policy makers are combining in collaboration with the Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) for the smooth running of the system, the educational future of girls remains worrying. In fact, in the program to accelerate the schooling and academic success of girls in the cross-border areas of UEMOA area, the commission concluded that, "if access to education is an imperative, making the students succeed remains the final objective" (UEMOA, 2011 p. 58). The follow up of the UEMOA aims, in the long term, to strengthen the role of women in regional integration through an improvement in the educational offer, particularly in cross-border areas. All these efforts made by State members, their partners and international organizations are undeniable and improvement has been made, but the objectives are far from being achieved. The challenges that face the education sector today, are therefore enormous. In addition to schooling, the matter of young girls' school retention, their success and above all their quality supervision remains problematic (UEMOA, 2011 p.59). According to Proteau (1995, p.75) "In Ivory Coast Republic, although the significant efforts made since independence, their educational situation is not fundamentally different from that of other African countries, particularly with regard to gender inequalities".

Table1: School enrollment rates in Ivory Coast Republic

Areas	First cycle of Secondary School		Secondary High School	
	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls
National level	40.7%	21.8%	19.9%	8.2%
Abidjan	52.9%	29.9%	25.1%	12.7%

Source: Data from RESEN (2010)

Like other countries, Niger is also facing problems related to illiteracy, low school performance of girls, and school retention (Roufai et al, 2011; Abdou, 2020). This problem continues to persist and hinders the retention of girls in schools. For example, the General Census of Population and Housing (RGPH) in Niger of 2012 shows a proportion of 55.6% of the population of 15 years and plus having no level of education, 62.69% of them are female. For the proportion of schooled children, it registers a significant decline according to the level. At the secondary level, according to the school census 2005-2006 carried out by the Ministry of Higher Education, Research and Technology, the number of students almost doubled, going from 92,463 to 179,721 students in 2005-2006. But these numbers do represent only 17.1% of the population of children of school age; the enrollment rate was 17.1% in 2005-2006.

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Table 2: Statistical report of school enrollment

Years	School Enrollment	
	Boys	Girls
2014-2015	93%	7%
2015-2016	91.4%	8.6%

Source: Statistical report 2015-2016

Thus, the last statistical report in table 2, shows that the girls' enrollment rate has increased of 1.6%. However, the rate increase remains high for boys. At the secondary school level, the poor academic performance of girls is also observed (Abdou 2023, Abdou & al. 2021). This situation is more accentuated and more recurrent in rural areas where girls' access to school is very low. This educational challenge requires careful analysis in order to find adequate solutions so that the secondary school level contributes to the production of human capital. This is why the government of Niger Republic created a law which carries the Orientation of the Educational System of Niger (LOSEN, law n°98-12 of June 1, 1998), because education is a right for all Nigeriens and the State guaranteed to children from 4 to 18 years old. The same law specifies that secondary school education receives children aged of 11 to 13 and its normal duration is 4 years. This sub-sector of secondary education is taken into account by the law and texts, but despite all these, exhaustive challenges are observable. The most noted challenge is the school dropout caused by the poor academic performance of female students (Abdou 2020, p.18), excluding each year a significant number of learners. Regarding this situation, the following research questions are asked.

Objective of the study

1. Assess the influence of small-scale business enrolment on academic performance of female students in middle schools in Takieta, Niger.
2. Assess the influence of time devoted for small scale businesses on academic performance among female students in middle schools in Takieta, Niger.

Research Questions

1. Do the female students who practice small scale business perform well at middle schools in Takieta, Niger?
2. Do the female students who devote much time to small scale businesses perform well at middle schools in Takieta, Niger?

Hypotheses

1. Girls who do small scale businesses do not perform well at school.
2. Girls who devote much time to small scale businesses do not perform well at school.

Methodology

This study was conducted using a quantitative approach through an explanatory research design as the study seeks to assess the correlation between small scale business practice and academic performance and time allotted to small scale business and academic performance. In this case, the academic performance is measured through the grades of the students. The Population of this study consists of all middle school class two students during the 2022/2023 academic session in Takieta city, zinder, Niger Republic. A representative sample of 100 female students which corresponds to 50% of the total number of the female students of that school was selected using multi-stage sampling technique. Considering the quantitative nature of this study, the data were collected through a questionnaire and analysed through SPSS and Excel software.

Results

Research Question

Do the female students who practice small scale businesses perform well at middle schools in takieta, Niger?

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Table 3: Statistical analysis of research question 1

Indicators	Do you have a good school performance?			
	Yes	No	Total	Percent
Do you practice the small trading?				
Yes	12	31	43	43%
No	41	16	57	57%
Total	53	47	100	
Percent	53%	47%	100%	100%

Source: Field Data (2021)

The results in Table 3 show the relationship between the small-scale business practice and school performance of the students. It is clear that, among the 43% of respondents who practice small scale business, only 28%, of them have good results and can have good school performance, compared to 72% who do not have good results and who do not even think they have a good academic performance. These results indicate that small scale business has a negative effect on the school performance of female students. So these data confirm the hypothesis no. 1 according to which: “Girls who do small scale businesses do not perform well at school.”. As a result, the poor school performance of girls results from the practice of small scale.

Research Question 2

Do the female students who devote much time to small scale businesses perform well at middle schools in takieta, Niger?

Table 4: Statistical analysis of research question 2

Indicators	How much time do you devote to the exercises?					
	None of them	1 to 2 hours	Total	Percent	Cumulated Percent	
How much time do you spend to small scale business?	None of them	20	37	57	57%	57%
	2 to 4 hours	39	03	42	42%	99%
	More than 4 hours	01	00	01	1%	100%
Total	60	40	100			
Percent	60%	40%	100%	100%		

Source: Field Data (2021)

The table 4 shows the influence of time devoted daily to small trading compared to that devoted to school exercises. In fact, the results of the survey show that, among the 100 students surveyed, among whom 43 students practice petty trade. It can be seen that only 7% of them devote approximately one to two hours of time to school activities, compared to more than 91%, who do not exercise but who devote more than 3 hours of time in their extracurricular activities. This situation has direct consequences on their academic performance and manifests itself mainly in the accumulation of bad grades. Thus, clearly and especially taking into account this table 4, we notice that the time devoted to exercises is insignificant compared to that devoted to small business. So this remark, based on the interpretation of the results, confirms hypothesis no. 2, which according to which “girls who devote time to petty trade unlike that of school activities cannot have a good academic performance”. Therefore, the more female students devote their time to petty trade, the greater their chance of having a good poor performance.

Discussion of Findings

This part presents previous works and studies that had the same or similar results with this study. The involvement and daily participation of students in small commerce can be a factor that affects the academic results of learners. Indeed, girls are the most involved in small trading and devote more time to it. Thus, the results of this study clearly show that girls who devote more time to small trading than to school activities, do not have good results and suddenly, they cannot have a good academic performance. This study is corroborated with that of ROUFAI et al. (2011). These situations have direct consequences on the school performance of the girls and are manifested essentially by a drastic and radical drop of grades in classes. They thus begin to accumulate bad grades linked to the many shortcomings and insufficiencies they have accumulated; partly related to the lack of concentration and attendance and lack of mastering the courses received.

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Still for ROUFAI et al. (2011), a girl forced to do a variety of domestic chores every day, apart from her school obligations, is no longer able to correctly and fully follow the lessons given in class. Even if the work is done moderately by the girl and adjusted so that she only works outside school hours (i.e. before or after the start of classes and/or on weekends), she cannot escape to physical fatigue, to the point where it will be impossible for her to attend school properly. Often, the girl is forced to go to school late and unlike these friends who arrived on time, she will have followed only part of the lessons that she should have followed in full if she was on time. In this same sense, the results are similar to the results of the Report Africa 2012 elaborated by the International Organization PLAN (2012) entitled “*Because I am a Girl!*”. This study was carried out in 11 African countries between November 2011 and May 2012. These results showed that for many children across Africa, finding enough time to study is a constant struggle against the daily works done for their survival and that of their families. This study found that it is difficult for learners to concentrate in class or to study well at home. Consequently, the pressure of the tasks to be accomplished is an essential factor limiting the academic success of girls. In addition, the results of this survey corroborates the results of SINON (2010) and Quenum (2011) who found that the time devoted to domestic chores outside of school hours influences the school performance of girls.

Conclusion

Ultimately, it is important to note that the practice of small trading by school girls is culturally spread widely in Niger. This is why it is traditionally believed that the small trading of girls has a socializing character because it initiates girls to support themselves and help their parents. However, this activity represents an influencing factor of academic performance and school retention of the girls. The results of this study indicates that the involvement of female students in small trading is considerably more important than in their school activities. Further these results show that the practice of these extracurricular activities is much more frequent among girls from low-income families. Therefore, the low level of education and socio-economic status of parents can be an explanation to the practice of small trading by school girls.

Recommendation

In view to the results presented, the following recommendation can play an important role in overcoming the problem of poor school performance of school girl due to the practice of small trading.

1. The female students who practice that activity, must plan their time and respect this planning;
2. Parents have to control the time of practicing the extracurricular activities of their daughter;
3. Parents must ensure and place a particular emphasis on the follow up of the schooling of their daughters;
4. They must also become more involved in the management of establishments through their representation and participation in the COGES and the AEP in order to know the role assigned to them in helping their children to improve their school performance;
5. They must also go to school from time to time in order to know the situation or the school work of their daughters.

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Awareness and Utilization of Web 2.0 Technology for Learning among Science Teacher Trainees in Akwa Ibom State

Itighise, Atim Edet¹

Email: atim_itighise@yahoo.com

Tel: 0814666 8803

Akpan, Anyanime O.¹

Tel: 0802 331 9141

Babayemi, John O¹

Email: babayemioluwole@gmail.com

Tel: 0803 842 1726

¹Department of Science Education, Akwa Ibom State University,

Abstract

This study examined assessment on awareness and utilization of Web 2.0 technologies among science teacher trainees in Akwa Ibom State University. Three research questions and two hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. Survey research design was adopted, the Population of the study consists of 387 (187 male and 200 female) science teacher trainees during the 2022/2023 academic session in Akwa Ibom State. 120 (52 male and 68 Female) science teacher trainees constitute the sample size of the study, this was arrived at using simple random sampling technique. A structured questionnaire tagged Science Teacher Trainees' Awareness and Utilization of Web 2.0 Technology (STTAUWT) was used for data collection and was validated by two experts. 30 respondents which were not part of the study were used to obtain reliability index of 0.75 using Cronbach's Alpha. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics to answer the questions while the independent t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The results revealed among others that there was no significant difference in the opinions of male and female science teacher trainees on their awareness and utilization of Web 2.0 technology in Akwa Ibom State University. It was concluded that Web 2.0 technology provide a level user interaction and offered free services, sites for immediate feedback. It was recommended among others that Web 2.0 technology should be used for teaching and learning in order to create opportunities for teacher trainees to learn and develop at their own pace in e-learning environment.

Keywords: Awareness. Utilization, technology and teachers' trainees

Introduction

The introduction of Web 2.0 technologies is an innovative method of disseminating knowledge and also serves as a powerful tool for the acquisition of skills. Communication skills for instance, are very important in teaching and learning processes (Babayemi & Utibe, 2017). Complete integration of technologies in teaching learning process enhances effective communication, lifelong and life-wide learning. Web 2.0 technology usage in learning process empower student to interact with others and access abundance resources. It provides immediate feedback and encourages self-directed learning to students. In this 21st century Web technologies when effectively used with others instructional materials make teaching and learning easy. In fact, the use of international networking allows for global transfer of data from one computer to another and allows free flow of communication and information for researches or assignment.

The term Web 2.0 is used to describe Web applications that are designed to be user centered and to aid the interaction of information sharing and collaboration on the World Wide Web which has created the social media platforms that are highly interactive. According to Yun-Jo and William cited by Ughelu (2016), Web 2.0 is a social revolution that makes it possible for people to participate through open application and services. Social medial sites and social networking are examples of Web 2.0 technologies amongst which is the dropbox and skype application. Wordu and Itighise (2020) comments that dropbox cloud-based applications is significantly critical to the progress and future of education serve as a way of transforming teaching-

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learning process and enhances students' academic performance when compared to expository methods. Itighise and Akpan (2021) comments that cloud computing technologies allow users to alter the content of web pages and interact with others. Web 2.0 technologies as a dynamic internet application that allows users to communicate with each other by creating, editing and sharing information. These technologies typically include Blogs, Forums, Wikis, Micro-messaging, Cloud computing, social Networking tools, Multimedia sharing, Social book-marking and podcast etc. The Web 2.0 technologies is different from the earlier Web 1.0 which is characterized as "read only Web".

According to Nazzal (2018) Web 2.0 technology is a "read-write Web" which are suitable for active and meaningful learning and information sharing, communication, collaborations and learning management. It provides users with room for interactivity that enhance the creation and sharing of information. Olannye, Nwaodume and Okegbe (2020) revealed that over 90% of students responded that they used social networking service such as Facebook, My space, Skype and LinkedIn in teaching and learning process. Technology usage in educational system have the potential to innovate, accelerate, enrich, deepen skills, motivate and engage students, relate school experience to work practices, create economic viability for tomorrow's workers, as well as strengthening teaching. Traditionally, teaching is viewed as a process of delivery to students what is required and without any opportunity for questioning. This means that the teacher has the Monopoly of knowledge required to be imparted. However, in the modern sense, teaching is an attempt to help learner acquire change of attitude, knowledge, idea, skill or application.

The features of Web 2.0 technologies are capable of helping students in their learning process. In the learning of science, the process involves doing, that is, hands-on. To help students learn and do science, they can use technology. Students can video laboratory processes like dissections and any form of practical work to be watched later as well as pictures can be taken and shared. Yan cited by Abudulkadir (2019) posits that students constantly use Web 2.0 technology for their daily communication and to access information for their personal use as they send Instant Message to friends and colleagues take pictures and post them online. Students share information, video, audio, chat and network with the people they met online which help in increasing learners' satisfaction with a course, improving their learning and writing ability and increasing students-students interaction.

Itighise and Thomas (2022) posits that teacher trainees use Web 2.0 tools for publishing their personal view, network with other students and promote student-centered interaction. According to Nazzal (2018), lecturers still adhere to the teaching method that stands them out as dispensers of knowledge rather than facilitators which is associated with chalk and talk method of teaching with the learning environment being teacher/lecturer centred. Tim (2016) comments that Web 2.0 websites enable users to create, share, collaborate and communicate their work with others, without any need of any web design or publishing skills. Generally, Web 2.0 technologies provide immediate feedback and dynamic internet applications that allows users to communicate with each other by creating, editing and sharing information. Anderson cited by Yin and Tsai (2021) indicate that there has been a growing trend of incorporating technology in education to fulfill some of the technological expectations of students. Evidently, emerging technologies such as Web 2.0 technologies have been adopted and integrate to foster teaching and learning activities in universities and colleges.

This study focused on Socio-constructivist theory propounded by Lev Vygotsky, a Russian teacher and psychologist in 1978. Lev Vygotsky state that people learn through their interactions, communications with others and how social environments influence the learning process. He proposed that learning takes place through the interactions students have with their peers, teachers, and other experts. Consequently, teachers can create a learning environment that maximizes the learner's ability to interact with each other through discussion, collaboration and feedback. Moreover, Vygotsky (1978) argues that culture and collaboration is the primary determining factor for knowledge construction. Vygotsky believed that knowledge is not only personally constructed but that it is also socially mediated. By this, he implied that although individuals have to construct their own meaning of a phenomena or idea, the process of constructing meaning is always embedded within the social setting of which the individual is part. Hence, social constructivists view learning as an active process where learners should learn to discover principles, concepts and facts for themselves through collaboration which encourage group work and intuitive thinking. The implication of this theory to the present study is that, the theory emphasizes the idea that learners make sense of their experiences by constructing their own understanding through their own "mental models" and by sharing of ideas among students. Utilization of Web 2.0 technology such as WhatsApp, Skype, Dropbox, IMOchat etc allow interaction between student-student and student-teachers in the classroom to accommodate new experiences.

Empirically, this study is in line with the earlier studies by Itighise and Akpan (2021) examined Educators utilization of ICT facilities for mastery learning in post COVID -19 era in selected state universities in South South, Nigeria. The population of the study was derived from 2019/2020 academic session which comprised of 225 science educators. A total of

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105 were selected using simple random sampling techniques. Data were gathered using questionnaire titled assessment of science educators' access and utilization of information and communication technology (ICT) for mastery teaching and learning". The questionnaire contained two sections: science educator access to ICT facilities and science Educators utilization of ICT facilities for mastering teaching and learning in post COVID-19 era. The reliability indices of the cluster A and B of the instrument were estimated to 0.89 and 0.78 using Cronbach's alpha method. The data collected were analyzed using percentages, mean and standard deviation to answer the two research questions. The result revealed that 52.50% of science educators access ICT facilities at home and 50.40% at their personal offices. The study also show that the mean score science educators utilization of ICT facilities for mastery teaching and learning in the post COVID-19 era are more 2.50 criterions mean. It was concluded from the study that all education activities in Nigeria should be geared toward ICT oriented to avoid closure of schools as in the case of COVID-19 pandemic. It was therefore recommended among other that government of Nigeria should direct political powers toward improving our education system through full blown ICT utilization in teaching learning process for promotion of mastery teaching in academic institutions. It is against this background the study assessed science teacher trainees' awareness and utilization of Web 2.0 technology in Akwa Ibom State.

It is a common knowledge that the utilization of the internet has made the world a global village. Experience are shared, knowledge are acquired, information transmitted via the Internet. The ability of a student to utilize the internet effectively is a significant advantage on their side. In Akwa Ibom State University, there is a provision of free internet connectivity for every staff and the entire department of Science Education have resource center with internet connectivity and computer analyst. The high level of low scores among science teacher trainees in universities has been traced to traditional teaching methods that promote activities of teachers and passiveness of learners who perceive the learning content with just the auditory mode assuring very poor retention an recall of contents.

However, web 2.0 technology as a social media platform has been developed to be an effective virtual communication medium through a computing platform that reside in a service provider's large data center which is able to dynamically provide servers the ability to address a wider range of needs of their clients or learners. This technology provides opportunities for supporting and enhancing teaching and learning strategies and practices. The question is: What is the level of science teacher trainees' awareness of the web 2.0 technologies in learning process? Do science teacher trainees' make use of the web 2.0 technologies available online for effective learning process? The study therefore assessed science teacher trainees' awareness and utilization of Web 2.0 technology in Akwa Ibom State.

Objectives of the study

The aim of this study is to assess level of awareness and utilization of Web 2.0 technologies for learning process among science teacher trainee in Akwa Ibom State. Specifically, the objectives of the study are to:

1. Determine the level of science teacher trainee's awareness on Web 2.0 technology tools for learning in Akwa Ibom State.
2. Assess the level of science teacher trainees' utilization of Web 2.0 technology tools for learning in Akwa Ibom State.
3. Determine the level of awareness on Web 2.0 technology tools for learning among male and female science teacher trainees in Akwa Ibom State.
4. Determine the level of utilization of Web 2.0 technology tools for learning among male and female science teacher trainees in Akwa Ibom State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study.

1. What is the level of science teacher trainees' awareness on Web 2.0 technology tools for learning in Akwa Ibom State?
2. What is the level of science teacher trainees' utilization of Web 2.0 technology tools for learning in Akwa Ibom State?
3. What is the level of awareness on Web 2.0 technology tools for learning among male and female science teacher trainees in Akwa Ibom State?
4. What is the level of utilization of Web 2.0 technology tools for learning among male and female science teacher trainees in Akwa Ibom State?

Hypotheses:

Base on the research questions two null hypotheses was formulated.

There is no significant difference between mean score of respondents on level of awareness of web 2.0 technologies for learning among male and female science teacher trainees in Akwa Ibom State

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Methodology

The design adopted for this study is the survey research design. The Population of the study consists of 387 (187 male & 200 female) science teacher trainees during the 2022/2023 academic session in Akwa Ibom State. 120 (52 male & 68 Female) science teacher trainees constitute the sample size of the study, this was arrived at using simple random sampling technique. The instrument for Data collection was research-made structured questionnaire, tagged Science Teacher Trainees Awareness and Utilization of Web 2.0 Technology Questionnaire (STTAUWTQ), which is made up of 40 items. The 30 items in questionnaire covered the level of awareness and utilization of Web 2.0 technology which was developed on a four point rating scale. The questionnaire had three Sections A, B and C which corresponded to the research questions. For research question one and two rating scale was as follow. Very High Level (VHL) - 4 points; High Level (HL) - 3 points; Low Level (LL) - 2 points; Very Low Level (VLL) -1point. In order to ensure content and face validity of the instruments, draft copies were given to two lecturers for face and content validation from the Department of science Education, Faculty of Education, Akwa Ibom state University. All comments and corrections were reflected in the final form of the instruments. The instrument was administered personally by the researcher to 30 respondents which were not part of the sample size and the data obtained were analyzed using Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient package using SPSS 17. The reliability coefficient of 0.75 was obtained. This coefficient shows that the instrument was reliable for the study. All the copies administered were returned with valid responses. The data generated from the retrieved instrument were analyzed using descriptive statistics to answer the research questions, while the independent t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the level of science teacher trainees' awareness on Web 2.0 technology tools for learning in Akwa Ibom State?

Table 1: Frequency Counts, Mean and Standard Deviation on Level of Science Teacher Trainee's Awareness of Web 2.0 Technology Tools For Learning Process in Akwa Ibom State. (N=120)

S/N	Items	VHL	HL	LL	VLL	Mean	Std. Dev.
i.	I am aware that IMO Web 2.0 allows learners to visually share lesson content through short compressed video or live experience video	59	36	13	13	3.18	1.00
2	I am aware that Facebook is free collaborative tool that provides anxiety free environment for learning	62	42	11	5	3.34	0.81
3	I am aware that Dropbox application is a fascinating, file hosting service that facilitates transactional learning	28	63	19	10	2.91	0.85
4	I am aware that Skype can be used to share video lesson content	32	51	25	12	2.86	0.93
5	I do not have knowledge of the potential of using WhatsApp in teaching and learning process	30	57	16	17	2.83	0.96
6	I do not have sufficient knowledge of effective application of Instagram as web 2.0 teaching and learning tools	27	56	23	14	2.80	0.92
7	I do not have knowledge of the potential of using Google Talk in teaching and learning process	25	58	21	16	2.77	0.93
8	I do not have knowledge of the potential of using My Space in the teaching and learning process	26	55	21	18	2.74	0.97
9	I am aware that Twitter can be used to share lesson content	61	31	15	13	3.17	1.02
10	I am aware that Blogs can be used to share video lesson content	58	26	20	16	3.05	1.09
11	I am aware of effective utilization of Email in teaching and learning process	52	29	21	18	2.96	1.10
12	I do not have knowledge of the potential of using Wiki in teaching and learning process	69	39	7	5	3.43	0.79
13	I do not have knowledge of the potential of using LinkedIn in learning process	17	25	47	31	2.23	0.99
14	I do not have knowledge of the potential of using Flickr in teaching and learning process	25	41	39	15	2.63	0.95
15	I am aware that YouTube can be used to share lesson content	71	37	9	3	3.47	0.74

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Grand Mean	2.96	0.94
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Table 1 shows the frequency counts, mean and standard deviation on the level of science teacher trainee’s awareness of Web 2.0 technology tools for learning process in Akwa Ibom State University. The result shows that the grand mean of respondents over the level of science teacher trainee’s awareness of Web 2.0 technology tools for learning process in Akwa Ibom State University was 2.96 and standard deviation of 0.94. Participants responded most positively to the item that stated “I am aware that YouTube can be used to share lesson content” (M = 3.47, SD = 0.74), this was followed by “I do not have knowledge of the potential of using Wiki in teaching and learning process” (M = 3.43, SD = 0.79). The participant also responded high to the item that stated that “I am aware that Facebook is free collaborative tool that provide anxiety free environment for learning” (M= 3.34, SD=0.81), and the least positive to the item that stated “I do not have knowledge of the potential of using LinkedIn in learning process” (M= 2.23, SD= 0.99).The mean scores for all items were high and since the grand mean is greater than 2.5, the result shows that there is a high of level of science teacher trainee’s awareness of Web 2.0 technology tools for learning process in Akwa Ibom State University.

Research Question 2

What is the level of science teacher trainee’s utilization of Web 2.0 technology tools for learning process in Akwa Ibom State?

Table 2: Frequency Counts, Mean and Standard Deviation on Level of Science Teacher Trainee’s Utilization of Web 2.0 Technology Tools For Learning Process In Akwa Ibom State

S/N	Items	VHL	HL	LL	VLL	Mean	Std.
9	I do use IMO Web 2.0 to share lesson content learners	7	22	53	38	1.98	0.86
2	I use Facebook as a collaborative tool that provides anxiety free environment for learning	24	47	33	16	2.66	0.95
3	I use Dropbox application as a fascinating file hosting service that facilitates transactional learning delivery	8	25	48	39	2.02	0.90
4	I do not use skype to share video lesson content with my colleagues	58	48	9	5	3.33	0.79
5	I use WhatsApp for teaching and learning process	30	45	26	19	2.72	1.01
6	I like using Instagram as web 2.0 technologies for active and meaningful learning, information sharing and collaboration	12	20	48	40	2.03	0.95
7	I use Google Talk for improving education quality in learning process	12	28	48	32	2.17	0.94
8	I make use of my Space to learn and develop at my own space in e-learning environment	7	19	51	43	1.92	0.87
9	I mostly use Twitter to share lesson content to the learners in order to change their attitude toward knowledge acquisition	3	22	69	26	2.02	0.71
10	I use faculty Blogs to share video lesson content and provides a level user interaction	4	14	53	49	1.78	0.78
11	I use Email for effective teaching and learning process	8	5	80	27	1.95	0.73
12	I make use of Wiki for teaching and learning process	77	34	9	-	3.57	0.63

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13	I make use of Flicker for collaboration and sharing of lesson content	42	26	33	19	2.76	1.10
14	I use LinkedIn in communicating the lesson content to colleagues	16	15	46	43	2.03	1.01
15	I use YouTube to share lesson	24	31	46	19	2.50	0.99
Grand Mean						2.36	0.88

Table 2 shows the frequency counts, mean and standard deviation on the level of science teacher trainee's utilization of Web 2.0 technology tools for learning process in Akwa Ibom State University. The result shows that the grand mean of respondents over the level of science teacher trainee's utilization of Web 2.0 technology tools for learning process in Akwa Ibom State University was 2.36 and standard deviation of 0.88. Participants responded most positively to the item that stated "I make use of Wiki for teaching and learning process" (M = 3.57, SD = 0.63), this was followed by "I do not use skype to share video lesson content with my colleagues" (M = 3.33, SD = 0.79). The participant also responded high to the item that stated that "I do use WhatsApp for teaching and learning process" (M= 2.72, SD= 1.01), and the least response to the item that stated "I do use faculty Blogs to share video lesson content and provides a level user interaction" (M = 1.78, SD= 0.78). Since the grand mean of 2.36 is lesser than 2.5, the result shows that there is a low level of science teacher trainee's utilization of Web 2.0 technology tool for learning process in Akwa Ibom State University.

Research Question 3

What is the level of awareness on Web 2.0 technology tools for learning among male and female science teacher trainees in Akwa Ibom State?

Table 3: Summary of Mean and Standard Deviation on the Level of Awareness of Web 2.0 Technology Tools for Learning Process by Male and Female Science Teacher Trainees

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean diff
Level of Awareness	Male	52	45.04	3.21	1.19
	Female	68	43.85	3.34	

The result in Table 3 shows the level of awareness of Web 2.0 technology for learning process by male and female science teacher trainees. The mean of 45.04 of male respondents was slightly higher than mean of female 43.85 with the mean difference of 1.19 showing slight difference in the level of awareness. To ascertain if the observed mean difference is statistically significant, the data was further subjected to test of analysis using independent t-test statistics. The result is presented in table 5.

Research Question 4

What is the level of utilization of Web 2.0 technology tools for learning among male and female science teacher trainees in Akwa Ibom State?

Table 4: Summary of Mean and Standard Deviation on the Level of Utilization of Web 2.0 Technology Tools for Learning Process by Male and Female Science Teacher Trainees

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean diff
Level of Utilization	Male	52	32.75	4.78	1.12
	Female	68	33.87	3.14	

The result in Table 4 above shows the level of utilization of Web 2.0 technology tools for learning process by male and female science teacher trainees. The result showed that the mean and standard deviation scores (32.75 and 4.78) of male respondents on level of utilization of Web 2.0 technology tools for learning process was slightly lesser than mean and standard deviation scores (33.87 and 3.14) of female respondents. This was observed with a remarkable mean difference of 1.12 showing the difference in the level of utilization of Web 2.0 technology tools for learning process by male and female students in science

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education. To ascertain if the observed mean difference is statistically significant, the data was further subjected to test of analysis using independent t-test statistics. The result is presented in table 6.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between mean score of respondents on level of awareness of web 2.0 technologies for learning among male and female science teacher trainees in Akwa Ibom State

Table 5: Summary of Independent T-Test on the Difference in the Opinion of Male and Female Science Teacher Trainees on their Level of Awareness of Web 2.0 Technology Tools

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	SD	df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Awareness of Web 2.0	Male	52	45.04	3.21	118	1.95	1.96	Accepted H ₀₁
	Female	68	43.85	3.34				

The result in table 5 revealed that the calculated t-value of 1.95 is lesser than the critical t-value of 1.96 at .05 level of significance and at 118 degrees of freedom. This implies that there is no significant difference in the opinions of male and female science teacher trainees on their level of awareness of Web 2.0 technology tools for learning process. This result shows that the level of awareness of Web 2.0 technology tools for learning process is at the same pace.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between mean score of respondents on utilization of web 2.0 technologies for learning among male and female science teacher trainees in Akwa Ibom State

Table 6: Summary of Independent T-Test on the Difference in the Opinions of Male and Female Science Teacher Trainees on their Level of Utilization of Web 2.0 Technology Tools

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Utilization of Web 2.0	Male	52	32.75	4.78	118	1.54	1.96	Accepted H ₀₂
	Female	68	33.87	3.14				

The result in table 6 revealed that the calculated t-value of 1.54 is lesser than the critical t-value of 1.96 at .05 level of significance and at 118 degrees of freedom. This implies that there is no significant difference between mean score of respondents on utilization of web 2.0 technologies for learning among male and female science teacher trainees in Akwa Ibom State. This result shows that the level of utilization of Web 2.0 technology tools for learning process is at the same pace.

Discussion of Findings

The result of findings in table 5 revealed that the calculated t-value of 1.95 is lesser than the critical t-value of 1.96 at .05 level of significance and at 118 degrees of freedom. This implies that there is no significant difference between mean score of respondents on level of awareness of web 2.0 technologies for learning among male and female science teacher trainees in Akwa Ibom State. Hence, the null hypothesis one of no significant difference is accepted. This result shows that the level of awareness of Web 2.0 technology tools for learning process is at same pace. Web 2.0 technology provide a level user interaction and offered a free service, sites, like Wikipedia and Facebook have grown at amazing fast rates (Berk, 2016). Teacher trainees used Web 2.0 tools for publishing their personal view, network with other students and promote student-centered interaction (Itighise & Thomas,2022).

The result of findings in this hypothesis revealed in table 5 that the calculated t-value of 1.54 is lesser than the critical t-value of 1.96 at .05 level of significance and at 118 degrees of freedom. This implies that there is no significant difference between mean score of respondents on utilization of web 2.0 technologies for learning among male and female science teacher trainees in Akwa Ibom State. Hence, the null hypothesis two of no significant difference is accepted. This result shows that the level of utilization of Web 2.0 technology tools for learning process is at the same pace. Web 2.0 technologies adoption indicates that developing interactive, technology-rich curricula is suitable for preparing students for the present complex world(Mohammad, 2011).

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Conclusion

From the results obtained in the study, technology encourages knowledge-based learning approach and helps to support a student-centered, constructivist, and progressive approach. It was therefore concluded that technology expanded course offerings, and increased students engagement and motivation towards learning. Web 2.0 technologies provide a level user interaction and offered free services, sites like Wikipedia and Facebook, and encourage immediate feedback.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. The findings established a generally low usage of Web 2.0 technologies for teaching and learning process in the university. There is therefore a need for institutional policy on the integration of Web 2.0 technology in teaching and learning activities.
2. The university authorities should consider creating awareness on the different types of Web 2.0 technologies for teaching and learning process and also encourage lecturer used Web 2.0 technologies for communication and collaboration. This would address the issue of non-use and will give students the opportunity to identify and choose the tools that are suitable for specific tasks related to personal, academics or general activities.
3. The university authorities should also put in a place, a programme of user education for students to encourage them and also learn how to use Web 2.0 technology for academic and other purposes
4. Science teacher trainees should be given adequate training through workshop and seminar on how to use Web 2.0 technology for effective learning process.

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Development of Emerging Technologies and Innovations through Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) Programmes in Nigeria

Onyeagbako, Stella Okwuchi¹

Email: stellaonyeagbako@gmail.com

Tel: 08033318670

Bema, Barida Nubari²

Email: Bema.barida@gmail.com

Tel: 08063518499

¹Imo State University, Owerri

²Department of Educational Management, Faculty of Education, University of Port Harcourt

Abstract

This article is an opinion paper which deals with managing and development of emerging technologies and innovations through technical and vocational education and training (TVET) programmes in Nigeria". It examined the concepts of technical and vocational education, innovation and management, objectives of technical/vocational education in Nigeria as entrenched in the National Policy of Education 2014. The paper looked at the historical perspective of technical and vocational education in Nigeria. The challenges of technical and vocational education include: Inadequate funding, parental attitude towards technical towards technical and vocational education in Nigeria, shortage of teaching staff and curriculum content. Provision of qualitative technical and vocational education is necessary for technical education to achieve its aim. Based on that, recommendation/Strategies for ensuring technical and vocational education were made which include emerging technologies and innovations for improved funding of technical and vocational education; there should be a change in parental attitude towards technical and vocational education, recruitment of qualified manpower and improved curricula content.

Keywords: Technical and vocational education, management and development.

Introduction

Education all over the world have been viewed as a tool for both personal and national development (FRN, 2004). It is the process of receiving or giving systematic instruction, especially at the secondary or University education levels. Therefore, Education focuses on the training and developing of knowledge, skills, mind and character of the people for maximum productivity. Education facilitates the acquisition of knowledge, skills, values, morals, beliefs and habits. It is adjudged, globally as an important instrument for socio-economic development of human skills, knowledge and attitude (Osim, 2022). Hence, education in Nigeria is an instrument par excellence for affecting national development FRN, 2014.

The Concept of Technical, Vocational Education and Training (TVET) Education in Nigeria

The development of human resources is one of the main factors in achieving sustainable economic and social development. TVET Education is described as the aspect of education which is concerned with the preparation of skilled manpower. It is a form of education, training and retraining which is directed towards developing the learner to become productive in a paid employment or in a self-employment (Marope, et. al., 2015). It can also be seen as that skilled based programme designed for sub professional level of education and based on a specific vocation. NPF (2014) notes that it is a comprehensive term referring to those aspects of the educational process involving in addition to general education, the study of technologies and related sciences and the acquisition of practical skills, attitudes, understanding and knowledge relating to occupations in various sectors of economic and social life. Consequently.

The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) defines TVET as that aspect of education which utilizes scientific knowledge in the acquisition of practical and applied skills in solving technical problems. Technical, Vocational Education and Training (TVET) requires the inculcation of practice and learnt experiences in real life. The National Policy on Education (NPE 2014) considered Technical, Vocational Education and Training (TVET) as an

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integral part of general education in Nigeria that is beyond compulsory education but excluding degree-level programmes, which provides individual with occupational or work-related knowledge and skills. It empowers individual's organization, enterprises and communities and foster employment, decent work and lifelong learning thereby promoting inclusive and sustainable economic growth and competitiveness social equity and environment sustainability.

In other words, TVET is a type of education that is designed to prepare learners for specific careers and trades. This type of education is offered at the post-secondary or tertiary levels of education. They typically include both classroom instructions and practical training education used as a comprehensive term. Marope, Chakroun and Holmes, (2015) define Technical, Vocational Education and Training as that which provides practical skills, knowledge and technology for knowledge based and transition societies to be skillfully employed.

National Policy of Education (2014) highlights the goals of Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) shall be to;

1. Provide trained man power in applied sciences, technology and business, particularly at craft, advance craft and technical levels.
2. Provide the technical knowledge and vocational skills necessary for agricultural, commercial and economic development.
3. Give training and impart the necessary skills to the individuals for economic self-reliance.

It is generally believed that one of the major parameters for measuring a country's economic growth and development and self-reliant is the extent of the technical education it has.

Concept of Management of Technical and Vocational Education and Training Program in Nigeria

Education is seen as the process of coordinating human effort towards the actualization of broad and specific goals of an organization while management is the act of applying the general processes and procedures to achieve the goals set for an organization. Hence, management is the process, which empowers, directs and motivates organizations to set and achieve their objectives by planning, organizing, directing and controlling their human and material resources meaningfully. Nzegbulem and Onyeagbako, (2019) define management as a kind of work a manager performs to enable people work effectively together. Therefore, management and development of Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET), through emerging technologies and innovations simply put is the ability to manage technical and vocational education effectively. For Nwankwo (2014) management in education is no longer the exclusive interest of the "Ivory Tower" experts and specialized research institutes, He notes that it has now become the concern of all training institutions, capacity building agencies, government agencies and schools. Concept of Innovation in Education. Innovation is defined as substantial change in the way of vocational and technical education as practiced in an institution and making it more relevant to the needs of the economy, society and environment (Abraham, 2017). It encourages teachers and students to explore research and use the tools to uncover something new. It brings improvement in to the already stereotyped educational systems as it helps students to use a higher level of thinking in problems solving (Abraham, 2017). Innovation deals with solving a real problem in a fresh and simple way to promote equity and improve learning in an emerging technological and innovating settings.

Historical Perspective of Technical, Vocational Education and Training (TVET) in Nigeria

Technical and vocational education has been in existence before the advent of formal Western education in Nigeria. Attempts were made to develop Nigeria children in various keys such as weaving, sculpturing, blacksmithing, caving, farming, fishing, cattle rearing, hair plaiting, dress-making, leather works, poultry, glass and bead working, catering, dyeing, tinkering and many more. According to Azuoma (2016), traditional education system of the various ethnic groups include; arts and craft of various types have existed as their own expression of vocational training, why traditional agricultural practices had been developed to suit the cultivation of the agricultural species predominantly produced in the different eco geographical areas of the country. The era was emerged by hearing to informed apprenticeship systems. TVET was formalized in the colonial period the Facet TVET in the 1920s, and the number of these institutions grew rapidly in the years leading up to 1960 (Azuoma, 2016). Vocational training was not encouraged in the early part of the colonial era. The origin of vocational and technical education could be traced to the precolonial era when traditional education was practiced. During this era the child was trained in the family trade by direct apprenticeship to either the parents or relations. The conscious planning of the system of technical education in Nigeria dates back to 1946, when it was given a major space in the 10 years plan for development (Nwosu & Micah, 2017). This led to establishment of Yaba Technical Institute in 1947 and several other trade centres in 1952 (Nwosu & Micah, 2017). The Ashby report of 1960 had considerable influence on Nigeria Technical Education and Nigeria Education as a whole by advocating for the introduction of technical subjects in secondary schools

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learning to the acquisition of a Technical School certificate. There have been visible developments in technical education at all levels in Nigeria with the enhancement of computer technology. Technical and vocational education were assumed to be designed for the less privilege and less intellectual ones in the society. Therefore, understanding the effects of technological innovations on students, teachers and schools is critical to developing strategies and techniques to manage and use technology in education. The early schools were built primarily for the purpose of evangelism by the early Christian missionaries, which was characterized by literally type of education tailored towards winning new convert and producing clerks and interpreters (Odionye, Anugom, Nzegebulem & Ojiako, 2015). Before the Yaba College in 1980, the government started to organized some form of vocational training in some departments of government such as lands and survey training school, the Marine training school in 1928 and railway schools in 1931 (Odionye, Anugom, Nzegebulem & Ojiako, 2015). More technical colleges, college of technology, colleges of education (Technical), polytechnics and universities of technology where is publish as a means of ensuring the successful implementation of the then 6 - 3 - 3 - 4 system of education. By 1999, there had been 128 technical colleges, 15 of which were owned by the Federal Government, 101 by the state governments and 12 by private/ religious bodies (Ajayi, 2007). During the same period there 48 polytechnics, 17 of which were owned by the Federal Government, 26 by state governments and 5 by private individuals Ajayi (2007).

Challenges of Technical and Vocational Education and Training TVET Program in Nigeria

Bello and Muhammad (2021) outlined a number of challenges facing technical and vocational education in Nigeria include;

1. Inadequate Funding
2. Negative attitude towards technical and vocational education.
3. Shortage of teaching staff.
4. Lack of continuity in the implementation of policies and practices.
5. Decay in infrastructure in schools.

Curriculum content:

The curricula of vocational and technical education to not provide students with enough technical skills for entrepreneurship but provide them with more in-depth knowledge. To this end, Muoghalu and Ahmad (2023) opined that there is need to address the issue of re - designing vocational and technical programs in Nigeria with the emerging trend in technological innovation to meet our commitments in creating workshops, instructional stimulations, that are relevant to the practice of industrial and commercial activities for viable business engagement. The curriculum content should explicitly provide and state clearly the occupational areas in which vocational skills will be provided.

Poor industrial training:

It is so sad that graduate of vocational and technical education now roam the street is search of White collar jobs because the lack the necessary skills required to be self-reliant or self-employed due to poor training. Technical and Vocational Education students no longer possess the necessary skills as a result of the failure of industrial based supervisors to assist the student in developing the right attitudes in training (Ayonmike, Okwelle & Okeke, 2015). Experience has shown that more of these graduates who are unable to secure paid jobs find it extremely difficult to set up businesses of their own because the lack entrepreneurial skills to do so. Nation is nothing to write home about. Ranging from the poor state of the classrooms to the laboratories are grossly inadequate. Lack of tools and equipment, gross inadequacy of available machines, lack of textbooks and materials are some problems which militated engage vocational and technical education. Hence, it has made the teaching of vocational and technical subjects and courses theoretical than practical. This has left most graduands in these subject areas to be half baked.

Structural Problems:

The structure of vocational and technical education in Nigeria is not balance. Ayonmike, Okwelle and Okeke (2015) identified some of the problems inherent in the structure of vocational and technical education in Nigeria. Non-inclusion of technical subjects in the entry qualification of JAMB and the products of the technical colleges flow into the job market directly because of their limitations in basic science and the structure of not being specific in the learning of technical and teachers at the colleges of education or university. Some Universities do not have such programs or even a department of vocational studies such, the prospective students in the area usually switch to other related discipline. A situation that has

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almost crippled the course.

Irregular power supply:

This has become the order of the day in Nigeria as most of the colleges do not have generating sets in the event of power failure.

Strategies for Ensuring the Management of Technical and Vocational Education program in Nigeria through Emerging Technologies and Innovations

1. Improved funding of technical and vocational education. Government are the various level should as a matter of urgent make adequate fund available for the smooth implementation of technical and vocational education in Nigeria. This would be achieved through increased budgetary provision to the education sub-sector of the Nigeria economy. It is understood that government cannot shoulder it alone, Jeff or other stakeholders in the Education industry such as parents, community, corporate organization philanthropists, should step up their financial commitment to the provision of vocational and technical education.
2. There should be a change in mindset attitude of auto words vocational and technical education in the country. People should stop saying technical and vocational education as a course that is meant for student from Paul background or less intelligent students.
3. Recruitment of qualified manpower: the government at all levels should employ more qualified and skilled teachers to hand technical and vocational subjects' courses in schools. Also, those other teachers who love the requirement power to carry on should be adequately trained and motivated. This case achieved by sponsorship teachers to workshop, seminars, conferences and training programmes to position damn in the market space.
4. Improved public awareness. This will go a long way to remedy some of the challenges associated with technical and vocational education in Nigeria. Members of the public should give more recognition two graduates of technical education in order to boost the morale of undergraduates in polytechnics and colleges of education technical. This would help parents to push their wards to the department of vocational and technical education.
5. There should be continuity in policies and programs of vocational and technical education. This is very important as somebody causes the political level and not offered at the post graduate level.
6. This should be innovations, regular accreditation and of courses and facilities a technical application on colleges. Most of the laboratories, equipment and classrooms are totally decapitated hence, government should give it a face lift to encourage the student and teachers to study in a conducive atmosphere or scenery environment.
7. Improved curricula contents. The curricula vocational and technical education should be redesigned to provide the required vocational and technical education across the country as this will make the graduates of technical college acquire the necessary jobs skills for the transformation of Nigeria educational system.
8. Effective industrial training should be more effective and encompassing. Also, the inclusion entrepreneurial skills to compliment the vocational technical skills acquired by the students.
9. They should be provision of world-class facilities in our vocational technical college to enable graduates compete favorably with our counterparts across the globe.
10. Programme restructuring, we go a long way in helping the students achieve educational aim. This can be done harmonization a vocational course in the polytechnics, colleges of education technical and universities.
11. There should be regular power supply in our institutions of higher learning to enable teachers and lecturers conduct practical and learn in a conducive environment.

Conclusion

The foregoing discussion has informed us about the place of technical and vocational education in Nigeria. Provision of qualitative technical and vocational education is necessary for technical education to achieve its aim. This can be achieved through improved funding of technical education, change in parental attitude toward vocational education to boost students moral, recruit qualified manpower, improved public esteem, continuity in policies and programmes, renovation of decayed facilities, improved curricular content, effective industrial training, programme restricting and regular provision of power supply.

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Effect of Collaborative Improvisation on Creative-Thinking Fluency in Basic Science among Upper Basic Students in Makurdi, Benue State

Ayua, Geoffrey Aondolumun¹

Email: ayuageoffrey@gmail.com

Ogah, Aladi Helen¹

Email: Aladihelen1961@gmail.com

Ikyernum, Gabriel Sesugh²

Email: sesughgabriel05@gmail.com

Awen, David Amenger³

amengerawen@yahoo.com

¹Department of Science & Mathematics Education, Benue State University, Makurdi, Nigeria

²Department of Agricultural Technology, School of Sciences, Federal Polytechnic, Ile-Oluji/Okeigbo, Ondo State, Nigeria.

³Department of Science Education, Joseph Sawuan Takar University, Makurdi, Nigeria

Abstract

Effect of Collaborative Improvisation on Creative-Thinking Fluency in Basic Science Among Upper Basic Students in Makurdi, Benue State was studied using pre-test post-test quasi-experimental-control group research design. The study was guided by two research questions and corresponding hypotheses. The study's population was made up of 1337 (680 male and 657 female) Upper Basic II government secondary school students in Makurdi metropolis. A multistage sample of 52 (22 male & 30 female) students in two intact classes from two schools was drawn. Torrance Test of Creative Thinking with a reliability coefficient of 0.82 determined by a test-retest method with Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used for data collection. Data were analysed using mean and two-way ANCOVA. Findings showed no significant difference in creative-thinking fluency among mixed ability students taught Basic Science using Collaborative Improvisation approach and those taught using Teacher Improvisation, $F_{(2, 45)} = 1.001$; $p = .375 > .05$. Although; there existed a significant difference in creative-thinking fluency in favour of those taught using Collaborative Improvisation, $F_{(1, 45)} = 22.534$; $p = .000 < .05$, no significant difference existed in the students' creative-thinking fluency based on gender, $F_{(2, 45)} = 1.291$; $p = .285 > .05$. Therefore, it was concluded that, enhancing creative-thinking fluency among students with different abilities can be achieved without any gender discrepancy by actively involving learners in the improvisation of instructional materials. Thus, Collaboration Improvisation Approach was recommended for teaching Basic Science in basic schools.

Keywords: Collaborative Improvisation (CI), Teacher Improvisation (TI), Creative-Thinking-Fluency, Mixed Ability and Gender

Introduction

In the midst of the fast-paced and ever-changing landscape of the current age, the imperative for individuals to harness their creative potential has never been more pronounced. Our world is marked by unprecedented technological advancements, global challenges, and dynamic economic shifts. In this context, creativity emerges as a driving force that not only empowers individuals to adapt and thrive but also propels societies forward. (Balci et al., 2023; Nazhifah et al., 2023). The ability to think innovatively, solve complex problems, and envision novel solutions is no longer a luxury but a necessity. Individuals are therefore confronted with a pressing need to cultivate and employ their creative potential in meeting current challenges where creativity has become synonymous with resilience, progress, and success.

In response to this pressing need, science education finds itself at a crucial juncture, ready to evolve and respond to the rapidly emerging challenges of our world. As breakthroughs in technology, shifts in the environment, and intricate societal issues redefine the boundaries of scientific exploration, fostering creativity within science education takes on heightened significance (Trisnayanti et al., 2020; Oliveira et al., 2021). To empower the upcoming generation with the requisite skills to

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confront these challenges effectively, science education must wholeheartedly embrace and prioritize creativity as an essential component (Smare & Elfatih, 2023). This approach not only enables students to grasp the complexities of scientific principles but also equips them to employ their creative prowess in shaping a sustainable, innovative, and adaptable future.

Creativity is our capacity to find new solutions to the problems we encounter by using our existing knowledge. Creativity is being able to establish new correlations between concepts, and to present new experiences and ideas (products) around this axis of thought (Apaydin, 2023). In our age, where information is developing and changing very rapidly, societies need individuals who are proactive, thinking creative, problem-solving, and constantly improving themselves in order to adapt to this change and development (Smare & Elfatih 2023; Apaydin, 2023). Hence, it becomes evident that to secure sustainable development, there is a need for ongoing enhancement of the creative potential among individuals who shape society. This necessitates the implementation of innovative strategies that foster essential creativity skills, notably creative thinking.

Creative thinking refers to thinking that is trained by reviving imagination, paying attention to intuition, and revealing new things that need to be explored (Nazhifah et al., 2023; Aldossari, 2021). According to Ayua et al. (2023) Creative thinking is one's cognitive process to generate effective ideas in solving problems under certain aims and conditions. It is a positive action in stimulating brain function that can create a proper learning style. In whichever way one views creative thinking, it is generally considered as a process of thinking based on what has been or formed from the knowledge relationship with reality, which results in creating something new.

In the realm of science education, particularly at the basic education level, the cultivation of creative thinking skills hinges on a crucial factor: hands-on learning experiences facilitated by the use of teaching materials. Creative thinking in science goes beyond rote memorization of facts; it thrives when students are actively engaged in exploring, experimenting, and problem-solving (Trisnayanti et al., 2020; Tanjung et al., 2023). By providing students with hands-on activities and tangible teaching materials, educators create a dynamic learning environment that encourages curiosity, critical thinking, and innovation. These activities not only enable students to apply theoretical knowledge in practical contexts but also foster a deeper understanding of scientific concepts (Handayani et al., 2022). Moreover, they empower learners to ask questions, make connections, and develop a holistic appreciation for the scientific method, ultimately equipping them with the creative thinking skills necessary for both academic success and real-world problem-solving. However, research has consistently highlighted the scarcity of instructional materials in Nigerian basic schools (National Teachers' Institute - NTI as cited in Ikyernum et al., 2022). Often, the available materials are insufficient or outdated. This shortage poses a considerable challenge to teachers who aim to nurture creative thinking among their students. In this context, improvisation emerges as an essential strategy for Basic Science teachers, enabling them to adapt and create effective learning experiences using readily available materials.

Improvisation refers to selection or provision for something not readily available. It is the process by which educational materials can be designed and developed using locally available materials to meet specific instructional needs (Ayua et al., 2022; Ikyernum et al., 2022). Improvisation according to Ayua (2021) could be by substitution, modification and construction either solely by the teacher (Teacher Improvisation) or by the collaborative efforts of the teacher and learners (Collaborative Improvisation).

Teacher Improvisation (TI) refers to teaching aid(s) made by the teacher alone and brought to the classroom for Basic Science teaching. TI is an improvisation approach that is teacher-based because learners are not involved in the process of producing the improvised instructional material(s) (Ikyernum et al., 2022). Collaborative Improvisation (CI) on the other hand refers to teaching aids that are produced by the combined efforts of the teacher and the learners for the purpose of Basic Science teaching and learning (Ikyernum et al., 2022). This approach emphasizes the active involvement of both the teacher and the students in creating these materials. Through the implementation of a collaborative improvisation approach, students not only acquire vital subject knowledge but are also prompted to exercise their creative thinking skills well before formal lessons commence. This approach cultivates a highly engaging and interactive learning atmosphere, which is a sine-qua-none for engendering creative thinking skills in Basic Science learners. This study will centre its attention on these two improvisation techniques with the objective of evaluating their influence on creative-thinking fluency among upper Basic Science learners of diverse abilities.

Creative thinking plays a pivotal role in the improvisation of instructional materials, making them a necessity in the educational realm. When teachers and learners possess the ability to think creatively, they can adapt and transform existing materials, or even develop entirely new resources (Ikyernum et al., 2022). This flexibility not only ensures that the teaching materials align with the specific learning objectives and student demographics but also makes the learning experience more engaging and effective. Harnessing improvisation in the teaching and learning process has been recognized as a pathway to foster and enhance creative thinking in learners (Ayua et al., 2023). By nurturing creative thinking through improvisation,

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students not only acquire valuable competencies to thrive in society but also contribute to economic growth and progress in this technology-driven 21st-century economy. As a result, promoting creative thinking and improvisation in educational settings becomes essential for preparing learners to succeed in the ever-evolving world and its demands. Creative thinking comprises five sub domains of fluency, originality, elaboration, resistance to premature closure and abstractness of titles (Teheмба et al., 2023). However, this paper focuses on creative-thinking fluency.

Creative-thinking fluency is the ability to generate many ideas that come from one's mind quickly in response to open-ended questions or refers to a person's thinking process (Trisnayanti et al., 2020; Ayua et al., 2023). In creative- thinking fluency, the emphasis is on quantity, not quality (Handayani et al., 2022;). According to Torrance, creative-thinking fluency is the ability to generate several ideas or produce many answers. Fluency in creative thinking is of paramount importance in nurturing creativity. It signifies the ability to generate a multitude of novel ideas, solutions, or perspectives in a given context. Creative thinking fluency not only fosters innovation but also enhances problem-solving skills and encourages adaptability (Haruna, 2016). When individuals can effortlessly produce diverse and imaginative ideas, they are better equipped to tackle complex challenges, explore unconventional possibilities, and contribute meaningfully to their respective fields. Empirically, Handayani et al., (2022) in their study “Students’ creative thinking skills in Biology learning: Fluency, Flexibility, Originality, and Elaboration” established that students’ creative-thinking fluency was low. However, Balci et al., (2023) and Chua et al., (2020) in their respective studies on creative thinking established that learners gained higher creative thinking fluency as a result of creativity enhancement programs. Though the studies assessed the creative-thinking fluency of learners, they however were not concerned with creative-thinking fluency as an aspect of creative thinking in relation to improvisation across mixed ability learners as proposed by this study.

Mixed ability in this research refers to the different educational performance levels of students in Basic Science, which can be categorized as high, average, or low based on their past academic scores. Maikano (as cited in Ikyernum, et al., 2022) suggests that ability grouping is determined by educators' assessments of students' abilities. When assigning students to different tracks, their prior test scores or performance measures from previous grades or schools are considered to determine their ability levels. Students’ ability levels for the study were guided by Benue State Ministry of Education – BSME (2021) and Benue State Examinations Board – BSEB (2019) grading system for basic schools. Based on the grading system, High Ability Level (A = 75-100% and B = 65-74%), Average Ability Level (C = 55-64% and D = 45-54%) and Low Ability Level (E = 40-44% and F = 0-39%). By using this grading system, the researchers were able to distinguish and group students based on their academic ability levels in Basic Science. Empirically, Ikyernum et al., (2022) in their study “Effect of teacher-learner improvised material on creative thinking among mixed ability upper Basic Science students in Makurdi metropolis” established that the level of creative thinking among mixed ability students was significantly enhanced without gender disparity as a result of learners’ active involvement in the improvisation of instructional materials. However, Setiawan and Fitriani (2023) in their study “Analysis of mathematical creative thinking ability on junior high school students in Bandung” reported low creative thinking fluency in learners of varied abilities. These studies however were not concerned with creative-thinking fluency in relation to improvisation and did not tell whether a difference existed in creative-thinking fluency based on gender as a result of learners’ involvement in improvisation of instructional materials.

Gender differences encompass the characteristics associated with being male or female, man or woman, boy or girl. Research by Danjuma (as cited in Ayua, 2021) indicates that these gender disparities have a worldwide impact, particularly in Africa, by hindering the equal participation of boys and girls in Science Education. Consequently, these gender-specific factors influence the teaching, learning, and creative thinking of students in Basic Science. Empirically, [Ulger and Morsunbul \(2017\)](#); [Zhang et al., \(2020\)](#), in their respective studies on differences in creative thinking found that a significant difference existed in creative thinking abilities between males and females in favour of females. However, Ayua and Agbidye (2020); He and Wong (2021); Ikyernum, et al., (2022) and Ayua et al., (2023) found no significant difference between boys and girls in the level of entrepreneurial creativity, divergent thinking and problem-solving skills, creative thinking, and creative-thinking fluency respectively. However, none of the studies were concerned with creative-thinking fluency as an aspect of creative thinking in relation to improvisation. That is why it was important to investigate the impact of collaborative improvisation on upper Basic science students’ creative-thinking fluency.

Since the dawn of the 21st century, the world has witnessed remarkable progress in scientific and knowledge domains, driven by factors like the knowledge revolution and rapid technological advancements. Simultaneously, the contemporary era necessitates a workforce equipped with robust creativity skills to navigate the ever-evolving global landscape. These developments have exerted a profound influence on the educational system and its components. To remain in sync with these dynamic shifts, educational decision-makers must realign their strategies accordingly. In this context, upper Basic Science

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students must cultivate creative-thinking abilities to excel in their academic and professional pursuits. Improvisation stands out as a promising method for nurturing creativity in learners, given its capacity to stimulate spontaneous thinking, imaginative problem-solving, adaptability, and unconventional approaches. However, there is a need to thoroughly explore the extent to which improvisation techniques can effectively enhance the creative-thinking fluency among upper Basic Science students. Therefore, this study investigated the effect of collaborative improvisation on creative-thinking fluency in Basic Science among upper Basic Science students in Makurdi, Benue State.

Objective of the Study

The objectives of the study were:

- To determine the mean creative-thinking fluency scores among students taught Basic Science using Collaborative Improvisation and those exposed to Teacher Improvisation in Makurdi, Benue State.
- To find out the mean creative-thinking fluency scores among mixed ability male and female students taught Basic Science using Collaborative Improvisation in Makurdi, Benue State.

Research Questions

11. What is the mean difference in creative-thinking fluency scores among mixed ability students taught Basic Science using Collaborative Improvisation and those taught using Teacher Improvisation?
12. What is the mean difference in creative-thinking fluency scores among mixed ability male and female students taught Basic Science using Collaborative Improvisation?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in creative-thinking fluency scores among mixed ability students taught Basic Science using Collaborative Improvisation and those taught using Teacher Improvisation.
2. There is no significant difference in creative-thinking fluency scores among mixed ability male and female students taught Basic Science using Collaborative Improvisation.

Methodology

A pre-test post-test quasi-experimental-control group design was used for this study. After pre-test administration, the experimental group of an intact class of 1:24 was taught concept of work, energy and power with 5 lesson plans using demonstration method blended with collaborative improvised materials (wooden toy car and wooden electric fan) constructed through active involvement of learners together with the teacher using procedures outlined in the lesson plans; while the control group was taught the same concept using same method blended with teacher improvised materials. This treatment lasted for five weeks. Thereafter, the students in both groups were given post-test. Students mixed ability were based on previous term's performance grades (high = A/B; average = C/D; low = E/F). A multistage sample of 52 (22 male and 30 female) Upper-Basic II students in two schools drawn from the population of 1337 (680 males and 657 females) Upper Basic II students in all the 21 secondary schools (Teaching Service Board Makurdi, 2021) was used for the study. Torrance Test of Creative Thinking (TTCT-Figural B) was used for data collection. Section "A" collected students' biodata; while section 'B' had three activities each lasting for 10 minutes with the opportunity for multiple responses of ideas, to test students' creative-thinking fluency in Basic Science. TTCT-Figural B was validated and trial-tested with a reliability coefficient of 0.82 determined by a test-retest method with Pearson Product Moment Correlation. Extraneous variables like group initial difference, group interaction effect and priming were controlled by homogeneity test, distant locations and impromptu tests respectively. Both pre-test and post-test were administered under standard examination conditions. The research questions were answered using mean and hypotheses were tested at 0.05 α -level using a two-way Analysis of covariance due to normality of the distribution, homogeneity of variance, randomness of selection, measurement based on interval scale and independence of samples.

Results

Research Question 1:

What is the mean difference in creative-thinking fluency scores among mixed ability students taught Basic Science using Collaborative Improvisation and those taught using Teacher Improvisation?

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Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Creative-Thinking Fluency Scores of Students Taught using Collaborative Improvisation and Teacher Improvisation.

Ability Level	N	Group	Pre-TTCT		Post-TTCT		Mean Gain	Mean Gain difference
			\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD		
High	12	TI	7.08	1.084	7.83	1.193	0.75	1.05
	10	CI	7.10	1.270	8.90	0.316	1.80	
Average	8	TI	7.13	1.126	8.13	0.991	1	0.43
	7	CI	7.43	1.397	8.86	0.378	1.43	
Low	8	TI	7.00	1.309	7.50	1.069	0.50	1.79
	7	CI	6.57	0.767	8.86	0.378	2.29	
Cluster		TI	7.07		7.82		0.75	1.09
		CI	7.04		8.88		1.84	

Table 1 shows homogeneity in the pre-test mean scores among mixed ability between experimental and control group with cluster means of 7.04 and 7.07. The table also shows that all the creative-thinking fluency mean scores among mixed ability in the experimental group were higher than those in the control group with cluster mean gain difference of 1.09

Research Question 2

What is the mean difference in creative-thinking fluency scores among male and female mixed ability students taught Basic Science using Collaborative Improvisation?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Creative-Thinking Fluency Scores of Male and Female Students Taught Using Collaborative Improvisation (CI)

Ability Level	Gender	N	Pre-TTCT		Post-TTCT		Mean Gain	Mean Gain Difference
			\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD		
High	Male	7	7.09	1.375	8.45	1.035	1.36	0.27
	Female	3	7.09	1.044	8.18	1.079	1.09	
Average	Male	2	7.14	1.215	8.14	1.069	1.00	0.83
	Female	5	7.38	1.302	8.75	0.463	1.37	
Low	Male	2	7.25	1.258	7.75	1.258	0.5	1.13
	Female	5	6.64	1.027	8.27	1.009	1.63	
Cluster	Male		7.14		8.18		1.04	0.33
	Female		7.00		8.37		1.37	

Table 2 shows homogeneity in the pre-test mean scores between male and female in the experimental group with cluster means of 7.14 and 7.00. Likewise, the table also shows that the creative-thinking fluency mean scores in the post-test was higher than those in the pre-test in both male and female with cluster mean gains of 1.04 and 1.37 respectively

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in creative-thinking fluency scores among mixed ability students taught Basic Science using Collaborative Improvisation and those taught using Teacher Improvisation.

Table 3: Summary of Two-way ANCOVA Results of Creative-Thinking Fluency Test Scores of Students Based on Improvisation Technique

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	20.899 ^a	6	3.483	5.562	.000	.426
Intercept	53.237	1	53.237	85.018	.000	.654
Pre_TTCT	4.978	1	4.978	7.949	.007	.150
Improvisation-Technique	14.110	1	14.110	22.534	.000	.334
Ability_Level	.232	2	.116	.186	.831	.008

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Improvisation_Technique *	1.254	2	.627	1.001	.375	.043
Ability_Level						
Error	28.178	45	.626			
Total	3638.000	52				
Corrected Total	49.077	51				

a. R Squared = .426 (Adjusted R Squared = .349)

Table 3 shows no significant difference in the creative-thinking fluency scores among mixed ability students taught Basic Science using CI and those taught using TI, $F_{(2, 45)} = 1.001$; $p = .375 > .05$. The null hypothesis was therefore not rejected. However, the result also showed that students' creative-thinking fluency scores in the experimental group was better than those in the control group, $F_{(1, 45)} = 22.534$; $p = .000 < .05$. This implies that, although Collaborative Improvisation (CI) enhances creative-thinking fluency, it is not dependent on students' academic abilities

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in creative-thinking fluency scores among mixed ability male and female students taught Basic Science using Collaborative Improvisation

Table 4. Summary of Two-way ANCOVA Results of Creative-Thinking Fluency Scores of Male and Female Students Taught Using Collaborative Improvisation

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	7.976 ^a	6	1.329	1.455	.215	.163
Intercept	51.923	1	51.923	56.848	.000	.558
Pre_TTCT	4.551	1	4.551	4.983	.031	.100
Gender	1.156	1	1.156	1.266	.266	.027
Ability_Level	.867	2	.434	.475	.625	.021
Gender * Ability_Level	2.358	2	1.179	1.291	.285	.054
Error	41.101	45	.913			
Total	3638.000	52				
Corrected Total	49.077	51				

a. R Squared = .163 (Adjusted R Squared = .051)

Table 4 showed no significant difference in the creative-thinking fluency scores between male and female mixed ability students taught Basic Science using Collaborative Improvisation, $F_{(2, 45)} = 1.291$; $p = .285 > .05$. The null hypothesis was therefore not rejected. This implies that, Collaborative Improvisation is gender unbiased; hence it enhanced creative-thinking fluency in both male and female mixed ability Basic Science students

Discussion of Findings

In regards to creative-thinking fluency based on involving them in improvising instructional materials, it was found that significant difference existed in creative- thinking fluency between students in the control and experimental groups in favour of those in the experimental group. However, among the ability levels there existed no significant difference in creative-thinking fluency. Following field experience, the finding of this study is not odd because during the construction process, students were given ample opportunity to fully express their open-mindedness towards generation of as many ideas that they can and as quick as possible which thus sharpened their overall thinking process. This finding is similar with those of Balci et al., (2023) and Chua et al., (2020) who found that there was a significant increase in creative-thinking fluency after students were exposed to creative thinking enhancement programs. However, the finding does not only contrast with, but is a potential solution to that of Handayani et al. (2022) who found that leaners' creative thinking fluency was low. The indifference among mixed ability students in creative-thinking fluency as found out, is similar to the finding of Ikyernum et al (2022) of no significant difference in creative thinking among varied ability students as they were actively involved in improvisation of instructional materials. However, the finding does not only differ with, but is also a potential solution to the finding of Setiawan and Fitriani (2023) who found low creative thinking fluency in learners of varied ability.

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Concerning students' creative-thinking fluency based on gender, it was discovered that no significant difference existed in creative-thinking fluency between male and female mixed ability students taught Basic Science using Collaborative Improvisation. Thus, involving students in the improvisation of instructional materials enhances their creative thinking fluency without difference in gender. This finding is similar to those of Ayua and Agbidye (2020); He and Wong (2021); Ikyernum et al., (2022) and Terhemba et al., (2023) who found no significant difference between boys and girls in the level of entrepreneurial creativity, divergent thinking and problem-solving skills, creative thinking, and creative-thinking fluency respectively. This finding however does not only differ, but also is solution to Ulger and Morsunbul (2017), Zhang et al., (2020) who found out that a significant difference existed between females and males upon creative thinking in favour of females.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it was concluded that: Creative-thinking fluency among mixed ability students can be enhanced without gender discrepancy if learners are actively involved in the improvisation of instructional materials.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made to effectively implement this approach:

2. Collaborative Improvisation approach should be adopted in teaching Basic Science.
3. School administrators should encourage researchers to organize workshops on the use of Collaborative Improvisation.
4. Ministries of Education and teacher training institutions in Nigeria should ensure in-service training and retraining of teachers on Collaborative Improvisation.
5. School proprietors, heads and parents' teachers' association should materially/financially support Collaborative Improvisation in Basic Science.

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Effect of Instructional Conversation Strategy on Achievement in Basic Science and Technology among Secondary School Students in Mkpat Enin Local Government

Robson, Blessing Okon¹

Email: blezokonrobson@gmail.com

Tel: 07039287469

Babayemi, John Olakunle¹

Email: babayemioluwole@gmail.com

Tel: 08038421726

Umanah, Felicia Ime¹

Email: feliciaumanah@aksu.edu.ng

¹Tel: 07088885603

Department of Science Education, Faculty of Education, Akwa Ibom State University, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Abstract

The study determined effect of instructional conversation strategy on achievement in basic science and technology among secondary school students in Mkpat Enin Local Government. Quasi-experimental research design, specifically pre-test, post-test control group design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised of 1645 (809 males and 836 female) Junior Secondary School class three (JS III) Public Secondary School students during the 2022/2023 academic session from all the sixteen (16) public secondary schools in Mkpat Enin Local Government. A total of 168 (63 male and 105 female) students using an intact class were used as sample for the study. Two research questions and corresponding hypotheses guided the study. The instrument validated and used was Basic Science and Technology Achievement Test, BSTSAT and Kuder Richardson KR-20 estimate was used to determine the reliability index which yielded 0.75. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics to answer the research questions and ANCOVA to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The results showed that instructional strategies had a significant main effect on students' posttest achievement scores [$F_{(1,168)} = 40.622$; $p < .05$], there was no significant influence of gender on students' academic achievement [$F_{(1,168)} = .296$; $p > .05$]. The study concluded that instructional conversation strategy improved students' academic achievement. It was recommended among others that in order to improve male and female students' achievement in Basic Science and Technology, instructional conversations teaching strategy should be adopted by the teacher in secondary schools.

Keywords: Instructional Conversations, Gender, Academic Achievement, Basic Science and Technology

Introduction

The teaching and learning of science and technology in Nigeria starts from acquiring knowledge, skills and attitude in Basic Science and Technology in Primary and Secondary schools. Therefore, the way Basic Science and Technology is taught in schools determines to a large extent, the achievement of curricular objectives for the target learners and overall scientific and technological attainments of the nation at large. Babayemi, Akpan and Emah (2018) observed that students have difficulty in learning scientific concepts. The difficulty encountered in the learning of Basic Science and Technology may be ascribed to how the teaching of the subject is done by the subject teachers. Babayemi *et al.*, (2018) identified science teachers as the key factors in students' learning. These researchers submitted that teachers must be equipped with appropriate strategies to proffer solution to the problem of any perceived difficult concepts. This seems to reduce the difficulty encountered during learning.

Federal Ministry of Education [FME] (2013) remarked that the society is faced with large number of teachers that are unable to manage the classroom of the 21st century and concluded that this state is counterproductive, antithetical to growth and development. The world outside the classroom keeps changing because of the innovations in science and technology and it is necessary for the classroom environment to undergo corresponding change so as to be able to meet the needs and aspirations of the learners. Many learners tend to become more sophisticated and highly proficient in the use of ICT and other media than their teachers. Teachers therefore need to seriously update their skills and pedagogies so as to be able to face the present

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challenges in the classroom. What is worrisome about these challenges common in research reports is the low academic achievement in schools (Babalola, 2018).

Profile of Basic Science (Basic Science and Technology) results as reported by Babayemi and Akinsola (2014) was not consistent over the years. If this abysmal failure in Basic Science and Technology follows the same trends subsequently, the realization of national objectives in scientific and technological developments would definitely be in jeopardy. The way science teaching and learning is done in schools need to be revisited. Basic Science and Technology teachers are expected to be flexible in the use of pedagogy so as to be able to meet the needs of diverse learners in science classrooms. In line with this, Afuwape and Olugbuyi (2019) observed poor academic performance of students in Basic science and Technology and recommended the use of activity package-based instruction to eradicate the menace.

There are innovations in methodology. Murugesan (2019) identified innovative teaching strategies that could be adopted for students' learning. These are: blended learning, embodied learning, learning by doing science, computational thinking, crossover learning, learning through argumentation, word wall and instructional conversations among others. Teaching pedagogy is a basic element of an effective teaching. This means that the right choice of pedagogy is very important for the teaching and learning to be effective. Teachers should see the need to consider what pedagogy will be appropriate for a particular curricular content and the particular category of learners. Hence, the need to conduct further research on strategies that seem to promote students' learning of science in a motivated environment such as instructional conversations and word wall teaching strategies. Girenton and Zucker (2013) viewed instructional conversations as planned discussions with small groups of children where teachers improve students' collaborative reasoning by using challenging questions which necessitate students to use complex language to relay their experiences, knowledge and opinions. Lending credence to this, Babayemi and Utibe (2017) pointed out that in every day-to-day activity (including class activities), communication is necessary and without an effective communication, the essence of discussion and the active purpose of a dialogue are forfeited. Ouboumerrad (2016) laying great emphasis on inter-personal conversation recommended and stressed that meaningful conversations should become essential activities in the classroom.

Ordinarily, a good instructional conversation might appear as "simply and excellent discussion conducted by a teacher and a group of students". Most people have a reasonably intuitive sense of what such a discussion might be like. It is, first, interesting and engaging. It is about an idea or a concept that has meaning and relevance for students. It has focus that, while it might shift as the discussion evolves, remains discernible throughout. There is a high level of participation, without undue domination by any individual, particularly the teacher. Students engage in extended discussions-with the teacher and among themselves. Gender issue in educational and social research remains the concern of researchers. Hence, there is the need to consider gender germane to this research. In this study, gender is categorised as either male or female learners. Gender has attracted the attention of researchers and has different research views and reports especially with reference to academic achievement. Calsmith (2010) explained that, the influence of gender and differences in academic achievement is a complex task, thus many studies appear to be contradictory. A tremendous amount of work has been done in an attempt to find out potential causes of differences between girls' and boys' academic performance in science and this has clearly demonstrated that male students are superior to their female counterparts in qualitative courses. Maccoby (2013) for example, pointed out that girls are conforming, suggestible, dependent on the opinions of others. The traits in turn have been adduced to dependency, inability to complete a set of tasks. Maccoby then suggests that, these same traits in females might also account for their superior performance on tests involving analytic thinking and spatial abilities.

Zhang, Zhao and Kong (2019) notes that female students are lower in Mathematics and spatial tasks and on specific abilities related to problem solving. Giofre, Allen, Caviola and Toffalini (2022) contended that there are gender differences in intellectual functioning which accounted for the differences in performance. Ayayo (2017) attributed the differences in performance between boys and girls to the school, general intelligence of girls higher than that of boys but the position gradually reversed with the findings. Therefore, this study determined effect of instructional conversation strategy on achievement in Basic Science and Technology among secondary school students in Mkpat Enin Local Government.

Objectives of The Study

The study aimed generally to determine effect of instructional conversation strategy on achievement in Basic Science and Technology among secondary school students in Mkpat Enin Local Government. Specifically, the study:

1. Determine academic achievement of students taught Basic Science and Technology using instructional conversation and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Mkpat Enin Local Government Area.

Effect of Instructional Conversation ... (Robson, et. al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10681420>

2. Determine academic achievement of male and female students taught Basic Science and Technology using instructional conversation in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided study:

1. What is the mean academic achievement scores of students taught Basic Science and Technology using instructional conversation and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area?
2. What is the mean academic achievement scores of male and female students taught Basic Science and Technology using instructional conversation in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha level.

1. There is no significant difference between the mean academic achievement scores of students taught Basic Science and Technology using instructional conversation and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean academic achievement scores of male and female students taught Basic Science and Technology using instructional conversation in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area.

Methodology

Quasi-experimental research design, specifically pre-test, post-test control group design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised of 1645 (809 male and 836 female) Junior Secondary School class three (JS III) Public Secondary School students during the 2022/2023 academic session from all the sixteen (16) public secondary schools in Mkpato Enin Local Government. A total of 168 (63 male and 105 female) students using an intact class were used as sample for the study. Three instruments were used and validated by the researcher to collect data for the study. The instruments are: Basic Science and Technology Achievement Test (BSTSAT), Teachers' Instructional Guide for Instructional Conversations Teaching Strategy (TIGICTS) and Teachers' Instructional Guide for Group Taught without Instructional Conversations Teaching Strategy (TIGGTICTS). Basic Science and Technology Students' Achievement Test, BSTSAT was designed by the researcher. The test was divided into two sections: A and B. Section A covered the personal data of the participants which are gender and name of school; Section B contained twenty (20) multiple choice items with five options (A-E) from which participants selected the correct answer. Each correct response attracted one mark while an incorrect response was awarded zero.

Teachers' instructional guide for instructional conversations teaching strategy (TIGICTS) was also developed by the researcher. It contains the lessons for the four weeks of treatment. The general features of this guide were: subject, class, instructional strategy, topic, sub-topic, duration, initial previous knowledge, instructional objectives, reference book, Introduction, presentation and evaluation. The specific features of this guide were: small group activity, individual activity. Researcher also developed Teachers' Instructional Guide for Group Taught without Instructional Conversations Teaching Strategy (TIGGTICTS). It contains lessons for four weeks of the treatment. The general information on the guide was: subject, class, topic, sub-topic, duration, instructional objectives, previous knowledge, instructional aids and reference book. The specific features of the guide were teachers' activities which are: daily reviews, assessment of pupils previous works, brief introduction, teacher presenting learning tasks in the usual traditional way, evaluation and assignment.

The initial draft of twenty-five multiple choice items of Basic Science and Technology Achievement Test (BSTAT) were given to experts for peer review and two lecturers in the Department of Science Education, Faculty of Education, Akwa Ibom State University, Akwa Ibom State who were experts in the field of Science Education. This was done to ascertain the face and internal consistency of the instruments. Twenty (20) items out of 25 for BSTAT were recommended. BSTAT was later trial-tested on 30 students in a secondary school that was not selected for the main study. The data collected were analysed using Kuder Richardson KR-20 estimate which yielded the reliability coefficients of 0.75. In each of the schools, the researcher obtained permission from the school authority and students for the administrations of the instruments. The treatments were done using the instructional guides. Pre-test and Post-test administered before and after the treatment. The data were collated for data analysis. Data collected were analyzed using mean and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of the posttest achievement scores of students by treatment and gender with the respective pretest scores used as covariates.

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Results

Research Question 1

What is the mean academic achievement scores of students taught Basic Science and Technology using instructional conversation and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area?

Table 1: Estimated adjusted Means of Post-Achievement Scores by Instructional Strategies

Instructional Strategies	Adjusted Mean	Std. Error
Students taught with Instructional Conversations Teaching Strategy	16.59	.251
Students taught with lecture teaching method	13.59	.397

Table 1 revealed that students in the instructional conversations teaching strategy group had the highest adjusted posttest mean achievement scores ($\bar{x} = 16.59$) while students taught with lecture teaching method had the least adjusted mean achievement score ($\bar{x} = 13.59$). The difference was high.

Fig. 1: Chart Showing Achievement According to Instructional Strategies

Research Question

What is the mean academic achievement scores of male and female students taught Basic Science and Technology using instructional conversation in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area?

Table 2: Estimated Marginal Means of Post-achievement by Gender

Gender	Adjusted Mean	Std. Error
Male	14.97	.336
Female	15.22	.329

Table 2 revealed that female students had higher post achievement mean score ($\bar{x} = 15.22$) while the male students had lower post achievement mean score ($\bar{x} = 14.97$). It shows that the female achievement score was different from their female counterpart. This influence on their mean scores was small. Both male and female Basic Science and Technology students had close mean academic achievement. This implies that there was difference in the mean academic achievement scores of male and female students taught Basic Science and Technology using instructional conversation in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area.

Hypotheses 1

There is no significant difference between the mean academic achievement scores of students taught Basic Science and Technology using instructional conversation and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area.

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Table 3: Posttest Achievement Scores of Students by Instructional Strategies

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	584.880	12	48.740	10.231	.000	.442
Intercept	3600.204	1	3600.204	755.732	.000	.830
Pre-Achievement	8.659	1	8.659	1.818	.180	.012
Gender	1.409	1	1.409	.296	.587	.002
Verbal Ability	95.011	2	47.505	9.972	.000	.114
Instructional strategies	193.518	1	193.518	40.622	.000	.208
Gender x Verbal Ability	3.961	2	1.981	.416	.661	.005
Gender x instructional strategies	.799	1	.799	.168	.683	.001
Verbal Ability x instructional strategies	3.116	2	1.558	.327	.722	.004
Gender x Verbal Ability x instructional strategies	1.258	2	.629	.132	.876	.002
Error	738.399	155	4.764			
Total	42027.000	168				
Corrected Total	1323.280	167				

a. R Squared = .442 (Adjusted R Squared = .399)

Table 3 reveals that instructional strategies had a significant main effect on students' posttest achievement scores [$F_{(1,168)} = 40.622$; $p < .05$; partial eta squared = .208]. The effect size of 20.8% was fair. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected. This means that There is significant difference between the mean academic achievement scores of students taught Basic Science and Technology using instructional conversation and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between the mean academic achievement scores of male and female students taught Basic Science and Technology using instructional conversation in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area.

Table 3 reveals that there is no significant influence of gender on students' academic achievement [$F_{(1,168)} = .296$; $p > .05$; partial eta squared = .002]. Hypothesis 2 was therefore accepted. This implies that there was no significant difference between the mean academic achievement scores of male and female students taught Basic Science and Technology using instructional conversation in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area.

Discussion of Findings

The result obtained revealed that instructional strategies had a significant effect on students' achievement in Basic Science and Technology. This means that there was a significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students exposed to instructional conversations teaching strategy and those taught with lecture teaching method. Students in the instructional conversations teaching strategy group had the highest adjusted post-test mean achievement scores while students taught with lecture teaching method had the least adjusted mean achievement score. The results obtained here could be because children are motivated by an atmosphere where they are allowed to talk, ask questions and expect a satisfactory response from a more knowledgeable person. They are allowed to share their experiences as they relate to the scientific concepts under discussion during the instructional processes.

The result from this study lends credence to Ghaffari and Fatemi's (2016) study which investigated the impact of instructional conversation on oral autonomy of Iranian English as Foreign Language (EFL) Learner. The findings revealed significant difference in the performance of students taught reading comprehension using instructional conversation method. The study further revealed that students from both groups made appreciable gain in the pre-test. The study concluded and encouraged teachers to adopt a thematic integrated approach (combining the instructional conversation method and the vocabulary method) since both methods could complement each other, if effectively used.

The results from this study differs from earlier study by HENDY and CUEVAS (2020) who examined the effectiveness of the Instructional Conversations (ICs) teaching method on elementary-aged English Language Learning (ELLs) students. Specifically, how ICs impact student academic achievement, academic language usage, and student engagement. Results indicated that ICs did not lead to an increase of academic achievement or academic language usage when compared to students

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taught through traditional instruction. Results did show that engagement increased when using ICs taught. With an increase in engagement combined with a decrease in academic acquisition, results suggest that ICs should be used with caution when teaching content related material.

The results obtained showed that the effect of gender was not significant on students' achievement. Female students had higher mean while the male students had lower mean). It shows that the female achievement score was different from their female counterpart but the difference in their mean scores was not statistically significant. Both male and female Basic Science and Technology students had similar academic achievement. The findings of this study could probably be attributed to the fact that in Nigeria, the common medium of communication used in schools from primary to tertiary institutions is English Language which would have served as background support for both male and female students.

Previous researchers have reported similar finding. Kola (2013) analysed gender achievement in physics in colleges of education, Nigeria and found no relationship between male and female achievement in Physics. The study concluded that students' achievement in physics in College of Education has no gender bias. Ani *et al.* (2016) examined effect of gender on Basic Science students' academic achievement in secondary schools. The result showed that gender (male/female) had no significant effect on students' achievement in Basic Science. In a related work in Basic Science, Babayemi and Ahmed (2019) in their work on effect of enhanced conventional lecture method and gender on students' achievement in Basic Science, the result showed that there was no significant effect of gender on achievement. Umanah and Sunday (2022) examined crossword puzzle, flashcards teaching strategies and senior secondary school students' academic performance in Chemistry. The study concluded that was not a significant determinant of students' academic performance. It can therefore be concluded that gender of students whether male or female, does not seem to have any influence on the effectiveness of any of the treatment employed in the study.

Conversely, Olagunju and Babayemi (2014) examined the effect of crossword-Picture puzzle (CPP) teaching strategy and gender on students' achievement in Basic Science. Gender had significant main effect on achievement score. A related study on gender by Babayemi (2019) investigated cognitive style and gender as predictors of students' academic performance in Basic Science and Technology in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The findings showed that there was significant difference in the performance of male and female Basic Science and Technology Students with reflective cognitive style and those with impulsive cognitive style.

Conclusion

The study has determined effect of instructional conversation strategy on achievement in basic science and technology among secondary school students in Mkpato Enin Local Government. The results from the study serve as an eye opener to Basic science and Technology teachers on the potential of students' conversations during instructional processes. Instructional conversations, from the findings of the study, improved students' academic achievement. This means that instructional conversation was very effective to teach Basic Science and Technology. The study also revealed that if students are exposed to the same appropriate teaching and learning strategy, both boys and girls can perform in the same way. The teaching strategy/method to be used by the teacher needs to cater for the instructional needs of both boys and girls for their learning gains.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made.

1. Teachers should use instructional conversation teaching strategy to teach Basic Science and Technology concepts in secondary schools. This will improve students' academic achievement.
2. To encourage both boys and girls' participation in science especially Basic Science and Technology, instructional conversation teaching strategy that would improve their achievement should be used.
3. Curriculum planners at all levels, should look into the curriculum and adopt instructional conversation teaching strategy in classroom so as to be able to meet the challenges of communication interest of 21st century learners.

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Effects of Guided-Inquiry and Coop-Coop Cooperative Strategies on Interest in Concept Geometry among Secondary School Students in Benue State

Abaver, Sharon Mnaena¹

Email: sharonjude85@gmail.com

Tel: 08062700484

Ogor, Christiana Ebele¹

Email: ogorebele247@gmail.com

Tel: 07036603385

¹Department of Science and Mathematics Education, Benue State University, Makurdi, Nigeria.

Abstract

This study investigated the Effects of Guided-Inquiry and Coop-Coop Cooperative strategies on Interest in Concept Geometry among secondary school students in Benue State. Quasi-experimental research design specifically, pretest, posttest non-equivalent research design was adopted for the study. Three research questions and corresponding hypotheses guided the study. Population of the study comprise of all government junior secondary school class three (JSSIII), 2022/2023 academic session students with special needs in Benue state. A sample size of 46 (28 Male and 18 female) students were selected from the population using multi-stage sampling technique. Instrument used for the study is Interest in Geometry Scale (IGS) with reliability index of 0.76 obtained using Cronbach Alpha. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics to answer the research questions and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings of the study revealed that there is no significant difference in the mean interest ratings in Geometry of students with special needs when taught using guided-inquiry instructional strategy and those taught using coop-coop co-operative instructional strategy. In conclusion, Guided-Inquiry and Coop-Coop Cooperative strategies on Interest in Concept Geometry among secondary school students in Benue State. The study recommended among others, that guided-inquiry instructional strategy and coop-coop co-operative instructional strategy should be encouraged in special secondary schools for students with special needs.

Keywords: Guided-inquiry instructional strategy, coop-coop co-operative instructional strategy, interest, concept geometry, special needs.

Introduction

Geometry is a branch of Mathematics concerned with properties of space such as distance, shape, size and relative position of figures. Mathematics can be defined as the science of structure, order and relationship that has evolved from counting, measuring and describing the shapes of objects. Geometry in its simplest form is the mathematical study of shapes and space. According to Matalone (2021) geometry deals with flat, two-dimensional shapes with depth, such as cubes and spheres, which are created using points, lines, line segments, rays and planes. The relevance of Mathematics concepts such as Geometry in the development of science and technology is crucial because it helps us understand and describe the fundamental properties of the world. Jones (2016) opined that Geometry enables us to solve real-world problems, design structure, and advance various fields: science, engineering and arts.

In Nigeria, Mathematics has been made a compulsory subject from primary to secondary school and also a requirement for admission into the university in science and social science courses. Mathematics is essential in our everyday life endeavors, for understanding and engaging with our world. It enables the development of pupils' natural ability to think logically, solve puzzles and apply these skills to real-life problems. Shimizu and Vithal (2023) posits that Mathematics specifications provides students with access to important mathematical ideas to develop mathematical knowledge and problem-solving skills.

People with special needs are people in need of special help or care because they have a physical disability or a variety of conditions such as an impairment. They are the physically challenged: crippled, blind, deaf, including, the mentally retarded. Not all children are born under normal circumstances; some are born with different conditions and special needs (Sabaruddin, Mansor, Rusmar & Husna, 2019). Those kinds of students will require special treatment in all aspects compared to other children who do not have such issues. Notwithstanding the alarming birth rate of children with special needs, the special

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education centers still record low intake of students with special needs as a result of their parents and guardians neglecting their need for educational development. Ilona (201) found that the birth rate of children with special needs has continued to increase worldwide. Onaolapo and Onaolapo (2017) stated that most of children with special needs face challenges or difficulty in performance especially autistic children. According to Aligba and Nyihemba (2022) it has been observed that a considerable population of school pupils is seen as having either special educational needs (SEN) or learning difficulties as well as disabilities (LDD). Some of these students in special educational schools also have learning difficulties linked to social deprivation, which could make them loss interest in learning Geometry. Learning difficulties experienced by some of these pupils could cause them to lose interest in class activities and at times withdraw from interacting with others both within and outside the class while some may drop out of school. The difficulties faced by pupils with special needs in learning Mathematics concepts could make them lose interest in learning or skip Mathematics classes (Sabaruddin, 2020).

Guided-inquiry strategy provides the opportunity for students to interact by asking questions, seek solutions, analysing and applying their knowledge to solving daily life problems. Guided inquiry instruction strategy (GISS) is an approach whereby the teacher leads his/her students with well formulated questions that are designed to bring students face to face with knowledge they are seeking, so that they can in effect find out such knowledge. According to Eche, Eriba and Gyuse (2021) guided inquiry is a student-centered instruction strategy whereby there is active participation of students in the learning process, it uses classrooms discussions, problem solving, role plays and collaborative learning Guided-inquiry strategy could ensure that students are given the opportunity to find out things themselves about events and scientific ideas through asking questions, investigation, observation, and construction of reasonable explanation, sharing information and experience (Audu, Ajayi, & Angura, 2017). Guided-inquiry strategy, as an instructional strategy in teaching Geometry could embraces students' deep understanding of the concept.

Coop-Coop Cooperative Learning was developed by Kagan (1989) in (Achor, Jack & Daiko, 2022). In this learning instruction, the teacher guides the process of learning at each phase. The teacher introduces the topic, and breaks it into sub-topics, and groups the students in small groups of 4-6 membered teams. According to Achor, Jack and Daiko, (2022) the teams discuss the instructor's defined topics and select one in which they have an interest, and each team segments its topics into micro-topics for each team member, the team topic must be fully covered. Coop-Coop Cooperate learning is a collaboration and co-operative learning of students in teams. It could be used as one of the cooperative strategies of learning that allows students to work together in small groups to advance their understanding and provide them with the opportunity to share the understanding with their peers. Birt (2023) opined that students can learn behavioural techniques like interpersonal skills, social interaction and collaborative skills that teach them how to work with others. Co-operative learning takes place through the interactions students have with their peers, through male and female interaction with their peers and also through the interactions the students have with their teachers in the learning process.

Interest in learning Mathematics is the willingness to learn mathematical concepts, it's the feeling of curiosity towards learning concepts in Mathematics and applying them in solving life problems. Interest is a vital aspect of the teaching and learning process, because the learners' interest is an essential factor in incubating the right knowledge, skills, values, and morals that the curriculum seeks to attain (Bileya & Achor, 2021). According to Herpratiwi and Tohir (2022) interest in learning accompanies the desire or ability to deliberate attention and liveliness that eventually give birth to a sense of fun in the form of a change of behavior or attitude of knowledge and skills. It could sustain concentration, purpose and commitment of students to learning. The special needs educator has the responsibility to make Mathematics class, comfortable, suitable and interesting for the pupils with special needs by having the ability to practice inclusivity and handle each pupils' special need. The special needs educator could use learning strategies that are learner –centered in boosting the interest of the pupils with special needs, enabling the students participate actively in the class by interaction through co-operation with their peers and answering questions of inquiry accordingly. Interest is an important variable in learning because when one becomes interested in an activity, he or she is likely to become more deeply involved in that activity (Achor, Jack & Daiko, 2022).

Interest affects all the learning domains of the student; the affective, the psychomotor and the cognitive domain of learning. Once a student develops the feeling of curiosity and willingness to learn Mathematics, this could affect his affective domain. This leads to taking actions, and acquiring necessary skills (psychomotor) in learning the concepts and with constant practice he is able to solve mathematical problems, by this, the student's understanding begins to widen and deepen towards cognitively applying mathematical concepts in various problem-solving aspects. Once the students are motivated and stimulated to learn, they will continue to learn as long as the teacher has the capacity to sustain the learners' interest on that object of learning (Herpratiwi & Tohir, 2022).

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From previous studies, guided-inquiry strategy and coop-coop co-operative instructional strategies has shown effectiveness in Mathematics concepts learning process. Ijeh (2023) study showed that there is a significant difference between the mean interest scores of students taught mathematics with inquiry-based instructional strategy (experimental) group and their counterparts in the lecture (control) group. Pujiastuti, and Haryadi, (2023) study revealed that Guided-inquiry Learning can further enhance students' mathematical literacy skills than the Direct Instruction Learning, however, this study did not consider interest of students towards mathematics. Sunday, Olaoye, and Audu (2021) study reveal that there is significant difference between the achievement of students exposed to cooperative strategy and those exposed to conventional method. This shows that cooperative learning methods improve students' achievement in mathematics and attitude towards mathematics. Lekan and Emmanuel (2020) study revealed that students in the cooperative learning strategy group retention ability in Mathematics was higher than compared to those in the conventional group. Anigbo (2016), Aligba and Abaver (2022) study revealed that the experimental group had improved their interest towards set theory after a student-centered strategy was used.

Gender is a socio-cultural concept that differentiates the roles of boys and girls in a given society. These are the physical, biological, mental and behavioral characteristics that distinguish between the masculine and the feminine (male and female) population. Gender could relate with student' interest in the learning process. Gender issue in Mathematics has posed a lot of worry and has attracted many researchers, studies on gender as it affects student' interest in Mathematics are inconclusive, hence the need for more investigations. The mathematics field has been for years considered as a male business, this could be the reason why the female students' show little effort towards learning and excelling in it, hence only few females are professionals in Mathematics. Gender differences in Mathematics achievement and ability has remained a source of concern as researchers seek to address the under-representation of women at the highest levels of Mathematics, physical sciences and engineering. According to Oluyemo, Musbahu, Kukwil, Anikweze and Shaluko (2020) on the influence on gender differences in Mathematics interest and achievement of junior secondary school students in Niger State, the findings revealed that male students excelled in Mathematics more than their female counterparts furthermore, Allahnana, Akande, Vintseh, Alaku and Alaku (2018) researched on assessment of Gender and interest in Mathematics achievement in Keffi Local Government Area of Nasarawa State, Nigeria. The study findings revealed that male students have interest in Mathematics concepts more than their female counterparts. None of the studies reviewed considered guided-inquiry and coop-coop co-operative strategies as instructional strategies that could enhance students' interest in Mathematics concepts such as geometry.

Interest in learning concept geometry could be stimulated by the strategies used in learning Mathematics concepts, this could in turn enhance student's active participation and enable better achievement scores. The persistent poor performance of students in Mathematics external examinations such as the Basic Education Certification Examinations (BECE) is of great concern in Nigeria and in Benue State (Ocheche & Oguche, 2022) This is not in exemption to special education school students with special needs, who also study Mathematics using the same Mathematics curriculum and also partake in the external examinations (Ballin, Davidson, Caron, & Drago, 2022). The Chief examiner's reports of Basic Education Certificate Examinations (BECE) from 2017-2022 portrays a concern, which shows that there is high level of impossibility of students passing BECE with 100 percent in Mathematics.

Table 1. Basic Education Certificate Examination 2017/2018-2021/2022 Result Review

Year	2017/2018	2018-2019	2019-2020	2020-2021	2021-2022
Candidates	66,375	75,057	75,938	82,589	66,500
Average Score	56.91	56.03	51.59	63.67	66.63
Passed	61,705 (92.96%)	71,313 (95.01%)	65,422 (86.15%)	74,602 (90.33%)	60600 (91.13%)
Failed	4,670 (7.04%)	3,744 (4.99%)	10,516 (13.85%)	7,987 (9.67%)	5,900 (8.87%)

Lack of interest and motivation in Mathematics concepts such as Geometry could be traced to Conventional learning strategies such as lecture methods used by teachers to teach. Innovative learning strategies such guided-inquiry strategy and coop-coop co-operative instructional strategies could be avoided by teachers with the intention to maximize time, since student's interaction could be more time consuming compared to lecture method. Thus, they persistently use Conventional learning strategy to teach the students. This has aggravated matters as students become passive rather than active learners. Conventional learning strategy are teacher-centered and do not provide opportunity for collaborative learning. Low rate of

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stimulation of students in learning Mathematics concepts could have great effect on students with special needs interest and could furthermore, create Mathematics phobia and a feeling of inability in solving mathematical problems.

The literature review accessed by the researcher has shown that research has being scarcely carried out on education of students with special needs in Benue State in Mathematics. There are few studies in Benue State on guided-inquiry strategy and coop-coop co-operative instructional strategies, however, they are not on students with special needs. Due to insufficient research on students with special needs education in Mathematics concepts such as Geometry, this study seeks to investigate the "Effects of Guided-Inquiry and Coop-Coop Cooperative strategies on Interest in Concept Geometry among secondary school students in Benue State"

Objectives of the Study

The objective of this study is to ascertain the effect of Guided-Inquiry and Coop-Coop Cooperative strategies on Interest in Concept Geometry among secondary school students in Benue State. Specifically, the study intends to:

1. Determine the effect of Guided-Inquiry and Coop-Coop Cooperative strategies on Interest in Concept Geometry of students with special needs in Benue State
2. Examine the effect of Guided-Inquiry strategy on Interest in Concept Geometry of male and female students with special needs in Benue State
3. Investigate the effect of Coop-Coop Cooperative strategies on Interest in Concept Geometry of male and female students with special needs in Benue State

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the difference in the mean interest ratings of students with special needs taught Concept Geometry using guided-inquiry instructional strategy and those exposed to coop-coop cooperative instructional strategy?
2. What is the difference between mean interest ratings of male and female students with special needs taught Concept Geometry using guided-inquiry instructional strategy?
3. What is the difference between mean interest ratings of male and female students with special needs taught Concept Geometry using coop-coop cooperative instructional strategy?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 significance level.

1. There is no significant difference between mean interest ratings of students with special needs taught concept Geometry using guided-inquiry instructional strategy and those exposed to coop-coop cooperative instructional strategy.
2. There is no significant difference between mean interest ratings of male and female students with special needs taught Concept Geometry using guided-inquiry instructional strategy.
3. There is no significant difference between mean interest ratings of male and female students with special needs taught Concept Geometry using coop-coop cooperative instructional strategy.

Methodology

The study adopted Quasi-experimental research design specifically, pretest, posttest non-equivalent research design. This design was considered appropriate for this study because intact classes were used and no possibility of randomization of the research participants. Emaikwu (2015) opined that the design is deemed suitable because the participants of the research were not randomized as in true experiment. Population of the study comprise of all government junior secondary school class three (JSSIII), 2022/2023 academic session students with special needs in Benue state. A sample size of 46 (28 Male and 18 female) students were selected from the population using multi-stage sampling technique. Two special secondary schools were used as experimental groups, which were taught concept Geometry using Guided-inquiry and Coop-Coop cooperative instructional strategies respectively. Intact classes where used, this was to ensure that the classes were not randomized and disarranged. The criteria was that the schools must be special schools, also, one school should be used for each of the two groups. The justification for simple random sampling was to ensure that all the six special needs secondary schools had the same opportunity to be picked, in order to eliminate selection bias. This helps to remove the disparity of schools in terms of validity of the study.

One instrument was developed by the researchers for data collection. Interest in Geometry Scale (IGS). Ten lesson plans were prepared for teaching. Five (5) lesson plans for teaching in each experimental group; guided-inquiry instructional strategy experimental group and coop -coop co-operative instructional strategy experimental group respectively. IGS is a 20-

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item researcher-developed rating scale with three sections developed by the researcher, each designed to measure the respondents' interest in Geometry. Section A sought the respondents' demographic data, section B contained ten (10) items designed to determine the students' interest in Geometry using guided-inquiry instructional strategies and section C also had ten (10) items designed to determine the students' interest in Geometry using coop-coop co-operative instructional strategies. The items of the instrument (IGS) include interchanged positive and negative statements for guided-inquiry and coop-coop co-operative instructional strategies. The statements were rated Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD); with scoring of 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively, with reverse scoring pattern for negative statements.

The IGS and lesson plans were validated by two experts in Mathematics Education and one in measurement and evaluation Benue State University, Makurdi. The comments and suggestions were used to improve the quality of the instrument and lesson plans. Pilot testing was conducted in another special school not among the two selected for the study, and an intact class was used of upper basic three students with special needs. The IGS reliability index of 0.76 was obtained using Cronbach Alpha. A pretest was administered to both experimental groups to determine students' homogeneity before the treatment. After the pretest, the research assistants taught experimental group 1 using guided-inquiry instructional strategy and experimental group 2 were taught using coop-coop co-operative instructional strategy. After treatment, the research assistants administered the post-IGS to determine students' interest in learning Geometry when taught using guided-inquiry and coop-coop co-operative instructional strategies. Teachers that participated in the study were Mathematics teachers teaching in those classes as their regular teachers, who have a minimum of three years' experience and graduates of Mathematics Education from either teaching colleges or other higher institutions of education.

In all the schools, the treatment procedural lasted for five weeks. Training of research assistants was held in the first week, while the pre-test conducted in the second week. Treatment of experimental group 1 and experimental group 2 were carried out simultaneously in the third, to fifth week. Post-test was administered in the fifth week. Before the commencement of the training, the researcher explained the objectives of the study to the research assistants and revealed the teaching packages for guided-inquiry and coop-coop co-operative instructional strategies for the two experimental groups to the research assistants. Data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the difference in the mean interest ratings of students with special needs taught Concept Geometry using guided-inquiry instructional strategy and those exposed to coop-coop cooperative instructional strategy?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Interest Ratings of Students with Special Needs Taught Concept Geometry Using Guided-Inquiry and Coop-Coop Co-operative Instructional Strategy.

Instructional Strategy	N	Pre-IGS		Post-IGS		Mean Gain
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation	
Guided Inquiry	29	2.6	0.04	3.01	0.35	0.39
Coop-Coop Cooperative	17	2.51	0.42	3.09	0.30	0.58
Mean Difference		0.11		0.08		0.03

Table 2 shows that students taught using guided inquiry had mean Pre-IGS and Post-IGS of 2.62 and 3.01 with standard deviation of 0.40 and 0.35 respectively. Students taught using coop-coop co-operative group had mean Pre-IGS and Post-IGS of 2.51 and 3.09 with standard deviation of 0.42 and 0.30 respectively. The mean difference in Pre-IGS and Post-IGS for students taught using guided-inquiry and coop-coop co-operative is 0.11 and 0.08. The mean difference between the mean Pre-IGS and Post-IGS of students taught using guided inquiry is 0.39 while that of students taught using coop-coop co-operative is 0.58 with mean gain difference of 0.03. This difference indicates that coop-coop co-operative strategy has more effect in enhancing students' interest than guided-inquiry strategy.

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Research Question 2

What is the difference between mean interest ratings of male and female students with special needs taught Concept Geometry using guided-inquiry instructional strategy?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation between Interest Ratings of male and female Students with Special Needs Taught Concept Geometry Using Guided-Inquiry Instructional Strategy.

z	N	Pre-IGS		Post-IGS		Mean Gain
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation	
Student' Gender						
Male	17	2.62	0.37	3.00	0.23	0.38
Female	12	2.26	0.46	3.05	0.48	0.43
Mean Difference		0.00		0.05		0.05

Table 3 shows that the mal mean pre-IGS interest rating of male students in the guided-inquiry group is 2.62, with 0.37 standard deviation, while the mean pre-IGS interest rating of female is 2.62 with standard deviation of 0.46. The difference between the mean pre-IMS interest rating of male and female students is 0.00. The mean post-IGS interest rating of male students is 3.00, with standard deviation of 0.23. While the female has mean post-IGS interest rating of 3.05 with standard deviation of .48. The difference between the mean post-IGS interest rating of the male and female students is 0.05. The mean gain of male students is 0.38, while that of female students is 0.43, with 0.05 increase in favor of female students. This implies that female students obtained higher interest ratings when taught geometry using guided-inquiry strategy.

Research Question 3

What is the difference between mean interest ratings of male and female students with special needs taught Concept Geometry using coop-coop cooperative instructional strategy?

Table 4: Mean and Standard Deviation between Interest Ratings of Male and Female Students' with Special Needs Taught Concept Geometry Using Coop-Coop Co-operative Instructional Strategy.

Student' Gender	N	Pre-IGS		Post-IGS		Mean Gain
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation	
Male	11	2.54	0.47	3.12	0.29	0.58
Female	6	2.45	0.37	3.04	0.34	0.59
Mean Difference		0.09		0.08		0.01

Table 4 shows that the mean pre-IGS interest rating of male students in the coop-coop co-operative strategy group is 2.54, with 0.47 standard deviation, while the mean pre-IGS interest rating of female is 2.45 with standard deviation of 0.37. The difference between the mean pre-IGS interest rating of male and female students is 0.09. The mean post-IGM interest rating of male students is 3.12, with standard deviation of 0.29. While the female has mean post-IGS interest rating of 3.04 with standard deviation of 0.34. The difference between the mean post-IGS interest rating of the male and female students is 0.08. The mean gain of male students is 0.58, while that of female students is 0.59, with 0.01 increase in favor of female students. This implies that female students obtained higher interest ratings when taught geometry using guided inquiry strategy.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between mean interest ratings of students with special needs taught concept Geometry using guided-inquiry instructional strategy and those exposed to coop-coop cooperative instructional strategy.

Table 5: ANCOVA of Mean Interest Ratings of Students with Special Needs Taught Concept Geometry Using Guided-inquiry and Coop-coop Co-operative Instructional Strategy.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	.281 ^a	2	.141	1.280	.289	.056
Intercept	13.234	1	13.234	120.521	.000	.737
Pre-IGS	.204	1	.204	1.854	.180	.041

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Strategy	.048	1	.048	.434	.513	.010
Error	4.722	43	.110			
Total	429.549	46				
Corrected Total	5.003	45				

a. R Squared = .056 (Adjusted R Squared = .012)

Table 5 results summary reveals that $F(1, 43) = .434$; $p = 0.513 > 0.05$. This signifies that the probability level is greater than the specified alpha-level of 0.05. Consequently, the null hypothesis is retained. This means that there is no significant difference between mean interest ratings of students with special needs taught concept Geometry using guided-inquiry instructional strategy and those exposed to coop-coop cooperative instructional strategy.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between mean interest ratings of male and female students with special needs taught Concept Geometry using guided-inquiry instructional strategy.

Table 6: ANCOVA of Mean Interest Ratings Between Male and Female Students with Special Needs Taught Concept Geometry Using Guided-Inquiry Instructional Strategy.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Squared	Eta
Corrected Model	.195 ^a	2	.098	.772	.473	.056	
Intercept	7.933	1	7.933	62.657	.000	.707	
Pre-IGS	.163	1	.163	1.287	.267	.047	
Gender	.030	1	.030	.236	.631	.009	
Error	3.292	26	.127				
Total	265.628	29					
Corrected Total	3.487	28					

a. R Squared = .056 (Adjusted R Squared = -.017) s

Table 6 results summary reveals that $F(1, 26) = .236$; $p = 0.631 > 0.05$. This signifies that the probability level is higher than the specified alpha-level of .05. Hence the null hypothesis is not rejected. This means that there is no significant difference between mean interest ratings of male and female students with special needs taught Concept Geometry using guided-inquiry instructional strategy.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference between mean interest ratings of male and female students with special needs taught Concept Geometry using coop-coop cooperative instructional strategy.

Table 7: ANCOVA of Mean Interest Ratings between Male and Female Students with Special Needs Taught Concept Geometry Using Guided-Inquiry Instructional Strategy Using Coop-coop Co-operative Instructional Strategy

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Squared	Eta
Corrected Model	.074 ^a	2	.037	.379	.691	.051	
Intercept	5.199	1	5.199	53.355	.000	.792	
Pre-IGS	.053	1	.053	.547	.472	.038	
Gender	.028	1	.028	.290	.599	.020	
Error	1.364	14	.097				
Total	163.921	17					
Corrected Total	1.438	16					

a. R Squared = .051 (Adjusted R Squared = -.084)

Table 7 results summary reveals that $F(1, 14) = .290$; $p = 0.599 > 0.05$. This signifies that the probability level is higher than the specified alpha-level of .05. Hence the null hypothesis is not rejected. This means that there is no significant difference

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between mean interest ratings of male and female students with special needs taught Concept Geometry using coop-coop cooperative instructional strategy.

Discussion of Findings

Findings from the current study reveals that there is no significant difference between mean interest ratings of students with special needs taught concept Geometry using guided-inquiry instructional strategy and those exposed to coop-coop cooperative instructional strategy. This finding contradicts Lekan and Emmanuel's (2020) findings which revealed that students in the cooperative learning strategy group retention ability in Mathematics was higher than compared to those in the conventional group. This finding also contradicts Sunday, Olaoye, and Audu's (2021) finding which reveal that there is significant difference between the achievement of students exposed to co-operative strategy and those exposed to conventional method. This shows that guided-inquiry instructional strategy and co-operative learning methods improve students' interest towards mathematics. This is possible since; the two instructional strategies are learner-centered and student activity-based learning strategies.

The finding is in cognizance with Ijeh's (2023) finding that there is significant difference between the mean interest scores of students taught Mathematics with inquiry-based instructional strategy group and their counterparts in the lecture group, and Aligba and Abaver's (2022) finding that students in the experimental group had improved their interest towards set theory after a student-centered strategy was used, compared to conventional methods. These findings though contradicting, indicates that learner-centered strategies will have a greater influence on students' interest compared to conventional methods such as lecture methods. But when two learner-centered strategies; guided-inquiry instructional strategy and coop-coop cooperative instructional strategy are used, the effect will be the same. This signifies that their effect is the same on the students' interest since they share similarities of students' activity-based classes and the teachers' guidance of the student to discover knowledge and self-evaluate the achievement of the lesson's objectives.

The findings from the present study reveals that there is no significant difference between mean interest ratings of male and female students with special needs taught Concept Geometry using guided-inquiry instructional strategy, neither between mean interest ratings of male and female students with special needs taught Concept Geometry using coop-coop cooperative instructional strategy. These findings are contrary to the finding of Allahnana, Akande, Vintseh, Alaku and Alaku (2018) which revealed that male students have interest in Mathematics more than their female counterparts. Furthermore, the study of Oluyemo, Musbahu, Kukwil, Anikweze and Shaluko (2020) findings revealed that male students exceled in Mathematics more than their female counterparts also contradicts the current study's findings. Mathematics has been considered as a hard subject that requires critical, analytical and creative thinking and as such is often regarded as a male subject, the findings of this study shows that with the use of student-centered strategies; guided-inquiry instructional strategy and coop-coop cooperative instructional strategy, both male and female students with special needs interest in mathematics concepts can be boosted.

Conclusion

Guided inquiry instructional strategy and coop-coop co-operative instructional strategy could be suitable for teaching Geometry in secondary school students with special needs to enhance their interest. This is because, these strategies have positive effect of boosting interest in Geometry, using guided-inquiry and coop-coop cooperative instructional strategies on students with special needs in Benue State. Guided-inquiry instructional strategy and coop-coop co-operative instructional strategy are also, found to enhance students with special needs interest irrespective of gender.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study.

6. The use of guided-inquiry instructional strategy and coop-coop co-operative instructional strategy should be encouraged in special secondary schools for students with special needs. This will motivate students with special needs and also, boost their interest in learning mathematical concepts such as geometry.
7. Government and education stakeholders should encourage the teaching and learning of mathematics concepts using guided-inquiry instructional strategy and coop-coop co-operative instructional strategy, which will stimulate both male and female students with special needs interest in learning Mathematics concepts.

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8. Curriculum planners should inculcate learner-centered strategies such as guided-inquiry instructional strategy and coop-coop co-operative instructional strategy in Mathematics concepts curriculum in order to enable students with special needs interact and collaborate during learning.

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Effects of Sequential Teaching Methods on Retention in Biology among Senior Secondary School Students in Niger State, Nigeria

Apochi, Maria Aladi¹

Email: apochma@gmail.com

Tel: 08057282513

Paul-Fiase, Rose Udoo¹

Email: rosyudoofiase@gmail.com.

Tel: 08145133422

¹Department of Science and Environmental Education, University of Abuja, Nigeria

Abstract

The study examined Effects of Sequential Teaching Methods on Retention in Biology among Senior Secondary School Students in Niger State, Nigeria. Quasi-experimental research design specifically, pre-test, post-test and post-post-test control group design was adopted for the study. Two research questions and corresponding null hypotheses guided the study. The population of the study consists of 165,034 (85,034 Male and 80,000 female) government senior secondary school class two (SSII) students during the 2022/2023 academic session in Niger State. 100 (51 Male and 49 Female) students constitute the sample size of the study using multi-stage sampling technique. The instruments for data collection were 30-item Biology Retention Test (BRT) validated by experts. Reliability coefficient of 0.85 was obtained using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient reliability test. Descriptive statistics were used to answer the two research questions, while ANCOVA was used to test null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that there was significant difference in students' retention in Biology between those exposed to sequential teaching methods and their counterparts taught with conventional method. Base on the findings of the study, it was further concluded that sequential teaching methods has positive effect on students' retention and is gender friendly. Hence, it was recommended that regular workshops, seminars and conferences should be held for teachers to make them familiar with the knowledge of sequential teaching methods and should be encouraged to explore the method frequently during teaching and learning process.

Keyword: Sequential teaching methods, biology, students, gender and retention

Introduction

Biology is the study of living organisms, their origins, anatomy, morphology, physiology, behavior and distribution. It studies life processes of a group or category of living organisms. A lot of reasons are borne in mind while studying Biology. These include among others, the understanding of self and the environment surrounding us, appreciation of nature as well as pollution control. Thus, Biology and its study are necessary not only for students but the whole of human populace. Of all the science subjects, Biology is the only descriptive science which is very much linked to human life unlike Chemistry and Physics which are quantitative in nature. Biology is one of the core science subjects that senior secondary school students offer in Nigerian secondary schools, it was introduced to students at this level as a preparatory ground for human development, where career abilities are groomed, potentials and talents are discovered and energized (FGN, 2013). It is also a prerequisite for higher learning in a number of sciences related professional courses like medicine, zoology, botany, biochemistry and microbiology. Biology is very wide with many branches such as genetics, ecology, morphology, evolution and the more advanced cell biology among others.

Science has a unique nature and it is an organized body of knowledge in form of concepts, laws, theories and generalizations. Ugbong (2016) defined science as a study of nature and natural phenomena in order to discover their principles and laws. Science enhances national development and also exposes an individual to recent ideas through reasoning and mental efforts (Orji & Anaduaka, 2010). All nations in the world including Nigeria are striving hard to improve or develop technologically and scientifically. This could be achieved through laying a solid foundation in science and technology studies. Science as school subjects comprises of Physics, Chemistry, Mathematics, Agriculture and Biology. Science Education is defined as the study of the connection between science as a discipline and the application of educational principles to comprehend science teaching and learning in the classroom (Dabah, 2016). Therefore, science education acquaints students with certain basic knowledge, skills and attitudes needed for future work in science and science-related fields. The impact of science education on national development could be felt in several ways; as it

provides humanity with knowledge about the environment, attitudes and values for social living, knowledge and skills to explore and transform resources, change in quality of life and improvement in economy (Udofia, 2010)

There are many factors that have been identified by researchers as being responsible for the decline and poor retention of students in Biology; some of these include; lack of instructional materials, lack of qualified teachers, lack of educational facilities like laboratories, overloaded syllabuses, laziness, poor attitude and lack of interest on the part of the students, large class size, family/home background of the students (Osuafor & Okonkwo, 2013; Sadi & Haruna, 2020)). Based on this premise, sequential usage of three teaching methods was applied: demonstration, discussion and conventional (talk-chalk) in teaching Biology content in a sequence of use in order to ascertain their effects on students' retention. Sequence is an act of putting events, ideas, and objects in a logical order (Frank, 2013). **Sequential teaching method is an instructional method that engages students to learn a particular topic in logical order of display or is a process of imparting knowledge to learners using different instructional methods in logical order.** It provides a concrete basis for conceptual thinking (promoting critical thinking skills).

Demonstration method involves the use of instructional materials to show learners how something is done in order to enable them acquire skills necessary for performing the given task. The method is mostly used in showing the students correct use of certain science equipment. Demonstration can be carried out as: teacher centred approach, quasi student centred approach or student centred approach. The method encourages students' participation which is necessary for teaching and learning in the classroom. It is a strategy that focuses on achieving psychomotor and cognitive objectives (Azubuike & Mumuni, 2018). Discussion method involves a group of people in a class who come together to exchange ideas, facts, opinions and expressions orally about a topic of mutual concern and interest under a guide. In a discussion class, the students talk to each other about the concept or problem until there is an agreeable understanding to it mentally. This method encourages children to be independent of teacher and discover knowledge and also see relationship on their own. The discussion method involves intelligent exchange of views, ideas and opinions on a topic, which covers a wide range of classroom activities and interactions or it involves written and oral expression of different points of view in a given situation (Cashin, 2011).

The lecture method (talk-chalk) is concerned with the teacher being the controller of the learning environment. It does not encourage deeper students' involvement as they are passive recipient of information already acquired by the teacher. Also, it does not facilitate the development of reasoning skills and processes in the students. These among other reasons had not enhanced learning in students and thus had led to poor retention of Biology concepts among students in secondary schools (Merriam & Grace, 2011). Retention involves the ability to recall the content that has been taught within a specific period of time. It is the ability exhibited by learner to demonstrate what he/she has learnt and has been able to demonstrate his/her cognitive skills in the subject learnt (Emmanuel, Ogbeba & Ahmed, 2014). Also retention means the ability to store information which can be easily recalled from the short term memory and long term memory (Alake, 2015). Fakotun & Eniayeju (2014) wrote that retention can be measured through verbal recall of learnt materials that is, the cognitive ability of learners. Retention occurs when experience are coded in the memory. There are many factors that may affect retention of Biology concepts, which are: Age, as one grows older the cells become weaker and weaker. The intervening variable influencing students' retention in Biology at SSCE is gender. Gender is a social construct that differentiate male from female based on physical features. Many researchers (Apochi, 2017, Nneka, 2015; Abdul-Raheem, 2012 & Okoro, 2011) have shown gender to be of significant influence in an investigation of this nature, hence the inclusion of gender as an intervening variable in this study. Based on this background therefore, the present study examined the effects of sequential teaching methods (STM) on retention in Biology among senior secondary school students.

The teaching of science particularly Biology should be consistent with the nature of science which lays greater emphasis on engaging students in inquiry activities as the use of one-size-fits-all curriculum no longer meets the needs of majority of learners. Education is an indispensable instrument for the development of any nation and teachers are the implementers of the educational programme and theories into practice. Hence, due to the usefulness of biology in nearly all fields of human endeavor, the poor retention of students biting hard at senior secondary schools' level is of significant concern to stakeholders in education. To buttressed this fact, it is observed by the Chief Examiners' Report of West African Examination Council (WAEC 2017-2023) that, the problem affecting poor achievement in Senior Secondary Certificate Examination is attributed to poor teaching delivery or teacher's method of presenting the content of the curriculum to learners amongst others, the results in 2017 showed that, one million, five hundred and fifty-nine thousand, one hundred and sixty-two (1,559,162) candidates sat for final examinations, 79.77% (1,243,772) have credits in five subjects including English Language and Mathematics while 20.23% failed. But it further disclosed that there was declined in 2018, 2019 and 2020 with 42.64%, 35.82% and 34.76% failures respectively as shown in table below:

Effects of Sequential Teaching (Apochi & Paul-Fiase, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10681446>

Table 1: Chief Examiners' Report of West African Examination Council (WAEC 2017-2023)

Year	No of candidates that sat for examinations	Number that passed	% that passed	Number that failed	% that failed
2017	1,559,162	1,243,772	79.77%	315,390	20.23%
2018	1,099,902	1,077,749	57.35%	2,153	42.64%
2019	1,600,000	1,020,519	64.18%	579,481	35.82%
2020	1,538,445	1,003,668	65.24%	534,777	34.76%
2021	1,560,261	1,398,370	89.62%	161,891	10.38%
2022	1,601,047	1,222,505	76.36%	378,542	23.64%
2023	1,613,733	1,287,920	79.81%	325,813	20.19%

Furthermore, Nwagbo (2011), also assert that the persistent negative retention of students in Biology and other related science subjects is attributed to inappropriate teaching method adopted by the teachers. In addition, Biology teachers use talk-chalk/lecture method to teach the subject, which does not in any way provide sequence of learning experience that is, the talk-chalk/lecture method is imperfect because it involves verbal presentation of pre-planned lesson to the students which requires little or no instructional aid and so does not promote students' higher level of thinking (Dajal & Mohammed, 2019).

Furthermore, the persistent use of these methods makes students passive rather than active learners and does not promote insightful learning and long-term retention of some abstract concepts in biology (Umar, 2011). Therefore, considering the importance of biology in all round development there is need for change in strategy/method in teaching so as to enable students in senior secondary schools to acquire adequate knowledge and skills in science. In the same vein, researchers in science education especially Biology have always been searching for better teaching method that will enhance better students' retention and promote their attitude so that they perform well in Senior Secondary School Certificate Examinations. In order to improve on the teaching and learning of Biology by exploring an innovative learner-centred method, it's therefore necessary to investigate sequential teaching methods on students' retention.

Objectives of the study

1. Examine the mean retention scores of students taught Biology with sequential teaching methods and those taught with conventional method;
2. Find out the mean retention scores of male and female students taught Biology with sequential teaching methods.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide this study:

1. What is the mean retention scores of students taught Biology using sequential teaching methods and those exposed to Lecture teaching method in Government secondary schools in Niger State?
2. What is the mean retention scores of male and female students taught Biology using sequential teaching methods in Government secondary schools in Niger State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at significant level of 0.05.

1. There is no significant difference in mean retention scores of students taught Biology using sequential teaching methods and those exposed to Lecture teaching method in Government secondary schools in Niger State
2. There is no significant difference between mean retention scores of male and female students taught Biology using sequential teaching methods in Government secondary schools in Niger State.

Methodology

The research design for this study was quasi-experimental research design specifically, pre-test and post-test non equivalent control group. Being an experimental study, the samples for the studies were grouped into experimental and control groups. The experimental group was taught biology concepts (Ecological Management: Association, Tolerance, Adaptation, Pollution, Nutrient Cycling in nature, Basic Ecological Concepts, Population Studies and Conservation of Natural Resources) using sequential teaching methods while the control group was taught the same biology concepts (Ecological Management: Association, Tolerance, Adaptation, Pollution, Nutrient Cycling in nature, Basic Ecological Concepts, Population Studies and Conservation of Natural Resources) using conventional talk-chalk method. Intact classes were used in order to avoid distortion on the normal class settings using the school timetables. The design is presented symbolically in Table 1.

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Table 2: Representation of Research Design

Group	Pre-test	Treatment	Post-post test	Post-post test
Experiment	O_1	X_1	O_2	O_3
Control	O_1	X_1	O_2	O_3

The population of the study consists of 165,034 (85,034 Male and 80,000 female) government senior secondary school class two (SSII) students during the 2022/2023 academic session in Niger State. 100 (51 Male and 49 Female) students constitutes the sample size of the study using multi-stage sampling technique. At first stage, simple random sampling was used to select a Local Government Area from the twenty-five (25) Local Government Areas in Niger state. The reason for the choice of simple random sampling technique is to give each Local Government Area equal chance of being selected in the study. At the second stage, two co-educational secondary schools were selected using simple random sampling technique. The choice of co-education schools was because gender is one of the variables in the study. At the third stage of sampling, one intact class of Biology students in SSII from the two sampled schools was selected randomly (hat-draw method) and the two classes were assigned experimental group and control group.

The instruments used for data collection in this study Biology Retention Test (BRT) was used for test of retention. It consisted of two sections: Section A and Section B. Section A entails the general information of the students while Section B entails the Biology Retention Test questions. The BRT comprised of thirty (30) items multiple choice objective test questions with four (4) options lettered A, B, C and D. The question numbers were administered as post-post-test to both experimental and control groups and the test was conducted 30 days of post-test in order to avoid retention error and help the researcher investigate the effect of sequential teaching methods on students' retention in Biology. The test items were based on concepts in ecological management: association, tolerance, adaptation, pollution, nutrients cycling in nature, basic ecological concepts, population studies and conservation of natural resources adopted from past West African Examination Council (WAEC, 2019-2023 standardized questions). The researcher prepared a table of specification (Test blue print) to guide the test development, in accordance to the senior secondary curriculum.

The researcher prepared two sets of lesson plans for teaching both experimental and control groups for each topic that was taught; each unit contained eight lessons that lasted for eight weeks. One set of lesson plan was prepared using sequential teaching methods while the other set was prepared based on conventional method. The Biology Retention Test (BRT) was subjected to scrutiny by four experts in the subject area and was content validated using table of specification and face validation by experts in the Department of Science and Environmental Education, University of Abuja; and two Biology teachers from sampled senior secondary schools in Tafa LGA, Niger state. The comments and recommendations of the experts had helped in selection and modification of the test items for the study. After the validation, the BRT items were subjected to Split half reliability test. A split half method was used to compute the reliability of the Biology Retention Test. It was administered once and the scores were divided into two to calculate the reliability of the instrument.

A method of estimating reliability involved twenty-five (25) senior secondary II Biology students (15 male and 10 female). Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (r) was used to calculate the internal consistency of the BRT. This method of estimating the internal consistency reliability of an instrument is appropriate for dichotomously scored items such as BRT which is a multiple-choice objective test with right and wrong answers and is easier to use. The outcome of the reliability estimate warranted modifications in the test item (BRT). The reliability coefficient of the instrument gave $r = 0.85$. Thus, BRT was considered reliable. The treatment lasted for a period of eight weeks of treatment, BRT instrument was administered as pre-test for both experimental and control groups; after the first week, the researcher went round the sampled schools and taught students personally for eight (8) weeks during their lesson period using the prepared lesson plans and notes was given. The researcher administered the BRT post post-test. The data collected were analyzed accordingly. The scores obtained were analyzed using descriptive statistics frequent counts, mean and standard deviations for the research questions while the hypotheses were using ANCOVA at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the mean retention scores of students taught Biology using sequential teaching methods and those exposed to Lecture teaching method in Government secondary schools in Niger State?

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Table 2: Mean and standard deviation showing retention scores of students taught Biology using sequential teaching methods and lecture teaching method

Treatment Groups	N	Pre-test X Sd.	Post-test X Sd.	Mean Difference
Sequential Teaching Methods (Experimental)	51	15.741.00	64.9630.23	49.2
Lecture Teaching Method (Control)	49	15.093.55	41.5441.38	26.450
Total	100			

Source: 2023 Field work data statistics

In Table 2, the mean scores of the students in the sequential teaching methods (experimental group) on pre-test and post-test are 15.74 and 64.96 respectively. These results give a post-test - pre-test mean difference of 49.22; while those of the students in conventional method (control group) are 15.09 and 41.54 respectively, giving a post-test - pretest mean difference of 23.42. The gains in scores show that the students in the experimental group taught sequential teaching method (23.42) performed better than their counterparts in conventional method (0.65). Considering the research question one - what are the mean retention scores of students taught Biology with sequential teaching methods and those taught with conventional method? - The observations indicate that students taught using sequential teaching method retained better than those taught with the conventional teacher-centered method.

Research Question 2

What is the mean retention scores of male and female students taught Biology using sequential teaching methods in Government Secondary schools in Niger State?

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation showing retention scores of male and female Students taught Biology using sequential teaching methods

Gender	N	Pre-test	Post-test	Mean Difference
		X Sd.	X Sd.	
Male	27	13.541.26	17.960.62	4.425
Female	24	13.669.56	17.920.00	4.261
Total	51			

Source : 2023 Field work data statistics

Table 3 the mean scores of the male students in the sequential teaching methods (experimental group) on pre-test and post-test are 13.54 and 17.96 respectively. These results give a post-test - pre-test mean difference of 4.43; while female students also taught the same instructional strategy are 13.67 and 17.92 respectively, giving a post-test - pretest mean difference of 4.26. The mean difference of 0.164 is an indication that both gender retained equally. A comparison of these retentions indicates that both male and female in sequential teaching methods had similar knowledge. These observations answered the question two - what are the mean retention cores of male and female students taught Biology with sequential teaching methods?

Hypotheses Testing

H₀₁:

There is no significant difference in the mean retention scores of students taught Biology using sequential teaching methods and those exposed to Lecture teaching method in Government secondary schools in Niger State.

Table 4: Summary of Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of Biology Students taught using Sequential Teaching Methods and Lecture Teaching Method

Source of Variation	Type III Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F.cal	Sig.	Decision at p<.05
Corrected Model	7681.545 ^a	3	4230.512	81.634	.000	S
Intercept	4762.004	1	4762.006	114.240	.000	S
Covariate Pre-test	174.15	1	174.15	6.431	.063	Ns
Methods	8762.202	1	4286.807	144.341	.000	s

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Error	4173.710	141
Total	119631.000	134
Corrected Total	9766.276	130

a. R Squared = .787 (Adjusted R Squared = .781)

Table 4, reading on the row Methods revealed that Mean Square = 8762.202, $F = 144.341$, $df = 1$ and $Sig. = .000 = p$. Since $p < 0.05$, the noted difference between retention scores of students taught using sequential teaching methods and conventional method is significant. So, the null hypothesis was rejected with the conclusion that there is a significant difference between the mean retention scores of the students taught using sequential teaching methods and those taught Biology with conventional method.

H₀₂:

There is no significant difference between the mean retention scores of male and female students taught Biology using sequential teaching methods in Government secondary schools in Niger State.

Table 5: Summary of Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of Male and Female Students taught Biology using Sequential Teaching Methods

Source of Variation	Type III Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F.cal	Sig.	Decision at $p < .05$
Corrected Model	56.355 ^a	2	23.436	.482	.342	Ns
Intercept	4163.420	1	4163.420	62.422	.000	S
Covariate Pre-test	62.023	1	62.023	2.003	.344	Ns
Sex	5.842	1	5.842	.163	.602	ns
Error	7122.411	70				
Total	6643.001	67				
Corrected Total	4071.374	68				

a. R Squared = .788 (Adjusted R Squared = .782)

Table 5, reading on the row heading Sex, revealed that Mean Square = 5.842, $F = .163$, $df = 1$ and $Sig. = .602 = p$. Since $p > 0.05$, the note in the difference of students taught using sequential teaching methods between male and female students is not significant. So, the null hypothesis was not rejected with the conclusion that there is no significant difference between the retention scores of male and female students taught Biology using sequential teaching methods.

Discussion of Findings

The first findings revealed that students taught Biology using sequential teaching methods retained significantly better than those taught using conventional method. This finding is in agreement with Snezana, Liljana & Milena (2011) and Namasaka, Mondoh & Chrulukovian, (2017) who found significant differences in favour of experimental group meaning the method gives retention of knowledge more than the oratory conventional method predominantly used in most places worldwide. Similarly, Ajaja (2013), Abdulhamid (2013) and Owolabi & Oginni (2013) showed that learning styles increases motivation, attracts attention and retention among learners. However, the results of these findings negate that of Amosa, Akawo, Gana & Ugovwa (2014), who asserted that there was no significant difference in the mean scores retention of students.

The second findings revealed that male and female students taught biology using sequential teaching methods did not differ significantly in their mean retention scores. This finding agreed with Oludipe (2012), who underscores sequential teaching methods as gender friendly. In a similar study by Gongden & Delmang (2016) recorded no significant difference in male and female students in experimental group. However, this contradict the findings of Duyilemi & Bolajoko (2014), Okeke (2011) which revealed that male students' retention was significantly higher than that of their female counterpart exposed to three (3) interaction patterns (cooperative, competitive and individualistic patterns of learning); This is so because the learner centered method promote low retention ability due to lack of active engagement or participation of some female students learning culture.

Conclusion

This article examined the Effects of Sequential Teaching Methods on Retention in Biology among Senior Secondary School Students in Niger State. The result revealed that STM significantly enhanced retention in Biology. That is, when STM is used to teach Biology, student's retention magnifies. Also, gender has no significant effect on students' retention. This study finally concluded that the use of sequential teaching methods was resourceful, innovative and would be a good asset to Biology teachers and students. The result revealed that students taught STM had drastic positive effect on students' retention in Biology. Also, it enhanced cooperate learning than those taught using lecture teaching method. Gender has no significant effect on students' retention. This study finally concluded that the use of sequential teaching methods was resourceful, innovative and would be a good asset to Biology teachers and students.

Based on the finding of the study, sequential teaching methods enhance student's retention due to its stimulation of attention or curiosity in the students by making them desirous to learn and know Biology. This finding makes the researcher to conclude that sequential teaching methods are elegant to students' retention and gender friendly.

Recommendations

Based on the findings in this study the following recommendations were made:

1. Teacher education institutions are encouraged to include sequential teaching methods in their Biology curriculum for training and retraining in workshops, seminars,
2. Biology teachers in schools should be encouraged to use sequential teaching methods in teaching other concepts.
3. Curriculum developers when developing curriculum, should embrace innovative teaching strategies like STM to enhance acquisition of critical thinking, problem solving and achievement skills for both genders.

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Impact of Beyond-The-Branch Banking System on Unemployment among Youths in Oyo East Local Government Area of Oyo State, Nigeria

Olayiwola, Aanuoluwa Oladiran

Email: connectaanuoluwaolayiwola@gmail.com

Tel: +234 703 329 7403

Department of Business Education, Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo

Abstract

This study examined the impact of beyond-the-branch banking system on unemployment among youths in Oyo East Local Government of Oyo State, Nigeria. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study was 995 beyond-the-branch bankers and 285 respondents were selected using simple random sampling technique. A self-structured questionnaire was used for data collection and it was validated by two Business Education experts. Pilot study was conducted and the data collected therefrom were tested using Cronbach's Alpha reliability test, 0.677 reliability level was obtained. The data collected from the respondents were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions while t-test was used to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that beyond-the-branch banking afforded the youth the opportunity to make regular profits, have a stable source of income and save money to set up other businesses. It was also revealed that the major challenges incapacitating young Nigerians from making the most of these opportunities include but not limited to shortage of working capital and security risks. Based on the findings, it was recommended that the Central Bank of Nigeria should facilitate loans specifically for youths venturing into the beyond-the-branch banking so as to provide them with sufficient working capital. Banks and other financial institutions, as a form of Corporate Social Responsibility, should help build the capacity of youths so as to enable them manage this new business model effectively and efficiently.

Keywords: Bank, Beyond-the-branch banking, Financial Institutions, Informal Sector, Unemployment

Introduction

The major recurring decimal in Nigeria's economic and social challenges is the youth unemployment. Youth unemployment in Nigeria, the most populous black nation in the world, has been on the increase for many years. Majority of youths are unable to find gainful employment in spite of their willingness to work. Despite the high number of youths' enrollment in formal education in Nigeria and the turnout of graduates each year, job opportunities to absorb these graduates are few (Akinsola, 2021). Youth unemployment is defined as young adults between the ages of 18 and 35 who are willing to work but unable to secure productive employment (International Labor Organization, 2019). Unemployment occurs when a person who is actively searching for employment is unable to find work. It is a state of not having jobs. Unemployment is one of the developmental problems that face every developing economy in the 21st century. This has become a global concern because of existential threats posed to other developed nations of the world who seem to have gotten it right economically and have a near-zero unemployment rate. For instance, in 2019, the Central Intelligence Agency alerted that Nigeria's bloated population of unemployed youths will have grave consequences for Nigeria, Africa, and the rest of the world if it is not tackled firmly. Olorunfemi (2021) asserted that unemployment has become a big issue for Nigeria's young population. The high percentage of youth unemployment in Nigeria has contributed to the country's poverty and insecurity. The National Bureau of Statistics (2019) puts the population of young people in Nigeria at 80 million, representing 60% of the total population of the country. Sixty-four million of them are unemployed and one million and six hundred thousand (1.6 million) are underemployed. (Opafunso & Omoseni, 2014).

A lot of scholars have posited several factors that caused astronomical rise in youth unemployment in Nigeria and some of them include lack of required skills by prospective employees and overreliance on white-collar jobs as career prospects (Emeh & Eke, 2012). Dike et al. in Akinsola (2021) pointed out that the causes of unemployment are multi-faceted, but criticized Nigerian education system for having a hand in the youth unemployment crisis. The first critique is that young people

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are only prepared for white-collar employment and not for entrepreneurial, technical, and vocational opportunities as job producers. The second critique is that the education is not tailored to the 21st-century workplace knowledge, skills, and training requirements. However, Jose in Nwagbara, Ugal, and Uyang (2011) argued that unemployment was not an issue in traditional African culture. In traditional African civilization, seventy-five percent of the population was involved in agriculture, while the other twenty-five percent earned a livelihood via minor trade, goldsmithing, blacksmithing, among others.

The Nigerian government, at various levels, has formulated and adopted different policies aimed at tackling the rising youth unemployment in the country through job creation and facilitation of various youth empowerment programmes. Some of these policies birthed the formation of the National Directorate of Employment (NDE), Youth Enterprise with Innovation in Nigeria (YOUWIN), Subsidy Re-investment Programme (SURE-P), the NPower programme, and the Government Enterprise and Empowerment Programme (GEEP) among others (Salami 2013; Olorunfemi, 2021). Although, it has been observed that these efforts have achieved limited success in reducing youth unemployment as evidenced in the prevailing unemployment rates in the country, it is notable that these interventions were aimed at developing both the formal and the informal sector of the economy.

Out of myriads of policies and interventions of the Nigerian government towards stemming the tides of youth unemployment, of essence to this study is the financial inclusion policy introduced by the Central Bank of Nigeria in 2012 to give a broad range easy access of formal financial products and services to the unbanked and underbanked population in Nigeria. Part of the strategies for achieving this policy is the introduction of agent banking service delivery and mobile banking system which are otherwise referred to, in this study, as beyond-the-branch banking. Beyond-the-branch banking is the process of engaging a licensed third-party retail outlets (otherwise known as agents) to conduct customer transactions on behalf of the financial institutions. It is of note that this policy was not directly targeted at reducing youth unemployment in Nigeria but its implementation has brought about job opportunities in the informal sector to the teeming population of Nigerian youths. Unemployment breeds poverty. Therefore, the realization that financial inclusion is pivotal in the fight against poverty and in reaching the goal of inclusive economic development leads to an increased focus on financial inclusion policies and initiatives, and the subsequent introduction of the Point of Sales (POS) service business to the Nigerian economy.

In recent time, there has been a tremendous increase in the population of young people owning or operating the beyond-the-branch banking business. Beyond-the-branch banking retail outlets are common sights everywhere in the urban, suburban and rural Nigeria. For instance, First Bank of Nigeria in 2022 announced that there are over 155,000 of its banking agents (Firstmonie agents) locations in 772 out of 774 local government areas in Nigeria, including the Federal Capital Territory. Bulk of the owners of these outlets are young demographic. The number of banking agents increased from 83,560 in 2018 to 236,940 in 2019, according to the Central Bank of Nigeria. However, these figures exclude agents who are not covered by Shared Agent Network Expansion Facilities. The implication of this is that beyond-the-branch banking facilitated the employment of 236,940 young Nigerians in 2019 excluding the huge number of direct and indirect employment facilitated by the CBN-licensed Super Agents and mobile money operators like Paga, OPay, PayCentre, PayCom, Baxi among others.

However, relative provision of employment is one, ascertaining whether the employment actually leads to profitability and income stability of the youth demographic is another. It is on this premise that this paper sought to study the impact of beyond-the-branch banking system on youth unemployment in Oyo East Local Government Area, Oyo State. The findings of this study would be greatly beneficial to government and other stakeholders in the banking industry in providing feedbacks on the policy implementation of the beyond-the-branch banking. It would provide feedbacks on the strengths and weaknesses of the policy as touching the youths and employment. This study would equally enlighten the Nigerian youths to look beyond the white-collar jobs and make the most of the opportunity provided by the informal sector of the economy.

Youth unemployment is one of the most challenging economic and social problems facing Nigeria. In fact, it is the trigger to many socio-economic and socio-political challenges bedeviling Nigeria. With the population of 80 million youth, out of which 64 million are unemployed while 1.6 million are underemployed as noted by the National Bureau of Statistics, Nigeria is sitting on a timebomb which when finally detonated would pose a sort of existential threats to the global community. Already, Nigeria has witnessed a high rate of poverty and insecurity which is a direct consequence of youth unemployment.

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Successive governments have formulated and adopted different policies aimed at tackling the rising youth unemployment in the country through job creation and facilitation of various youth empowerment programmes. But these reforms seem to have achieved limited success in reducing youth unemployment as evidenced by the prevailing unemployment rates in the country. However, with the introduction of the beyond-the-branch banking through the implementation of the financial inclusion policy, there seems to appear another strategy for combating the youth unemployment in Nigeria. It is on this premise that this study intended to investigate the impact of beyond-the-branch banking on youth unemployment in Oyo East Local Government Area, Oyo State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

The objective of this study was to determine the impact of beyond-the-branch banking system on youth unemployment in Oyo East Local Government Area, Oyo State, Nigeria. Specifically, this study sought to determine;

- the extent to which profitability of beyond-the-branch banking reduce youth unemployment in Oyo East Local Government Area, Oyo State;
- whether income stability of beyond-the-branch bankers reduce youth unemployment in Oyo East Local Government Area, Oyo State;
- the correlation between beyond-the-branch banking and youth employment in Oyo East Local Government Area, Oyo State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide this study.

4. To what extent does profitability of beyond-the-branch banking reduce youth unemployment in Oyo East Local Government Area, Oyo State?
5. Does income stability of beyond-the-branch bankers reduce youth unemployment in Oyo East Local Government Area, Oyo State?

Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis was formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

- H₀₁ There is no significant relationship between beyond-the-branch banking and youth employment in Oyo East Local Government Area, Oyo State.

Methodology

The descriptive survey research design was adopted for this study. Both primary and secondary sources of data collection were employed for the study. Primary data were collected through the administration of questionnaire while secondary data were gathered through related research journals and textbooks. The study was conducted in Oyo East Local Government Area, Oyo State, Nigeria. The population of the study was 995 beyond-the-branch bankers (including 553 beyond-the-branch bankers that registered with the commercial banks and 442 beyond-the-branch bankers that registered with super agents) in the local government as at year 2023. The sample size for the study was 285 beyond-the-branch bankers. Slovin's formula was used to get the sample size, and simple random sampling technique was used to select the respondents. A self-structured questionnaire was used for data collection and it was validated by two Business Education experts. Pilot study was conducted on the beyond-the-branch bankers outside the target population of the study. The reliability of the data collected from the pilot study was tested using Cronbach's Alpha reliability test and 0.677 reliability level was obtained. Therefore, the reliability of the instrument was considered reliable for the study. The data collected from the respondents were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions while t-test was used to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Characteristics of Respondents

Table 1 shows the distribution of respondents by type of beyond-the-branch banker

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Table 1: Type of Beyond-the-branch Banker

Type of beyond-the-branch Banker	Frequency	Percent
POS Terminal-Enabled Super-Agent	117	41.1
MoMo Agent	69	24.2
POS Terminal-Enabled Bank Agent	99	34.7
Total	285	100

Table 1 above shows the distribution of types of beyond-the-branch bankers that participated in the study. They include POS Terminal-Enabled Super-Agent 117 (41.1%), MoMo Agent 69 (24.2%) and POS Terminal-Enabled Bank Agent 99 (34.7%).

Table 2: Distribution of Respondents by Gender

Gender of beyond-the-branch Banker	Frequency	Percent
Female	165	57.9
Male	120	42.1
Total	285	100

Table 2 reveals the gender distribution of the beyond-the-branch bankers who participated in the study. 57.9% of the respondents were female while 42.1% of the respondents were and male.

Table 3: Distribution of Respondents by Educational Qualification

Educational Qualification	Frequency	Percent
M.Sc.	03	1.1
HND/B.Sc.	103	36.1
NCE/OND	157	55.1
O' Level	22	7.7
Total	285	100

Table 3 shows the educational qualification of the respondents. The majority (i.e., 55.1%) of the respondents are NCE/OND holders while O' level, HND/B.Sc., and M.Sc. holders represent 7.7%, 36.1% and 1.1% respectively.

Research Question 1

To what extent does profitability of beyond-the-branch banking reduce youth unemployment in Oyo East Local Government Area, Oyo State?

Table 4: Mean and standard deviation scores on the extent to which profitability of Beyond-The-Branch Banking reduce youth unemployment in Oyo East Local Government Area, Oyo State.

S/N	Items	Mean (X)	Std. Dev.	Decision
9.	Beyond-the-branch banking as a lucrative business reduces youth unemployment.	3.08	1.037	Very High
10.	The making of ends meets by beyond-the-bank bankers can assist in reducing youth unemployment.	3.04	.828	Very High
11.	The opportunity to save money from the beyond-the-bank banking to set up other business can reduce youth unemployment.	2.99	1.020	Very High
12.	Reduction in profit making as a result of charges from the principal bank can lead to youth unemployment.	2.43	1.174	Low Extent
13.	Reduction in sales due to competition from other beyond-the-bank bankers can promote youth unemployment.	2.54	1.167	High Extent

Source: Field survey (2023)

From table 4 above, the respondents agreed to a very high extent that the profitability of beyond-the-branch banking reduce youth unemployment. This is evident by the mean rating of items 1, 2, 3 and 5 which were above the criterion mean

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weight of 2.50. This implies that to a very high extent, the respondents perceived that the beyond-the-branch banking is a lucrative business and that it reduces youth unemployment. However, the respondents disagreed that the charges from the principal bank could lead to youth unemployment.

Research Question 2

Does income stability of beyond-the-branch bankers reduce youth unemployment in Oyo East Local Government Area, Oyo State?

Table 5: Mean and standard deviation scores on income stability of beyond-the-bank bankers and reduction in youth unemployment in Oyo East Local Government, Oyo State

S/N	Items	Mean	Std. Dev.	Decision
•	Because I can predict my sales volume per day, Beyond-the-branch banking reduces youth unemployment.	2.79	.998	Agreed
•	I make regular profits from the beyond-the-bank operation; therefore, it reduces youth unemployment.	2.95	1.086	Agreed
•	Beyond-the-branch banking enables me to have a stable source of income; therefore, it reduces youth unemployment.	3.02	.985	Agreed
•	I would need more capital to maintain a higher level of income in order to benefit from the employment opportunity provided by the beyond-the-branch banking.	3.10	1.087	Agreed
•	Beyond-the-branch banking enables me to meet my immediate financial needs; therefore, it reduces youth unemployment.	2.72	1.155	Agreed

Source: Field survey (2023)

Table 5 revealed that the ability of the beyond-the-branch bankers to relatively predict their sales volume per day, make regular profits and meet their immediate financial needs lead to their income stability and consequently reduce youth unemployment. On the other hand, the higher the working capital or float to meet customers' needs the higher the level of income and profitability of the business.

Hypothesis 1

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between beyond-the-branch banking and youth employment in Oyo East Local Government Area, Oyo State.

Table 6: The relationship between beyond-the-branch banking and youth employment in Oyo East Local Government Area, Oyo State.

	N	t	df	sig. (2-tailed)	Mean	St. Deviation
Relationship	285	54.824	99	.000	8.07	1.472

Source: Field survey (2023)

Data in table 6 indicated that there is a positive relationship between beyond-the-branch banking and youth employment. The calculated alpha level of 0.000 is less than the significant level of 0.05 hence, the stated null hypothesis is therefore rejected.

Discussion of Findings

Research question one in table 4 indicates that the lucrativeness of the beyond-the-branch banking, ability of the beyond-the-branch bankers to make ends meet, opportunity to save money from the beyond-the-branch banking to set up other businesses and low transaction charges are some of the indicators that rate the extent to which profitability of beyond-the-branch banking reduce youth unemployment. This is in line with the position of Mohamad, Suraidi, Rahman and Suhaimi (2016) that agency banking is a lucrative option for the unemployed. Akintoye (2018) equally posited that quite a number of

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young Nigerians are no longer fixated on the non-existent white-collar jobs but have now sought comfort in the opportunity provided by the informal sector through the beyond-the-branch banking. Beyond-the-branch banking has created more employment opportunities in the informal sector with the same vigor with which the introduction of the mobile telecommunications networks otherwise known as the Global System for Mobile communication (GSM) generated employment for the teeming Nigerians. Macjohn (2022) reported that the total amount of transactions at POS terminals in year 2021 in Nigeria hit ₦4.1 trillion. The reason for the huge transaction is that banks in Nigeria only open their branches in busy areas, where there are markets or many other businesses. People living far from the bank are often stranded and resort to patronizing the POS business thereby resulting in huge profitability for the operators.

Results in table 5 shows that the ability of the beyond-the-bank bankers to relatively predict their sales volume per day, make regular profits and meet their immediate financial needs lead to their income stability and consequently reduce youth unemployment. The income of a business is considered to be stable if its earnings from work or capital does not suffer more than 25% variation over the period of a year. This is in tandem with the proposition of Omoseni and Opafunso (2014) that a stable business by income is one whose owner is able to track expenses, forecast sales volume, maintain a positive budget and leverage on opportunity for growth. The findings also revealed that the higher the working capital or float to meet customers' needs the higher the level of income and profitability of the business.

Conclusion

This paper concludes that despite the prevailing rate of youth unemployment in the country, quite a number of young Nigerians have availed themselves of the opportunities provided by the informal sector through the beyond-the-branch banking to mitigate the challenges. The extent to which the profitability and the income stability of the beyond-the-branch bankers reduce unemployment among the youths is significantly high. It afforded the youth the opportunity to make regular profits, make ends meet, have a stable source of income and save money to set up other businesses. Whereas the policy of beyond-the-branch banking was not directly targeted at reducing youth unemployment, its implementation has brought about job opportunities in the informal sector to the teeming population of Nigerian youths. However, the major challenges incapacitating young Nigerians from making the most of these opportunities include but not limited to shortage of working capital/float requirement and security risks.

Recommendations

Stemming from the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made, that;

13. government should assist in the provision of adequate physical and cyber security;
14. the Central Bank of Nigeria should also provide or facilitate loans specifically for youths venturing into the beyond-the-branch banking so as to provide them with sufficient working capital;
15. Banks and other financial institutions, as a form of Corporate Social Responsibility, should help build the capacity of youths so as to enable them manage this new business model effectively and efficiently;
16. Nigerian youths should look beyond the formal sector and avail themselves of opportunities provided by the informal sectors.

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Impact of Community Participation on Effective Implementation of Universal Basic Education Programme in Gombe State Local Government Education Authorities

Zubairu, Abdulazeez¹

Email: abdulazeezzubairu14@gmail.com

Tel: [08038480213](tel:08038480213)

Usman, Saleh Muhammad²

Email: Sdeba@fukashere.edu.ng

Tel: 08065105919

Abdulqadir, Bello²

Email: belkadir65@gmail.com

Tel: 08065469834

Muhammad, Sanusi Haruna²

Email: sanusiharunamuhammad123@gmail.com

¹Gombe International School, Gombe

^{2,3 & 4} Faculty of Education, Department of Educational Foundations, Federal University of Kashere, Gombe State

Abstract

The study was on the Impact of Community Participation on Effective Implementation of Universal Basic Education Programme in Gombe State Local Government Education Authorities and two objectives and corresponding research questions were formulated to guide the study. The descriptive survey design method was adopted for the study which was conducted in all the eleven Local Education Authorities of Gombe State with a population of 4604 (3565 male & 1039 female) education stakeholders within all the eleven local education Authorities in Gombe state during the 2018/2019 academic session. The sample of 379 (292 male & 87 female) education stakeholders were selected using simple random sampling technique by hat and draw method. The data for this study were gathered through the use of a questionnaire titled “community involvement on the implementation of Universal Basic Education Programme questionnaire” (CIIOUEP). To ensure the validity of the instrument used, two experts in the area of research measurement were contacted to read through and made comments and observations on the items contained on the questionnaire. The test and retest method was used in two schools where the questionnaire was administered to them and collected after 2 weeks and it was redone. The reliability test had a α value 0.86. The data was analysed using mean and standard deviation and the Grand mean to take decisions. The study revealed that effective community participation is very imperative for the realization of the Universal Basic Education objective in Gombe State. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that aggressive mobilization and sensitization visit to the various stakeholders should be indulged by the management of the Gombe State Universal Basic Education Board and they should endeavour to create forum to be meeting at intervals with the various communities.

Keywords: Influence, Community, Involvement, Implementation

Introduction

The emphasis on multi-sectorial approaches to solving the problems of poverty, and other human development challenges in the developing societies of the world has become the emerging trend since the turn of the new millennium. This paradigm shift is influenced by the premises that the resources available at the disposal of the government is inadequate to cater for the enormous challenges facing mankind in his social environment. This therefore means, the government, the private sector, community and other relevant stakeholders must partner and collaborate. This new approach has been described by developmentalists as Public Private Partnership (PPP) approach to addressing the human development challenges in the society. It is within the context of the above that the whole concept of community participation in the running of the Universal Basic Education (UBE) Programme of the federal government came into being. The concept of community participation in the

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provision of social services has been described as bottom-up approach to development. According to Egwu (2004) in Zubairu (2020), it is an evolving concept which builds on community resources, expertise, supplies and the best way to utilize the development Latent Potentials which are abundant in the communities.

The Universal Basic Education Programme of the federal government was a brain-child of the Chief Olusegun Obasanjo's administration on assumption of office as President and Commander in Chief of the Federal Republic of Nigeria in 1999, he inaugurated and launched the UBEC programme in Sokoto. The UBE Programme is a current educational reform which focuses on the issues of access, equity and quality in the delivery of Basic Education. The Programme is intended to provide a free, compulsory, Universal Basic Education for every Nigerian child of school age as contained in the enabling law, UBE Act of 2004. The programme is primarily aimed at eradicating illiteracy, ignorance and poverty in all facets in Nigeria because education is regarded as the panacea to human and development problems of any society. The objectives of the UBE Programme as contained in the UBE Act of 2004: includes among others developing in the entire citizenry a strong consciousness for education and a strong commitment to its vigorous promotion, provision of free, Universal Basic Education for every child of school age; reducing drastically the incidence of school dropout from formal school system; catering for the learning needs of young persons who for one reason or another have had to interrupt their schooling through appropriate form of complementary approaches to the promotion of basic education; and ensuring the acquisition of the appropriate levels of literacy, numeracy, communicative and life civil values needed for laying a sound and solid foundation for Life-Long Learning (UBE Act, 2004).

Communities as major stakeholders in the Universal Basic Education Project are expected to collaborate with the government in the following areas in the implementation of Basic Education; Prompt repair and renovation of blown-off school roofs; Construction/innovation of school through Self-help; Mobilization for enrolment of School Aged Children in schools; Provision of infrastructural and Instructional materials in school to support effort of Government; Assistance in procurement of books for School Libraries to improve reading and writing skill of Pupils; Provision of school Uniform and books to wards/children; Assist in provision of Teaching/Learning materials in Schools; Pooling of resources to assist the schools in areas of needs; Provision of friendly environment for teaching/learning in School; Encourage enrolment and retention of pupils in school and Checkmate Child Trafficking through enrolment of School Aged Children (UBE Act, 2004). The Universal Basic Education (UBE) Programme being a programme of the federal government is implemented in the 36 States of the Federation including the federal capital territory through the various States Universal Basic Education Boards (SUBEB). It is on the background of the above that this research work, "Impact of Community involvement on Implementation of UBE Programme in Gombe State" will be investigated.

The realization of the Universal Basic Education Programme of the federal government requires the collaboration of state government with communities and other stakeholders. Based on the implementation blueprint, Communities are expected to perform certain roles which include: ensuring the maintenance of infrastructure and facilities for the UBE programme in their local schools; prompt responds to renovation of blown-off school roofs through Community Self-help Initiative; Mobilization for enrollment/retention of pupils in school; provision of logistic support and enabling environment for the implementation of the UBE programme; assisting government to address challenges of out-of-school children in the State; identifying and responding to the needs of the schools among others. There is dearth of information on the level of Influence and participation of Community Members in the implementation of the Universal Basic Education (UBE) Programme in Gombe state Zubairu (2020). Therefore, it is imperative to ascertain whether communities are actually addressing the roles indicated in the implementation blueprint adequately and at the same time influencing the programme positively.

Objectives of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to examine Impact of Community Participation on Effective Implementation of Universal Basic Education Programme in Gombe State Local Government Education Authorities. Specifically, the purpose of the study is to determine the following:

1. The level of community contributions in the provision of infrastructural/instructional materials for the UBE programme in schools that will influence the programme effectiveness.
2. The level to which parents give their wards support toward educational development.

Research Questions

1. To what extent do contribution of members of the community in the provision of infrastructure and instructional materials in the UBE Programme in the state influence the effectiveness of the programme?
2. What is the extent of parental contribution to the education of the children/wards in the UBE Programme in the state?

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Methodology

The study adopted the survey design on which Groves, Fowler, Couper, James, Singer & Tourangeau, (2004,) in Jansen (2010) sees it as, "The survey is a systematic method for gathering information from (a sample of) entities for the purpose of constructing quantitative descriptors of the attributes of the larger population of which the entities are members." Gombe State is located in the North Eastern part of Nigeria with its capital in Gombe. It shares common borders with the states of Borno, Yobe, Taraba, Adamawa and Bauchi. The population for this study was 1247 public Primary Schools and 285 junior secondary schools in the Communities spread across the 11 Local Government Areas of the State with uneven distribution of schools. Descriptive survey design method was adopted for the study which was conducted in all the eleven Local Education Authorities of Gombe State with a population of 4604 (3565 male & 1039 female) education stakeholders within all the eleven local education Authorities in Gombe state during the 2018/2019 academic session. The sample for this study was generated using the R.V. Krejcie and D.W. Morgan table 379 (292 male & 87 female) education stakeholders were selected using simple random sampling technique by hat and draw method. The data for this study were gathered through the use of a questionnaire titled "community involvement on the implementation of Universal Basic Education Programme questionnaire" (CIIOUEP). Twenty questions were set (ten for each research question) to guide the research. To ensure the validity of the instrument used, two experts in the area of research measurement were contacted to read through and made comments and observations on the items contained on the questionnaire. The test and retest method was used in two schools where the questionnaire was administered to them and collected after 2 weeks and it was redone. Reliability test done had a α value of 0.86. The data was analysed using mean (\bar{x}) and standard deviation (σ) and the Grand mean to take decisions. The decision rule considered was that a mean rating of 2.0 and above was positive while a mean rating that is below 2.0 was considered as negative.

Results

Research Question 1

To what extent does contribution of members of the community in the provision of infrastructure and instructional materials in the UBE programme in the state influence the programme effectiveness?

S/ N.	Provision of Infrastructural/ Instructional Materials for Teaching/ Learning	Mean (\bar{x})	STD(σ)	Remarks
1	The school-based management committees in my school support the school by provision of instructional materials	2.4	1.0	P.E
2	The school-based management committees and other stakeholders provide furniture for teachers without waiting for government.	2.5	0.7	ME
3	The existence of the school Based Management Committee, PTA and other stakeholders provide relevant material and facilities for teaching/ learning in the school.	2.7	1.0	M.E
4	Parent and other stakeholders provide books for the school libraries in my community	2.3	1.1	S.E
5	Community members often assist volunteers/UBE teachers posted to my school in areas of transport accommodation.	4.0	0.9	G.E
6	The PTA members sometimes assist the school in my area with books, and other instructional materials. Parental support is very necessary for the implementation of Basic Education delivery in my area.	2.8	1.0	M.E
7	Members of the community and other stakeholders at the grass root regularly participate in making decision and implementing polities that affect physical facilities.	3.3	0.9	M.E
8	Community and other stakeholders help in the procurement of teaching/leaning materials for the school.	2.2	1.0	S.E
9	Parents and community members do support in the provision of school libraries and other reading materials.	2.1	1.1	G.E
10	Members of the PTA in my school often assist the school in preparation and use of locally available learning materials and resources.	2.5	0.8	M.E
Grand Mean		2.6		

Source: Field Survey 2018

Table 1 shows the responses of stakeholders on perception on how their contributions of infrastructure and instructional materials influence the UBE programme effectiveness. The result shows that the mean

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of the stakeholders ranged between 2.1 to 4.0 with standard deviation ranging between 0.7 to 1.0 indicating that a poor extent to a great extent with a grand mean of 2.6 indicating a moderate extent of contributions of community members in the provision of infrastructure materials in the UBE programme implementation in the state.

KEY~ PE-Poor Extent; ME-Moderate Extent; GE-Good Extent; SE-Strong Extent

Research Question 2

To what extent does parental support for the education of their child/wards influence the UBE programme in the state?

S/N	Items:	MEAN (\bar{x})	STD (σ)	Remarks
Parental Support for Children/Wards Education				
1	Parents/Guardians in my area usually equip their ward for school by providing them with uniform.	2.6	1.1	M.E
2	Parents/Guardians in my area usually equip their ward for school by providing them with books and other relevant materials to achieve UBE Programme.	3.2	1.6	G.E
3	The stakeholders discourage certain aspect of traditional norms and practices education in my community.	2.3	1.1	S.E
4	Many parents were sensitized on the importance of basic education as means to achieve self-reliance and contribution to economic development of a community/state.	3.5	0.4	S.E
5	Some parents prefer sending their wards to acquire vocational skills rather than enrolling them for basic education.	3.8	1.2	M.E
6	Parental support is very necessary for the implementation of Basic Education delivery in my area.	4.6	0.4	G.E
7	Because of poverty and poor economic background of some parents, they prefer sending their wards to acquire vocational skills rather than enrolling them for Basic Education.	3.6	0.8	G.E
8	Child trafficking still exist in my community in spite of the existence of UBE law.	3.3	1.0	M.E
9	Parents advices their wards on the need for Education.	2.9	0.9	M.E
10	Parents in my area gives moral support.	3.0	1.1	M.E
Grand Mean		3.2		

Source: Field Survey 2018

Table 2 List of variables were generated and the respondents were asked to indicate the extent to which they agree or disagreed with the variables that influence parental support in the implementation of the programme. The result shows the mean of stakeholders on parental support ranging from 2.3 to 4.6 with standard deviation of ranging from 0.4 to 1.2 indicating from a poor extent to a great extent with a grand mean of 3.2 indicating a moderate extent of parental support for children/ward's Education in the various communities in the implementation of the UBE programme of the state.

Discussion of Findings

The first Research question of this study explored the level of community participation and the influence on the implementation of the UBE Community Initiated Self-help project in schools. The Universal Basic Education Programme stresses on active community participation and involvement in the renovation/construction of school blocks through Self-help to enhance effective teaching/learning environment. This finding agrees with the position of Zubairu (2020) in his justification of the need for community participation in the delivery of Basic education in Nigeria. According to him, Basic Education like any social service cannot be left in the hand of government alone, that stakeholders including the community should pool resources together to enhance the successful delivery of basic education. He further posited that the involvement of community is a strategy to galvanize grassroots and stakeholders support for Education Service delivery to achieve Education for All. The findings from the study also justifies the call for community participation in Basic education programme as contain in the UBE

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Act of 2004 and CRS Law No. I of 2006 – including other policy framework and Federal Ministry of Education documents which stressed the need for involvement of communities and stakeholders in the Management and implementation of Basic education.

The second research question for this study explored the level of community participation and its influence on the increase/retention of pupils in schools for the attainment of the objective of the Universal Basic Education Programme. The objective of the UBE Programme is to provide free Universal Basic Education for every Child of school age; reduce drastically the incidence of school dropout amongst others. Otu (2002) in Usman (2018) spoke on the need for parents and community members to support the school in provision of child friendly school environment for effective teaching and learning to take place. This is in the area of provision of teaching/learning materials, provision of seats and learning environment among others to complement the effort of the government for the effective delivery of Basic Education in Gombe State.

From the above, it's apparent that increase and retention of pupils for the actualization of the Universal Basic Education Programme in Gombe State is dependent on active community participation. Regrettably, the community is not rendering the expected level of participation to ginger increased enrolment in public schools in the State to enhance the success of the Universal Basic Education Programme. It was observed from the field study that, in some communities/areas like Nomadic and Migrant Schools, teachers still appeal to Parents to allow their wards attend schools. Some parents in these settlements prefer their wards especially the boy-child to go farming or rearing animal which will bring immediate income to support the home rather than remain in the school. It was also observed that other socio-cultural factors tend to prevent parent from sending their boy-child or even girl-child to school. This no doubt will impede the realization of the universal basic programme of the federal government.

Conclusion

The conclusion drawn from the findings of this study is that effective Community Participation is very imperative for the realization of the Universal Basic Education Programme of the Government in Gombe State.

Communities should be actively involved in the implementation of the Community Initiated Self-help Projects of the Universal Basic Education Programme. Through this the Challenges of blown-off school roofs, dilapidated School buildings and infrastructure decays etc will be promptly addressed which will facilitate the realization of the objective of the UBE in the State. Active Mobilization and Sensitization of Parents and Community Members on the Universal Basic Education Programme will lead to increase in enrollment and retention of pupil in school for the realization of the Universal Basic Education Programme in the state. Community support to schools in the provision of infrastructural and instructional materials for effective teaching and learning is very essential if the objective of the Universal Basic Education Programme is to be achieved in the state. Lastly, parents and guardians should regularly give educational support to their wards through provision of relevant text-books/reading materials, uniform and other necessary material needed for school. Through these, the objectives of the UBE programme can be achieved since Government alone cannot achieve this.

Recommendations

From the foregoing, it has been observed that active community participation is very imperative for the realization of the Universal Basic Programme (UBE) of the federal government. Regrettably, the level of community participation in Basic Education Programme in Gombe State does not give the desired encouragement to realize the objectives of the Universal Basic Education programme as conceived by the Enabling Laws, UBE Act of 2004 and Gombe State UBE Law No 1of 2006. This therefore means certain measures must be taken to encourage maximum community participation in the implementation of the Universal Basic Education Programme. The following recommendations are hereby made as a way of boosting or encouraging community involvement or participation in the provision of Basic Education since government alone cannot do it.

1. There is need for regular sensitization and creation of awareness to parents and community members to be actively involved in the implementation of the community-initiated self-help projects of the Universal Basic Education Programme in the State. Through this, the challenges of infrastructural delay, dilapidated school block and furniture will be reduced.
2. The State Ministry of Education (SMOE), and State Universal Basic Education Board (SUBEB) should use proper mechanism to encourage community members, parents and guardians on the need to assist schools in the provision of needed infrastructural and instructional material which will enhance effective teaching and learning in schools.
3. Aggressive Mobilization and Sensitization visit to Traditional rulers, Parent Teachers Association members, members of the School Based Management Committee (SMBC), religious organizations, market women and other stakeholders at the grassroot to support school programmes, encourage enrollment/retention of pupils in schools.

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4. The Management of the Gombe State Universal Basic Education Board should endeavour to create a forum where they can meet at intervals with members of Parent Teachers Association, of schools, and appeal to them to provide their wards with relevant textbooks, uniform and other materials needed for school.
5. The Board should create a proper synergy with traditional rulers in the various communities to regularly mobilize their subjects using the villager Town Criers to send their wards to school for increase enrollment and retention for the UBE Programme.
6. The Board and Local Government Education Authorities should at the beginning of every academic session, air jingles on UBE enrollment in the Radio and Television appealing to parents to send their wards to schools and also provide them with relevant materials for school.

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Impact of Job Satisfaction and School Climate on Teaching Efficiency among Secondary School Teachers in Kebbi State, Nigeria

Ibrahim, Musa

Email: musaibrahim@noun.edu.ng

Tel: +2348062622999

Wodi, Catherine Kekeshi¹

Email: wodicatherine@gmail.com

Tel: +2348063453378

¹Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education National Open University of Nigeria

Abstract

Lack of job satisfaction among teachers in secondary schools has been linked with low performance and efficiency, a phenomenon that has been attributed to low academic performance of students. This study therefore, investigated the impact of job satisfaction and school climate on teaching efficiency among secondary school Teachers in Kebbi State. Three research hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significant. Descriptive survey of ex-post-facto design was adopted for this study. Two hundred and sixty-one teachers (male 135 & female 126) were randomly selected. Three standardized instruments were used for the data collection, these includes; job satisfaction (0.73), school (0.85) and teaching efficiency (0.78) scales. Correlation analysis and multiple regression analysis were used for data analysis. The results revealed that there was significant positive relationship between job satisfaction and teaching efficiency ($r = .42, p < .01$). There was significant positive relationship between school climate and teaching efficiency ($r = .74, p < .01$). School climate and job satisfaction jointly predicted teaching efficiency ($R^2 = 0.55, F(2,258) = 159.87, p < .01$). The result further revealed that school climate ($\beta = .77, t = 14.70, p < .01$) found to be significant independent predictor of teaching efficiency among secondary school teachers while job satisfaction ($\beta = -.04, t = -.81, p > .05$) had no significant independent prediction on teaching efficiency. The study therefore concluded that job satisfaction and school climate significantly predicted teaching efficiency. It was recommended that government should provide necessary incentives to arouse the interest of teachers, funding of extra-curricular activities in schools and teachers should be motivated to attend workshop, seminars and training programmes as possible through sponsorship.

Keywords: Job satisfaction, school climate, teaching efficiency

Introduction

Teachers develop skills over time through best experiences shared by others, in-service training and classroom practice. Teachers of all walks of life and subjects have the ability to figure opinions and assist form ideas about humanity, society, life and personal goals. Teachers can also develop students' confides and push their originality. Teaching is a tough career, but it is one where you can make the most impact in another person's life. Teachers are arguably the most important members of our society. They give children purpose, set them up for success as citizens of our world and inspire in them a drive to do well and succeed in life. The children of today are the leaders of tomorrow, and teachers are the critical point that makes a child ready for their future. The reason why teachers matter is that children carry what they are taught at young age throughout the rest of their lives. They will use what they have learned to influence society. Everyone knows that today's youth will become tomorrow's leader, and teachers have the access to educate the youth or the students in their most impressionable years whether in teaching preschool, teaching extracurricular, sports or traditional classes. Teachers have the ability to shape leaders of the future in the best way for society to build positive and inspired future generations and their design society, both on a local or global scale. In reality, teachers have the most important job in the world. Those who have an impact on the children of the society have the power to change lives. Not just for those children themselves but for the lives of all.

Teachers are the ultimate role models for students. The fact that students come into contact with many different types of teachers in their academic career means that more likely than not, there will be a teacher that speaks to them. The teacher-student connection is invaluable for some students, who may otherwise not have that stability. Teachers will stay positive for their students even when things can seem grim. A great teacher always has compassion for their students, understanding of

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their student's personal lives, and appreciation for their academic goals and achievements. Teachers are role model for children to be positive, always try harder, and reach for the Stars. They also expose children to ideas and topics that they might otherwise not have come into contact with. They can expand on interest and push their students to do better. Teachers don't accept failure and therefore, students are more likely to succeed. Teachers know when to push students, when to give a gentle nudge in the right direction, and when to let students figure it out on their own. But they won't let a student give up. Teachers provide guidance to students of all types. Teachers are able to see each child strengths and weakness and can provide assistance and guidance to either get them up to speed or push them higher. They will help to reveal students' best skills and teach valuable life skills as well, such as communication, compassion, presentation, organization, following directions and more. Teachers increase productivity and creative of students and therefore, of future workers.

Job satisfaction is a measure of workers contentedness with their job and can be measured in cognitive (evaluative), effective (or emotional) and behavioral components source. It also refers to a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job or job experiences. It is assessed at both the global level (whether the individual is satisfied with different aspects of the job) Speator, (1997) as cited in Ibrahim (2015) mentioned fourteen (14) list of common facets of job satisfaction. Appreciation, communication, co-workers, fringe, benefits, job conditions, nature of the work, organization, personal growth, policies and procedures, promotion opportunities, recognition, security and supervision. Classroom setting, although not something teachers convey to students, classroom setting creates a place where students can learn. Classroom setting involves knowing the students well and placing them into appropriate learning groups. It also involves having an efficient discipline plan in place that secondary students in Kebbi State can understand. This gives a clear picture of the teacher's expectations and places the emphasis on rewarding good behavior instead of punishment. Classroom setting also deals with the use of time throughout the day. Secondary students in Kebbi State need to be on task with very little down time, for the day to run smoothly. Good classroom setting means planning well and including both physical activity and independent study to Foster good habits among secondary students Kebbi State.

School Climate refers to factors that contribute to the lone in schools, and attitudes of staff and students to ward their schools (Ibrahim, & Awoyemi, 2016). Positive school climate is associated with well managed classrooms and common areas, high and clearly stated expectations concerning individual responsibility, feeling safe at school, and teachers and another supporting staff that consistently acknowledge students and fairly address their behavior (Ibrahim & Abdulsalam, 2023). The size of the school is equally important. In this regard, Ademidara, (2016) examined the impacts of performance appraisal on employees' job satisfaction and organizational commitment and found out that teacher's employees were greater in smaller organization than in large organizations. Teaching and learning situation in schools seem to be a function of the atmosphere of the school and the productivity of the teachers. School Climate is a set of unique characteristics of a school. These characteristics distinguish one school from another. In one school, the school head, teachers and staff may find pleasure in working together. In another school, it may be discontent among the staff. In one school, staff may appear well organized seem competent exhibit confidence in whatever they do, yet in another school, there may be tension as the school heads loses control (Campbell, 2019). School climate is related to school connectedness because without a positive and welcoming school climate, both students and teachers are unlikely to experience connectedness; the poor conceitedness would have negative effect on teacher's job satisfaction and student's achievement. Job satisfaction of an organization is defined as the ratio of outputs produced by the organization and the resources consumed in the process. Teacher's efficiency is the ratio of output produced by the teachers, here the output refers to the quality and quantity of students produces by the teachers.

Climate has been defined in various ways by authors as the perceived subjective effect of the formal system , the informal styles of managers and other important environmental factor that impact on the attitudes, beliefs, values and motivation of people who work in a particular organization , personality of an organization , the atmosphere of the work place , including a complex mixture of norms , values , expectations, policies and procedures that influence individual and group patterns of behavior (Ibrahim & Abdulsalam, 2023, Spencer, Pelote & Seymour, 2008). The school as an organization has certain intends which it has to achieve, in order to achieve these, the institutional climate of the organization including the school system is very important (Ibrahim, & Ihuoma, 2017). This organization climate refers to the working condition among super ordinates (school heads) and subordinates (teachers) in a bid to achieve the aims and objectives of the school system. In one school the school head, teachers and staff may find pleasure in working together. In another school, it may be discontent among the staff. In one school, staff may appear well organized seem competent and exhibit confidence in whatever they do, yet in another school, there may be tension as the school heads loses control (Ibrahim, & Abdulsalam, 2023; Adamu, 2020). School climate is related to school connectedness because without a positive and welcoming school climate, both students and teachers are unlikely to experience connectedness; the poor conceitedness would have negative effect on teacher's job satisfaction and

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student's achievement (Ibrahim, 2022). Efficiency of an organization is defined as the ratio of outputs produced by the organization and the resources consumed in the process. Teaching efficiency is the ratio of output produced by the teachers, here the output refers to the quality and quantity of students produced by the teachers (Ibrahim, 2022).

Climate has been defined in various ways by authors as the perceived subjective effect of the formal system, the informal styles of managers and other important environmental factors that impact on the attitudes, beliefs, values and motivation of people who work in a particular organization, personality of an organization, the atmosphere of the work place, including a complex mixture of norms, values, expectations, policies and procedures that influence individual and group patterns of behavior (Spencer, Pelote & Seymour, 2008). High productivity is the hall mark of growth and development of nations all over the world, the level of efficiency, productivity and the ability of the educational system to achieve its set goals depend on the teacher as reflected in performing their defined roles because teachers are the fulcrum upon which the whole educational system revolves (Ibrahim 2015; Eduese, 2006). Teachers have been shown to have an important impact on student achievement and also play a crucial role on educational attainment (Lloyd, Mensch & Clark 2000). Teaching and learning achievement depend on teachers, for there can be no meaningful socio-economic and political development in any society without teachers. Productivity is concerned with the overall effectiveness and efficiency of getting things done. It is essentially a ratio to measure how well an organization converts resources into goods and services. In the school system, teachers' productivity may be measured in terms of their performance. In assessing teachers' performance, qualitative tools such as standardized test scores of students have been used (Schacter & Thum, 2004). Bratton and Gold (2017) opined that grades and test scores do not reflect the quality of instruction because teacher input is not the only factor that influences student's achievement in the school system, other factors that have been identified to have significant influence on student's achievement include peer effect, ethnicity, gender, motivation, income as well as family background variables such as household environment and parental educational background (Williams, 2016). This suggests that teacher's productivity level may be evaluated in terms of what the teachers control and actually do in the classroom such as teaching effectiveness and classroom performance. Teaching effectiveness has been accepted as a multidimensional construct since it measures a variety of different aspects of teaching (Ford & Walker, 2016).

Lack of job satisfaction among teachers in secondary schools has been linked with low performance and efficiency among secondary school teachers (Ibrahim, 2015), a phenomenon that has been attributed to low academic performance of students. The poor student academic performance in recent times has generated serious condemnation and criticisms among members of the public and various organizations. These people according to Elijah and Frederick (2015) attributed non-performance of students to low morale and apathy on the part of the teachers due to poor incentives. Other people even blamed the teachers as being lazy and unproductive, while many blamed the failure on the irresponsibility of both students and their parents (Ibrahim & Rukkaya, 2019; Bandura & Ahmad 2019). Education as an agent of national rebirth and transformation needed to be handled with all seriousness. The expected outcome of most secondary school teachers especially in Kebbi State lack efficiency in discharging their duties in the school system. Quality education is required for national growth and development. Hence, this research investigates the impact of job satisfaction and school climate on teaching efficiency among secondary school teachers in Kebbi State.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of this study is to investigate the impact of job satisfaction and school climate on teaching efficiency among secondary school teachers in Kebbi State. Specifically, the study tends to;

1. Investigate the influence of job satisfaction on teaching efficiency among secondary school teachers
2. Examine the impact of school climate on teaching efficiency among secondary school teachers
3. Find out the relative contribution of job satisfaction and school climate on teaching efficiency among secondary school teachers

Research Questions

1. What is the relationship between job satisfaction and teaching efficiency on secondary school teacher?
2. Is there any relationship between school climate and teaching efficiency on secondary school teachers?
3. What is the joint influence of school climate, job satisfaction and teaching efficiency on secondary school teacher?

Hypotheses

The study was guided by the following hypotheses and were tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significant relationship between job satisfaction and teaching efficiency among secondary school teachers
2. There is no significant relationship between school climate and teaching efficiency among secondary school teachers
3. School climate and job satisfaction has no significant influence on teaching efficiency among secondary school teachers

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Methodology

The descriptive survey of ex-post-facto design was adopted for this study. This was to ensure the study is devoid of manipulation of the variables in concern. The researcher was interested in knowing the joint contribution and the relationship that exist between independent variables and the dependent variables. The population for this study comprised of all public Secondary School teachers in Kebbi State. As at the time of this study, Kebbi State has a total number of 201 senior secondary schools, with 4083 teachers, (SSMB, 2022). Simple Random Sampling techniques was used to select 10 secondary schools, twenty-six (26) teachers were also randomly selected from nine (9) secondary schools, while twenty-seven (27) teachers were selected from the remaining one (1) school. This is due to the fact that the last school visited by researchers has a total number of twenty-seven (27) teachers, after selection of twenty-six (26) needed, the remaining one insisted to partake in the study. That makes a total number of samples to be two hundred and sixty-one (261) participants. Three standardized instruments were utilized for the study. These include: Job Satisfaction scale (JSS) by developed by Mahmoud, Helen and Ijeoma (2015). This scale has 18 items which are positively worded. These items were given scores of 4, 3, 2, and 1 which range from strongly agreed, agree, disagree and strongly disagree respectively. The sum of this value gives job satisfaction score. The reliability coefficient of the sum of the scale is 0.85. A test retest was carried out using pilot tested method on 10 teachers who were not part of the participants and has a Cronbach Alpha of 0.73. School Climate Scale, the instrument was used to measure the school climate and was developed by Keith (2005). The determination of a school's climate is based on 55 items which made of five-point scoring format of, (1) strongly Disagree, (2) Disagree, (3) Undecided, (4) Agree (5) strongly Agree. It has reliability coefficient of 0.85. lastly, teaching efficiency scale, the instrument used to measure the participants' teaching efficiency was adapted teaching effectiveness scale which was developed by Emmanuelle (2010), it was used to determine the participants' teaching efficiency, and it was comprised of ten (10) items with scoring format (1) Strongly disagree (2) Disagree (3) Agree (4) Strongly agree It has reliability coefficient of 0.78.

The researchers personally distributed and collected a complete questionnaire from the participants. Permissions were obtained from the principals of the sampled schools after which the researchers with other research assistants administered the questionnaire on the participants. The concept of all the participants was also sought before administration. Maximum return was ensured. It took 3 weeks to administer this instrument. Relationship between the independent variables (Teaching Efficiency) and the dependent variables (job Satisfaction and School Climate) was ascertained using corresponding scores obtained from the variables and tested through Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient statistics, similarly, data on the predictive ability of the independent variables on the dependent variables was analyzed using multiple regression statistics. More so, the hypotheses were analyzed using ANOVA and T-Test. All analysis was carried out at 0.05 margin of error

Results

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between job satisfaction and teaching efficiency among secondary school teacher

Table 1: Pearson Product Moment correlation showing the relationship between satisfactions and teaching efficiency

Variables	Mean	S.D	r	P
Teaching efficiency	26.27	7.26	.42**	<.01
Job satisfaction	17.62	3.54		

** . Correlation is significant at 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The result from table one revealed that job satisfaction has a significant positive relationship with teaching efficiency ($r = .42$, $p < .01$)

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant relationship between school climate and teaching efficiency among secondary school teachers

Table 2: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Showing the Relationship between School Climate and Teaching Efficiency

Variables	Mean	S. D	R	P
Teaching efficiency	26.27	7.26		<.01

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School climate	94.98	20.88	.74**
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** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

It was revealed from table two that school climate has a positive relationship with teaching efficiency ($r = .74, p < .01$).

Hypothesis 3

School climate and job satisfaction has no significant influence on teaching efficiency among secondary school teacher

Table 3: Summary of Multiple Regression Analysis Showing the Influence of School Climate and Job Satisfaction on Teaching Efficiency among Secondary School Teachers

Predictors	B	T	P	R	R ²	F	P
School climate	.77	14.70	<.01	0.74	0.55	159.87	<.01
Job satisfaction	-.04	-.81	>.05				

The result from table three shows that school climate and job satisfaction jointly predicted teaching efficiency ($R^2 = 0.55, F(2,258) = 159.87, p < .01$). The result further revealed that school climate ($\beta = .77, t = 14.70, p < .01$) found to be significant independent predictor of teaching efficiency among secondary school teachers while job satisfaction ($\beta = -.04, t = -.81, p > .05$) had no significant independent prediction on teaching efficiency.

Discussion of Findings

The first hypothesis stated that, there is no significance relationship between job satisfaction and teaching efficiency among secondary school teachers. The results show that there was significant positive relationship between job satisfaction and teaching efficiency. This result implies that positive job satisfaction significantly relates to increase in teaching efficiency among secondary school teachers. The null hypothesis is thus rejected while the alternate hypothesis is accepted. The result is in line with study of Bandura and Ahmad (2019); Ibrahim (2015), which reported that the degree of employees' involvement in decision making at workplace has an impact on teachers' productivity. Amos (2018) emphasized that job satisfaction, that is, the attitudes and feelings that people has about their jobs, for Armstrong, positive or favorable attitude about the work and the work climate indicate job satisfaction. Brayfield and Crockett (2015) found that teachers with higher levels of job satisfaction have also been reported to have higher levels of teacher enthusiasm and self-efficiency (motivations). These are key factors that affect teachers' well-being and instructional behaviour as well as being influential in students' learning, motivational, and emotional outcomes. Given the important role that motivation plays in improving teachers' performance in the classroom, one of the most important variables that is thought to be linked to teachers' job satisfaction is their efficiency as teachers and how well they teach in the classroom.

The second hypothesis which stated that, there is no significant relationship between school climates and teaching efficiency among secondary school teachers, the result shows that there was significant positive relationship between school climate and teaching efficiency. The result implies that increase in better school climatic condition significantly relates to increase in the level of teaching efficiency and commitment. The null hypothesis is thus rejected while the alternate hypothesis is accepted. The result is in line with studies of Robbins (2019), Almond, (2015), Ibrahim and Awoyemi (2016). Robbins (2019) found that teachers with high sense of belonging to the school system and have more opportunity to participate among stakeholders are reported to have high self-efficiency which translates to high job satisfaction. On the other hand, teachers' perceived disciplinary climate has been reported to negatively impact self-efficiency which in turn translates to low job satisfaction (Bandura & Ahmad 2019; Adewale, 2018).

The third hypothesis stated that school climate and job satisfaction would jointly and independently predict teaching efficiency among secondary school teachers. The result revealed that school climate and job satisfaction jointly predicted teaching efficiency. When combined the school climate and job satisfaction accounted for 55% of the change observed in the teaching efficiency among secondary school teachers. This revealed that the collective presence of school climate and job satisfaction has significant influence on the teaching efficiency. The result further revealed that school climate found to be significant independent predictor of teaching efficiency among secondary school teachers while job satisfaction had no significant independent prediction on teaching efficiency. The hypothesis is therefore corroborates the studies by Amos, (2018). Adeyemi, (2015) connotes 'the beliefs that teachers have of their ability to enact certain teaching behaviour that influences students' educational outcomes, such as achievement, interest, and motivation'

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Conclusion

From the result of the findings, it was therefore concluded that job satisfaction had significant positive relationship with teaching efficiency among teachers sampled. Also, school climate had a significant positive relationship with teaching efficiency. Apparently, there was a joint contribution of job satisfaction and school climate on the teaching efficiency among teachers, whereas independently on school climate predicted teaching efficiency while job satisfaction had no significant independent prediction on teaching efficiency.

Recommendations

In order to positively overhaul, remove drastically alleviate the problems enumerated in the study, with a view to improve teachers' efficiency and raise the standard of education, the following recommendations are offered.

1. There should be adequate school plants. This includes school buildings, classrooms, laboratories, libraries, vocational workshops, furniture, laboratory equipment, instructional materials, play grounds etc. the Kebbi State government should provide the above named materials and facilities to meet the ever-growing students population
2. The Government should provide necessary incentives to arouse the interest of teachers in the teaching profession. Incentives like regular promotion, employment of experienced and qualify teachers, increment in salary and emoluments and opportunity for professional advancement to mention but a few
3. Funding of extra-curricular activities in the school. This will help arouse students' interest in schooling and thus change their negative activities in school. The literary and debating societies, jet clubs, vocational clubs, drama and cultural society, young farmers' club, boys and girls brigades, boys scout and girls guilds should be well funded by the government in our schools, to keep the students busy and prevent unwholesome activities such as truancy, cultism, rioting and hooliganism among the students
4. In order to encourage and motivate teachers to be more effective, it is suggested that the government, principals and parents' teachers' association (PTA) should constitute "Best Teacher Award" in our schools.
5. Teacher should be motivated to attend as many workshop and training programmes as possible through sponsorship. This will go a long way in improving and imparting better and in-depth knowledge in their subjects.
6. Merit promotion schemes for teachers may be introduced and implemented systematically, periodically and scientifically. This measure naturally motivates teachers to involve themselves actively in publishing books and articles besides research activities. Because education is the best legacy any parent can give to their children

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Impact of Joint Improvised Material on Creative-Thinking Originality among Mixed-Ability Upper Basic Science Students in Makurdi Metropolis

Ayua, Geoffrey Aondolumun¹

ayuageoffrey@gmail.com

Ikyernum, Gabriel Sesugh²

sesughgabriel05@gmail.com

Gwamna, Mariana Nenadi³

nenadi@gmail.com

Akaasah, Yvonne Yuadoo⁴

yakaasah@gmail.com

¹Department of Science & Mathematics Education, Benue State University, Makurdi, Nigeria

⁴Department of Chemistry, Benue State University, Makurdi, Nigeria

³Department of Special Needs Education, Kaduna State College of Education, Gidan Waya, Nigeria

²Department of Agricultural Technology, School of Applied Sciences, Federal Polytechnic, Ile-Oluji/Okeigbo, Ondo State, Nigeria

Abstract

Impact of Joint Improvised Material on Creative-Thinking Originality among mixed ability upper Basic Science students in Makurdi was studied using pre-test post-test quasi-experimental-control group research design. The study was guided by two research questions and corresponding hypotheses. The study's population was made up of 1337 (680 male and 657 female) Upper Basic II government secondary school in Makurdi metropolis. Fifty-two students (22 male & 30 female) constitute the sample size of the study. Hence, this was arrived at using multi stage sampling technique. Torrance Test of Creative Thinking with a reliability coefficient of 0.82 determined by a test-retest method was used for data collection. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and two-way Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). Findings showed no significant difference in creative-thinking originality among mixed ability students taught Basic Science using Joint Improvised Material and those taught using Teacher Improvised Material, $F_{(2, 45)} = 1.095$; $p = .343 > .05$. Although, there existed a significant difference in creative-thinking originality in favour of those taught using Joint Improvised Material, $F_{(1, 45)} = 61.438$; $p = .000 < .05$, no significant difference existed in the students' creative-thinking originality based on gender, $F_{(2, 45)} = 1.564$; $p = .220 > .05$. Therefore, it was concluded that, enhancing creative-thinking originality among students with different abilities can be achieved without any gender discrepancy by actively involving learners in the improvisation of instructional materials. Thus, Joint Improvisation Approach was recommended for teaching Basic Science in basic schools.

Keywords: Joint Improvised Material (JIM), Teacher Improvised Material (TIM), Creative-Thinking Originality, Mixed Ability and Gender

Introduction

In today's rapidly changing world, where innovation and adaptability are paramount, the role of creativity in education has never been more crucial. Education no longer solely revolves around the acquisition of knowledge; it must also empower students with the creative thinking skills necessary to navigate the complexities of the 21st century (Handayani et al., 2022; Nazhifah et al., 2023). To prepare learners for the ever-evolving challenges, fostering creativity within educational institutions has become imperative. Creativity not only equips students with the ability to adapt and innovate but also empowers them to think creatively and engage with the world in meaningful ways. Creativity in education sparks curiosity, fosters creative thinking, and nurtures problem-solving abilities, equipping students with the tools to confront novel challenges and envision innovative solutions (Akhshabi & Dortaj, 2022; Setyaningsih & Kustiana, 2023). This shift towards a more creative educational

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paradigm not only enhances individual growth but also cultivates a generation better prepared to shape a dynamic and ever-evolving global landscape of the current age.

Creativity in science education is contemporarily indispensable. Science is not merely about memorizing facts and formulas; it's about exploration, discovery, and innovation (Handayani et al., 2022; Tanjung et al., 2023). Fostering creativity in science education empowers students to ask questions, experiment, and think creatively, preparing them to tackle complex real-world challenges (Oliveira et al., 2021; Fatmawati et al., 2022). In a rapidly advancing scientific landscape, where interdisciplinary collaboration and novel solutions are essential, nurturing creativity ensures that the next generation of scientists can adapt, contribute, and lead in pushing the boundaries of knowledge and addressing pressing global issues through creativity.

Creativity is the human capacity to discover fresh solutions to challenges by leveraging our existing knowledge. It emerges from our awareness of an imbalance in the environment, leading to productive actions that defy established thought patterns and conventions, ultimately giving rise to novel outcomes, whether tangible objects or abstract mental and emotional constructs. (Apaydin, 2023; Balci et al., 2023). Creativity thus implies the act of turning new and imaginative ideas into reality. In our age, where information is developing and changing very rapidly, societies need individuals who are proactive, thinking creative, problem-solving, and constantly improving themselves in order to adapt to this change and development (Apaydin, 2023; Smare & Elfatih 2023). Therefore, this infers that in order to confirm a sustainable development, implementing innovative strategies aimed at nurturing creativity skills, particularly fostering creative thinking among learners becomes pertinent.

Creative thinking refers to the ability to generate diverse and numerous responses to a particular issue that increases the likely output of creative ideas (Aldossari, 2021; He & Wong, 2021; Tanjung et al., 2023). According to Ayua et al., (2023) Creative thinking is one's cognitive process to generate effective ideas in solving problems under certain aims and conditions. It is a positive action in stimulating brain function that can create a proper learning style. In whichever way one views creative thinking, it is generally considered as a process of thinking based on what has been or formed from the knowledge relationship with reality, which results in creating something new. Creative thinking skills are highly prized by nations, researchers, educators, and workplaces, motivating them to adopt inventive teaching strategies to bolster creativity. In alignment with this, the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013) in her national policy on education emphasizes the exposure of learners to Basic Science concepts to develop skills and knowledge necessary for meeting contemporary societal needs. This approach aims to cultivate the skills and knowledge essential for addressing the evolving demands of modern society. A fundamental goal of Basic Science education is to promote the development of creative thinking skills in learners, which is facilitated through the use of effective teaching and learning materials.

However, it is worth highlighting that research consistently emphasizes the insufficient access to instructional materials in Nigerian primary and secondary schools, as pointed out by the National Teachers' Institute (NTI) as cited in the work of Ikyernum et al., 2022. Frequently, the existing materials are insufficient or outdated, compelling educators to take on the task of implementing hands-on teaching strategies at the fundamental education level. In their role as facilitators of the teaching and learning process, teachers find themselves compelled to improvise and adapt to the tenets of Basic Science teaching as outlined by FRN (2013), ensuring effective classroom instruction even when confronted with a dearth of suitable teaching and learning resources.

Improvisation refers to selection or provision for something not readily available. It is the process by which educational materials can be designed and developed using locally available materials to meet specific instructional needs (Ayua et al., 2022; Ikyernum et al., 2022). To impart meaningful science education, especially at the basic school level, it is crucial to have sufficient teaching and learning materials. Unfortunately, Ayua (2021) reported that education is facing challenges due to inadequate funding and a growing student population, leading to difficulties in acquiring resources for practical demonstrations. Consequently, there arises a need to utilize local materials and improvise in the teaching and learning of Basic Science. This approach is essential as it aligns with Bruner's (1966) emphasis on learning through hands-on experiences and creative thinking, aided by the use of concrete objects. By incorporating these methods, Basic Science can become more engaging and relevant to students. Improvisation according to Ayua (2021) could be by substitution, modification and construction either solely by the teacher (Teacher Improvised Material) or by the combined efforts of the teacher and learners (Joint Improvised Material).

Teacher Improvised Material (TIM) refers to teaching aid(s) made by the teacher alone and brought to the classroom for Basic Science teaching. TIM is an improvisation approach that is teacher-based because learners are not involved in the process of producing the improvised instructional material(s) (Ikyernum et al., 2022). Joint Improvised Material (JIM) on the

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other hand refers to teaching aids that are collaboratively produced by both the teacher and the learners for the purpose of Basic Science teaching and learning (Ikyernum et al., 2022). This approach emphasizes the active involvement of both the teacher and the students in creating these materials. By adopting a joint improvisation method, students gain essential knowledge about the subject matter and are encouraged to think creatively even before the actual lessons take place. This process fosters a more engaging and interactive learning environment, allowing students to actively participate in their education and take ownership of their learning experiences. This paper will center its attention on these two improvisation techniques, with the objective of assessing their impact on creative-thinking originality of mixed-ability upper Basic Science learners.

In the realm of science education, creativity takes center stage as an indispensable catalyst for innovation and progress. The process of improvisation, fueled by creative thinking, plays a pivotal role in fostering deeper comprehension and engagement among learners. It empowers students to explore unfamiliar territories, experiment with new ideas, and adapt to evolving scientific challenges (Ikyernum et al., 2022). The integration of improvisation into the teaching and learning process is increasingly acknowledged as a means to cultivate and amplify creative thinking among students (Navarro, 2018). This approach not only equips students with essential skills for societal achievement but also serves as a catalyst for economic progress in our technology-driven 21st-century global landscape.

Consequently, it becomes crucial to prioritize the development of creative thinking and improvisation within educational settings, enabling students to thrive amid the dynamic and multifaceted challenges of our ever-evolving world. Creative thinking comprises five sub domains of fluency, originality, elaboration, resistance to premature closure and abstractness of titles (Tehemba et al., 2023). However, this paper focuses on creative-thinking originality.

Creative-thinking originality is the ability to remove the phrase, idea, or an idea to solve a problem or make a combination of parts or elements are unusual, unique, novel that had not occurred to anyone else or the ability to produce a definition of rare and original of ideas, ability to generate original ideas, techniques or design of the expression that is rarely encountered (Trisnayanti et al., 2020; Chua et al., 2020). Creative-thinking originality breeds creativity. Originality frequently stands out as one of the most commonly acknowledged aspects of creativity (Fontenot as cited in Terhemba et al., 2023). Originality can be seen in something as small as a unique idea produced in everyday life to something as big as unconventional scientific progress (Terhemba et al., 2023). Creative-thinking originality holds significant importance in the realm of creativity, as it plays a pivotal role in nurturing valuable ideas. These ideas, in turn, provide individuals with the essential competences necessary to excel in contemporary societies fueled by creativity. Empirically, Empirically, Özgenel et al., (2019) and Chua et al., (2020) in their respective studies on creative thinking found that there was a significant increase in creative thinking originality after students were exposed to the enriched trainings to foster creative thinking skills. Likewise, Ng and Lee (2019) in their study “assessment of creative thinking of Hong Kong undergraduate students using the Torrance Tests of Creative Thinking” found that learners’ creative-thinking originality scores were well above average. In contrast, Trisnayanti et al., (2020) found no significant improvement in the creative thinking originality scores of learners as originality scores had the lowest percentage value of all the five sub domains of creative thinking. In the same vein, Fatmawati et al., (2022) reported no significant treatment effect on creative-thinking originality scores after learners were exposed to Creative Problem-Solving based Learning. Though the studies assessed the creative-thinking originality of learners, they however were not concerned with creative-thinking originality as an aspect of creative thinking in relation to improvisation across mixed ability learners.

Ability in this research refers to the different educational performance levels of students in Basic Science, which can be categorized as high, average, or low based on their past academic scores. Maikano as cited in Ikyernum, et al., (2022) suggests that ability grouping is determined by educators' assessments of students' abilities. When assigning students to different tracks, their prior test scores or performance measures from previous grades or schools are considered to determine their ability levels. Students' ability levels for the study were guided by Benue State Ministry of Education – BSME (2021) and Benue State Examinations Board – BSEB (2019) grading system for basic schools. Based on the grading system, High Ability Level (A = 75-100% and B = 65-74%), Average Ability Level (C = 55-64% and D = 45-54%) and Low Ability Level (E = 40-44% and F = 0-39%). By using this grading system, the researchers were able to distinguish and group students based on their academic ability levels in Basic Science. Empirically, Ikyernum et al., (2022) in their study “Effect of teacher-learner improvised material on creative thinking among mixed ability upper Basic Science students in Makurdi metropolis” established that the level of creative thinking among mixed ability students was significantly enhanced without gender disparity as a result of learners' active involvement in the improvisation of instructional materials. However, Setyaningsih and Kustiana (2023) in their study “Analysis of Students' Creative Thinking Ability in Solving HOTS Problems Viewed from Numeration Ability” established that learners mathematical creative-thinking originality is dependent on their numerical abilities; as learners with average and low numerical abilities could not achieve creative-thinking originality in Solving HOTS Problems. These studies

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however were not concerned with creative-thinking originality in relation to improvisation and did not tell whether a difference existed in creative-thinking originality based on gender as a result of learners' involvement in improvisation of instructional materials.

Gender differences encompass the characteristics associated with being male or female, man or woman, boy or girl. Research by Danjuma (as cited in Ayua, 2021) indicates that these gender disparities have a worldwide impact, particularly in Africa, by hindering the equal participation of boys and girls in Science Education. Consequently, these gender-specific factors influence the teaching, learning, and creative thinking of students in Basic Science. Empirically, Ulger and Morsunbul (2017); Zhang et al., (2020), in their respective studies on differences in creative thinking found that a significant difference existed in creative thinking abilities between males and females in favour of females. However, Ayua and Agbidye (2020); He and Wong (2021); Ayua et al (2022) and Terhemba et al. (2023) found no significant difference between boys and girls in the level of entrepreneurial creativity, divergent thinking and problem-solving skills, creative thinking, and creative-thinking originality respectively. However, none of the studies were concerned with creative-thinking originality as an aspect of creative thinking in relation to improvisation. That is why impact of joint improvisation on creative-thinking originality among mixed ability upper Basic Science students is pertinent.

In the contemporary era, characterized by remarkable scientific and technological advancements, the educational landscape has witnessed profound transformations. These shifts, attributed to the knowledge revolution and rapid technological progress, underscore the paramount importance of nurturing creativity skills in an ever-evolving world. To effectively navigate this dynamic environment, educational leaders must realign their strategies to align with these transformative trends. This is particularly relevant for upper Basic Science students, who must cultivate creative-thinking abilities for both academic and professional success. One promising avenue for fostering creativity is through improvisation. By encouraging spontaneous thinking, imaginative problem-solving, adaptability, and unconventional approaches, improvisation holds the potential to ignite creativity. However, there is a need to explore in-depth the extent to which improvisation techniques can effectively enhance the creative-thinking originality among upper Basic Science students. This study aims to investigate the impact of implementing improvisation techniques on learners' creative-thinking originality in the context of Basic Science education. By examining the practical application of improvisation in the classroom, this research seeks to provide insights into its viability as a means to nurture creative-thinking originality in students. This investigation addresses the pressing demand to cultivate creativity skills in today's educational landscape and offers valuable insights into how improvisation can serve as a catalyst for enhancing creative-thinking originality among 21st-century learners.

Objectives of the Study

Specifically, the study seeks to:

17. To determine the mean creative-thinking originality scores of students taught Basic Science using Joint Improvised Material and those taught using Teacher Improvised Material
18. To find out the mean creative-thinking originality scores among mixed ability male and female students taught Basic Science using Joint Improvised Material-

Research Questions

14. What is the mean difference in creative-thinking originality scores among mixed ability students taught Basic Science using Joint Improvised Material and those taught using Teacher Improvised Material?
15. What is the mean difference in creative-thinking originality scores among mixed ability male and female students taught Basic Science using Joint Improvised Material?

Hypotheses

- There is no significant difference in mean creative-thinking originality scores among mixed ability students taught Basic Science using Joint Improvised Material and those taught using Teacher Improvised Material.
- There is no significant difference in mean creative-thinking originality scores among mixed ability male and female students taught Basic Science using Joint Improvised Material.

Methodology

A pre-test post-test quasi-experimental-control group design was used for this study. After pre-test administration, the experimental group of an intact class of 1:24 was taught concept of work, energy and power with 5 lesson plans using demonstration method blended with Joint Improvised Materials (wooden toy car and wooden electric fan) constructed through active involvement of learners together with the teacher using procedures outlined in the lesson plans; while the control group

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was taught the same concept using same method blended with Teacher Improvised Materials. This treatment lasted for five weeks. Thereafter, the students in both groups were given post-test. Students mixed ability were based on previous term's performance grades (high = A/B; average = C/D; low = E/F). Fifty-two (22 male & 30 female) students constitute the sample size of the study. Hence, this was arrived at using multi stage sampling technique from the population of 1337 (680 males and 657 females) Upper Basic II students in all the 21 secondary schools (Teaching Service Board Makurdi, 2021) Torrance Test of Creative Thinking (TTCT-Figural B) was used for data collection. Section "A" collected students' biodata; while section 'B' had three activities each lasting for 10 minutes with the opportunity for multiple responses of ideas, to test students' creative-thinking originality in Basic Science. TTCT-Figural B was validated and trial-tested with a reliability coefficient of 0.82 determined by a test-retest method with Pearson Product Moment Correlation. Extraneous variables like group initial difference, group interaction effect and priming were controlled by homogeneity test, distant locations and impromptu tests respectively. Both pre-test and post-test were administered under standard examination conditions. The research questions were answered using mean and hypotheses were tested at 0.05 α -level using a two-way Analysis of covariance due to normality of the distribution, homogeneity of variance, randomness of selection, measurement based on interval scale and independence of samples.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the mean difference in creative-thinking originality scores among mixed ability students taught Basic Science using Joint Improvised Material and those taught using Teacher Improvised Material?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Creative-Thinking Originality Scores of Students Taught Using Joint Improvised Material and Teacher Improvised Material.

Ability Level	N	Group	Pre-TTCT		Post-TTCT		Mean Gain	Mean Gain difference
			\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD		
High	12	TIM	2.01	0.620	3.35	0.996	1.34	2.44
	10	JIM	2.27	0.726	6.05	1.202	3.78	
Average	8	TIM	2.35	1.078	3.11	0.806	0.76	1.97
	7	JIM	2.30	0.166	5.03	1.053	2.73	
Low	8	TIM	1.79	0.669	2.35	0.930	0.56	3.14
	7	JIM	1.84	0.207	5.54	1.398	3.70	
Cluster		TIM	2.05		2.94		0.89	2.52
		JIM	2.13		5.54		3.41	

Table 1 shows homogeneity in the pre-test mean scores among mixed ability between experimental and control group with cluster means of 2.13 and 2.05. The table also shows that creative-thinking originality mean scores among mixed ability in the experimental group were higher than those in the control group with cluster mean gain difference of 2.52.

Research Question 2

What is the mean difference in creative-thinking originality scores among mixed ability male and female students taught Basic Science using Joint Improvised Material?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Creative-Thinking Originality Scores of Male and Female Students Taught Using Joint Improvised Material

Ability Level	Gender	N	Pre-TTCT		Post-TTCT		Mean Gain	Mean Gain Difference
			\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD		
High	Male	7	2.38	0.701	4.80	1.184	2.42	0.72
	Female	3	1.87	0.548	3.57	1.657	1.70	
Average	Male	2	1.99	0.953	4.01	1.040	2.20	0.83
	Female	5	2.63	1.155	4.00	1.622	1.37	
Low	Male	2	2.00	0.000	4.00	2.160	1.80	

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	Female	5	1.75	0.566	3.78	2.257	2.03	0.23
Cluster	Male		2.12		4.27		2.15	
	Female		2.08		3.78		1.70	0.45

Table 2 shows homogeneity in the pre-test mean scores between male and female in the experimental group with cluster means of 2.12 and 2.08. Likewise, the table also shows that the creative-thinking originality mean scores in the post-test was higher than those in the pre-test in both male and female with cluster mean gains of 2.15 and 1.70 respectively

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant mean difference in creative-thinking originality scores among mixed ability students taught Basic Science using Joint Improvised Material and those taught using Teacher Improvised Material.

Table 3: Summary of Two-way ANCOVA Results of Creative-Thinking Originality Test Scores of Students Based on Improvisation Technique

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	98.200 ^a	6	16.367	12.054	.000	.616
Intercept	85.353	1	85.353	62.863	.000	.583
TTCT_pretest	1.035	1	1.035	.763	.387	.017
Ability_Level	5.792	2	2.896	2.133	.130	.087
Improvisation_Technique	83.418	1	83.418	61.438	.000	.577
Ability_Level * Improvisation_Technique	2.974	2	1.487	1.095	.343	.046
Error	61.100	45	1.358			
Total	1076.580	52				
Corrected Total	159.300	51				

a. R Squared = .616 (Adjusted R Squared = .565)

Table 3 shows no significant difference in the creative-thinking originality scores among mixed ability students taught Basic Science using TIM and those taught using JIM, $F_{(2,45)} = 1.095$; $p = .343 > .05$. The null hypothesis was therefore not rejected. However, the result also showed that students' creative-thinking originality scores in the experimental group was better than those in the control group, $F_{(1,45)} = 61.438$; $p = .000 < .05$. This implies that, although Joint Improvised Material (JIM) enhances creative-thinking originality, it is not dependent on students' academic abilities.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant mean difference in creative-thinking originality scores among mixed ability male and female students taught Basic Science using Joint Improvised Material

Table 4. Summary of Two-way ANCOVA Results of Creative-Thinking Originality Scores of Male and Female Students Taught Using Joint Improvised Material

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	28.549 ^a	6	4.758	1.638	.159	.179
Intercept	76.865	1	76.865	26.454	.000	.370
TTCT_pretest	.572	1	.572	.197	.659	.004
Ability_Level	4.641	2	2.321	.799	.456	.034
Gender	6.247	1	6.247	2.150	.150	.046
Ability_Level * Gender	9.091	2	4.546	1.564	.220	.065
Error	130.751	45	2.906			
Total	1076.580	52				
Corrected Total	159.300	51				

a. R Squared = .179 (Adjusted R Squared = .070)

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Table 4 showed no significant difference in the creative-thinking originality scores between male and female mixed ability students taught Basic Science using Teacher-Learner Improvised Material, $F_{(2, 45)} = 1.564$; $p = .220 > .05$. The null hypothesis was therefore not rejected. This implies that, Joint Improvised Material is gender unbiased; hence it enhanced creative-thinking originality in both male and female mixed ability Basic Science students.

Discussion of Findings

Concerning students' creative-thinking originality based on involving them in improvising instructional materials, it was found that significant difference existed in creative- thinking originality between students in the control and experimental groups in favour of those in the experimental group. However, among the ability levels there existed no significant difference in creative-thinking originality. Following field experience, the finding of this study is not odd because during the construction process, students were given ample opportunity to fully express their open-mindedness towards production of novel, unique and uncommon ideas and converting same into meaningful and scintillating materials or objects which thus entail creative-thinking originality. This finding is similar with Özgenel et al., (2019) who found that there was a significant increase in creative-thinking originality after students were exposed to the enriched training to foster creative thinking. The finding also agrees with that of Ng & Lee (2019) who established that learners' creative-thinking originality was well above average. However, the finding does not only contrast with, but is a potential solution to those of Trisnayanti et al., (2020) and Fatmawati et al., (2022) who found no significant improvement in the creative thinking originality after learners were exposed to creative thinking enhancement programmes. The indifference among mixed ability students in creative-thinking originality as found out, is similar to the finding of Ikyernum, et al. (2022) of no significant difference in creative thinking among varied ability students. However, the finding does not only differ slightly with, but is also a potential solution to the finding of Setyaningsih and Kustiana (2023) who found that learners mathematical creative-thinking originality is dependent on their numerical abilities; as leaners with average and low numerical abilities could not achieve creative-thinking originality in Solving HOTS Problems.

Regarding students' creative-thinking originality based on gender, it was discovered that no significant difference existed in creative-thinking originality between male and female mixed ability students taught Basic Science using Joint Improvised Material. Thus, involving students in the improvisation of instructional materials to enhance their creative-thinking originality is gender unbiased. This finding is similar to those of Ayua and Agbidye (2020); He and Wong (2021); Ayua et al., (2022) and Terhemba et al., (2023) who found no significant difference between boys and girls in the level of entrepreneurial creativity, divergent thinking and problem-solving skills, creative thinking, and creative-thinking originality respectively. This finding however does not only differ but also is solution to Ulger and Morsunbul (2017), Zhang et al., (2020) who found out that a significant difference existed between females and males upon creative thinking in favour of females.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it was concluded that: Creative-thinking originality among varied ability students can be enhanced without gender discrepancy if learners are actively involved in the improvisation of instructional materials.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made to effectively implement this approach:

- Joint Improvisation approach should be adopted in teaching Basic Science.
- School administrators should encourage researchers to organize workshops on the use of Joint Improvisation.
- Ministries of Education and teacher training institutions in Nigeria should ensure in-service training and retraining of teachers on Joint Improvisation.
- School proprietors, heads and parents' teachers' association should materially/financially support Joint Improvisation in Basic Science.

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Perceived Influence of Educational Media on Academic Performance among Secondary School Teachers and Students in Oyo East Local Government Area, Oyo State

Ojo, Oloyede Akinniyi¹

Email: dr.oloyedeojo@gmail.com

Tel: 08030744727

Adesipe, Muyiwa Adedayo

Email: muyiwaadesipe78@gmail.com

Tel: 08062664992

¹Faculty of Specialized and Professional Education, Emmanuel Alayande University of Education, Oyo, Oyo State, Nigeria

²Faculty of Education, Ekiti State University, Ado Ekiti, Ekiti State.

Abstract

This study assessed the educational media on academic performance among secondary school students. A descriptive survey research design was used. The population entails all the teaching staff and 2021/2022 Junior Secondary School students at public secondary schools in Oyo East Local Government, Oyo State. The study consists of 160 respondents (80 teachers & 80 students), this was arrived at by randomly selecting four public secondary schools using purposive sampling techniques. Educational Media and Academic Performance Questionnaire (EMAP) developed by researcher with reliability coefficient of 0.75 using the test-retest method. Descriptive and correlation statistical tools was used. Results revealed that 54(67.5%) agreed, 14(17.5%) strongly agreed that any lesson taught with educational media are remembered easily. Again, 42(52.5%) disagreed while 19(23.8%) strongly disagreed that the use of educational media prevents teacher's full class control. The highest mean value on student response was 3.51 while the highest standard deviation was 0.874. Results on teachers' response shows 42(52.5%) and 27 (33.8%) agreed and strongly agreed respectively that the use of educational media aids students' comprehension in learning. The highest mean value of teachers' responses 3.49, 3.48, 3.40, 3.27, and 3.24 was indicated in items 7,8,5,1, and 10 respectively while the standard deviation ascendingly ranges from 0.935, 0.8n78, 0.876, 0.868 and 0.853 as revealed in item 2,3,9,4 and 6 respectively. It was concluded that governmental, non-governmental, and professional organizations should help the schools provide educational media and recommended that state secondary schools must all have educational media centers installed in the schools.

Keywords: Educational Media, Academic Performance, Computer Assisted Instruction & Students

Introduction

The availability of educational media significantly improved the academic performance of secondary school students. Educational media covers all the tools and tangible resources a teacher could employ to carry out a lesson plan and help pupils meet learning goals. Since instructors became the major method of delivering instruction to students in the 1900s, educational media have existed. According to Duban (2019), the first school museum was established in St. Louis in 1905. Museums had supplementary educational resources that might help teachers when instructing various subjects. The first collection of instructional movies was created in 1910 for use in classrooms. In 1913, Thomas Edison stated, "Books in schools will soon be obsolete. In due course, education for students will be visual. With the help of a movie, you can instruct students in every field of study. Also, Usman & Madudili (2020) affirmed that researchers at IBM began to use computers in the 1950s and the first CAI application to be utilized in public schools was created by the researchers, who also created the Computer Assisted Instruction (CAI) author language. The majority of computer usage in primary schools was for drills and practice or for teaching student's computer-related skills like typing. However, it took until the 1980s for computers to gain widespread use as a teaching tool and this made it imperative to teach virtually all the subjects with the aid of using educational media.

Njoroge (2019) defines educational media as both print and nonprint materials that are intended to influence students' access to knowledge during the educational process. Print, textbooks, magazines, newspapers, presentations, photos, workbooks, and electronic media are only a few examples of the materials used in educational media. The use of educational media in the teaching-learning process is crucial. The availability of textbooks, proper chalkboards, math and science kits,

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teaching guides, science guides, audio-visual aids, overhead projectors, and other educational materials are crucial (Bukoyo 2019) However, practically all the state's secondary schools lack several amenities. The textbook is the first educational medium, claims Kamba (2019). Numerous definitions of a textbook emphasize its value as a teaching tool. The foundation of every learning activity connected to a certain curriculum is the textbook. The significance of textbooks in educating pupils in developing nations is crucial.

Ritakumari (2019) ascertained that there are numerous benefits to educational media in terms of reproducibility, portability, and improved equity access. Additionally, as they aid students in higher knowledge acquisition, educational media support teachers in their ability to impart knowledge in an impressive manner, improving the effectiveness of learning. Educational media is one of the factors that affect learning, therefore students who have access to information will study more ardently and be motivated (Puspitanni, & Hanif 2019) All the tools and physical equipment a teacher could employ to carry out a lesson plan and assist pupils in meeting their academic goals are referred to as educational media. In addition to more modern tools and materials like computers, DVDs, CD-ROMs, the internet, and interactive video conferencing, this may also include conventional tools e.g. charts, slides, overheads, real objects, etc. Diverse definitions exist for the phrase "educational media." In some circumstances, it alludes to the tools that instructors and students both employ. Other times, it solely refers to tools and resources utilized in the teaching and learning processes, such as printed materials or devices. According to Chand, Chaudhary Prasad & Chand (2021) educational media is a system component that may be used in the educational process and is used to distribute educational messages and ideas or to enable communication throughout the teaching and learning process.

The term "educational media" describes forms of media that disseminate information for educational purposes. Without functional educational media to support inventive output in contemporary disciplines like science and technology, among others, effective instruction could not be possible. Idris (2018) claimed that regardless of a child's moral, mental, emotional, or psychological state of health, education is the key to a nation's true growth and progress. In the Universal Basic Education curriculum teachers are also expected to use a variety of high-quality educational media for effective and efficient teaching and learning activities in the classroom. Ritakumari (2019) listed a few factors that teachers should take into account before choosing educational media.

Firstly, the learner's age and abilities should be considering, the teacher must be very careful to take the kids' ages and skills into consideration. The purpose of educational media is to enhance learning and not to hamper it in any way, therefore, the process and procedure for selection should be germane and effective for successful outcome. Secondly, Educational media must be relevant to the lesson objectives; one of the major stages of teaching and learning is stating of educational objectives which will later determine the outcome of that lesson at the evaluation stage, to ascertain the attainment of the lesson objectives, there is need to ensure that the selected educational media is relevant to the lesson. Thirdly, informational currency: Any instructional media that is appropriate for use in the classroom must be up to date. Despite the desire for technological advancement, secondary school topics are crucial to it, and as a result, their teaching and learning, as well as students' subpar academic performance, have become a sort of source of concern for all parties involved. Ritakumari (2019) asserts that the following aspects of educational media are relevant:

1. The foundation of the educational system is the teacher. High-quality teaching and learning processes are maintained with the support of qualified teachers. The high results are then impacted by this. Leaders provide an example of how to execute the curriculum both within and outside of the classroom. The manner that which technology is used and integrated into the teaching and learning process is significantly impacted by its deployment.
2. Different educational media and multimedia technologies are currently used in teaching and learning processes. These include computer systems, microphones, mobile devices, interactive whiteboards, digital-video-on-demand, online media streams, digital games, podcasts, and more.
3. Educational media support the teaching and learning process from the lesson's introduction to its evaluation, or from beginning to end. It offers tangible experiences that act as a foundation for thinking, arguing, and problem-solving. It improves both initial learning and learning retention.
4. The modern educational system is heavily reliant on computers. Internet research is more convenient for students than browsing through thick books. Learning now extends beyond textbooks to the internet, where there is a wealth of knowledge.
5. Education now extends well beyond the four walls of the classroom. Due to computers and the internet, locations that were once far apart have become closer. Information presentation has gotten simpler; this has made audio-visual representation of information easier and made teaching and learning more engaging.

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6. A computer system enables a teacher to showcase a new lesson, animate, present new materials, demonstrate how to use new applications, and display new websites in the classroom. Microphones can be employed in the teaching and learning process in a noisy classroom.
7. Mobile devices such as clickers or smartphones can be utilised in enhancing feedback activities during and after instruction delivery by the teacher. An interactive whiteboard provides touch control of computer applications which enhance the experience in the by displaying visuals that can be viewed on a wider screen by learners. This assist in visual learning, and interactivity for learners to draw, write or manipulate images on the interactive whiteboard.
8. With digital video, there is no longer a need for hardware players in the classroom, and both instructors and students can instantly view video content without a connection to the internet. Online media streams can improve classroom teaching and learning procedures on websites that stream video. The use of the digital game, which encourages students to learn the topic at hand, is growing daily. Podcasts are a relatively innovation and are a popular medium for accessing and consuming audio and video content. Computer and telecommunications system integration is known as video conferencing.

The use of educational media in teaching and learning is necessary for effective and high-quality instruction. In Nigeria and all other African nations, secondary schools' education must properly guide in order to improve academic achievement. Therefore this, study assessed the Educational Media on Academic Performance among secondary school students in Oyo East Local Government Area of Oyo state.

Objectives of the study:

1. To examine the student's response to the assessment of educational media on Academic Performance?
2. To determine the teacher's responses to the assessment of educational media on Academic Performance?
3. To find the significant relationship between the response of the students and the teachers on the assessment of educational media on Academic Performance.
4. To elicits the different between the response of the students and the teachers on the assessment of educational media on Academic Performance.

Research Questions:

1. What is the student's response to the assessment of educational media on Academic Performance?
2. What are the teacher's responses to the assessment of educational media on Academic Performance?

Research Hypothesis

1. There is no significant relationship between the response of the students and the teachers on the assessment of educational media on Academic Performance.
2. There is significant different between the response of the students and the teachers on the assessment of educational media on Academic Performance.

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive research design. The population entails all the teaching staff and 2021/2022 Junior Secondary School students at public secondary schools in Oyo East Local Government, Oyo State. The study consists of 160 respondents (80 teachers & 80 students), this was arrived at by randomly selecting four public secondary schools in Oyo East local government using purposive sampling techniques. Educational Media and Academic Performance Questionnaire (EMAPQ) developed by researcher with reliability coefficient of 0.75 using the test-retest method. The researchers visited the chosen school twice, the first time was to see the principal for the briefing on the research study and to seek for permission for the use of the school. After the proper documentation and the appropriate approval, all the 80 students and 80 teachers randomly chosen in the four schools were asked to respond to the questions on the instrument that was made available to them for the study. They received guarantees that all the information would be kept completely private and used only for study. All the instruments were properly filled and returned on the spot. This research used descriptive statistical method such as frequency and percentage to examine the influence of instructional media on academic performances of secondary school students of public schools. Also, the correlation was conducted to establish the relationship between the teacher's response and the student's response.

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Results

Research Question 1

What are the student's responses to the assessment of educational media on Academic Performance?

Table 1: Students Response

S/N	ITEMS	Strongly Agreed	Agreed	Disagreed	Strongly Disagreed	Mean	Standard Deviation
1	I noticed improvement in my academic performance especially subject taught with Educational Media	21 (26.3)	43 (57.%)	10 (12.5%)	06 (7.5%)	3.44	.624
2	I easily remembered any lesson taught with the aid of Educational Media	14 (17.5)	54 (67.%)	07 (8.8%)	05 (6.3%)	3.24	.784
3	I hardly understand some subjects without the aid of Educational Media	18 (22.5)	33 (41.%)	21 (26.3%)	08 (10%)	2.78	.874
4	There is no difference in my academic performance with the use of Educational Media	29 (36.3)	33 (41.%)	14 (17.5%)	04 (5%)	3.25	.702
5	Educational Media affected my performance poorly because it confuses me	11 (13.8)	24 (30%)	39 (48.8%)	06 (7.5%)	2.56	.842
6	The use of educational media helps my retentive ability	19 (23.8)	49 (61.%)	07 (8.8%)	05 (6.3%)	3.37	.594
7	The use of educational media catches my attention in the class.	12 (15%)	44 (55%)	13 (16.3%)	11 (13.8%)	3.17	.687
8	My academic performance improves whenever the use of educational media was adopted	29 (36.3)	41 (51.%)	03 (3.8%)	07 (8.8%)	3.51	.524
9	The use of educational media do not allows the teacher to have full class control.	11 (13.8)	08 (10%)	42 (52.5%)	19 (23.8%)	2.20	.858
10	I always prefer educational media teaching to a non-educational media teaching	27 (33.8)	42 (52.%)	08 (10%)	03 (3.8%)	3.24	.783

Sources: Data Collection by Researcher

This table shows the student's response to the assessment of educational media on Academic Performance.

Research Question 2

What are the teacher's responses to the assessment of educational media on Academic Performance?

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Table 2: Teacher’s responses to the assessment of educational media on Academic Performance

S/N	ITEMS	Strongly Agreed	Agreed	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean	Standard Deviation
1	My students’ performance has improved since we started using Media	17 (21.3)	46 (57.%)	07 (8.8%)	10 (12.5%)	3.27	.702
2	Educational media is only good to teach some selected topics	12 (15%)	16 (20%)	38 (47.5%)	14 (17.5%)	2.15	.935
3	The students’ performance in competitions with other schools has improved since Educational Medias is in place	18 (22.5)	43 (53.%)	11 (13.8%)	08 (10.%)	2.64	.878
4	There is no difference in performance of the student with or without Educational Media	09 (11.3%)	13 (16.%)	38 (47.5%)	20 (25%)	2.20	.868
5	Educational media is a tool for effective teaching and learning process	21 (26.3)	43 (53.%)	11 (13.8%)	05 (6.3%)	3.40	.635
6	I do not enjoy teaching without educational media	11 (13.8)	13 (16.%)	32 (40%)	24 (30%)	2.40	.853
7	Special training is required in using educational media to teach	18 (22.5)	44 (55%)	10 (12.5%)	08 (10%)	3.49	.586
8	The use of educational media aid students’ comprehension in learning	27 (33.8)	42 (52.%)	05 (6.3%)	06 (7.5%)	3.48	.566
9	Educational media are difficult to handle for teaching and learning process	14 (17.5)	28 (35%)	25 (31.3%)	13 (16.3%)	2.78	.876
10	The use of educational media for teaching and learning is time consuming	23 (28.8)	40 (50%)	07 (8.8%)	10 (12.5%)	3.24	.784

Sources: Data Collection by Researcher

Table 2 shows the teacher's response to the assessment of educational media on Academic Performance.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between the response of the students and the teachers on the assessment of educational media on Academic Performance.

Table 3: This table shows the result of the correlation between the response of the students and the teachers on the assessment of educational media on Academic Performance.

	N	Total Mean	Average Mean	Total Standard Deviation	Average Standard Deviation
Students Response	80	30.76	3.08	7.272	0.73
Teachers Response	80	29.05	2.91	6.981	0.70

Table 3 shows the value of students' and teachers' responses in terms of mean and standard deviation, the total mean of the student's response and teachers' response totaling 30.76 (3.08) and 29.05 (2.91) respectively while the standard deviation revealed a total of 7.272 (0.73) and 6.981 (0.70). it was noticed from the results that both students and teachers have similar opinions on the influence of educational media on students' academic performance since the mean and standard deviation have a close range of differences.

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Hypothesis 2

There is significant different between the response of the students and the teachers on the assessment of educational media on Academic Performance.

Table 3 Correlations

		Sum (Students)	Sum (Teachers)
Sum (Students)	Pearson Correlation	1	0.191
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.183
	N	79	80
Sum (Teachers)	Pearson Correlation	0.191	0
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.183	
	N	80	80

There is strong positive relationship between the student response and teachers' response and is statistically significant $r(80) = 0.18, p=0.19$. Hence, the correlation between the students' response and that of their teachers is significant. Therefore, Null Hypothesis two (H_{02}) was rejected.

Table 4: t-Test: Paired Two Sample for Means

	Students	Teachers
Mean	3.08	2.91
Variance	4.564898	4.473877551
Observation	80	80
Pearson Correlation	0.191294	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
Df	79	
t Stat	1.516912	
P (T<=t) one tail	0.067857	
T Critical one tail	1.676551	
P (T<=t) one tail	0.135715	
t Critical two-tail	2.009575	

The p -value is 0.135715 greater than 0.05 alpha level, we reject the H_{02} . Hence, there is no significant different between the students and the teachers' responses.

Discussion of Findings

Table 1a revealed the student's opinions on the four likert scale namely Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD) in respect to each of the statements in the influence of educational media on the secondary school students' academic performance in Oyo east local government area of oy state. The table indicated their perspectives in frequency and percentage shown in the bracket. Moreover, mean value and the standard deviation for each of the statements was also calculated and presented. The student's opinion about 8 out of the 10 items has the highest rating value as majority of them either strongly agreed or agreed. 54 (67.5%) agreed and 14 (17.5%) out of 80 respondents strongly agreed that they easily remembered any lesson taught with educational media. Also 49 (61.3%) accepted to agree while 19 (23.8%) strongly agreed that the use of educational media helps their retentive ability. Moreover, 41 (51.3%) respondents, 29 (36.3%) believed their academic performance improves whenever the use of educational media was adopted. On the contrary, a few numbers of respondents also either strongly disagreed or disagreed with certain statement, for example 42 (52.5%) totally disagreed while 19 (23.8%) joined to strongly disagreed that the use of educational media do not allow teachers to have full class control during teaching and learning process. In addition, 39 (48.8%) disagreed and 6 (7.5%) strongly disagreed that educational media affected their performance poorly because it causes confusion in learning. The highest mean value was 3.51 on item 8 which stated that academic performance improves when educational media is used while the highest standard deviation value was 0.874 on item 3 that they hardly understand some subjects without the use of educational media.

This table 1b presented the Teacher's opinion in respect to each of the statements in the influence of educational media in the secondary school students' academic performance in Oyo East local government area. The table shows their perspectives both in frequency and percentage in bracket under the heading Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly

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Disagree (SD). It also shows the mean value and the standard deviation (SD) for each of the statements. The highest value of 46 (57.5%) where the teachers agreed that students' academic performance improved since they started using educational media in teaching. Another statement of interest was found in no 8, the results shows that 42 (52.5%) and 27 (33.8%) were agreed and strongly agreed respectively that the use of educational media aid students' comprehension in learning. Furthermore, 44 (55%) agreed and 18 (22.5%) strongly agreed that special training is required in using educational media to teach. 40 (50%) and 23 (28.8%) respondents both agreed and strongly agreed respectively in their responses that the use of educational media for teaching and learning is time consuming. Although, a total of 56 (70%) were either disagreed or strongly disagreed that they do not enjoy teaching without educational media as stated on item 6, this revealed that they still enjoy teaching with or without educational media. Another statement in this dimension was stated in item 2 that educational media is only good to teach some selected topics, no fewer than 52 (67.5%) either disagreed or strongly disagreed, they believed that there is no topic that cannot be taught with educational media. The highest mean value of 3.49, 3.48, 3.40, 3.27 and 3.24 was indicated in item 7,8,5,1, and10 respectively while the standard deviation ascendingly ranges from 0.935, 0.878, 0.876, 0.868 and 0.853 as revealed in item 2,3,9,4 and 6 respectively.

Table 2 shows the value of students' and teachers' responses in terms of mean and standard deviation, the total mean of the student's response and teachers' response totaling 30.76 (3.08) and 29.05 (2.91) respectively while the standard deviation revealed a total of 7.272 (0.73) and 6.981 (0.70). it was noticed from the results that both students and teachers have similar opinions on the influence of educational media on students' academic performance since the mean and standard deviation have a close range of differences.

Conclusion

The secondary level of education is crucial because it serves as both a transitional period between primary and university education and the foundation of the labor force in the nation. In order to achieve the intended objectives, it is required to create a body that will be in charge of its efficient implementation process. Any less will result in the secondary education system consistently producing mediocre work that will exacerbate Nigeria's economic, social, and political issues. The conclusion that can be drawn from the examination of the data is that the use of educational media can improve the teaching and learning process. The use of print and electronic media in the classroom will improve secondary school pupils' academic performance. Given this, governmental, non-governmental, and professional organizations should help the schools provide educational media. In the event that the necessary materials are not accessible, teachers occasionally have to improvise.

Recommendations

1. As educational media are generally helpful to students' academic progress, secondary school teachers are rapidly becoming more aware of their use. It is crucial that the proper arrangements be established for its provision and utilization as a result.
2. Governments or management organizations should make a greater effort to supply schools with crucial instructional material and to hire qualified professionals who can make the most use of it.
3. The government should also regularly organize workshops and training sessions on how to use educational media in teaching and learning.
4. The state's secondary schools must all have educational media centers installed; this will inspire both students and teachers to enhance the teaching and learning process.
5. Good academic performance as a result of the use of educational media should be praised, and teachers should be encouraged to use it to educate in the classroom.
6. Teachers or subject-matter experts should instruct students on the creation and improvisation of instructional media.
7. The maintenance and storage of educational media should be handled appropriately.

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Physical Resources Utilization as Correlates of Job Performance among Secondary School Teachers in Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria

Adedeji, Israel Olusegun

Email: segdeji2014@gmail.com+2348038093496

Department of Educational Foundations, School of Education, Federal College of Education (Technical) Gusau

Abstract

This study investigated physical resources utilization as correlates of job performance among secondary school teachers in Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria. This study examined the extent to which the available physical plant, printed and non-printed resources are utilized in enhancing teachers' job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria. The research design adopted was a descriptive (survey) design. The population for this study comprised 1,976 teachers in the 158 public secondary schools in Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State (Field work, 2023) while the sample was 322 teachers using proportionate stratified and random sampling techniques. The instrument used for data collection was an adapted Umeazor's (2019) questionnaire titled "Physical Resources Utilization and Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire". The method used for analyzing the data was descriptive statistic of mean score. The findings of the study revealed that the extent of utilization of the available physical plant resources, printed resources and non-printed resources to enhance teachers' job performance was to a low extent with the mean scores of ($x = 2.11$); ($x = 2.02$); and ($x = 2.14$) respectively in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria. This study concluded that most of the physical resources are inadequately available and poorly utilized by teachers. This study concluded that most of the physical resources are inadequately available and poorly utilized by teachers. Based on the findings of this study, it was recommended among others that the government and other stakeholders such as School Based Management Board (SBMC), Parent-Teachers Association (PTA) and other well-to-do individuals in the society should constantly up-grade, audit and maintain the available physical plant resources in secondary schools in order to ensure that they are properly utilized to influence positively the teachers' job performance.

Keywords: Physical Resources, Utilization, Job Performance, Availability

Introduction

Educational resources, be it human or material resource, play vital role in both the education system and instructional delivery in the classroom. The extent of acquisition of knowledge, skills and attitudes relevant to life altogether depends on the quality of teaching/learning activities that teachers provide for learners to interact with and the quality of the interaction; factors largely dependent on the nature and the quality of resources at the teacher's disposal (Umeazor, 2019). Such resources, if well used, increase the achievement level of the students and also engender positive changes. Educational resources have great significance in promoting administrative processes and likewise students' academic achievements (Amadi & Gbarador, 2021). For instance, the presence of material resources as part of educational resources in the school environment impacts greatly on teachers' job performance in the classroom. Teaching and learning cannot yield positive results without the teacher making use of some educational resources during classroom presentations. The level of teachers' job performance and their success in teaching various subjects in secondary schools is greatly dependent on the degree and extent of utilization of up-to-date education resources which revolve around facilities, equipment and supplies like the physical plants, printed and non-printed materials (Umeazor, 2019).

The availability and subsequent utilization of physical resources are vital to the excellence of students in school. The significance of physical resources in the success of secondary curriculum cannot therefore be over emphasized. The number of facilities that are available at a school determine the quality of education that is offered by the institution and in turn, it affects the performance of the students in examinations. World Bank (2018) established that the quality of an education system is dependent on the availability of certain key inputs which include; physical infrastructure, teachers and curricular. Societies and governments around the worlds should therefore strive to ensure that they improve their education systems by providing enough funding for key infrastructure in order to ensure that every child has an equal opportunity during the acquisition of the skills and knowledge that they require to lead productive and healthy lives. Physical resources form part of the external environment

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to learners which has been found to be associated with the quality of academic grades. Physical resources are comprised of facilities such as classrooms, dormitories, dining halls, playing fields, toilets, urinal pits, computer labs, schools halls, laboratories, offices and libraries among others (Umeazor, 2019). However, despite the fact that the availability of these resources is crucial to the learning process, their quality and effective utilization is equally important (OECD, 2018).

Education in most Sub-Saharan countries is faced chronic shortages in physical and human resources (Omego & Simatwa, 2015). Omego and Simatwa opined that rather than distributing the limited resources available for secondary education uniformly across schools, many governments allocate a relatively large share of available resources to a selected number of secondary schools. Similarly, findings by World Bank (2018) in a study on provision of textbooks and physical resources in secondary schools in sub-Saharan African countries: Botswana, Cameroon, Coted'vore, Ghana, Kenya, Malawi, Rwanda, Tanzania and Togo revealed that urban secondary schools have better textbook supplies and physical facilities than those in the rural areas. Dania. Obro, and Owzorhu, (2016) posited that inadequate instructional materials and poor utilization of physical and workshop facilities available for teaching has led to student failure and lack of competencies. Also, Dania. Obro, and Owzorhu noted that one of the problems in the Nigerian school system with regards to material resource management is not quite the non-availability or inadequate provision of good quality facilities but the inability to take good care of what is already available. Therefore, Dhakal (2020) affirmed that "the essential materials for teaching and learning are often unavailable in most of community secondary schools. The unavailability of such materials in secondary schools leads the teachers to talk and chalk in the teaching and learning". This means that without necessary material resources, teaching and learning will only become mechanical instead of interactive and this in the long run will affect teaching and learning outcomes.

Educational resources are of tremendous importance to the accomplishment of educational objectives and goals worldwide (Ajiboye, 2022) and teachxer' job performance. The performance of the teacher is often determined by the extent to which the outlined goals and objectives of the school are achieved as expected from the teacher (Onalapo *et al.*, 2019). Teachers' job performance is central to all of the activities that are carried out in the school. The duties of the teacher in today's school system extend beyond the four walls of the classroom as they sometimes discharge their responsibilities even to the home front (Ayoro, Onyeike & Jack, 2023). Limon and Nartgun (2020) stated that job performance is the expected total value of what an employee is able to discharge in the line of duty. Amadi and Ezeugo (2019) highlighted that physical resources are very significant as they create conducive environment for teaching and learning; help the learners to develop skills through extra-curricular activities; motivate the school teachers in the execution of their duties; and help the retention of teachers through friendly teaching environment and good allowances among others. Therefore, principals who wish that their teachers do well need to also bear in mind that the materials used by the teachers must be regularly maintained to put them in good working condition and this is what obtains across different schools (Osuji &Iheanyichukwu, 2021).

A cursory look at the development of secondary schools in Zamfara State has shown that there are evidences of lapses in teachers' job performances (Umeazor, 2019). These lapses are mostly expressed through their negative behaviour and poor attitude towards work. Dania. Obro, and Owzorhu (2016) posited that inadequate instructional materials and poor utilization of physical and workshop facilities available for teaching has led to student failure and lack of competencies This also seems to have negative consequences on students' performances in both internal and external examinations as observed by the researcher. It was observed by the researcher that the issue of resource utilization as regards to the school physical plant facilities, printed and non-printed facilities in connection with teacher job performance in secondary schools in Zamfara State has become a new matter of discourse for researchers and likewise questionable. The current situation showcases that many of the teachers in Zamfara State secondary schools, whether rural or urban secondary school, are still teaching and working under very difficult conditions and poor working environment where many of these educational resources like the physical plants' resources, printed and non-printed resources are not properly utilized (Umeazor, 2019). With this devastating state, teachers find difficulties in performing their task and function efficiently and effectively.

Despite the Zamfara State government (past and present) efforts to support schools with educational resources in order to improve teachers' job performance as noted by the researcher, a lot are still at stake and the situation has not changed much. The problem concerning educational resources utilization for teacher job performance which has necessitated the present study therefore stands as the gap which must be filled. The present study sought to address the extent of educational resource(s) utilization for teacher job performance in secondary schools in Zamfara State, which is the problem of the study. It is against this background that this study is carried out to investigate the influence of physical resources utilization as correlates of job performance of secondary school teachers in Gusau Local Government Area of Zamfara State, Nigeria.

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Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study was to examine physical resources utilization as correlates of job performance of secondary school teachers in Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study examined the:

- extent to which utilization of the available physical plant resources enhance teachers' job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State.
- extent of utilization of the available printed resources enhances teachers' job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State.
- extent of utilization of the available non-printed resources enhances teachers' job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

19. To what extent are the available physical plant resources utilized to enhance teachers' job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria?
20. To what extent are the available printed resources utilized to enhance teachers' job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria?
21. To what extent are the available non-printed resources utilized to enhance teachers' job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were raised and tested at α 0.05 level of significance in the study:

1. There is no significant relationship between utilization of the available physical plant resources and teachers' job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria
2. There is no significant relationship between utilization of the available printed resources for teachers' job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria
3. There is no significant relationship between utilization of the available non-printed resources for teachers' job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria

Methodology

The research design adopted for this study was a descriptive (survey) design. This according to Adewale (2004) is an approach that looks for relationship on the basis of which projections are based. Also, it involves a planned collection of data over a large area for the purpose of making description. Thus, this method is considered appropriate because it allows the researcher to make careful record of what was observed so that the researcher can analyze the information obtained from a representative sample of the population and to describe situation as they exist (physical resources utilisation and teachers' job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria).

The population of this study comprised 1,976 teachers in the 158 public secondary schools in Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State. The sample size was made up of 322 teachers from secondary schools using proportionate stratified and random sampling techniques. The instrument used in gathering data for this study was an adapted questionnaire from Umeozor (2019). A structured questionnaire titled "Physical Resources Utilization and Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (PRUATJPQ)" which contained 21 items was used to collect data for the study. Items on the instrument were measured on a 4-point scale and rating as Strongly Agreed (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SA). In order to ascertain that the instrument measured what it was expected to measure, the questionnaire was subjected to face validation by making the questionnaire available to three (3) experts in the fields of Educational Foundations and Measurement and Evaluation, Federal College of Education (Technical) Gusau for comments, criticisms and suggestions. Professional advice offered was adhered to before a final draft of the instrument was produced.

The reliability of the instrument was determined through a pilot-test. Copies of the questionnaire were administered on a sample of 30 teachers from three public secondary schools in Bungudu Local Government Area, Zamfara State. The Cronbach Alpha technique was used to measure the internal consistency of the questionnaire which yielded coefficients 'r' value of 0.68, 0.60 and 0.64 for each of the three clusters, and an overall reliability 'r' value of 0.82.

Data collected and collated were quantitatively analyzed using the descriptive statistics of mean score, aggregate mean and standard deviation. The decision rule for the items on each of the research questions was based on the premise that any statement with a mean score of 2.50 and above was agree, while any one below 2.50 was disagree. The three null hypotheses

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were tested at 0.05 level of significance using Pearson Product Moment Correlation statistics. The decision rule was based upon that wherever p-value obtained or calculated value is greater than or equal to the alpha 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1

To what extent are the available physical plant resources utilized to enhance teachers' job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean Scores of the Respondents Ratings on the Extent to which the Available Physical Plant Resources are Utilized for Teachers' Job Performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria (N= 322)

S/N	Statements	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Decision
1	Staff rooms with adequate ventilation are utilized by teachers for consultations and timely give feedback to students	14	76	143	88	2.04	Disagree
2	Functional library stocked with up-to-date books are journals are utilized by teachers for their research consultations and private reading	21	58	171	72	2.08	Disagree
3	Technical workshop are utilized by teachers to teach basic technology practical for skill acquisition	31	60	163	68	2.17	Disagree
4	Functional guidance and counseling unit are utilized by teachers for consultations and to support students' academic growth	27	50	192	63	2.06	Disagree
5	Classrooms of 35-40 seating capacity with adequate space and ventilation are utilized by teachers to aid active teaching and students' participation in class	20	79	198	25	1.61	Disagree
6	Classroom furniture and fittings with cupboards/cabinets and shelves are utilized teachers to keep books and other materials in all the classrooms	29	71	189	33	2.30	Disagree
7	Computer room are used for students practical during computer class	20	14	186	102	1.85	Disagree
Grand Mean 2.02							

Fieldwork (2023)

Table 1 revealed the perceptions of the respondents on the extent to which the available physical plant resources are utilized to enhance teachers' job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria. The respondents disagreed to all the statements in Table 1 that the available staff rooms with adequate ventilation are utilized by teachers for consultations and timely give feedback to students ($x = 2.04$); that functional library stocked with up to date books are journals are utilized by teachers for their research consultations and private reading ($x = 2.08$); that technical workshop are utilized by teachers to teach basic technology practical for skill acquisition ($x = 2.17$) and that Functional guidance and counseling unit are utilized by teachers for consultations and to support students' academic growth ($x = 2.06$). Also, the respondents disagreed to the statements that classrooms of 35-40 seating capacity with adequate space and ventilation are utilized by teachers to aid active teaching and students' participation in class ($x = 1.61$); Classroom furniture and fittings with cupboards/cabinets and shelves are utilized teachers to keep books and other materials in all the classrooms ($x = 2.30$) and Computer room are used for students practical during computer class ($x = 1.85$). This implied that physical plant resources such as staff rooms, classrooms, workshops and furniture available were not adequate enough to enhance effective teachers' job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria with the grand mean of 2.02.

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Research Question 2

To what extent are the available printed resources utilized for teacher job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean Scores and SD of the Respondents Ratings on the Extent to which the Available Printed Resources Utilized are Utilized for Teacher Job Performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria (N= 322)

S/N	Statements	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Decision
1	Educative wall charts are pasted by teachers on the walls in the classrooms to promote learning in different subject areas	20	79	198	25	1.61	Disagree
2	Graphics for picture representation in teaching various subjects are displayed to support teaching	19	50	189	64	2.07	Disagree
3	Maps are used during geography teaching to support students' learning	19	34	189	80	2.18	Disagree
4	Work books are utilized by teachers in all subjects to give students assignment that will boost their cognitive and independent study	89	153	37	43	2.89	Agree
5	Posters and cartoons are used to support and display evidence of the lesson taught in the classrooms	27	50	192	63	2.06	Disagree
6	Up-to-date textbooks in the library with wider coverage in all subjects are used by teachers to promote research and teaching in varying context	23	37	181	81	2.01	Disagree
7	Pamphlets on past questions and answers available for different subjects	19	34	189	80	2.18	Disagree
Grand Mean = 2.14							

Fieldwork (2023)

Table 2 revealed the perceptions of the respondents on the extent to which the available printed resources are utilized for teacher job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria. Majority of the respondents agreed to only item 4 that workbooks are utilized by teachers in all subjects to give students assignment that will boost their cognitive and independent study with the mean score of 2.89. However, the respondents also disagreed to items 1, 2, 3, 5, 6, and 7 with the mean scores of 1.61, 2.07, 2.18, 2.06, 2.01, and 2.08 respectively. This implied that educative wall charts, dictionary, graphic pictures and maps were not available to enhance teachers' performance. Therefore, the grand mean of 2.14 was obtained and indicated that the available printed resources are utilized for teacher job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria was to a low extent.

Research Question 3

To what extent are the available non-printed resources utilized for teacher job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria Zamfara State?

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Table 3: Mean Scores and SD of the Respondents Ratings on the Extent to which the Available Non-printed Resources Utilized are Utilized for Teacher Job Performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria (N= 322)

S/N	Statements	SA	A	D	SD	Mean X	Decision
1	Laboratory tools and kits available for teaching physics practical	20	14	186	102	1.85	Disagree
2	Computers available for practical and research	30	34	187	71	2.07	Disagree
3	Public address system available in the classroom for presentations	19	50	189	64	2.07	Disagree
4	Chalkboard/whiteboard installed on the wall in all the classrooms	120	151	23	28	3.13	Agree
5	Internet facilities installed in the school for browsing and surfing of information from different websites	31	60	163	68	2.17	Disagree
6	Projectors available for teaching in different subjects	20	14	186	102	1.85	Disagree
7	Models/dioramas available for display in teaching various subjects in the classrooms	21	39	241	21	2.19	Disagree
Grand Mean = 2.01							

Fieldwork (2023)

Table 3 shows the perceptions of the respondents on the extent to which the available non-printed resources are utilized for teacher job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria. It was indicated as shown in the Table that Chalkboard/whiteboard were installed on the wall in all the classrooms with the mean score 3.13. On the other hand, majority of the respondents disagreed that laboratory tools and kits available for teaching physics practical with the mean score of 1.85, computers available for practical and research with the mean score of 2.07 and public address system available in the classroom for presentations with the mean score of 2.07. Also, the respondents disagreed to these statements that internet facilities installed in the school for browsing and surfing of information from different websites, that projectors available for teaching in different subjects and models/dioramas available for display in teaching various subjects in the classrooms with the mean scores of 2.17, 1.85 and 2.19 respectively. The grand mean of 2.01 was obtained and this implied that the what extent to which the available non-printed resources utilized teacher job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria was low.

Hypotheses Testing

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between utilization of the available physical plant resources and teachers' job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria secondary schools in Gusau Local Government

Table 4: Significant relationship between utilization of the available physical plant resources for teachers' job performance secondary schools in Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria

Variables	Sample Size	Mean	Standard Deviation	t-cal	Degree of Freedom	STD Error	p-value	Decision
Physical Resources	322	30.24	12.76	-8.594	321	.89851	0.00	Ho1 Rejected
Teachers' Job Performance		37.96	15.67					

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Fieldwork (2023)

The result in Table 4 indicates that the calculated t-cal value is -8.594 and a p-value .000 with degree of freedom (d.f) 1193 at 5% (0.05) level of significance. Since the p-value .000 is less than the alpha level ($P < 0.05$), the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, there is a significant relationship between utilization of available physical plant resources and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria.

Ho2: There is no significant relationship between utilization of the available printed resources for teachers' job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria

Table 5: Significant relationship between utilization of the available printed resources for teacher job performance secondary schools in Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria.

Variables	Sample Size	Mean	Standard Deviation	t-cal	Degree of Freedom	STD Error	p-value	Decision
Printed resources	322	29.88	11.28	-3.194	321	.89851	0.01	Significant Difference
Teachers' Job Performance		32.28	12.86					

Fieldwork (2023)

The result in Table 5 indicates that the calculated t-cal value is -3.194 and a p-value of .001 with degree of freedom (df) 321 at 5% (0.05) level of significance. Since the p-value .001 is less than the alpha level ($P < 0.05$), the tested null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, there is a significant there is a significant relationship between utilization of available printed resources for teacher job performance in Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria.

Ho3: There is no significant relationship between utilization of the available non-printed resources for teachers' job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria

Table 5: Significant relationship between utilization of the non-printed resources for teacher job performance secondary schools in Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria.

Variables	Sample Size	Mean	Standard Deviation	t-cal	Degree of Freedom	STD Error	p-value	Decision
Non-printed resources	322	26.52	12.39	-9.782	321	.89851	0.00	Significant Difference
Teachers' Job Performance		35.29	15.78					

Fieldwork (2023)

The result in Table 6 indicates that the calculated t-cal value is -9.782 and a p-value of .000 with degree of freedom (df) 321 at 5% (0.05) level of significance. Since the p-value .000 is less than the alpha level ($P < 0.05$), the tested null hypothesis is therefore, rejected. Thus, there is a significant there is a significant relationship between utilization of available non-printed resources for teacher job performance in Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The first purpose of this study was to find out the extent to which utilization of the available physical resources to enhance teacher job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria. The findings to this purpose revealed that the extent of utilization of the available physical plant resources for teachers' job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria was to a low extent ($x = 2.02$). Also, the hypothetical test indicated that a significant relationship was found in the mean ratings of teachers on the extent of utilization of available physical plant resources for teacher job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria. This finding concurs with Eze (2010) whose study reported that physical plant resources such as school building, library services and laboratories, among others as regards to teachers' utilization were lacking in the schools. This

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was the major factor that affected students' academic learning and teacher effectiveness in schools. Unavailability of school health services, school fence and provision of power supply were also important variables that affected teachers' job performance (Eze, 2010). Atieno (2014) also confirmed that physical plant facilities in the schools were overstretched and thus affected quality education in the schools. Whereby the physical plant resources were not effectively utilized by the teachers in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria, and such situation will affect teacher job performance and has negative consequences on accomplishment of instructional task and students' academic achievements will be put in jeopardy in school.

The second purpose of this study was to find out the extent to which utilization of the available printed resources to enhance teacher job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria. The finding of the study also discovered that the extent of teachers' utilization of the available printed resources for teacher job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria was to a low extent ($x = 2.11$). The hypothetical test showed that a significant difference was found between the mean ratings of teachers on the extent of utilization of available printed resources for teacher job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria. This finding concurs and corresponds with the finding of Adebule and Ayoola (2014) who affirmed that instructional materials were found in schools to an extent; however, teachers were not putting the materials into good use in teaching of some subjects. Stephen (2011) finding showed that there was low frequency in teachers' use of the available resource materials. Andambi and Kariuki (2013) reported that the most commonly available printed resources used for teaching were textbooks, charts, maps, teacher made materials and newspapers; however, teachers were not using them for teaching and learning. Whereby the printed resources are not effectively utilized by the teachers in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria, and this situation will continually affect teacher job performance. This situation has negative consequences on instructional goal accomplishment and stands to jeopardize students' academic achievements in school. Kimeu, Tanui and Ronoh (2015) also observed that both teachers' and students' academic performances depended on teachers' utilization of printed resources.

The third purpose of this study was to find out the extent to which utilization of the available printed resources for teacher job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria. The findings of the study further discovered that the extent of teachers' utilization of the available non-printed resources for teacher job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria was to a low extent ($x = 2.01$). The finding discovered that in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria, computers available for practical and research and television set available for teaching in different subjects among other non-printed resources were both utilized to a low extent. The hypothetical test showed that a significant relationship was found between the mean ratings of teachers on the extent of utilization of available non-printed resources for teacher job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria.

This finding concurs and is in line with Kimeu, Tani and Ronoh (2015) whose study found that students' academic performance depended on use of non-printed teaching and learning materials like the chalkboard, laboratory apparatus and chemicals, among others, but teachers were not making adequate use of them. Ntui and Udah (2015) found in secondary schools in Calabar, Cross Rivers State, Nigeria, that teachers were not making use of the audio-visual materials in the schools. A significant difference was observed in the schools concerning teachers' utilization of non-printed resources. Andambi and Kariuki (2013) also confirmed that radio was the most commonly available non-printed resources in the schools, but teachers were not using them for teaching and learning. Whereby the non-printed resources are not effectively utilized by the teachers in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria, and this situation will continually affect teacher job performance. This situation has negative consequences on instructional goal accomplishment and stands to jeopardize students' academic achievements in school. Ugwuanyi (2013) reported that no meaningful learning or transfer of what has been learned will take place if such learning occurs in a situation devoid of relevant non-printed materials and activities as well as concrete experiences – given through teacher job performance.

Conclusion

Educational resources be it physical plant resources, printed resources or non-printed resources are very vital for effective teacher job performance. In Zamfara State, most of the physical resources are inadequately available and poorly utilized by teachers to a low extent for their job performance, while a huge number of these resources are unavailable to a high extent in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State. Failure for secondary school teachers to deliver

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their lessons effectively in the classroom has negative consequences on both schools' development and students' academic achievement. The situation in Zamfara State calls for absolute redress in order to impact positively on teacher job performance through resource utilization.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of this study, the following recommendations are made that:

1. The Zamfara State government and other stakeholders such as School Based Management Board (SBMC), Parent-Teachers Association (PTA) and other well-to-do individuals in the society should constantly up-grade, audit and maintain the available physical plant resources in secondary schools in order to ensure that they are properly utilized to influence positively the teachers' job performance.
2. Secondary schools' principals should ensure that they encourage teachers to utilize properly the available printed resources for their job performance in secondary schools. They should not only improvise the printed resources but also supervise teachers to ensure their effective utilization during instructional delivery in the classroom.
3. The principals should also apply appropriate maintenance culture in order to protect the available non-printed resources for effective teacher job performance in secondary schools. Constant training and retraining should be given to teachers in order to improve utilization of the non-printed educational resources in the schools.

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Qualitative Study on Foreign Aid Intervention on Civil Conflict Intensity and Sustainable Economic Development in West Africa

Ekuerhare Sylvia Efe

Email: efe_sylvia@yahoo.com

Tel: 08023282224

Directorate of General Studies, Federal University of Petroleum Resources, Effurun, Delta State. Nigeria

Abstract

Civil conflicts and war have become major threats to several local, regional and global economic growth and sustainable development because of their adverse effects on economic growth and development. Several internal strategies have been deployed but yielded no effective outcome hence, this have led to countries in the West Africa to seek for external assistance. A major focus of assistance is the use of foreign funding. This article examined the use of foreign funding in cushioning civil conflicts in West Africa. The study deployed a mixed studies systematic review, which places emphasis on the use of several studies that have deployed different research designs such as quantitative, qualitative, review, among others from searching from the databases of publishers, television websites, and other publications. Also, materials deployed include those within the years 2013 and 2023. In addition, thematic analysis and content analysis were deployed and used to analyse the information and materials obtained for this study from where inference was made from the study. The findings of this article revealed that seeking foreign aid funding could affect civil conflict intensity in West Africa in two ways. The first is that it could pose a negative effect by increasing the intensity of the civil wars due to selfish ambitions and mismanagement of funds released by donors. Second is that, it could also pose positive effect when used effectively to cushion the civil conflicts. Therefore, this study recommended that foreign aid donors should ensure that monitoring strategies such as donor harmonization, alignment with national development strategies with the recipient country, accountability between donors and countries should be put in place to ensure the proper and effective use of such aids received by West Africa.

Keywords: Foreign Funding, Foreign aids, Civil Conflict, Civil Conflict Intensity, West Africa

Introduction

Civil conflicts and war have become major threats to several local, regional and global economic growth and sustainable development. Gyimah-Brempong and Corley (2001) and Hasan (2022); noted that civil conflicts have adverse effects on economic growth and development. According to Doyle and Sambanis (2003); Clément (2005) and the United Nation (2023), noted that from global level, several civil wars have occurred since after the World War II and have claimed approximately 20 million lives and has displaced approximately 67 million. Also, in West Africa, for several decades, nations in Africa have been affected by various conflicts and civil strife accompanying with high intensity of violence and persistent killings. This has raised major challenges in several West African countries such as Mali, Côte d'Ivoire, Liberia and Sierra Leone, Niger, Ghana, Nigeria, Mauritania, among others (Annan, 2014). In addition, approximately 20 countries in sub-Saharan Africa have experienced at least a period of civil war after their independence and this is even grave and intensified for some countries such as Angola, Sudan, Nigeria, among others. In recent times, the incidence of civil conflict has intensified (Annan, 2014; Stockholm International Peace Research Institute (SIPRI) Yearbook, 2000; Clément, 2005; United Nation, 2023).

Several studies such as Keili (2008); Voz di Paz and Interpeace (2010); Vinck et al (2011); Annan (2014); Amnesty international (2021); among other have noted that civil conflicts in West Africa have been intensified and fuelled by several factors such as the high rate of poverty, human rights violations, bad governance, corruption, ethnic marginalization, among others. A number of factors have been identified as relevant in explaining civil wars in Africa. These factors include the historical legacies of slave trade and colonialism, the nature of the African state after independence, external intervention in the internal affairs of African countries, human rights abuses by African governments, and ethnic and religious grievances. The economic theory of civil war, however, sees civil wars in Africa as being caused by poor growth, poverty, and the abundance of natural resources such as diamonds, gold, and other precious minerals that can often be the source of much greed. Clément (2005) and United Nation (2023) revealed that civil conflict is development in reverse because it has reversal effects on economic development of a nation. This civil conflict related issue is much grave in developing countries such as those in West Africa. Collier and Hoeffler (2002); Clément (2005); United Nation (2023); among others, also revealed that civil conflicts

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reflect both a problem for development and also a failure of development. Also, several studies such as Usman and Mathew (2014); Audu, Lukman and Nyah (2014); Ebeh (2015); Olanrewaju, Folarin and Folarin (2017); Mou and Mou (2017); Akinade(2018); among others have argued that a civil conflicts challenge could pose significant negative effect on sustainable development. Therefore, it affects the three-dimensional variables of sustainable development: economic, social and environmental as stated by United Nation’s ESCAP (2015).

What constitute civil conflict could be difficult to explain, because it is frequently difficult to differentiate between the beginning and the end of a conflict period. Every conflict might not be the same because they have different causes, of different intensity, have different geographical spread, and have different duration (Cramer, 1999; Fang, Kothari, McLoughlin &Yenice, 2021). The consequences and the effect of civil conflict in West Africa have led to countries in the region to seek for external assistance because all internal strategies have not yielded effective outcome (Olufemi, 2015; Epron, 2019). According to Obi (2015) and Nwagboso (2018) civil conflict challenges are handled with lukewarm attitude in Africa and this has led to the distortion of structural development. To this end, African countries seek for external foreign aids to help cushion the civil conflict intensity in Africa (Nielsen et al., 2011). Svensson (2019) maintained that several economies, which include African economies, rely heavily on foreign aid, and this has led to a high dependency state for the country. Although, several other studies have argued that such foreign aid dependency could pose negative influence on countries and the region of Africa development. This school of thought is premised on the fact that, according to United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (2007); Omiunu (2012) and Adeoye &Iwegbu (2020), development that lasts is those that rely, harness and deploy the resources within towards achieving development goals.

Africa is the only continent where reliance on official aid inflow outstriped private capital inflow with a large margin and this has constituted a problematic global scenario because, from global perspective, there is no country that has really achieved substantial development relying foreign aid (Melesse, 2021). Focusing on and deploying domestic resources can assist African nations to achieve long term sustainable and higher economic growth and development and will also help them to reduce the problem of overdependence on foreign donor funding couple with the rules that apply to it (United Nations Conference on Trade and Development, 2007; Melesse, 2021). According to Melesse (2021), foreign aid as a practice has failed to achieve poverty reduction targets in Africa.

Despite this, many African countries still seek for foreign aids to handle civil crisis and towards ensuring internal development (Melesse, 2021). The significant positive and negative effect of foreign aid reliance has two sides of the coin in its debate especially in Africa (Melesse, 2021). The first, is that this model provides free money, which in the long run, prevents several African countries from taking the various global and development advantage of opportunities provided through the global economy. Second, is that, this foreign aid may not be seen as an economic problem, but in most occasions, it is the misallocation of these resources, the corruption that covers these misallocations of resources, and in extension bad governance have in one way or the other limit the ability of Africa countries to judiciously use those aid hence, it failed to achieve the major goals and objectives for which they were obtained. To this end, in 2005, the Paris Declaration on Aid Effectiveness has noted the need for several effective monitoring strategies such as donor harmonization, alignment with national development strategies with the recipient country, accountability between donors and countries to at least increase the positive impact of such collected aid (Izobo, 2020).

Foreign aid is ineffective in nations with bad governance and it is unnecessary in nations with good governance. Therefore, sourcing for foreign funding towards ameliorating civil conflict intensity in West Africa may pose a confusing debate. This could be why Melesse (2021) admonished that foreign aid as a practice has failed to achieve poverty reduction targets in Africa hence, has not yielded its objective. However, the continued reliance on foreign aids in West African countries continue to present the need for understanding whether it is still of benefits despite its significant and potential odds to development towards alleviating civil conflicts in the region. Hence, it is important to further examine how the reliance and deployment of foreign funding could assist in cushioning the several civil conflicts in West Africa- this is a major focus of this present paper.

West Africa has recorded several large-scale civil wars and at least seven other conflicts that are more of localized unrest (M’Cormack 2011). Examples of these large-scale civil war are the Biafran War which occurred between 1967 and 1970 in Nigeria, the Liberia civil war which occurred between 1989 and 1996 and also 1999 to 2003), the Sierra Leone civil war which happened between the year 1991 and 2002, the civil war in Guinea-Bissau between 1998 and 1999, civil war in Côte d’Ivoire between 2002 and 2007 and also resurfaced between 2010 and 2011; among others. Marc et al. (2015) revealed selected conflicts in West Africa presented in Table 1.

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Table 1: Selected Conflicts in West Africa to 2012

Name of conflict	Country	Years	Nature of conflict	Estimated fatalities
Guinea-Bissau War of Independence	Guinea-Bissau	1962–74	Insurgency	15,000
Biafran War	Nigeria	1967–70	Civil war	500,000–2,000,000
Casamance conflict	Senegal	1982–present	Insurgency	5,000
Mauritania and Senegal War	Mauritania and Senegal	1989–90	International conflict	500
First Liberian Civil War	Liberia	1989–96	Civil war	100,000–220,000
Tuareg rebellion	Mali	1990–95	Insurgency	—
Sierra Leone Civil War	Sierra Leone	1991–2002	Civil war	50,000–300,000
Guinea-Bissau Civil War	Guinea-Bissau	1998–99	Civil war	655
Second Liberian Civil War	Liberia	1999–2003	Civil war	150,000–300,000
First Ivorian Civil War	Côte d'Ivoire	2002–07	Civil war	3,000
Niger Delta conflict	Nigeria	2004–09	Insurgency	2,500–4,000
Tuareg rebellion	Niger	2007–09	Insurgency	270–400
Boko Haram uprising	Nigeria	2009–present	Insurgency	11,200
Second Ivorian Civil War	Côte d'Ivoire	2010–11	Civil war	3,000
Conflict in Northern Mali	Mali	2012–13	Insurgency	1,270

Source: Data on fatalities are derived from various sources, including Marshall 2005; ACLED 2014; Human Rights Watch 2011b; Nigeria Social Violence Dataset 2014; and Reuters 2009.
Note: — = not available.

Source: Marc et al. (2015)

The impacts of these claimed several lives as revealed in Table 1 above. The impact of these civil war on the civilian population was grave, generating a high number of refugees and internally displaced persons (IDPs) (Luckham and others 2001; Hasan, 2022; United Nation, 2023). There were also much of sexual and gender-based violence against both men and women leading to increased psychological and physiological trauma in the society affected with significant high economic and social costs of the wars on the societies of Liberia, Sierra Leone, among others (Marc et al., 2015). Also, Nigeria has suffered from various overlapping and different forms of political, communal, ethno-religious, election-related, and strives that occurred due to resource allocation and distribution, among others which has also affected the society (Marc et al., 2015). To this end, various strategies have been deployed and sought for towards ensuring that such civil conflicts and unrest are abated to the barest minimum which could include both the internal and external sourcing. Grady (2017), noted that the yearning to [prevent such conflicts and violence has been one of the priorities of the provision of foreign aid which involves given out hundreds of billions of dollars annually which have been expected to be spent on several suggested aid programs towards the decreasing of such civil conflicts. From the actual form of it, such external aid supports and programs should be directed to decrease civil conflicts due to its positive impact on the lives of the beneficiaries within the society of the country of recipient. However, foreign aid supports on civil conflicts have proven frustratingly difficult. This is because in most areas where such aids have been provided especially in West Africa, various and several other problems have made such societies to even have more aggressive civil conflicts due to the inappropriate dissemination of such financial foreign aids (Grady, 2017). Hence, such aid programs fail to achieve their aims and objectives thereby increasing the rate of civil conflicts in many societies in Africa.

Nevertheless, there is the positive aspect of foreign aid support to West African countries. For example, several other studies such (Collier & Hoeffler, 2002; Ree & Nillesen, 2009; Savun & Tirone, 2012; Grady, 2017; Melesse, 2021; Izobo, 2020; among others) also argued that foreign aid could exert a decreasing effect on civil conflicts or war in West Africa. These studies further argued that such foreign aid programs could empower the governments by deploying and using such foreign aid to support domestic expenditures, which could eventually free up other domestic revenue source to increase the local military capacity which could eventually decrease armed rebellion opportunities and could also deter further civil conflict or wars.

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Objective of the Study

The study focuses on examining foreign aid intervention on civil conflict intensity and sustainable economic development in West Africa. The specific objectives are to:

1. Examine foreign aid intervention and how it affects civil conflict intensity and sustainable economic development in West Africa.
2. Ascertain the influence of foreign aid intervention on civil conflict intensity towards enhancing sustainable economic development in West Africa

Research Question

The following research question was used to drive this study:

1. How does foreign aid intervention affect civil conflict intensity in West Africa?
2. How does the influence of foreign aid intervention on civil conflict intensity affect sustainable economic development in West Africa?

Methodology

The study deployed a mixed studies systematic review, which places emphasis on the use of several studies that have deployed different research designs such as quantitative, qualitative, review, among others. A systematic review strategy focuses on using systematic methods to collect and appraise data and information obtained from secondary sources or studies which could include searching from the databases of publishers, television websites, and other publications. It is designed to enumerate and provide a complete and exhaustive summary of current evidence (Giang et al., 2019) which in this study focus on fighting for Aid: deploying foreign funding to cushion civil conflict intensity in West Africa. In addition, the major search engines used to search for materials in this study are the google scholar and the google search engines. The Cochrane reviews style was deployed and used in this study for the reviewing of the literature as stated by Sieving (2007) and Chapman (2014). Also, the PICOS framework was used to inform the search strategy (Huang et al., 2006) as represented by Richardson (1995): P – Problem or Population; I – Intervention; C – Comparison, control or comparator; O – Outcome(s); S – Study.

With regards to this study, the PICOS framework used is presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1. PICOS

	Inclusion	Exclusion	Search terms
Problem and Population Intervention	Civil conflict intensity in West African Countries Foreign funding	Other national issues Other sources which could include internal sources	Civil conflict intensity in West Africa Foreign funding Aids
Comparator Outcome	None Cushioning Civil conflict intensity	None	None Strategies to cushioning Civil conflict intensity
Study type	Mixed studies systematic review	None	Mixed studies systematic review

The initiation of searching process commenced April 12, 2022 and this was also repeated on May 2-4, 2022 so as to obtain wide relevant resources that have not been previously covered in the previous search especially in the process of writing of and also reviewing the paper. Mixed studies were all considered and adopted in this study and materials deployed include those within the years 2000 and 2021. Also, the PRISMA Flow Diagram for the study search is provided in Figure 1 below.

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Figure 1: The PRISMA Flow Diagram for the Study

To ensure effective materials appraisal in this study, several components were inculcated such as the evaluation of the appropriateness of the study design that was used in the study, the methodological features of such design, the author of the article; sources of the articles, among others. Moreover, to further synthesize the information retrieved, data extraction was deployed but this was revolved around the research aim of the study as stated by Frederiksen (2017). In addition, thematic analysis and content analysis were deployed and used to analyse the information and materials obtained for this study from where inference was made from the study.

Empirical Results and Discussion

The study focused on examining the impact of foreign aid funding on civil conflict intensity in West Africa, and it is divided into two major sections based on the research questions of the article.

Research Question 1

How does foreign aid intervention affect civil conflict intensity in West Africa?

Mousseau (2021) did a study on whether foreign development aid trigger ethnic war in developing states, and revealed that higher availability of foreign development aid could exacerbate the propensity for ethnic war. This implies that foreign aid could play major role in stimulating ethnic violence in countries such as West Africa hence, it posed negative impact on the probability for a civil conflict. However, increasing aid flow could decrease the duration of conflict. Hence, foreign aid flows could be an important tool for policymakers and aid agencies towards the prevention of future civil wars especially in West Africa.

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Annan (2014) examined the violent conflicts and civil strife in West Africa: causes, challenges and prospects, through a review study, stated that ending violent conflicts and civil strife in West Africa requires the collaboration and collection of various efforts which could also include those related to foreign aid funding towards the

1. Identification of the causal factors of conflicts;
2. Development of concrete strategies and also programmes that could be directed towards the prevention, management and totally resolving the various conflicts;
3. The documentation, management and disseminating of information on the various lessons learnt and best practices of conflict prevention and resolution towards ensuring effective peace building across West Africa
4. Harnessing the indigenous conflict prevention mechanisms while trying to leverage on other contemporary advanced mechanisms so as to adequately address the present and emerging insecurities and violent conflicts in West Africa.

The study of Annan (2014) revealed that to an extent, foreign aid funding support could be useful when it is deployed to ensure that civil conflicts for which it was obtained for are addressed to the barest minimum to attain and achieve peacebuilding across West Africa. Mousseau (2021) examined whether foreign development aid trigger civil war in developing states, and the findings revealed that foreign aid could trigger society imbalance which could increase the risk of civil war. This supports the arguments that foreign aid can exacerbate tensions and cause division in the societies, leading the marginalized populations of the society to rebel. Hence, foreign aid plays a significant role in the stimulation of society violence such as civil conflicts. Although, foreign aid has an inherent designed that should be directed to improve stability within the state, but the disbursement of foreign aids does not guarantee peace but rather could be a cause of civil conflicts. Foreign aid donors should pay emphasis on the differences on domestic politics while trying to formulate and provide aid packages to the various developing countries for assistance. This could be used to justify the work of United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (2007); Svensson (2019); Adeoye and Iwegbu (2020); and Melesse (2021), that economies such as African economies rely heavily on foreign aid which has led to high dependency state for countries. However, Annan (2014) noted that West African Countries have rich indigenous cultural and social values such as respect, protection of human life, freedom, cooperation and tolerance; consists of diverse population and various civil society organizations that should and could harnessed as prospective and major strengths that could be used as driving force to cushion the various violent conflicts and civil strife in West Africa.

Research Question 2

How does the influence of foreign aid intervention on civil conflict intensity affect sustainable economic development in West Africa?

Drawing inference from the study of Annan (2014), that to an extent, foreign aid funding support could be useful to achieve peacebuilding, it could be deduced that this could include sustainable economic development across West Africa. Also, Izobo (2020) investigated the Impact of foreign aid in Africa: a case study of Botswana and Somalia and found that despite donors' original intentions for the distribution of aid, the high levels of corruption in Africa within recipient governments couple with poor democratic institutions, difficult conditions attached to the aids, fiscal imprudence from the recipients are major factors that have changed the original intention of foreign aid from blessing to a curse rather in several African countries. This implies that, such foreign aids could enhance sustainable, bur for the prevalence of corruption, it could impede sustainable economic development in West Africa. To cushion this, there is need to curtail directing foreign aid to countries that lack strong democratic institutions, and various economic sanctions should be used to monitor and motivate governments and political elites into political and economic reforms towards enhancing the effective use of such foreign aids. Such could constitute an effective aid conditionality that could be deployed to improve the chances of political and economic development. Hence, justifying the assertion of Omiunu (2012), that countries such as the West African Countries should focus on local and indigenous resources as another option for cushioning civil wars and conflicts in West Africa.

Izobo (2020) maintained that however, foreign aid supports enable African governments to strengthen local institutions through the provision of educational and technical support. Also, foreign aid can improve governance and also respect for the rule of law through the reduction in corruption be the effective management of expenditure and revenue creation for a country. Nevertheless, foreign aid can also pose significant impact by also challenging the rule of law and democratic reforms. For example, in an autocratic government, foreign aids can be used by such autocratic government by creating larger pool of resources officials and political elites in the government circle which they can fight on and also used for selfish and personal gains, this, in the long run may be detrimental to the country. Hence, civil conflicts, political instability, among others

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that have occurred in Africa over the past five decades could be as a result of the misappropriation of foreign aid received. Izobo (2020) further revealed that when countries are exposed to higher levels of foreign aid, it could destroy the quality of national and regional governance, hence, affect sustainable economic development. For example, the political in African countries have little or no motivation for acquiring such reform, they only use such accrued fund for selfish ambition such as salary increments, luxurious vehicles and houses, among others. This implies that, foreign aids could pose a positive and negative impact on African countries depending on the government and the environment of the nation that is whether it operates a corrupt economy or not.

Also, Grady (2017) examined aid for peace: does foreign aid deter violence, and found that foreign aid is associated with a little increase in violence, but this is only true when the aid programs and support are not provided on a continuous basis in future years. Also, it was revealed by Grady (2017) that there are two primary mechanisms that are used to justify the negative impact of foreign aids as it tends to increase conflicts and include from the political and economic effects. With regards to politics, there could be constant pressure for elections and the involvement of multiparty democracy without previous and future political development giving room for the deployment of ethnicity as a primary tool for mobilization especially among the elites that seek the public votes. Also, from the economic aspect, foreign aids release and give resources to the deprived areas of a society, and this may often lead to the neglect of inequality thereby neglecting some other ethnic groups within that society hence the existence and prevalence of biased resource allocation. Therefore, foreign aids could heighten the propensity of civil war in a given African society due to the fact that it has the tendency to increase the financial value within the state and also to lead to rebel that could cause civil conflicts. The following are several aspects provided by Grady (2017) that foreign aids could increase civil wars:

1. By adding resources to ongoing conflict, foreign aid could fuel civil crisis especially if such aid resources are distributed to the conflict actors which could occur via poor oversight, particularly when it is hard to track the resources.
2. By increasing the value of the zero-sum resources, foreign aid, focuses at increasing the value of an area's resources. In the case where the increased resources fail to reach the hands of active or potential conflict actors, the increase in the value of something will definitely increase the demand for such. For example, if there is an agricultural aid which could tend to increase land productivity, individuals may fight to possess more land or try as much as possible to defend their land.
3. By destabilizing the local economies leading to economic volatility. For example, economies that tend to rely on foreign aids tend to be more volatile than economies that do not because such allocations of aid could change year-in-year-out than the domestic production. This could further affect national governments and the local areas because local national workers would tend to develop skills necessary to gain employment into the aid organizations thereby leaving out other skill or local skills that are identified with the local environment of the nation. Such process may drain the local indigenous value of the nation in the long run.
4. By mismanagement of foreign aids. Aid provided to local environment could be mismanaged or poorly managed thereby increasing the civil conflicts or war tension again due to the mismanagement of the foreign aid resources disseminated to the local environment.

This justifies the findings of Melesse (2021) that foreign aid has actually failed to achieve poverty reduction targets in Africa. Also, Grady (2017) noted that foreign aids could reduce civil wars through the following:

1. Peace & Security aid aims at changing attitudes towards crisis or war and changing attitudes towards the potential targets of crisis or war, and also teaching about conflict resolution skills that could help cushion the civil crisis or war.
2. It could lead to economic increase because crisis or war is said to be caused by material deprivation and the resulting personal desperation. Hence, economic aid tends to indirectly affect crisis or war by the improvement of material lives of the aid recipients' nation. Hence, this could decrease the propensity to for the people to perpetrate crisis or war.
3. Result in democracy & Governance effect because politics is often used to mobilize societal cleavages, hence, such aids could be deployed to decrease civil crisis or war. This is because an inclusive electoral system tends to diminish civil crisis or war tendency through the decreasing of political grievances. It could also aid then decrease in likelihood a candidate feels the election was rigged. It could make the polling stations secure, thereby decreasing the propensity to intimidate voters.
4. Leads to better education through the same indirect mechanisms as it does in the economic and Peace & Security. Hence, increasing education tends to increase economic opportunities that could tend to remove incentives that are deployed to perpetrate violence.
5. Increases Health that could reduce such civil wars because poor health is often the cause of terrible material realities and much poverty and desperation.

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This finding concurs with the works of Collier & Hoeffler (2002); Ree & Nillesen (2009); Savun & Tirone (2012); Grady (2017); among others that foreign aid could exert a decreasing effect on civil conflicts or war in West Africa

Conclusion

In conclusion, foreign aid funding could have a two side of coin to affecting civil conflict intensity in West Africa. The first is that it could pose a negative effect by increasing the intensity of the civil wars due to selfish ambitions and mismanagement of funds released by donors. Second is that it could also pose positive effect when used effectively to cushion the civil conflicts.

Recommendations

Therefore, this study recommended that:

1. Foreign aid donors should ensure that monitoring strategies such as donor harmonization, alignment with national development strategies with the recipient country, accountability between donors and countries should be put in place to ensure the proper and effective use of such aids received in West Africa.
2. Donor of foreign aids should also endeavour to see to it that recipient countries have proper and accountable governance system following previous pattern of fund allocation.
3. Also, donor of foreign aids to West African countries should support research that seeks to search into the population of West African countries to investigate how government use funds, even local funds to meet local and the population needs. This could be used to know which country can have access to such foreign aids towards supporting them to cushion conflicts in their societies.

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Qualitative Study on Integration of Exercise Therapy and Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Devices for Healthy Workforce in Nigeria

Fatoba, Mercy Titilayo¹

Email: fatobamercy@yahoo.com

Tel: 08035380841

Fatoba, Oluwabusuyi John²

Email: fatoba.busuyi@yahoo.com

Tel: 08162346627

¹Department of Physical and Health Education, Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo State

²Department of Human Kinetics, University of Ilorin, Kwara State

Abstract

Participation in regular physical activity has been demonstrated to reduce all-cause mortality, prevent cardiovascular disease, regulate blood pressure, and weight control among others. In today's society, individuals can easily fall into the trap of developing a sedentary lifestyle as a result of choosing the easy way out in one's daily activities coupled with the hectic lifestyle which prevents one from engaging in regular physical activity. Due to the high prevalence of physical inactivity, increased levels of physical activity are a global public health priority. This paper presents a qualitative study into the varying functions and roles played by exercise therapy and information and communication devices in advancing healthy workforce. The advent of technology-based innovations has further brought about various ways IQ staying physically active regardless of constraints that might be encountered during the course of one's daily activities, with the presence of tracking devices for physical activity levels and other tools, acting as testaments to this. It is thus, recommended that individuals be informed and made aware of the need for active participation in physical activities for optimum health. Also, development of fitness centres should be encouraged to bring about mass involvement in physical activity irrespective of age groups. A healthy nation is a wealthy nation and as such, the need for a proactive approach towards health is required, as it has a backdrop effect on the sustainability of the nation's economy.

Keywords: Physical activity, Fitness, Health, Mortality, Technology, Economy, Nation

Introduction

Over the past years, there has been a huge shift from a lifestyle that was, by definition, physically active to one that is predominantly sedentary. It is well acknowledged that, engaging in physical activity is a crucial means of improving the physical and mental health of individuals. According to Riseth and Colleagues (2019), the effects of physical activity to improve or maintain good health are well documented. Despite public health recommendations and encouraging advice to stay physically active, approximately 30% of adults worldwide are physically inactive (Riseth, Torunn, Tom & Aslak, 2019). Exercise therapy is the practice of using physical activities to enhance physical function and health status (or reduce or prevent disability) in order to help patients or clients reach better levels of functionality at home, school, workplace, or community. It also includes activities that allow healthy clients to improve or maintain their health or performance status (for work, recreational, or sports purposes) and prevent or minimize future potential health problems (Bandy & Sanders, 2001). In recent times, technology-based innovations have advanced participation in physical activity through the use of tracking devices for physical activity enhancement, statistical tools for evaluation and feedback, and visual interactive demonstrations for analyzing playbacks. Tracking devices can aid athletic performance by utilizing sensors and chips that aid in evaluating skill and movement through Computer Aided Designs (CAD) which gives room for virtual design and testing techniques to be effected on all aspects of physical activity, sport and equipment research and development (Buchheit, Allen, Modonutti, Gregson, & Di Salvo, 2014). Hence, there is the need to widely emphasize on the varying potentials and benefits accruable from active participation in exercise and the role of ICT devices in further enhancing fitness.

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Exercise Therapy and Health Promotion

World Health Organization [WHO] (1948), defined health as a complete state of physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of sickness or disability. Physical activity can promote health and prevent the onset of disease including cardiovascular disease, type 2 diabetes and osteoporosis, forms of cancer, obesity and injury. Participation in physical activity is also known to improve mood, reduce stress and anxiety while also improving self-confidence, self-esteem, energy levels, sleep quality and the ability to concentrate (Mallikarjun & Vijaykumar, 2017). In a similar fashion as stated by Bandy & Sanders (2001), exercise therapy seeks to achieve the following goals; 1) Increase the normal range of motion 2) Improve and strengthen weak muscles 3) Improve the performance in daily activities 4) Release contracted muscles, tendons, and fascia 5) Mobilize joints 6) Improve circulation 7) Improve respiratory capacity 8) Improve coordination 9) Improve balance 10) Increased motor or sensory function 11) Reduction of medication, reduction of hospital visits, and increased overall health and 12) Improve exercise performance and functional capacity (endurance). All these goals are achieved through the participation in exercises targeting one's range of motion (passive, active and assisted active), flexibility, strength, aerobic and proprioceptive or neuromuscular improvement (Nagavani, 2013). Any exercise that tackles a restriction in natural motion at a joint or tissue interface can increase range of motion. Exercises can be done through the application of passive, active assisted, or active range of motion utilized to provide controlled stress to a joint and can be modulated by a number of factors including injury to muscle, tendon, ligament, joint capsule, and soft tissue structures. When connective tissues are not stretched, the soft tissues gradually shorten, which impairs range of motion and causes disuse-related impairments. Therefore, gentle A/AA/P range of motion should be initiated to avoid the vicious cycle of pain, immobility, contracture, and overall impaired function (Nagavani, 2013). Stretching is generally incorporated during range of motion exercises in order to facilitate improvements in mobility, with McKenzie and May (2003), stating the existence of three common types of stretching; static, passive and dynamic. Many different strengthening modalities exist and may include elastic or resistance bands, body weight and/or gravity-based resistance, manual resistance, and weights in the form of dumbbells, bars, or machines to name a few. The American College of Sports Medicine (ACSM, 2015) formulated minimal requirements to evaluate the quality of training programs for effective muscle strength training in healthy adults. The ACSM recommends a progressive individualized program, for all major muscle groups with at least 1 set of 8 to 12 repetitions and a frequency of 2 to 3 days a week.

Aerobic exercise, also known as endurance training, is defined as any exercise designed to increase cardiovascular fitness, often described as an increase in the maximal uptake of oxygen (Madden, 2013). This entails rhythmic, repeated, and continuous movements of the same large muscle groups for at least 10 minutes at a time. Aerobic exercise stimulates the heart rate and breathing rate to increase in a way that can be sustained throughout the exercise session. Examples of aerobic exercises include cardio machines, spinning, running, swimming, walking, hiking, aerobics classes, dancing, cross country skiing, cycling and many others. Aerobic exercise has long been noted as a key tool in the prevention and treatment of many of the chronic diseases typically associated with old age. These include impaired glucose tolerance, hypertension, heart disease and osteoporosis. Regular and moderate aerobic exercise increases certain antibodies in the blood called immunoglobulins which ultimately strengthens the immune system. Aerobic exercise may slow the loss of brain tissue and improve cognitive performance. (Ashley, 2020).

Proprioceptive exercise training, sometimes called functional fitness training, incorporates motor skills such as balance, coordination, gait and agility training. In the elderly, Tai chi has been shown to improve balance and reduce the risk of falls. In female athletes, there are anterior cruciate ligament injury prevention programs that focus on functional strength, balance, and neuromuscular control. The use of BOSU balls, foam pads, and unstable surfaces can be used to progressively challenge balance while performing functional activities to train the integrated balance system, therefore potentially reducing the risk of lower limb injury (Jurkiewicz, Marzolini, & Oh, 2011). Aquatic exercise, Pilates, Tai-Chi and even Yoga may be considered as functional activities to complement the therapeutic exercise.

ICT-Based Approach to Physical Activity and Fitness Testing

Anmol (2014), described information and communication technologies (ICT) as forms of technologies that are used to create, store, share or transmit, exchange information which spans across technologies such as: radio, television, video, telephone, satellite systems, computer and network hardware and software; as well as the equipment and services related with these technologies. Information and communications technology (ICT) in the field of exercise and sport science makes use of various technological tools and resources to produce, distribute, store and manage information and knowledge (Majoka, Fazal, & Khan, 2013). Sport & exercise science focuses on comprehending and interpreting individual responses and adaptations to muscular activity, with the goal of enhancing sports performance, reducing the risk of injury and enhancing the health and

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wellbeing of individuals. It involves the study of biomechanics, nutrition, exercise and assessment of health and exercise. With physical inactivity being the fourth highest leading risk-cause of mortality on a global level while also increasing the risk of many chronic diseases and conditions (WHO, 2009). The advent of innovation like ICT gadgets and services (pedometers, accelerometers, mobile in-built accelerometers, heart rate monitors, body-fat monitors, social networking, sport gaming and computer-based counseling systems, global positioning technologies, and mobile entertainment electronics) have greatly improved people's access to information about their body and state of health (Koskivaara, Laukkanen & Heinonen, 2011).

Technology is now being used to increase the number of people involved in physical activity and sport, as well as to enhance the performance of those people. With the production of new equipment, resources, and tools; sport participation and performance have become significantly improved. The combination of information technology in mass sports has experienced a substantial development, with the application of virtual reality technology to create virtual reality information in fitness equipment; such as network virtual reality treadmill, digital tennis, boxing. Through the guidance of fitness experts, internet users can also sum up a set of effective fitness methods for themselves with experts suggesting that internet-based physical activity interventions should be used by clinicians to promote and change exercise behavior (Marcus, Ciccolo & Sciamanna 2009). This kind of economical and efficient fitness demand brought by information technology makes the sport/fitness world experience fast rising growth.

Fitness trainers are expected to understand how computers and other technological devices can contribute to data collection for the analysis of movement patterns, sport skills, evaluation of student learning, and assessment of health-related physical fitness. This includes using exercise equipment to evaluate physical activity (e.g., accelerometers, heart rate monitors, pedometers, interactive dance machines), body composition (e.g., bioelectrical impedance devices, electronic skin-fold calipers) (Woods, Karp, Miao, & Perlman, 2008). A fitness test is any method of gathering information about the health and physical capability of an individual, with the measurement and evaluation of the different components of fitness allowing for the planning of effective training sessions and programmes for individual performers or individuals within groups, squads and teams.

Reasons for Fitness Testing

Some of the reasons for fitness testing include but not limited to: 1) as a measure of general health 2) to set realistic training goals and provide feedback on the effectiveness of a training programme 3) provides a means of talent identification, comparison of performance / performers and preparation for competition and 4) To motivate the athlete / performer (Woods et al., 2008).

ICT Tools/Devices and their Roles in Fitness Testing

The most common technology devices used in day-to-day fitness testing today are pedometers and heart rate monitors. With the increase in obesity levels, technologies for measuring activity levels have become prominent. Pedometers, accelerometers, and heart rate monitors can be used to track physical activity levels and collect useful information concerning exercise intensity and/or duration (Mears, 2010).

Pedometers are sensor-based devices which counts and monitors the number of steps taken throughout the day. Most pedometers provide a fairly accurate count of steps taken during ambulatory activities such as walking, jogging, and running. To provide accurate step counts, most pedometers need to be attached to a firm waistband; however, some pedometers can be carried in a shirt pocket, pants pocket, or bag held close to the body. Others can be worn on the ankle or in a shoe (Tudor-Locke et al., 2011). Studies report that pedometer-based walking increases physical activity (Williams et al. 2008; Ben, Ugwu, Eneka & Alor, 2019). In a synthesis of studies addressing the use of pedometers to increase physical activity, Bravata and colleagues (2007) reported that on average, pedometer users increase their physical activity by 27% over baseline levels. A key predictor of increased physical activity is setting a step goal (e.g., 10,000 steps per day) for participants. Pedometer-based walking programs are associated with significant decreases in body mass index, body weight, and systolic blood pressure (Bravata et al. 2007; Richardson, Newton, Abraham, Sen, Jimbo, & Swartz, 2008).

Accelerometers capture the steady progression of bodily acceleration, providing detailed information about the frequency, duration, intensity, and patterns of movement. Counts from accelerometers are used to estimate energy expenditure. Accelerometers have been used to provide an objective measure of compliance with physical activity recommendations for the United States population (Troiano, Berrigan, Dodd, Masse, Tilert & McDowell, 2008). Accelerometer technology is now finding its way into newer classes of waist-mounted pedometers and smartphones with the piezoelectric mechanism being

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sensitive to the vertical acceleration at the hip with the capability of data storage over a long period of time (Tudor-Locke *et al.*, 2011).

Heart Rate Monitors are also sensor-based devices used to determine whether or not an individual is in his/her target heart rate zone. This is considered to be 50-85% of your maximum heart rate. This is beneficial to know because it is the zone where one's body is operating most efficiently and frequently burning the most fat. Maximum heart rate is calculated using the simple formula: $HR_{max} = 220 - \text{one's biological age}$. Devices that simultaneously monitor heart rate and body motion provide valid and reliable measures of physical activity of children, adolescents, and adults in free-living conditions (Barreira, Kang, Caputo, Farley, & Renfrow, 2009; Ben *et al.*, 2019). An athlete's preparation for a sport or activity can also be aided by heart rate monitoring technology. This equipment comprises a recorder and a receiver to collect data, and assist a participant in exercising at the required exertion level for best results and safety. The data collected includes the heart rate of the participant when training, time, distance covered, and average and maximum speed. Additionally, it can make comparisons between this data and that of other performances and participants. The data can be graphed visually for an athlete to analyze and monitor their performances, which assists with preparation by allowing an athlete to train with the required intensity, and evaluate what improvements they have made by comparing their results to previous outputs (Heyward & Gibson, 2014).

Interactive Video Games

With exergames emerging and providing individuals with motivational and movement opportunities that produce fitness and health benefits, other video games may assist in knowledge and motor acquisition (Papastergiou, 2009). Videogames such as Dance Dance Revolution (DDR), has revolutionized exergames as means to enhance physical activity levels. According to Coshott, Thin and Young (2009), exergaming is the positive exercise experience gained by combining exercise and multimedia gaming (software and hardware). Positive gains ranging from elevation in the heart rate levels and increment in energy expenditure have been shown in a variety of studies using Dance Dance Revolution (DDR), a well-known dance simulation game by Konami Corporation, where the player is required to dance to a variety of songs, guided by watching scrolling directional arrows on the screen, which correspond to arrows on the pad that he/she has to step upon in synchronization with the music (Sell, Lillie, & Taylor, 2008; Iortimah & Tyoakaa, 2020). Due to dancing being a good aerobic activity, DDR has been used to promote physical activity and weight loss in obese children and adults (Epstein, Beecher, Graf & Roemmich, 2007; Zhu, 2008). As predicted by Zhu (2008), more than 1500 schools in the United States use DDR in physical education classes. Many fitness centres are now offering interactive games to promote physical activity of children, adolescents, and older adults. These interactive games are well suited for playing alone or with others, and they require little training or skill, provide an alternative to exercising in bad weather, and may serve as a transition to actually participating in sports and physical activities however, gaining system should not be considered equivalent to traditional exercises but should be seen as a supplement and not a replacement of traditional exercises. (Chamberlin & Gallagher, 2008; Ben *et al.*, 2019).

A reduction in weight gain, waist circumference, and blood pressure was also reported by some researchers who carried out studies on overweight children who participate in exergaming (Murphy, Carson, Neal, Baylis, Donley & Yeater, 2009; Maddison, Foley, Mhurchu, Jiang, Jull, Prapavessis, Hohepa, & Rodgers, 2011). While a great majority of the exergaming focus has been on children, it also holds promise for promoting functional independence, improving balance, preventing falls, reducing premature disability, and maintaining health by increasing the physical activity levels of adults (deJong, 2010).

Bioelectrical Impedance Device

This is a device for estimating the total body water or fat-free mass using measures of the body's resistance to current flowing through the body. This method requires minimal skill and experience on the tester's part. The machine passes a harmless electronic current through the client's body and records the impedance (opposition) to the current. The current will flow through tissues with a high-water content faster than through tissue with less water, such as fat. An individual who has more fat will record a slower speed for the current. The speed at which the current moves is measured and used to determine body composition. Research has shown that this method has a good level of accuracy with only ± 4 per cent error (Heyward & Gibson 2014).

Digital Video Camera and Visual Analysis Software

The use of the motion analysis system will surely enhance many areas of fitness both in research and instruction. Using a digital video camera has indeed simplified the collection of data as the visual analysis software allows coaches and

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fitness trainers to view captured movements and to analyse them (Anmol, 2014). Software is set of instructions which tells the computer what to do once instructed. There are various kinds of software and applications available in the market with its usage in sports and physical education further classified according to their performed task. Most of the biomechanical analysis software are integrated with number of video cameras (Hemantajit, 2019). Using cameras and computers, an individual or athlete is recorded when performing a movement or skill and his/her motions are analyzed to identify areas for growth. Coaches can identify shortcomings or improper techniques and prepare a program to correct them.

Conclusion

Fitness centres serve as one of sport mediums to improve health and physical fitness. The development of fitness centres in developing countries has generated a lot of positive responses. The positive response is proven by the increasing number of people who love physical activity. Commercial fitness centres present the opportunity to be physically active. The majority of fitness centres offer both group and individual activities (Riseth, Torunn, Tom, & Aslak, 2019). Fitness equipment is a worldwide ever-growing phenomenon and its usage is nowadays popular both in human routines and academic investigations. With access to fitness amenities, instructors, personal trainers, coaches and club operators are well positioned to help bring about a healthier world (Silvio, Jerónimo, Leonor & Jorge, 2020).

Recommendations

1. Individuals should be informed and made aware of the need for active participation in physical activities for optimum health.
2. Development of fitness centres should be encouraged to bring about mass involvement in physical activity irrespective of age groups.
3. Occupational physical activity programmes should be encouraged in order to discourage sedentariness across all sectors.
4. Fitness test measurements should be taken regularly, in order to monitor one's health status.

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Role of Field-Trip Strategy in Promoting Effective Teaching and Learning of Business Education in Nigerian Tertiary Institutions

Gidado, Sulayman Dauda¹

Email: sulaymangidado@gmail.com; sdgidado@yahoo.co.uk

Tel: 08060599833, 09011442083

Dauda, Rafat Bukola²

Email: dauda.rb@unilorin.edu.ng

Tel: 08035029816

Daramola, Rilwan³

Email: daramolarilwan65@gmail.com

Tel: 08037657983

¹Department of Business Education, Federal Capital Territory College of Education, Zuba-Abuja, Nigeria

²University of Ilorin, Nigeria

³Department of Accounting Education, School of Secondary Education (Business), Federal College of Education (Technical), Bichi, Kano State Nigeria

Abstract

This study is qualitative research which relies on available literature. It focuses on role of field-trip strategy in promoting effective teaching and learning of business education in Nigerian tertiary institutions. It dwells on business education, field-trip strategy as well as teaching and learning of business education at tertiary level of education. It also establishes that field-trip strategy can promote effective teaching and learning of business education because it motivates the learners to try new things and retain what they have already learnt, gives room for practical experience, enables lecturers to use resources in the community to make teaching to be more meaningful, enhances curriculum enrichment, encourages provision of current office materials for teaching purpose, avails lecturers with relevant information which will aid illustrations in the classroom and provides opportunity for hands-on learning. The study concludes that field-trip technique could serve as a recipe for promoting effective teaching and learning of business education in Nigerian tertiary institutions due to the fact that it makes the lecturers to play the roles of moderators, while the students play active roles leading to acquisition of the desired skills. Finally, the study among others recommends that lecturers should adopt field-trip as part of their teaching strategies, field trips should be properly and adequately planned and lecturers who wish to use the strategy should be supported by their schools' managements and parents/guardians.

Keyword: Role, Field-trip, Effective teaching, Learning, Business education.

Introduction

Acquisition of functional skills for positive performance leading to rapid transformation of human society is the fundamental goal of education all over the world. This can be achieved through teaching and learning. This is because Gidado et.al (2016) state that both teaching and learning are the most important activities in the educational enterprise and they contribute to the generation, transmission and application of knowledge. For teaching to be effective in order to enhance the attainment of educational goals (learning), numerous strategies can be adopted by the teachers in line with the peculiarity of the message to be passed to the learners. Business education is a skill-based programme which is sometimes regarded as an education for and about business. It is also practical based which requires the students to see some things for themselves as they occur in the field so as to make them to exhibit better performance after graduation either as self-employed or employees of organizations. To achieve this goal, field trip/excursion is among the effective strategies for teaching and learning of business education. This owes to the fact that the National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) in Gidado et.al (2016) stresses that field-trip makes it possible for a teacher to use resources in the community to make teaching to be more meaningful and allow the students to have concrete experience and practical illustrations of theoretical skills they have acquired in the classroom.

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Field-trip is a student-centered approach to teaching which puts the learner in position of dominance with the teacher playing the role of a moderator. In addition to this, a deduction from Kehinde and Salami (2020) shows that the learner-centered method allows the learners to play active roles in the teaching-learning process, while the teacher carries out passive roles in the sense that it gives the learners the opportunities for discussing, debating and questioning. Omo-Ojugo and Ohiwerei in Gidado et.al (2016) are of the opinion that the use of expository method in teaching business education which puts the teacher in control is ineffective and it negatively effects students' perception of the practical aspect of business education. This is because it does little in advancing conceptual understanding and critical thinking.

In addition to the aforementioned, constructivism theory is a student-centric strategy which can lead to effective teaching and learning. According to Ekpenyong and Edokpolor (2016), the basic tenet of constructivism is that students construct their own knowledge in relation to the information or idea of the subject matter that is presented to them rather being mere passive receivers of information from a given source. Based on this, the authors state that information cannot just be deposited in the heads of the learners. It has to be discovered through activities that are meaningful to them. In line with this, they assert that people develop their knowledge through active participation in learning. Furthermore, Ekpenyong and Edokpolor point out that there is no single constructivism theory, but they all agree that students are active in constructing their own knowledge and social interactions are important in knowledge construction process. Application of this theory is therefore useful in the educational system. This because when its principles are applied by a lecturer using field-trip as a teaching strategy to teach business education in tertiary institutions, teaching and learning would be effective. This owes to the fact that it allows the lecturer to take advantage of the learners' previous knowledge while preparing for the excursion. It also enables the learners to break new grounds by themselves through relating their entry behaviours (classroom experience) with what is practically done in the industry thereby making them to relate theory with practice so as to have clear pictures of the concepts that were theoretically discussed in the classroom. It is thus, based on the aforementioned that this paper focuses on the role of field-trip strategy in enhancing effective teaching and learning of business education in Nigerian tertiary institutions.

Business Education at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

Business education is one of the major components of vocational education and it is viewed differently by people and institutions based on their views and exposure. This shows that there are numerous definitions of business education. According to Ibrahim in Obi (2020), business education is a programme of study which aims at equipping its products with multiple skills for teaching or working in industry as well as being able to establish businesses as entrepreneurs. Chiaka and Tiku (2020) also posit that business education is an aspect of general education which has the goal of equipping the learners with distinctive skills, knowledge, aptitude and attitudes that are required for occupational competence in areas of education and business. In the same vein, Azuka and Obi in Azuka (2020) are of the view that business education is an academic programme that is made up of four components namely; creation of occupational awareness, preparation of youths for work in business, preparing people to become better citizens and consumers of goods and services as well as production of business teachers. A look at these definitions reveals that at the tertiary level of education, business education is a course of study which has the goal of enhancing human capital development which would all things being equal bring about sustainable development in the society. This is because the products have the chance of acquiring skills necessary for societal progress in the educational enterprise through serving as educational administrators and teachers. The products can also work in the government's Ministries, Departments and Agencies (MDAs) and the private sector or become self-reliant through setting up their businesses.

Field-trip Strategy at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

The major objective of field-trip is to enable an individual to be exposed to different environments, learn and be able to try new things. Field-trip is embarked upon by scholars, researchers and students for the purpose of accessing firsthand information on a given research or curriculum content in an industry, factory, museum, archeological, geographical or historical sites. In line with these, Aliyu in Gidado et.al (2016), states that field-trip is a process of visiting or taking trip(s) to a place(s) where relevant teaching material could be found in the sense that not all materials could be found within the four walls of the classroom. In addition to this, a deduction from Dasun et.al (2023) reveals that field-trip is an instructional strategy that allows students to discover things by themselves thereby getting firsthand knowledge on a given subject component through visiting places outside the normal classroom. Upula (2023) also states that field-trip deals with taking students outside the classroom in order to enable them to make relevant observations and obtain specific information. Similarly, deduction from Momozoku et.al (2022) shows that it is an educational adventure which is organized by the school and gives the learners the opportunity of going out of the school premises in order to interact with what they learnt theoretically in the classroom through physical

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manipulation and or participation, work in a team or co-operatively with others and get experience that might not be possible in the classroom. Finally, the steps involved in field-trip include; trip selection, logistics planning, field-trip preparation/pre-trip discussion, field-trip, post field-trip and evaluation of field-trip. From the foregoing, it is obvious that field-trip is a strategy that enables the students of tertiary institutions to move out of the confines of their classrooms and school environments in order to see things for themselves and enhance the attainment of the objectives of a given curriculum.

Teaching of Business Education at Tertiary Level of Education

Teaching is a challenging but rewarding profession in which a teacher plays an important role of helping learners to acquire and develop knowledge and skills that would be useful and applicable in future. According to Akinpelu in Abdulkadir (2017), teaching is a deliberate attempt by an experienced person (teacher) to impart knowledge, information and skill unto a less experienced person (learner), in line with this, Salami (2016) sees teaching as an activity carried out by an agent (teacher) whose primary aim is to at the end of an experience modifies the behaviour, feeling and or thinking of an audience (learner). Furthermore, a deduction from Enyekit and Enyekit (2019) shows that teaching attempts at bringing about desirable changes in the behaviours of the learners which improves and transforms the learners as well as the society so as to enhance qualitative changes which would result into sustainable development in the society. Similarly, Vin-Mbah in Buba and Hamman (2019) holds the view that teaching is a multi-purpose occupation which focuses on human resource development and economic growth. It could be deduced from the aforementioned that at the tertiary level of education, teaching of business education is carried out by teachers (lecturers) who guide the students into learning. Teaching of business education is therefore said to be effective, if positive change in behaviour, attitude and conception is noticed in student(s) through the ability of analyzing, developing, creating and demonstrating understanding for personal and societal progress.

Learning of Business Education at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

Learning is a continuous process which begins at birth and ends at death. It is shaped by experience in the sense that experience is used in dealing with new situation or condition and developing new relationship(s). It is based on this that Bingham and Corner in Malamed (2016) point out that learning is based on input, process and reflection and it is what changes us. This owes to the fact that it is a transformative process of taking information which when internalized and mixed with what we have experienced, would change what we know and build on what we do. Similarly, Clark and Mayer in Malamed (2016) are of the view that learning has to do with strengthening correct responses and weakening incorrect ones. It also involves adding new information to a person's memory and making sense of the presented material by attending to relevant information, mentally reorganizing it and connecting it with what they have already known. From the foregoing, it could be seen that learning can occur in both the formal and informal set up. This is because; a person could gain and internalize an experience(s) anywhere. It should however be noted that at the tertiary level of education, it results from an interaction(s) between the teacher (lecturer) and the learner. It is based on this that Salami (2016) sees learning as a change in behaviour which arises due to the interaction between the teacher and the students in the classroom. This implies that the interaction would lead to acquisition of knowledge and skills and also enable the learners to readily make them available from memory for the purpose of solving future problems and utilizing opportunities. To corroborate this, Buba and Hamman (2019) are of the assertion that learning is all about change which is brought about by coming up with skills, change in an individual's attitude and societal development. It is worthy of note that these are among the goals of education at the tertiary level of education

Field-Trip and Effective Teaching and Learning of Business Education at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

Field-trip is a teaching method whose purpose is to promote effectiveness in teaching and learning. As deduced from Momozoku et.al (2022), field-trip enables the learners to have the desire for trying new things and retain what they learnt. A deduction from Cooke-Nieves in Kasumu and Kasumu (2023) also states that field-trip gives room for practical experience of actual performance of work processes through observation which stimulates the desire to learn and leads to actual learning. In line with these, when the interests of business education students in tertiary institutions are aroused; curiosity would be ignited leading to acquisition of effective skills that are needed for efficiency in the discipline which are expected to make them to be highly productive and competitive after graduation. The National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) in Gidado et.al (2016) also states that field-trip enables a teacher to use resources in community to make teaching to be more meaningful and allows students to have practical experience and illustrations of how things are done in organizations so as to compliment the theoretical skills they acquired in the classroom. Furthermore, Aliyu in Gidado et.al (2016) is of the view that field trip is used due to the fact that not all learning resources are available within the four walls of the classroom. In the context of business

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education at the tertiary level, the possible places where students could be taken to on excursion include; factories, industries, accounting firms, offices, business organizations, post office, financial institutions and other business-related outfits. This is a manifestation of the fact that field-trip could promote effective teaching and learning of all aspects of business education such as accounting, commerce, entrepreneurship, insurance, marketing, office practice/procedure, secretarial duties/administration and word processing. Based on this, if a lecturer chooses to use the strategy, it would allow the students to observe, classify, collect data, study relationship and manipulate objects. It will also allow the students to learn on the basis of seeing for themselves. In line with this, seeing is said to be “believing” which implies that practical experience which creates lasting impression in the minds of the learners will all things being equal make learning of business education at the tertiary level of education to be effective.

In addition to the aforementioned, field-trip can promote effective teaching and learning of business education at the tertiary level through enhancing curriculum enrichment, encouraging the provision of current office materials for teaching purpose, availing the lecturers with relevant information which will aid illustrations in the classroom and providing opportunity for hands-on learning. These imply that the strategy can give rise to information that can lead to curriculum improvement which could make tertiary level business education to be tailored towards the need of the industry and the entire society, it could make the school administrators, government or private proprietors do away with obsolete instructional materials and provide the current ones for teaching. Furthermore, the lecturers will be exposed to new ideas that will enable them to give relevant and practical examples in the classroom. Lastly, it helps in enabling the learners to acquire psychomotor skills. This will therefore make them to have practical touch of what they learnt theoretically in the classroom.

Conclusion

Business education is a skill-based course which could be taught and learnt using different strategies. Field-trip allows the teachers to use community resources which are not available in the school to teach and make it possible for the learners to get practical touch of the theoretical knowledge they learnt in the classroom. The strategy could lead to effective teaching and learning of the business education at the tertiary level of education and the implication of these is that field-trip is a recipe for promoting effective teaching and learning of business education in Nigerian tertiary institutions in the sense that it makes the lecturers to serve as moderators, while the students play active roles leading to better acquisition of the desired skills.

Recommendations

Based on the foregoing as well as the conclusion which was drawn, the following recommendations are suggested as the way forward:

1. Lecturers should ensure that they adopt field-trip as part of their teaching strategies so as to enhance effectiveness in teaching and learning activities.
2. Lecturers should ensure that field-trip is properly planned and executed.
3. Lecturers who are willing to use field-trip should always be supported by their schools' managements.
4. Parents/guardians should support the lecturers by allowing their children/wards to participate in field-trip.
5. Students should be properly briefed on the nitty-gritty of the field-trip.

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Role of Mathematics Teachers at ... (Aliyu, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10687555>

Role of Mathematics Teachers at Secondary School Level of Education: Implication for National Development in Nigeria

Aliyu, Ganiyatu

Email: aliyuganiyatu@fugusau.edu.ng

Tel: 08035374735

Department of Science Education, Faculty of Education, Federal University Gusau, Zamfara State

Abstract

Secondary education remains a solid bridge in terms of knowledge gain in Nigerian school systems. Secondary education serves as the epicenter of the knowledge acquired by learners from pre-primary, primary, and basic education up to the college, polytechnic, and university levels. This paper focuses on mathematics teachers' role in secondary school education and its implications for national development. Secondary school education remains at the epicenter of levels of education, being the kind of education received by learners after primary education before they proceed to tertiary institutions. It also highlighted the role of mathematics teachers in secondary education for sustainable national development. However, the study concluded that the need for effective teaching of mathematics at the secondary school level of education is very important for sustainable national development. Therefore, a quality secondary education system will produce vibrant human resources that can be beneficial to Nigeria in terms of a sustainable economy and technological development. The paper, among others, recommended that Implement comprehensive teacher preparation programs that emphasize both deep content knowledge and effective pedagogical approaches in mathematics education, provides ongoing professional development opportunities for practicing mathematics teachers to stay abreast of advancements in mathematics education, pedagogy, and technology integration and ensure that mathematics teachers are adequately compensated for their expertise and dedication, fostering a sense of value and appreciation for their contributions and encourage mathematics teachers to pursue specialization and expertise in specific areas of mathematics, such as algebra, geometry, or statistics, to enhance their teaching proficiency.

Keywords: Mathematics, teachers' role, secondary education, national development.

Introduction

In view of the fast-growing technologically and scientifically engineered society of today, mathematics is a very important subject in that regard. Mathematics is a highly structured and important subject, and its teaching and learning deserve the highest level of seriousness from teachers in order to meet the desired national goal. Mathematics is a compulsory subject taught in both primary and secondary schools in Nigeria. Mathematics and its applications are all-encompassing, which explains its renown as an "everyday" subject and its importance in the curriculum. Today, it is a reality that it is the creation, mastery, and utilization of modern science and technology that basically differentiate the developing from the developed nations of the world. (Okeke, 2016) The foundation of science and technology, which is the basic requirement for the development of a nation, is mathematics (Eunice, 2020).

The National Policy on Education recommends the teaching of mathematics at all levels of education. In a similar vein, the National Policy on Science and Technology envisages an education system that shall emphasize all levels and re-orient the entire society towards scientific thinking in order to develop new technologies and adapt existing ones to improve societal wellbeing and security. The government has demonstrated commitment to this end by, among other things, directing that university admission into the science and liberal arts disciplines be in the ratio of 60 to 40 percent, respectively, and has even gone further to establish universities of science and technology (Eunice, 2020). Therefore, mathematics plays a vital role in nation-building, and mathematics is crucial for many careers and job opportunities in today's increasingly technological society. This study intends to clarify the concepts of mathematics teachers, secondary education, and national development with the intent of presenting the reciprocal benefits of one to the other.

Mathematics education is the practice of teaching and learning mathematics, as well as the scholarly research that goes with it in modern education (NCTM, 2000). Mathematicians are interested in the tools, methods, and approaches that make practice easier. The industrial revolution resulted in a massive increase in urban populations in the 18th and 19th centuries. Basic numeric skills, such as telling time, counting money, and simple arithmetic, were essential in this new urban lifestyle.

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Mathematics is integrated into the curriculum from an early age in the new public education systems. By the twentieth century, mathematics was taught in all developed countries as part of the core curriculum. The cultural impact of the "electric age" was also taken up by educational theory and the teaching of mathematics in the twentieth century, whereas previous approaches focused on "working with specialized problems in arithmetic" (Clements & Guryan, 2015). They also postulated that the "electric age" transformed mathematics education in the 20th century. The authors argue that the "electric age" led to a shift in the focus of mathematics education from "working with specialized problems in arithmetic" to a more conceptual and broad-based approach. They also discuss the role of technology in mathematics education, both in the 20th century and today. Here are some specific examples of how the "electric age" influenced mathematics education:

1. The invention of the calculator led to a shift away from rote memorization of arithmetic facts and towards a more conceptual understanding of mathematics.
2. The development of computers led to the creation of new tools for teaching and learning mathematics, such as computer algebra systems and dynamic geometry software.
3. The internet has made it possible for students to access a wealth of mathematical resources, including online textbooks, tutorials, and simulations.

The "electric age" has had a profound impact on mathematics education, and its influence is likely to continue in the years to come. Small children were meditating on number theory and sets as part of the emergent structural approach to knowledge (Clements & Guryan, 2015). The methods used in any given context are heavily influenced by the goals that the relevant educational system is attempting to achieve.

In order to have a viable system of education that can pilot the stirring of national development in Nigeria and any other country in the world, teachers play most of the important roles needed, which can be instilled in the learners through imitating teachers (Agan, 2010). Teachers, not only of mathematics but of every subject, perform most of the critical roles in setting the future goals that every nation intends to achieve for growth and development (Sarick, 2020). This is because teachers are the second parents to every school-going age, from elementary schools through senior secondary levels (pre-primary, primary, and secondary schools). Teachers go to great lengths to ensure that students achieve the highest level of learning and are responsible in their future endeavors. Throughout their service periods, teachers consider what is best for the students and where they should be placed around the world. Teachers' good intentions are only to help and invest heavily in national growth and development.

Mathematics Teacher at Secondary School level of Education

A mathematics teacher is someone who inspires students to look beyond the pages of the textbook to become problem solvers and critical thinkers. As a mathematics teacher, you are ensuring that your students will have the knowledge and skills that will help them not only succeed in the classroom but also be empowered by mathematics to become productive citizens of our democratic society. (NCTM, 2019) According to Odogwu and Odafe (2013), a mathematics teacher is a purposeful leader who impacts mathematics information or skills on another individual or group of individuals. Therefore, a mathematics teacher is one who organizes the mathematics learning experience in a conducive environment where learning can conveniently take place. Mathematics teachers are also individuals who assist others in acquiring mathematical knowledge. Singh (2010) outlined, among other things, the following qualities of a good mathematics teacher for effective mathematics teaching in secondary school settings: 1) He must possess a basic qualification in the subject 2) In terms of abilities, he must be aware of his students' capabilities 3) He must be an innovator who changes teaching strategies, techniques, texts, and material and 4) He must be a model of enthusiasm for not only mathematics but other subjects in the curriculum. From the above, mathematics teachers are the sole agents in the teaching and designing of learning. The bedrock of the development of any nation could be traced to education, while education cannot exist without teachers.

Mathematics at Secondary School level of Education in Nigeria

Education is a tool that avails people of knowledge, skill, technique, and information, which empowers them to know their rights and duties toward the family, society, and nation. One of the most important benefits of education in a society is that it improves the standard of living and allows individuals to contribute to the development of the nation or society (Adam, 2016). Secondary education is the basic catalyst that will bring about the development of an individual and society. The importance of secondary education in our educational system cannot be overemphasized. Apart from serving as a link between primary and secondary education, it provides the opportunity for a child to acquire additional knowledge, skills, and traits beyond the primary level. A major factor that necessitates the acquisition of secondary education in Nigeria is that the education

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being provided at the primary level is proving insufficient for a child to acquire the permanent literacy, communication, and numeracy skills expected of him or her at the end of the training. Ige, (2011). Also, secondary education remains at the centre, being the kind of education received by learners after primary education before they proceed to tertiary institutions (FRN, 2013). The following are the aims and objectives of secondary education in Nigeria as stipulated in the national policies on education: 1) preparation of students for useful living within society 2) preparation of students for higher education 3) Diversification of the curriculum to cater for the differences in talents, opportunities, and roles opened to students after their secondary school course; 4) Raising a generation of people who can think for themselves, respect the views and feelings of others, and 5) Fostering Nigerian unity with an emphasis on communities that unite us in our diversity. According to the above terms and objectives, secondary school is the bridge between the primary and tertiary levels. It is the springboard from which all the students of higher education take off, and all primary school leavers must pass through it to become useful to them, their families, and society. According to Lere (2014), who pointed out that Nigeria is a country in search of development and that national development is realizable through general education.

Mathematics for sustainable National Development

National development is the ability of a country to improve the social welfare of its people. It involves the development of infrastructure such as roads, hospitals, airports, schools, quality education, and the health sector, as well as the development of its citizens. According to Easterly (2021), economic development is an essential component of national development, but it is not the only factor. True national development requires a broader set of conditions that promote inclusive growth, equitable distribution of resources, and sustainable progress. Easterly's work provides a valuable framework for understanding the complex relationship between economic development and national development. Ichipi and Panya (2016) proposed that national economic development can be defined as a country's or nation's overall development or collective socioeconomic, political, and religious advancement. Also, national development can be viewed as the capacity of the country to raise the standard of living of its residents. It can be accomplished by providing individuals with the necessities of life, such as food and shelter, as well as employment.

Significant role of Mathematics Teachers for sustainable National Development

Gadanidis and Petoczky (2022) are of the view that mathematics teachers play an indispensable role in shaping the future of nations. By nurturing critical thinking, fostering innovation, promoting informed decision-making, preparing students for the future of work, and cultivating global citizenship, mathematics teachers are not merely educators; they are architects of sustainable national development. Investing in mathematics teachers is an investment in the future of humanity, paving the way for a world that is more equitable, prosperous, and sustainable. A mathematics teacher should realize that the mathematics classroom is an artificial environment full of individuals with their own learning experiences. The role of secondary mathematics teachers in promoting national development is critical in the country. **Most of the Key Roles of Mathematics Teachers in Sustainable National Development** as provided by Gadanidis and Petoczky, (2022, p. 419) are highlighted as;

1. **Nurturing Critical Thinkers and Problem-Solvers:** Mathematics teachers equip students with the ability to analyse information, evaluate arguments, and formulate creative solutions to challenges, fostering a citizenry capable of addressing societal issues effectively.
2. **Promoting Innovation and Creativity:** Mathematics teachers encourage students to think outside the box, embrace experimentation, and explore new ideas, fostering a culture of innovation that drives progress and advancement.
3. **Empowering Informed Decision-Making:** Mathematics literacy is crucial for informed decision-making, enabling individuals to make sound choices about their own lives and contribute to the development of their communities.
4. **Preparing for the Future of Work:** Mathematics education equips students with the skills and adaptability necessary to thrive in an ever-changing employment landscape, characterized by automation, technological advancements, and new industries.
5. **Fostering Global Citizenship:** Mathematics provides a common language that transcends cultural and linguistic barriers, enabling individuals to collaborate and address global challenges effectively.

Also, the provides that Investing in Mathematics Teachers can help in recognizing the transformative power of mathematics education, governments and educational institutions must prioritize investments in mathematics teachers. This includes:

- i. **High-Quality Teacher Training:** Providing aspiring mathematics teachers with rigorous training programs that emphasize both content knowledge and pedagogical skills.

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- ii. **Continuous Professional Development:** Offering ongoing professional development opportunities for practicing mathematics teachers to stay abreast of advancements in mathematics education and pedagogy.
- iii. **Competitive Compensation and Support:** Ensuring that mathematics teachers are adequately compensated and provided with the resources and support they need to be effective in their roles.
- iv. **Promoting Collaboration and Mentorship:** Fostering a culture of collaboration and mentorship among mathematics teachers, enabling them to share best practices and support each other's professional growth.
- v. **Recognizing Excellence:** Acknowledging and celebrating the achievements of outstanding mathematics teachers, inspiring others and raising the overall quality of mathematics education.

In a comprehensive manner, the contribution of secondary education to national development cannot be overemphasized. Secondary schools serve as the recruitment grounds for the tertiary institutions in the country. Secondary education supplies the needed manpower for national development. According to Kasim & Usman (2019), a developed or educated society is one that has enough manpower and each person occupies his or her rightful position to enhance the growth of the society. Secondary education promotes social and group relationships. The school system within the educational system fosters this development. The school brings people of different cultural backgrounds together for a common purpose. Secondary education also promotes the culture of productivity by enabling individuals to discover their creative potential and apply it. The improvement of their existing skills and techniques when performing specific tasks, thereby increasing the efficiency of their personal and societal efforts.

Mathematics teachers and educators have an important role to play in national development. A mathematics teacher should realize that the mathematics classroom is an artificial environment full of individuals with their own learning experiences. It is well known that the quality and extent of learner achievement are determined primarily by teacher competence, sensitivity, and motivation. The National Council for Teacher Education has defined teacher education as "a program of education, research, and training of persons to teach from pre-primary to higher education levels." Teacher education is a program related to the development of teacher proficiency and competence that would enable and empower the teacher to meet the requirements of the profession and face the challenges therein. The role of secondary mathematics teachers in promoting national development is critical for a country like Nigeria. Mathematics teacher education has to become more sensitive to the emerging demands of the school system. For this, it has to prepare mathematics teachers for a dual role as stated by Arora, (2002, p.24) in a book titled "mathematics teachers and their teaching" as to;

1. encouraging, supportive, and humane facilitator in teaching-learning situations who enables learners (students) to discover their talents, realize their physical and intellectual potentialities to the fullest, develop character and desirable social and human values to function as responsible citizens, and,
2. An active member of the group of persons who make conscious effort to contribute towards the process of renewal of the school curriculum to maintain its relevance to the changing societal needs and personal needs of learners, keeping in view the experiences gained in the past and the concerns and imperatives that have emerged in the light of changing national development goals and educational priorities

The role of mathematics teachers in Nigeria and many other developing countries cannot be overemphasized. Even with the advent of technology, no tool has been able to completely replace a teacher. The National Policy on Education (FRN, 2013) maintained that no educational system can rise above the quality of its teachers. Mathematics teachers have an important role to play in promoting national development. When all students are educated in a classroom environment, mathematics teachers are capable of handling and guiding all the students in the classroom in teaching and learning, which can help to promote national development. Therefore, teachers of mathematics, with their developed skills, can impart mathematical knowledge to students in a classroom environment in order to help them become self-reliant and productive individuals since mathematics is the bedrock of all civilizations. Mathematics knowledge gained from a mathematics teacher assists students in making future plans. The knowledge of mathematics is being applied everywhere, like in the economy of a country and the construction of buildings, among others. With the knowledge of mathematics, students can practice agriculture, and mathematics plays a role in investments, advertising, revenue generation, and investment.

If we go by the position acclaimed by mathematics as true, then paying lip service to it would not make its benefits a reality. A new attitude must be adopted on the part of the government to reward the teaching and learning of mathematics. Not only the government but all stakeholders' students, teachers, parents, and the entire society should be committed to mathematics teaching and learning. The government's first and most beautiful step has been to make mathematics a core subject in the school curriculum from primary to secondary school levels. The mathematics teacher is the sole stakeholder in the national development that this study is based on, especially secondary school mathematics teachers. The teacher is pivotal in the

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acquisition of mathematical knowledge (Afolabi, 2020). Adler and Rippin (2023) discuss the role of the teacher as a mentor in mathematics education. They argue that effective mathematics teachers go beyond simply imparting knowledge and skills; they act as mentors, guiding and supporting students as they develop their mathematical understanding. Based on the Adler and Rippin (2023) report several key characteristics of effective mathematics mentors are identified as:

1. **Deep understanding of mathematics:** Mentors should have a deep understanding of the mathematics they are teaching, enabling them to provide clear explanations, answer students' questions effectively, and identify and address misconceptions.
2. **Ability to connect mathematics to real-world contexts:** Mentors should be able to connect mathematical concepts to real-world applications, making mathematics more relevant and engaging for students.
3. **Strong communication and interpersonal skills:** Mentors should have strong communication and interpersonal skills, enabling them to create a supportive learning environment where students feel comfortable asking questions and taking risks.
4. **Ability to differentiate instruction:** Mentors should be able to differentiate instruction to meet the needs of all learners, providing appropriate challenges and support for students at different levels of mathematical proficiency.
5. **Passion for mathematics:** Mentors should have a passion for mathematics, which is contagious and can inspire students to develop their own love of the subject.

Adler and Rippin (2023) conclude that mentoring is essential for effective mathematics education. They argue that by acting as mentors, teachers can help students develop the confidence, perseverance, and problem-solving skills they need to succeed in mathematics and beyond.

Conclusion

Mathematics as a subject is vital to understanding many other subjects. A good understanding and knowledge of mathematics is an indispensable instrument in many other fields, including the social sciences, engineering, medicine, and the natural sciences. Based on the importance of mathematics, it is hereby concluded that without mathematics, there can be no development. Investing in mathematics teachers is an investment in Nigeria's future. By enhancing their training, fostering a culture of collaboration, addressing resource deficiencies, promoting innovative teaching strategies, and supporting their well-being, Nigeria can empower its mathematics teachers to play a pivotal role in shaping the nation's development. Through effective mathematics education, Nigeria can nurture a generation of critical thinkers, problem-solvers, and innovators capable of driving sustainable progress and prosperity.

Recommendations

To produce good mathematics education output at the secondary school level in Nigeria therefore, this study recommends among others that there is need for stakeholders, government, school administrators and non-governmental organisations to;

1. Implement comprehensive teacher preparation programs that emphasize both deep content knowledge and effective pedagogical approaches in mathematics education.
2. Provide ongoing professional development opportunities for practicing mathematics teachers to stay abreast of advancements in mathematics education, pedagogy, and technology integration and ensure that mathematics teachers are adequately compensated for their expertise and dedication, fostering a sense of value and appreciation for their contributions
3. Encourage mathematics teachers to pursue specialization and expertise in specific areas of mathematics, such as algebra, geometry, or statistics, to enhance their teaching proficiency.
4. Establish collaborative learning communities among mathematics teachers to share best practices, discuss challenges, and provide mutual support and Encourage peer observation and feedback sessions among mathematics teachers to provide constructive feedback and improve teaching practices.
5. Provide mathematics teachers with access to up-to-date textbooks, supplementary resources, and technology tools for effective instruction and incorporate real-world applications of mathematics into lessons to demonstrate the relevance of mathematics to students' lives and future careers.
6. Upgrade and maintain mathematics laboratories with modern equipment, technology, and software to support hands-on learning and experimentation.

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7. Ensure that all secondary schools have reliable internet access to facilitate online learning resources, professional development opportunities, and communication with colleagues and Integrate technology effectively into mathematics instruction to enhance visualization, data analysis, and problem-solving capabilities
8. Encourage mathematics teachers to incorporate active learning strategies, such as project-based learning, inquiry-based learning, and collaborative problem-solving, to engage students and promote deeper understanding

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Test Anxiety and Interventions for Mental Health and Improvement in Learning Outcome among Secondary School Students in Nigeria: Implication for Counselling

Akpeji, Ozavogu¹

Email: ozavoguakpeji@gmail.com

Tel: +2348065331448

Dange, Abdullahi Sulaiman²

Email: alhajiheadmaster@gmail.com

Tel: +2348036970807

¹Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education & Extension Services, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto

²College of Arts and Humanities, Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic Sokoto

Abstract

The paper analysed past reviews regarding test anxiety as it affects students in their learning outcome. The purpose of this paper is to give a qualitative analysis of test anxiety and its interventions for mental health and improvement in learning outcome among secondary school students. The paper also identified causes of test anxiety and coping strategies for test anxiety. The paper noted that it is necessary to pay attention to the fact that test anxiety is common among students but it varies in degrees. For some students' it may be beneficial, for others it may lead to poor academic performance and may cause negative effect on their wellness. It further states that for a person to be seen as adjusted to test anxiety issues his/her state of mind as well as general mental health should be seen to be stable and the individual should be able to effectively make use of his/her capacity by showing psychological reliance in taking personal and social adjustments to meet with the ever-changing environment within which he/she co-exist. The paper suggest that teachers and other stakeholders involved in the process of educating the students should emphasize on the importance of holistic preparation for test, in order to prevent the negative effects of test anxiety and ensure a stable physical and mental health in their process of learning.

Keywords: Test Anxiety, Mental Health, Interventions, Students and Counselling.

Introduction

Anxiety is a typical occurrence that establishes a cause of poor academic performance among students. Anxiety leads to self-preoccupation which is manifested as self-minimization and results in negative cognitive assessment, lack of focus, negative physiological reactions, mental health problems and academic setback. Anxiety has its origin in early childhood with both developmental and environmental elements; these elements are all connected to perceived feelings of insecurity and inadequacy that are conveyed into adulthood. Anxiety is also viewed as a reoccurring effect of tension resulting from anticipated necessity. Atsehe, Kwaghgbah, Iorlumun and Agbecha, (2022) noted that anxiety is a state of uneasiness, worry or feeling of uncertainty about impending or on-going programmes, examinations or tests. Cognitive performance and information processing may be critically affected by anxiety. Anxiety is one of the emotional components of a person's life. Every task performance to an extent is accomplished by some measures of anxiety. Anxiety as a collection of physiological and cognitive reactions forms disturbances, fear of failure and stomach discomfort. It is a menace that has eaten deep into the fabric of student's life and at the same time, become an obstacle to their progress. (Agbor, Chile & Ruth, 2020).

Anxiety was defined by Bethel-Eke, and Ikpa, (2017) as the experiencing of an undesirable and unclear like feeling, which the individual predicts a negative outcome of an activity. The extreme level of anxiety impairs an individual's mental and physical health and also has a negative effect on the persons, social, occupational, and educational performance. Anxiety can be divided into two categories: state anxiety and trait anxiety. The trait anxiety is described as the individual's capability to perceive different situations from the environment like danger and threat. On the other hand, state anxiety is described as the perception of individual's emotional situation. State anxiety is also seen as a transient response to stress that consist of subjective feeling of worry, nervousness, apprehension, tension and arousal of autonomic nervous system (Sudheer & Naachimuthu, 2022).

In recent years "test anxiety" has evolved with different variety of definitions and different researchers have given their views of the concept which has increased the needed knowledge of the concept. Test anxiety is grouped under a category

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of anxious states and negative emotions that are often linked with neuroticism. Owens-Sogolo, (2021) explains that test anxiety is often developed out of fear of negative evaluation, it is comparable to social phobia, which causes fears of being negatively judged and these might lead to students spending more of their time worrying about the outcome of an expected test and how others will judge their performance than on the test itself. It is also feeling of worry, apprehension, nervousness or uneasiness that occurs when a student encounters test or examination in any form and at any level (Balogun, Balogun & Onyencho, 2017). Biologically individual's genetic makeup predisposes them to react differently to anxiety provoking situations. The environment a person belongs to may also play a role in contributing to the reaction to stimuli. Getting used to exam phobia due to negative perception which is associated with failure, will bring about different levels of anxiety in different individuals. In most situations it is expected that students' levels of test anxiety will increase during the examination period as compared to other school activities. Koramoah, Dzakadzie and Danyoh, (2022) explained that a little anxiety during exams is required which will help students to get motivated and learn. Mounting up so much of anxiety will not help the student to perform, rather it will influence the academic performance negatively. Some of the psychological symptoms that build up in students before a test include difficulty in concentrating, restlessness, insomnia, fatigue, abdominal pain among others.

Test anxiety has induced an unfavorable condition which constitutes intense fear of test situations which affects the mental health of the individual. Students who experience high level of test anxiety are more likely to perform poorly academically. Persistent test anxiety is associated with low academic performance. The need for the study of students is warranted, because of the disturbing cases of poor academic performance in schools (Balogun, Balogun & Onyencho, 2017). Mental health can be seen as a state of mind of an individual that can effectively make use of his or her capacity by showing psychological reliance in taking personal and social adjustments to meet with the ever-changing environment within which he or she co-exist with people (Eze & Mgbenkemdi, 2019). Student's test anxiety is one of the biggest problems that affect the mental health which in most cases is seen as the reason for poor academic performance. The need for strategies for lifelong adjustment have been noted over the years by stakeholders in the education sector as one of the most viable options for student's positive performance expectations. Students are often expected to study hard and improve their study habits. Even if classes are larger, instructors should have different teaching techniques, which could help them still pay attention to those who need them in solving their anxiety issues (Galle, Atiku & Bala, 2020).

The fear of one's ability to do well in a testing situation is one of the main reasons for students experiencing anxiety. Anxiety prevents students from showing the most of their ability on examination. This is because students in most cases have phobia for examinations. Examination anxiety comes with various symptoms; that include insomnia, lack of appetite and lack of concentration (Tambaya, 2019). Bentil, Donkor, Oti, and Adzifome, (2020). Investigated the factors that trigger test anxiety while using coping strategies needed to reduce anxiety among Junior High School students in the Effutu Municipality. The investigations employed the cross-sectional descriptive survey design with quantitative approach where through proportionate stratified random sampling was carried out, a sample of 746 students was obtained from both public and private Junior High Schools in the three (3) circuits of the Effutu Municipality. Data was collected using a structured questionnaire and analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The study revealed that even though different kinds of factors trigger test and examination anxiety amongst the students, lack of self-esteem was the most contributory factor while subject load of the students shows the least influence on test anxiety. The study further established that good study habits as well as skills, effective teacher support, motivation, reduction of students' workload, updating curricular activities, and having enough resting and sleeping time were the coping strategies to be employed to reduce test anxiety. Additionally, it was found that factors such as having low self-confidence, past experience and beliefs about test, history of consistent poor academic performance, subject load, and psychological factors jointly contributed significantly to test anxiety among students. Besides, motivation of students, reduction of subject load and good teachers support for students were the coping strategies needed to manage examination anxiety. Based on these results, it was recommended that regular educational programmes such as symposia and school festivals should be conducted to heighten students' self-esteem, and remove negative past experiences and beliefs about test while exploring other coping strategies to reduce test anxiety for better academic performance.

Causes of Anxiety

Anxiety is the experience of feeling anxious from time to time as well as nervousness and thudding of a person's heart, the shortness of breath, and the mind going places within the person's mind without control. Despite some negative attributes of anxiety, it can also be seen as a big contributor of us staying alive as human beings because it helps us not to take things for granted. The early exposure to stress and the experience of trauma are substantial risk factors for anxiety disorders. Anxiety has biological causes, such as issues with the regulation of neurotransmitters and heritable genetic causes (Smoller, 2016; Milne

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& Munro 2020). The ability to relate to a person who experiences anxiety is a crucial part of a therapeutic relationship and, as such, it is crucial to acknowledge that anxiety is not ‘just’ a mental state but also has physiological causes and responses, which can be frightening (Milne & Munro 2020). A recent review identified that there is a genetic heritability of around 30% for GAD and that the same predisposing genes are present across sexes (Gottschalk & Domschke, 2017; Milne & Munro 2020). Pro-inflammatory markers have also been shown to directly modulate affective behaviour and heightened concentrations of inflammatory signals have been described in GAD, post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), panic disorder and phobias (Milne & Munro 2020). Exposure to stress has been linked to anxiety, as well as having a negative impact on the body’s immune, cardiovascular, neuroendocrine and central nervous systems (Khan & Khan, 2017; Milne & Munro 2020). Physical health problems can also cause anxiety disorders, in some people with a malignant disease, for example, a response of anxiety is understandable however, in other individuals, anxiety may increase to an extreme level, if it does not improve.

Test anxiety is a common phenomenon among students, and anxiety disorders are increasingly prevalent among them (Milne & Chakraborty, 2023). Studies also have suggested that older students tend to experience more stress than younger students, and female students have a higher likelihood of experiencing anxiety than male students (Milne & Chakraborty, 2023). Tertiary students are seen to encounter different challenges, such as adapting to new environments that can alter their routines and habits. Additionally, there is an increased demand for academic success. These emotions can have adverse effects on their academic performance, subsequently causing heightened levels of stress, depression, and anxiety (Milne & Chakraborty, 2023). Research has determined the effects of test anxiety on academic outcomes, given that this phenomenon stems from various sources. Numerous studies have ventured into the complex interplay between psychological, physiological, and environmental factors that contribute to the onset of test anxiety, and how it can impair students' ability to perform at their optimal. Different studies have suggested that inadequate preparation may be the underlying cause of test anxiety in students. It has also been postulated that the fear of poor performance or failing to meet one's own or others' expectations can cause a vicious cycle of anxiety, leading to decreased motivation and increased negative self-talk. Such disturbing thought patterns can further escalate the feeling of poor preparation, creating feedback that can in great measure hamper students' test-taking abilities (Chakraborty, 2023).

According to Naveh-Benjamin, Craik, Guez and Dori as cited in Chakraborty, (2023), highly test-anxious students exhibit lower aptitude in organising the material to be learned in contrast to their less anxious peers. Their research has shed light on the pivotal role of anxiety in impeding students' cognitive processing and information retrieval. Individuals experiencing high levels of test anxiety tend to experience cognitive overload, which can impair their ability to spot critical information from irrelevant information, organise it effectively, and integrate it into their existing knowledge base. As a result, test-anxious students may struggle to perform well on tests, leading to a vicious cycle of anxiety, poor performance, and decreased self-confidence. Several research studies have consistently noted that students with high levels of test anxiety tend to have suboptimal academic behaviors in contrast to their less anxious counterparts (Chakraborty, 2023). This observation is further corroborated by Hembree as cited in Chakraborty, (2023), which postulated that ineffective study skills can contribute to poor academic performance, leading to heightened anxiety levels during subsequent examinations.

Interventions for Test Anxiety

Anyone who faces test or exam anxiety is vulnerable to the negative impact on their test or exams and mental health. The need for effective interventions of test anxiety for lifelong adjustments of students cannot be over emphasized. Majority of interventions focuses on increasing cognitive restructuring. Nevertheless, most practical interventions focus on improving the whole picture of an individual's test-taking behaviors. Test-anxious students can learn several cognitive behavioral techniques, such as fighting irrational beliefs with self-reinforcing statements, self-instruction, and coping strategies when faced with the sensation of anxiety. The major goal of cognitive behavioral interventions for anxiety is to help the students recognize irrational or maladaptive thoughts and replace those thoughts with more realistic versions of the initial perception. Grouping of the various methods students have in approaching learning tasks. Dodgson in Ossai (2012) grouped these methods to include the utilization of those procedures known as “SQ3R” and others. The SQ3R method includes a series of five steps designated by the initials S-Q-R-R-R. The first step “S” that is to be employed is the survey of the material by reading the parts of the chapter that gives an overview of the topics covered. The next step is the “Q” in SQ3R which stands for question. Formulate a question either aloud or in writing-before actually reading a section of the material. The following step “R” is to read the materials. This involves reading carefully and even more importantly, reading actively and critically. The next step is the second “R” which stands for ‘recite’ meaning to recite what is been read and describe to one or ones reading partner. The final “R”

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refers to review. This will involve looking over the information and re-reading the features in one's textbook that provide one with an overview of the chapter.

Coping and life adjustment strategies for test anxiety

Test Anxiety is common and disabling. Today it seems more and more often students experience anxiety. If you suffer from test anxiety, there are a number of coping strategies that you can employ. Below are some tips to help you cope.

1. Preparing well for your test can help reduce test anxiety. First, make sure you have done all you have to do in terms of preparation. Cramming for a test or exam will only increase anxiety, so give yourself enough time to learn your materials well.
2. Always being negative of one's self can worsen test anxiety. When performance suffers because of test anxiety, it can be easy to fall into a downward spiral of negative thinking. Check what you say to yourself and replace any negative thoughts with positive ones.
3. Some thoughts are not helpful such as I should have prepared more than I did, I must be an unfortunate person and I have to do well, everything is on the line. It is better to tell yourself positive things like I am prepared for this test, I am smart enough to do well and Even if I don't do well, it's not the end of the world.
4. It is important you arrive early for your exam to reduce anxiety. Nothing will heighten anxiety like the feeling of rushing to get to a test. Arrive at least few minutes early. If waiting for the test to begin makes you nervous, revise your notes to keep your mind occupied. Avoid people who are anxious before a test and do not second guess what you know.
5. Make use of relaxation strategies such as muscle relaxation and take your imagination off negative things as well as control rapid breathing. Use these strategies in the weeks leading up to a test, and during the testing situation as needed.
6. Maintain focus and stay away from distractions during a test. During the test, do everything you can to avoid talking or answering anybody. Remember to take your time but check your watch to pace yourself. Before starting the test, do a quick review and read directions twice. Start with the easiest questions first.
7. Accept that you can accommodate little test anxiety. Recognize that a little bit of anxiety before a test is a good thing. If you did not feel nervous at all, you might not be motivated to do your best. It is only when anxiety becomes hard to manage that it is a problem.
8. Gratify yourself for overcoming your test anxiety. Plan a reward for yourself after the test. Take some time to enjoy yourself and clear your mind. Do not dwell on mistakes you may have made or worry about whether you did well or not. Whenever possible, give yourself a break before studying for another test.

Counselling Implication

Counselling encourages the use of therapeutic approach in handling problems that affect clients. Based on this, the therapeutic approaches that can be used in reducing academic anxiety are behavioral therapy (BT), cognitive therapy (CT), and cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT). BT, such as systematic desensitization or applied relaxation, principally intervening in the somatic symptoms of test anxiety, whilst CT, such as rational-emotive therapy or schema-based therapy, which is used to treat cognitive beliefs and structures for modification. CBT combine's treatment principles from both BT and CT approaches (Huntley, Young, Jha, & Fisher, 2019). CBT intend to discover and modify the client's thinking patterns that are associated with anxiety and worrying feelings. This type of treatment has two main parts: a cognitive part made to limit distorted thinking and a behavioral part designed to change the way people react to the objects or situations that trigger anxiety. For example, a client receiving cognitive-behavioral therapy for anxiety disorder might work on learning that experiencing panic attacks does not mean that one's heart is failing.

CBT assist people faced with their fears and try to help them become desensitized to anxiety-triggering situations. Psychotherapy is another treatment of counselling for anxiety disorders. It involves a client talking to a trained mental health professional, psychiatrist, psychologist, or counsellor. Sessions may explore the causes of anxiety and possible ways to deal with symptoms. The intent of CBT is to help the client or counselee think more positively about life and free himself from unhelpful patterns of behaviour. CBT deals with current situations more than events in client's past or childhood. CBT has been shown to work for a variety of mental health problems. In particular, CBT can help with: depression, anxiety, panic attacks, phobias, obsessive compulsive disorder and so on.

Huntley, Young, Jha, & Fisher, (2019) Explained that there are two main forms of educational intervention for test anxiety; 'Test-wiseness' training that focuses on the skills needed to take an examination (e.g. surveying a written test to know which questions are given greater marks and so require more time and attention) and study skills training that focuses on ways

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of learning and encoding material in the most optimal way e.g. more emphasis on deeper levels of processing of to-be-learned material and less emphasis on rote memorization.

Conclusion

The paper concludes that it is normal for students to have test anxiety that helps them prepare themselves for a test, on the other hand it also states that uncontrollable test anxiety can also negatively disturb the students and affect them physically, emotionally, as well as cognitively and can result in poor test performance. It further states that for a person to be seen as adjusted to test anxiety issues his/her state of mind and general mental health should be seen to effectively make use of his/her capacity by showing psychological reliance in taking personal and social adjustments to meet with the ever-changing environment within which he/she co-exist. The study affirms that major causes of test anxiety among students are high grades expectations, phobia for failing and judgment of their academic performance by others which in turn negatively affects the outcome of their test.

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An Overview of Trauma-Informed Education and Counselling in Nigeria

Anake, P. M¹

Email: anakepaulina@gmail.com

Tel: 08034839236

Anyin, Nnyenkpa N¹

Email: nnyenkpaanyin595@gmail.com

Tel: 08160407330

Dibang, Sunday T²

Tel: 08060711103

Anake, Godwin A³

Tel 07066260025

¹Department of Guidance and Counselling, University of Calabar, Calabar

²Department of Geography, Faculty of Environmental Science, University of Calabar, Calabar

³University of Calabar Teaching Hospital, Calabar

Abstract

This work is an opinion paper on trauma informed education and counselling. The manuscript looked at the historical development of guidance and counselling in western world and Nigeria inclusive. It also revealed that counselling practices in Nigeria involves a relationship between the professional counsellors and counsellee or client or a group of clients in an attempt to help him or her make adequate choices and adjusts his or her life. Historical development of guidance and counselling; trauma informed education in Nigeria; trauma informed counselling interventions for Internally Displace Persons (IDPs) in Nigeria; trauma informed counselling and menace of drug use or addiction in Nigerian schools; trauma-informed counselling and mental health; and the ethical standards for the relationship were stated. Thus, trauma informed education in Nigeria (which calls for counselling intervention to prevent the problem or crisis from further occurrence) was discussed extensively. These include trauma informed counselling interventions for internally displace persons (IDPs) in Nigeria; trauma informed counselling and menace of drug use/addiction in Nigerian schools; and trauma-informed counselling and mental health.

Keywords: Trauma, informed education, counselling, Nigeria

Introduction

Trauma is an adverse experience that compromises an individual's sense of being safe in relationships and in the world around them, and can significantly inhibit both self-regulatory and relational capacities required for successful learning (Brunzell, 2021). In recent years, there has been growing awareness of the widespread prevalence of trauma experiences. Trauma is a physiological and psychological experience where an individual experiences overwhelming fear for their life either literally or figuratively (Van der Kolk, 2014). One can figuratively fear for their life through witnessing a violent act or accident without being directly involved, such as witnessing a car accident where a person dies. After a traumatic event or a series of events, it is normal for one to experience fear, stress and a heightened state of alertness (Shonkoff et al 2012). With simple trauma, these experiences tend to be brief, often occurring only once, however, complex relational trauma occurs over time. The effects of complex relational trauma are profound and multiple. Trauma informed education helps teachers understand the impacts of trauma and suggests proactive strategies to position the school itself as a predictable milieu for healing and growth. Trauma informed education practices is a mindset, an acceptance of diversity, including background, knowledge, skills and life experiences and an understanding that some of those life experiences may be varied. Trauma informed education can help create an equitable learning environment supportive of all learners (Najjaar, 2023).

Trauma informed education plays education is played out as foremost in ensuring that the policy of education and goals are actualized in its citizenry. Thus, trauma informed education and counselling is geared towards ensuring mental

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wellbeing, drug use and addiction, skills and ethics and counselling intervention may perhaps address and arrest the overwhelming flood of traumatized individuals in the institutions of learning. Trauma informed counsellors are open and honest with clients. They make sure that they are education and up-to-date with clients who have experienced trauma. They are also aware of the unique cultural considerations that each client experiences (Marschall, 2023).

Historical development of guidance and counselling in the western world

Formal counselling started in the western countries as a philanthropically outreach to children who were maltreated in factories as factory workers. Jersey B. Ravis in 1898-1907, on philosophical and moral grounds, did not like child labour. He gathered children in the stress and talked to them on how they were used for selfish interest. He saw the practice as an extreme situation of child abuse and abuse of their fundamental human rights. He said that they were used as slaves by the employers to work for them at the expense of schooling (Enya & Obot, 2021).

In the same vein in 1900 in Boston Frank Parson also showed concern about child abuse. He was dissatisfied with how children were being handled by industrialists. Between 1900-1960, many people had become involved in the in and out of school activity. In Michigan schools, principals organized the children and addressed them in a forum that resembled a career seminar. They even taught career education in their English lesson.

In 1910, efforts were collated and put in a journal called National vocational guidance Association (NVGA). In 1915, a conference was organized in Boston City involving all pioneer guidance workers. Later, emphasis shifted from children to all who had to work in both public and private enterprises. In 1952, American Personnel and Guidance Association (APGA) was formed to replace the former body. In 1983-85, took a name American Association for Counselling and Development (AACD). Under this name they become a larger organization in behavioural sciences that had to do with human organization. This expansion was facilitated by factors such as philanthropy, personality awareness, mental hygiene movement and religious organizations that gave the association enough challenges.

In line with the formal guidance started in Nigeria in 1959 among some religious sisters from Ireland in St. Theresa's College, Oke Afa, Ibadan. The Rev. Sisters organized careers' week activities and invited community members to advise and direct them on the placement of their final year students. The advisers were not guidance counsellors, but they were experience in job selection and placement of secondary school graduates. This group formed themselves into a group called Ibadan Careers Council. They further organized workshops for career mistresses and masters on vocational guidance in Ibadan. Similarly, at the Comprehensive High School, Aiyetoro, guidance programme commenced with the use of American Standardized Tests by a Harvard (USAID) (Denga, 2012). These Harvard USAID sponsored counselors at Aiyetoro really started the guidance programme in Nigeria. They trained some Nigerian counselors in the task of implementing vocational and educational counselling. In 1974, the idea of school guidance had spread to all parts of Nigeria.

Today, the professional body is known as the Counselling Association of Nigeria (CASSON). The second and third national development plans of 1970 and 1972, respectively backed up the innovation of guidance and counselling and it growth rapidly in Nigeria. Counselling practice in Nigeria involves a relationship between the professional counsellors and counsellee or client or a group of clients in an attempt to help him or her make adequate choices and adjusts his or her life. The ethical standards for this type of relationship are as follows: 1) to respect the integrity of the individual; 2) to keep counselling information confidential; 3) make the counsellee to be aware of the purpose, goals, techniques and rules of the procedure and limitations of the counselling activities; 4) make referrals to other professionals or specialists you feel can assist the counsellee; and 5) where there is an evaluative relationship between professional and client, counselling is not necessary or may not be successful. Based on this historical origin of guidance and counselling in Nigeria, trauma informed education which calls for counselling intervention to prevent the problem or crisis from further occurrence.

Trauma informed education (TIE) in Nigeria

Life holds much in stuck for all who are born into the world. Unfortunately, not all who are born into this world would go through life's channels without facing adversities. Adversity constitutes life challenges that overwhelm individual(s), but coping skills and ability to overcome these challenges when not possessed by those who needs them; it becomes a traumatic situation. Trauma as it were is used to describe a gamut of stressful event that invitro children pass through (children and young adults up to the age of 24 years. Trauma can include collection of adversities in its entirety that afflicts a child directly and indirectly. These assortments of experience include physical abuses such as kicking, slapping, hitting, spitting on and multiple others. These may lead them to emotional trauma such as withdrawal of affections, neglects, snide remarks, negative confrontations, shouting and verbal missiles; these abuses are related to familial experiences among household members and

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close relationship. Abuses sweep across the sexual and non-sexual approaches. Such abuse on a child and young adults leaves them paralyzed throughout life time. Trauma can occur at variant levels and at different stages of a child's life her or she may experience trauma. Examples of such trauma are parental separation, domestic violence, parental drug abuse, financial hardship and mental instructionalization of parents.

Birtwek (2017) adjoined that trauma is an overwhelming experience that undermines a person's belief in himself and the world. In a same light, Samhsa (2014) defined trauma as the various ways an individual had been exposed to various experiences that engulfs both the internal and external coping resources available to them, submerging them into a sense of extreme threat that inflict negative effects on their function and wellbeing. The American Psychological Association (2022) flashed out that trauma may have concocted as a result of various adversities, which may be natural or man-made disasters. Furthermore, Bellis et al (2014) brought forward that at least one type of adversity had occurred to a person prior to 18 years. The traumatic experience underpins the potentials of the person. On this basis, education plays a key role in ensuring that trauma informed education is played out as foremost in ensuring that the policy of education and goals are actualized in its citizenry. Thus, trauma informed education, counselling towards ensuring mental wellbeing, drug use and addiction, skills and ethics and counselling intervention may perhaps address and arrest the overwhelming flood of traumatized individuals in the institutions of learning in Nigeria. There is an urgent need to understand the implication of trauma on the educational system and how trauma informed education can unveil the menace of poor wellbeing, drug intake habits and other associated symptoms of traumatized lives. The impacts of trauma in the lives of traumatized adolescents leave nothing to be desired. It is linked to fear, detrimental health, increase inn behavioural disorders, neurotism and its associated factors, high risk sexual behaviours, absenteeism from classes, gangterism, long term health disorders, truncated relationship, job instabilities, unemployment, environmental unrest (armed robbery, cultism among others) (DuPaul et al, 2014).

Ne-Meroff (2015) has positioned that early childhood trauma such as neglect, abuse and isolation, imparts the brain. As admitted in studies, Ne-Meroff initiated that normal brain development is disrupted when an individual experiences trauma to the point that a clear distinction is made between biological age and physical development. Likewise, (Dye (2018) pointed out that the brain functioning is abruptly disrupted by aversions experiences. He noted that the brain including the brain stem (regulating stress and metabolism), the midbrain (responsible for sensory motor control, sleep and appetite), the limbic system (regulates emotions, attachment, affiliation, language and reasoning. Dye (2018) further enumerated that experiencing trauma may result in depression, anxiety, anger and aggression.

Cognition is the bedrock of knowledge while traumatic symptoms are physiologically and neurologically implicated. The impact of trauma on children and young adult or adolescents impairs learning and triggers assorted educational problems in the individual(s) and the national institutions as a whole. The uneducated populace, poorly educated populace and traumatized persons is of grave concern to the educational institutions and reform of the nation(s). This gives room to questioning on: What can be done to alleviate these maladies, what are the steps to be taken to remedy traumatized lives, where do we go from here as educationists? How do we help these adolescent students from traumatized background and how do we as institution implement a system of trauma informed education organization. The educational institution is perturbed by the numerous undergraduates, graduates and postgraduates' students who have had and are still experiencing trauma in the midst of our educational system. Thus, can trauma-informed counselling skills and ethics have required by counselor trainees. A counsellor believes that you have answers within you and together you can find them. Counselling is not an imposition on the client but a willing relationship by the client to seek for help. Like any other professions, there are boundaries and parameters for practice. In maintaining appropriate boundaries for the counselor, trainee and client, so that they do not enter inappropriate relationship with client or take physical, emotional, sexual psychological or financial advantage of clients. This brings to bear the issue of ethical standard and practice. The guidelines are based on the code of ethics (2004) as approved by the American Counselling Association (ACA). The private nature of counselling session leaves a gap for unsuspected practice, thus the need of code of ethics that identifies principles and behaviour that are in harmony and congruent with the mission and purpose of counselling based on moral precepts and professional behaviour. This calls for the need of adopting counselling skills for maintaining compassionate regard for the client by demonstrating a way of being courteous, tactful, sensitive, accepting, empathetic and nonjudgmental. Therefore counselor, psychotherapist, trainees undertaking role(s) of counselling skills must be conversant with the need of preventing further traumatic disorder among client or adolescents in school.

Similarly, professional code of ethics provides a substantive basis for decision making. To educate counselor trainees about sound ethical conduct, provide mechanism for professional accountability for improving practice. To safeguard the welfare of the client by providing what is in their best interest. Also provide an objective standard of evaluation of specific traumatic areas of potential conflict. Also provide template that professional can take to resolve complex issues in a rational

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manner. Provide guidance in what is expected to professional and what is accepted responses to problem which arise. All these with clarity of purpose help the adolescent(s) with problem to resolve issues and adjust positively. Trauma informed counselling skills and ethics in addressing and proffering services to students faced with problems of financial hardship, family problems, issues of rape, poor academic performance, poor accommodation, school and community unrest and unhealthy relationships and unemployment. All these traumatic situations call for the need of counselling services and help to put the individual back on track. Also to overhauled the educational system and implement policy that provide opportunity for a wholistic development of the child in school and society.

Trauma informed counselling interventions for Internal Displace Persons (IDPs) in Nigeria

An individual's (or children's) physical, mental and emotional wellbeing supports their overall development and learning which helps them to grow and learn optimally while building skills required to attained their full potential (Childhood Education International, 2021). Along the course of life's journey, something precarious happened which affect their physical health and wellbeing. This may lead to poor access to food, shelter, poor sanitary and unsafe living conditions, no access to places to play and exercise, pre-primary education, or higher education. Thus, early exposure to insensitive, maltreatment and neglectful caretaking can affect a child's sense of safety and security which is essential to the development of a secure person. In line with this, Fonagy (2014) affirmed that the exposure to trauma in early childhood, namely abuse or neglect has the potentials to derail a parent's capacity to attend to their children, especially in moment of distress, and has been found to impact their children's attachment style and educational outcome. Luberman, Ghosh and Van (2015) vent that cues children given when needing their caretaking attention can be misinterpreted by parents with a history of child abuse or neglect as threatening and overwhelming and can lead to perceptual distortions that inhibits the child's need from being met and the parents' capacity to respond abruptly. Trauma informed counselling interventions becomes very crucial to address the neurological, physiological and psychological disruption that ultimately impacts on the parents and young person's education and school related outcomes in IDPs. The counselor adopting the theory of Bowlby attachment and Ellis rational emotive behaviour therapy, should advise parents and caregivers in IDPs to be more loving, caring and accepting their adolescents or children with no personal regards. Also, professional should help victims in IDPs to start rethinking positively about their life experiences; replacing negative thoughts with positive thinking and reasoning.

The counselling also in collaboration with government, social health workers, philanthropists, policy makers should help make adequate provision for shelter, food, safety, security, education and create a sense of belongingness among victims. Also create in them a sense of safe, stable and nurturing relationship with community members, prevent violence and improve mental health and support. Chafoules et al (2019) posited that schools have the opportunity to create safe and supportive environment by applying trauma aware assumptions in their day to day practice. This informed educators to understand and draw from trauma-aware pedagogies and help teachers to cater for the behavioural and learning needs of trauma affected children or adolescents in a meaningful way, creating an environment that promotes inclusion of healing and personal growth.

Trauma informed counselling and menace of drug use/addiction in Nigeria school

The fastest and easiest road to teenage child's ruin is drug use and addiction. Any chemical substance whether of natural and synthetic origin, which is used to alter perception, mood or other psychological states, affects the individual. Adolescents do not believe the effect of drug used. Many are simply unaware of the dangers and damages to health, which may lead to disorders such as depression and memory loss. Bergholz, Stafford and D'Andrea (2016) observed that students who struggle to adhere to rules, inability to handle pressure, inability to form connection with team-mates, exhibit aggressiveness, defiance, social withdrawal, unable to regulate their emotions and symptomatic trauma. Ellison, Watton-Fisette and Eckert (2019) ascertained that individual nature of traumatic experiences may be individualized, depending on maturation, intelligence, social environment, family support, school support, nature of the experience and relationship with perpetrators of drug used. An adolescent who is traumatized with drug use and addiction is one at risk; they are frustrated, hostile and aggressive. They exhibit temper tantrums and destructiveness. Based on this, counselors create awareness and sensitization programmes on the influence of drug use and addiction and its consequences on the health and mental imbalance of an individual. Parents should check their life style in the use of drug and even being addicted, to guide their upspring from being exemplary of their parents. An addicted adolescent is one at risk, parent should find it necessary to socialized their adolescents to common forms and values of the home, school and society.

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Trauma-informed counselling and mental health

Childhood Education International (2021) explained that traumatic and stressful childhood experiences can place children at great risk for emotional and mental health challenges. In schools, trauma-informed counselling and mental health as required administrative byelaw and support practices, traumatic sensitive classroom practice, negative response to behaviour, policy and procedure changes, teacher and staff professional development and strong cross system collaboration among school staff and mental health professionals (Oehlberg, 2020). Trauma can have long-term effects on the person's well-being. If symptoms persist and do not decrease in severity, it can indicate that the trauma has developed into a mental health disorder called post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD).

Finally, trauma informed education, mental wellbeing, counselling skills and ethics, counselling interventions, drug use and addiction and mental health; to help alleviate the negative impact of adverse childhood experiences leading to trauma as resilience that can help the counselors, educators and parents protect children from the detrimental effects of traumatized experiences; such as safe, stable and nurturing relationships and improve self-reliance and mental health of individuals.

Types of traumas

There are several types of trauma, including: 1) Acute trauma – This results from a single stressful or dangerous event; 2) Chronic trauma – This results from repeated and prolonged exposure to highly stressful events. Examples include cases of child abuse, bullying, or domestic violence; 3) Complex trauma – This results from exposure to multiple traumatic events; 4) Secondary trauma, or vicarious trauma – With this form of trauma, a person develops trauma symptoms from close contact with someone who has experienced a traumatic event. Family members, mental health professionals, and others who care for those who have experienced a traumatic event are at risk of vicarious trauma.

Treatment of Trauma

Several treatments can help people with trauma to cope with their symptoms and improve their quality of life. This can be treated through therapy.

- a. **Therapy:** Therapy is a first-line treatment for trauma. Ideally, an individual will work with a trauma informed or trauma focused therapist. Types of therapy a person with trauma could benefit from include:
 1. Cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) helps people to change their thought patterns in order to influence their behaviors and emotions.
 2. Eye movement desensitization and reprocessing: Eye movement desensitization and reprocessing (EMDR) is another common trauma therapy. During EMDR, individuals briefly relive specific traumatic experiences while the therapist directs their eye movements. EMDR aims to help people process and integrate traumatic memories.
 3. Somatic therapies: Some therapists use somatic or body-based techniques to help the mind and the body process trauma. These therapies include: i) Somatic experiencing – This approach involves a therapist helping a person to relive traumatic memories in a safe space; ii) Sensorimotor psychotherapy – This type of therapy combines psychotherapy with body-based techniques to turn traumatic memories into sources of strength; iii) Acupoint stimulation – This involves a practitioner applying pressure to specific points on the body, which induces a state of relaxation; and iv) Touch therapies – Other touch therapies include Reiki, healing touch, and therapeutic touch therapy.
- b. **Medications:** Trauma can also be managed through medication. Medication alone cannot cure trauma or PTSD, but it can help a person manage symptoms such as anxiety, depression, and sleep disturbances. A person should talk to their doctor about their options.
- c. **Self-care:** Practicing self-care can help individuals to cope with the emotional, psychological, and physical symptoms of trauma. Examples of self-care for trauma include: 1) Exercise: Trauma can activate the body's fight-or-flight response. Exercise may help mitigate some of these effects. Individuals can aim to exercise for at least 30 minutes a day on most days of the week; 2) Mindfulness: Mindful breathing and other mindfulness-based exercises can ground people in the present, which can stop them from reliving the traumatic event; 3) Connection with others: Withdrawal from others is a common symptom of trauma. However, connecting with friends and family is important.
- d. **A balanced lifestyle:** A person with trauma may find it difficult to relax or to sleep well. However, sleep, relaxation, and diet all play a role in mental health. If possible, a person should try to: sleep for 7–9 hours a night; eat a balanced diet; avoid alcohol and drugs; and relieve stress with mindful or enjoyable activities.

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Conclusions

Trauma informed counselling allows you to validate your emotions, assess your current coping mechanisms (which may for example involve unhealthy habits such as substance abuse), help to make sense of what has happened in your life, move away from avoidance and suppressive behaviours, understand, recognize and integrate self in traumatic situations. Hence trauma counselling (also referred to as trauma debriefing) is essentially the healing process of which assists an individual(s) to deal with symptoms that you are struck with after a traumatic event. Trauma counselling helps individual(s) to identify and come to terms with feelings and emotions they may experience during and after a traumatic event. These emotions may vary from individual to individuals. As well as helping with identifying the causes of stress, counselling can also help to understand the role that one's thoughts play in increasing stress level. The process of counselling also provides employees with a sounding board to talk about issues that they are experiencing. Counselling can help improve mood, treat mental illness, reduce medical illness, improve communication and relationships and promote self-esteem and resilience. Furthermore, counselling in trauma informed education, is known as one of the greatest helping professions on earth, yet many people remain perplexed about its true meaning, purpose and intention. Most likely, the practice of offering counselling to others has always occurred in some fashion within human society – humans are relational beings experience a range of emotions and have an innate desire to avoid suffering and live abundant lives. Today, one in five American adults, has mental health condition and research shows that these conditions can be effectively treated (Centre for Disease Control and Prevention, 2018). Not only can counselling treat mental health conditions, it can also help individuals, groups, organizations and society optimizes wellbeing.

Accordingly, millions of people have experienced the benefits of counselling. Counselling is a specific mental health discipline that includes aspects of guidance and psychotherapy. It focuses on a wellness model aimed at improving the quality of life and involves both counsellor and client in collaboration. Psychotherapy and other counselling techniques help individuals explore moods and behaviours, provide fresh perspectives and offer a better understanding of emotions. Trauma is the physical emotional and psychological response when a person experiences high levels of fear or stress without having the chance to escape or mobilize (more away). It is a stress response that remains frozen in time within the person. A good trauma therapist can provide a grounded presence where individual(s) can begin to explore their trauma while feeling safe, listened to and held. This helps the effected person learn how to come down from hyperarousal and help to be grounded in the here-and-now experience. Moreso, trauma informed education and counselling and mental health to help a trauma survivor to recognize their resources and skills and to build on these. Also, survivor of traumatic situation learns how to regulate emotions and feel safer in the here-and-now. Thus, working with a trauma therapist can help individuals to understand trauma symptoms and to start working through their experiences.

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Assessment on Regulation of Teachers Registration Council of Nigeria (TRCN) on Teachers' Attitude towards Students Behaviour Disposition

Alhassan, Abubakar Musa¹

Abubakar Sadiq Rabiu²

Email: abubakar.rabiu@kasu.edu.ng

Tel: 08035900306

Danfulani, Nafisah A.³

Email: naffylani@yahoo.com

Tel: 08034004691

¹Department of Arts Education, Faculty of Education, Prince Abubakar Audu University, Anyigba

²Department of Arts and Social Sciences Education, Faculty of Education, Kaduna State University, Kaduna

³Department of English, Federal College of Education, Zaria

Abstract

This study assessed the regulation of teacher's registration council of Nigeria and teachers' attitude towards student's behaviour disposition. The authors adopted episode conceptual method and inferential statistics. The population consists of 601 teachers that came for 2019/2020 in-service training in Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. Sample and sampling techniques was used in selecting the sample size for the study. The instrument for the study was a questionnaire tagged ARTCATA structured along 2 points Likert scale. Data collected was analysed using percentage and ANOVA. The findings revealed that most teachers in Kaduna State have negative attitude towards TRCN and this invariably affects behaviour disposition. The paper concludes that motivation determine what teachers do and attitudes determine how well they do their tasks.

Keywords: TRCN, behaviours, regulatory council, discipline

Introduction

Generally, good behavior among secondary school students could be achieved by setting a high positive standard of attitudes by the teachers and executing strong disciplinary control measures over it. Teachers form the bedrock on which the whole of the school activities are built. Consequently, once their attitude is not favourable towards their Regulatory Council, the whole objectives of teaching and learning become defective. Teacher's attitudes towards the TRCN are relevantly significant to the school system because it affects the role of the teacher and his/her teaching methodology, mastering of lessons and good behaviours which in turn affect the students' general behaviour. We cannot keep on complaining about Nigerian problems while we do nothing on her future. The kind of education that lacks discipline will definitely produce graduates that lack integrity and morals. If teachers are not having positive attitudes towards their regulatory body (TRCN), it then means that they are rebellious to anything good for National Development. They will replicate themselves to their young learners and the vicious cycle of indiscipline and corruption continue. One wonders therefore, whether teachers of today will have such moral strength to defend their professional integrity. These have occasioned conflicts and controversies and have misled many into opposing teaching as a profession. It was in the light of these facts that the Nigerian Union of Teachers (NUT) on several occasion embarked on an exceptional strike demanding among other things the establishment of Teacher's Registration Council of Nigeria (TRCN) as a regulatory body for the teaching profession. On 21st August 2002, the Council was inaugurated and registration of teachers began in earnest in 2005. Presently, more than 700,000 teachers according to TRCN statistical digest (2021) have responded positively in terms of registration. However, the Council noted that poor attitudes of teachers and students, poor educational culture and character and lack of good behaviour among students and teachers arc the cause of acute falling standard of education in Nigeria. This was confirmed by 2019 WAEC record which revealed that out of 1.5 million candidates that sat for the May/June 2019 WAEC examination, only 472,906 candidates obtained five credits and above including English and Mathematics. These, if not well controlled may mar the National efforts to meet education for all (EFA)

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made at Jomtien (Thailand) and reconfirmed in Dakar 22 years later. The position of this research is therefore not for the Council to take the erring teachers to Court, rather is concerned with mechanisms, procedures, managerial and organizational processes to reduce opportunities for teachers to hold poor attitudes towards TRCN as regards to students' behaviour and to redirect the erring ones into positive attitudes. It will also provide to the council key tools that will identify "red flags" that /can help to detect risks of attitudes of teachers. This is because teachers are meant to make a positive change in the lives of their students. To guide this study therefore, four research questions were raised, three questions were answered while one question was hypothesized and was tested at 0.05 level of significance. A functionalist theorist, Katz (2011) proposed that attitude is determined by the functions they serve. According to him, people hold given attitudes because it helps them to attain their basic goals. He developed four types of functions that attitudes meet. They are as follows:

1. Instrumental: People develop positive attitudes towards things that aid or reward them. They want to maximize reward and minimize penalties. People develop attitudes that help them meet these goals.
2. Knowledge: Attitudes help in supplying people with evaluation.
3. Value-Expression: Professional workers adopt certain beliefs and values that guide their way of life.
4. Ego-Difference: Attitude acts as defensive mechanism on the working group. Those with feelings of inferiority may develop attitude of superiority.

According to this theorist, attitude change the teachers towards TRCN. It may be negative when the TRCN no longer serves its function and so teachers feel frustrated. On the other hand, Gimba (2020) opined that attitude is a persistent tendency to feel and behave in favourable or unfavourable ways towards the attitude object (i.e. TRCN). Attitudes may have both good and bad elements. Teachers are the attitude holders while TRCN is the attitude object in this context. In every organization, managers are concerned about employee's attitudes. This is because; attitudes are the major causes of employees work behaviour. Positive attitudes according to Katz (2011) always leads to productivity efforts, whereas negative ones lead to poor work habit and so TRCN as the teachers' Regulatory Body needs to know this facts. Katz still maintained that when one has favourable attitudes, one intends to promote the interest and welfare of the object while someone with unfavourable attitude tends to somehow work against it. From the above concept, teachers' attitudes towards TRCN could mean teachers prevailing tendency to respond favourably or unfavourably towards TRCN Code of Professional Conducts.

It is important to note that misconducts are inevitable part of school as a system. This is because individuals working in the school system are of varied background and make-up. However, every system including school has goals to achieve. To unify these people with different threats, the TRCN has the followings as viable benchmarks in assessing teachers' attitudes towards the Council as regard to students' behaviours TRCN (2005). Respects for learners right and dignity. No child should suffer any form of discrimination. Responsibility to the educational programme. The council expects all students to learn and be directed towards excellence. The TRCN expects teachers to be focused and genuine active listener of their students.

1. Confidentiality: TRCN expects teachers to keep strictly secret concerning anything discovered from their students which when disclosed may hamper their social relationship or academic excellence.
2. Fair remuneration: This seems to be the sine qua non for personal regard. Unless students perceive the teacher as being fair in making decisions that affect them such as marking answer scripts, giving help, arbitrating in disputes, they cannot begin to love such teacher. This accounts why Johnson (2011) lamented that teachers often create classes of students - the "bright" and the "slow" and the "Have" and the "Have not". Student of course read these partial attitudes of teachers and consequently, they develop either high or poor self-image resulting from high or low academic performance.
3. Sexual misconduct: Some teachers according to the TRCN (2010) indulge in sexual relationship with their students, which in most cases lead to favouritism in the form of giving marks than what they deserve and unwanted pregnancy.
4. Abuse of Office: According to Ilori (2000), students quickly learn a variety of new responses such as drug addiction and sexual harassment from their teachers. It is no more a secret that most teachers exploit their students through lesson fees and other illegal fees.
5. Examination Malpractices: According to Alutu (2016) teachers are the prime movers of this ugly trend. Each year, according to Ekejuiba (2010) most examination bodies cancel an average of 74,000 results on account of exam malpractice. An average of 450 principals and teachers are blacklisted for aiding it.
6. Patronage of illegal learners Group: It has been generally observed that some influential teachers successfully create

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factions with the students against their fellow teachers or school authorities. They mislead the students by discussing personalities and things that are not related to the students. Consequently, students display undesirable behaviour towards their authorities.

7. **Role Model:** The mode of some teachers dressing tends to reduce the image of teaching profession. Some female teachers wear tight shirt and transparent skirt while their male counterparts wear flowing gowns (baba-riga). Some wear dark glasses which are not in line with teachers dressing ethics. According to TRCN (2005), registered teachers cannot lay claim to be professionals if their conducts before students fall short of what is expected by the Council.
8. **Corrupt Practices:** There is general allegation that some teachers' violet this guideline through the following means:
 - a. **Bribery:** Teachers bribe their employees.
 - b. **Fraud:** Teachers according to the public has become a mill where GCE, WAEC and NECO question papers are created.
 - c. Existence of ghost teachers on pay-rolls.
 - d. Favouritism.
 - e. **Nepotism:** Some teachers give priority to their children and family members.
 - f. **Illegal collection of fees:** These teachers do them through sales of handouts, extra-lesson and handworks.
 - g. **Corporal punishment:** In our contemporary society, the administration of corporal punishment by school teachers has led to "loss of lives and permanent injury" (Peretomode, 1993). This is an outright violation of human rights (FRN, 1999).
 - h. **Discipline:** TRCN under this guideline expects the teachers to administer these disciplinary exercises in accordance with school rules and regulation and with strict adherence to human right law.
 - i. **Ideological influence:** The council expects the teachers not to influence the students in whatever form and not to involve them in any of their political, social or religious idiosyncrasies.

Within a given organization, each person develops a distinctive pattern of traits that characterized his or her social conducts. This stable response disposition according to Katz (2011) channels the behaviour of individual within an organization. Thus, the way a teacher complies with the council's code of conduct is determined by his attitude to it. It is not surprising therefore; those teachers' attitudes towards TRCN affect their working situation. With the author's experiences as desk officers of TRCN and through teachers/public opinions, it was discovered that the following factors influence teachers' attitudes towards the council.

Some teachers run illegal schools where they manufacture answers to any questions. Students in turn have strong hope in these centers and hardly work for any exams. This is against TRCN (2005) (5) Code of conducts. According to functionalist theorist Katz (2010), attitudes develop in the process of want satisfaction. In trying to cope with daily problems to satisfy their basic needs, teachers develop attitudes. For instance, Gowon (2005) lamented that lack of indiscipline among teachers resulting to lateness to school; absenteeism and divided loyalty are the major factors that affect students' moral and academic excellence. This is against the expectation of TRCN even when teachers' wants such as recognition, promotion, professional salary scale and training are met.

The attitudes of teachers towards TRCN are shaped by the information to which they are exposed. Communication is seen as a process of sharing opinions and ideas openly and freely being mindful of others' views. Since some teachers especially in private schools are not sufficiently informed on TRCN expectations, they do not want to change the behaviour of truant students. Thus, making them to become frustrated, resentful and resort to act of indiscipline which is against TRCN Code of Conduct (2005). And as long as suspicions prevail among some teachers in the private schools about TRCN, problem is bound to erupt. Many of the attitudes of the individual teacher have their source and their support in the groups to which the individual gives his/her allegiance. In some schools as observed by these researchers, for teachers to maintain their unfavourable attitudes towards the TRCN, they must have support of likeminded persons. If such teachers cannot find or form informal groups which hold negative view towards the council to their own, they collapse into positive attitudes and comply accordingly. Some others seek out informal groups in which the prevailing attitudes are congenial and turn to propaganda which support their established negative attitudes. Such kind of attitudes makes students to create faction among themselves

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and rebel against school authorities. **Poor working** condition causes teachers' attrition rather than attraction. When this happens students quickly learn a variety of new responses like aggression and drug addiction.

There have been some counterfeit agencies that collect illegal money from the teachers. Some of these agencies which emanate under the umbrella of NUT officials were exposed. Nation' Tuesday July 21st 2019, which had the caption "Nigeria teachers union officials face trials over alleged seventy- three-million-naira scam. The detail of the story reveals that some officials of NUT in Narrageve and Fika Local Government Area of Yobe State are standing trial before a Senior Magistrate Court in Potiskun for allegedly collecting a loan of N73.5 million (NUT, Money) from Bank with the aim of purchasing motor cycle for teachers on hire purchase. The accused NUT officials bought motor cycles worth of N33 million and embezzled the rest alongside with other reported illegal money collected from teachers in the name of their welfare and they were asked to pay back the money. This act of fraud equally makes the teachers to exploit the students with different illegal fees.

Research Objectives

The aim of the study is to examine the assessment on regulation of Teachers Registration Council of Nigeria (TRCN) and teachers' attitude towards students' behaviour disposition. The specific objective of the study is to;

1. examine the attitudes of teachers towards students' behaviour disposition
2. determine how teachers' attitudes has affects students' behaviours disposition
3. investigate the factors that influence teachers' attitudes towards students' behaviour disposition

Research Questions

1. What are the attitudes of teachers towards students' behaviour disposition?
2. Do teachers' attitudes affect students' behaviours disposition?
3. What are the factors that influence teachers' attitudes towards students' behaviour disposition?

Hypothesis 1:

H₀₁: There are no significant differences among the factors that influence teachers' attitudes towards students' behaviour disposition.

Methodology

The researchers employed a comprehensive and systematic episodic conceptual approach, utilizing a series of in-depth literature reviews to elucidate and advance the understanding of teachers' attitudes towards the Teachers' Registration Council of Nigeria (TRCN). This method was particularly chosen to delve into the intricacies of teacher attitudes in relation to the expectations outlined by TRCN, as well as their attitudes towards students, incorporating inferential statistics for a more nuanced analysis. In order to capture a representative sample for the study, a meticulous sample and sampling technique were employed, resulting in the selection of 120 participants. The researchers judiciously chose this sample size to ensure the robustness and reliability of their findings. To gauge the multifaceted aspects of teachers' attitudes, the researchers designed a meticulously crafted questionnaire labeled as the Attitudes towards TRCN Assessment (ARTCATA). This instrument employed a structured format, utilizing a 2-point Likert scale to allow for a nuanced exploration of teachers' perspectives and sentiments.

In the subsequent phase of the research, the amassed data underwent a thorough analysis employing both quantitative and statistical methods. Percentages were employed to provide a descriptive overview of the data, offering insights into the prevalence and distribution of various attitudes among the participants. To unravel more intricate patterns and relationships within the data, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was employed, bringing a sophisticated statistical lens to the investigation. This methodological framework, blending conceptual depth, meticulous sampling, and advanced statistical analyses, contributes to a more comprehensive understanding of the complex interplay between teacher attitudes, TRCN expectations, and the dynamics of teacher-student relationships.

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Result

Research Question 1

What are the attitude of teachers towards student's behaviour disposition?

Table 1: Attitude of teachers towards TRCN in relation to students

S/N	ATTITUDES	AGGREE	DISAGREE
1	Respect student's right	31	69
2	Committed to the teaching and learning program	50	50
3	Empathy	57	43
4	Confidential	56	44
5	Fair to all students	63	37
6	Sexual misconduct	67	33
7	Examination Malpractice	59	41
8	Abuse of office	61	39
9	Patronage of illegal learners	52	48
10	Role model	43	57

Source: Field Survey 2023

Based on the numerical evidence in table 1, it could be held that though some teachers have positive attitudes towards TRCN, majority of them have negative attitudes towards TRCN in the following ways: disrespect for student's right [69%], Sexual misconduct [67%], Examination Malpractices [59%], Abuse of Office [61 %],[Patronage of illegal Learners Group[52%], and poor role Model [57%] .The findings were in accordance with the conclusion of Wokocho [2011], the findings of Alutu [2006] and Ekejiuba [2010]. The implication of these findings was that the students would not be open to teachers because of fears of unknown and therefore unable to learn.

Research Question 2

Do teachers' attitude affect students' behaviours disposition?

Seventy two percent (72%) of teachers agreed that teachers' attitudes affect student's behaviour. This finding was in line with the theory of Katz (2010). This implied that most students behave as they are made to be behaved by their teachers. They could either be affected positively or negatively depending on the actions and inactions of their teachers

Research Question 3

What are the factors that influence teachers' attitudes towards students' behaviour disposition?

Table 2: factors that affect teachers' attitudes towards TRCN

S/N	FACTORS	Agreed	Disagreed
1	Special/Miracle Centers	43	57
2	Individual Teachers Wants	31	69
3	Inadequate information from TRCN	64	36
4	The informal group Affiliations	63	37
5	Poor working condition	87	13
6	Past experience / teacher's perception about the Council and NUT	66	34

Source: Field Survey 2023

The findings in table 2 revealed that certain factors such as inadequate information from TRCN (64%), the informal GROUP AFFILIATIONS (63%), poor working condition (87%) and past experience/teacher's perception about the Council and NUT (66%) were believed to affect teachers' attitude towards TRCN negatively more than other factors. These findings were not in favour of TRCN (2005), (5) and (13) professional code of conduct. These implied that poor standard of education, communication gap, lack of teachers' motivation and transfer aggression did exist in the educational system on account of

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these factors. These account for noncompliance with TRCN with according to TRCN (2005) and Katz (2011) affect students' academic performance and behaviours negatively.

Hypothesis 1

There are no significant differences among the factors that influence teachers' perception towards students' behaviour disposition

Table 3: the ANOVA test of significant differences among the factors that influence teachers' attitudes towards students' behaviour disposition:

Part C	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sign
Between groups	110.281	6			
Within groups	548.900	763	18.380	25.549	.000
Total	659.181	769			

Table 3 shows significant differences among the factors that influence attitudes towards TRCN. This is because the mean square indicated that were differences in the level at which the factors significantly influence teachers' attitudes TRCN. However, it was not clear at his stage if the differences were between only two series or/and all the six series. To determine this, the authors made use of the tabulate command (i.e Post Hoc Test) with the summarized option, as shown in table 4.

Table 4: Post Hoc Tests: Means of Group in the Homogeneous sub set displayed

Ducan		Subset (means) for alpha 0.05		
Factors	N	1	2	3
Special / Miracle Centers	110	2.27		
The informal group Affiliation	110		2.58	
Individual Teachers wants	110			
Inadequate information from TRCN	110			
Teachers perception bout NUT	110			
Poor working condition				
Sign		0.691	.150	1.00

Table 4 indicates that there is significant differences among the factors that influence teachers' attitudes towards student's behaviour disposition.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study have bearing with the 601 teachers that came for 2019/2020 in-service training in Ahmadu Bello University Zaria. The null hypothesis which states that there are no significant difference among the factors that influence teacher's perception towards students' disposition which is in line with Gimba (2020) who posits that TRCN expects teachers to keep strictly secret concerning anything discovered from their students which when disclosed may hamper their social relationship or academic excellence and Johnson (2011) lamented that teachers often create classes of students - the "bright" and the "slow" and the "Have" and the "Have not". Student of course read these partial attitudes of teachers and consequently, they develop either high or poor self-image resulting from high or low academic performance.

The finding on Teachers' Attitudes towards Students' Behavior Disposition reveals a concerning landscape of teachers' attitudes towards students. While some teachers exhibit positive attitudes, a majority display negative attitudes in critical areas. For instance, 69% of teachers disagree with respecting students' rights, and 67% are in disagreement with the prohibition of sexual misconduct. These findings are consistent with previous research by Gowon (2015), which has also highlighted issues related to teachers' attitudes.

The finding on The Influence of Teachers' Attitudes on Students' Behavior suggests that 72% of teachers agree that their attitudes affect students' behavior. This finding aligns with the conclusion of Johnson (2010), which emphasizes the strong influence teachers have on their students. Students often model their behavior based on their teachers' actions and attitudes.

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Therefore, teachers' positive attitudes can inspire and motivate students, while negative attitudes can discourage and potentially lead to poor behavior.

The finding on Factors Influencing Teachers' Attitudes towards Students' Behavior Disposition highlights several factors that influence teachers' attitudes towards the Teaching Regulatory Council of Nigeria (TRCN) and, by extension, students' behavior. Inadequate information from TRCN, informal group affiliations, poor working conditions, and past experiences significantly affect teachers' attitudes negatively, according to the findings. These factors agree with TRCN (2005) potentially leading to issues in the education system.

Conclusion

Motivation determines what teachers do and attitudes determine how well they do their tasks. Ability is what teachers are capable of doing, motivations determine what they do, and attitudes determine how well they do their tasks. There is no substitute for teachers who are dedicated to their nation and students. The future of the nation rests in the hands of its teachers. The moral qualities of teachers today will inevitably be reflected in the citizens of tomorrow. In spite of the TRCN giant stride on teachers' welfare, there persists a worrisome dwindling demand for teachers' progress and commitments. There are many compelling reasons why teachers' attitudes are not in congruent with TRCN Code of Conduct on students' behaviour. If good behaviours are not inculcated to students by teachers, to wipe away robbery, militant groups, kidnapper and all kinds of anti-social acts will be a mirage in Nigeria.

Recommendations

1. TRCN should ensure that teachers are met at their different need disposition
2. TRCN should create a forum for dialogue and decision making with teachers' representatives over the matters that concern them.
3. Adequate control and monitoring measures by TRCN should be put in place for teachers.
4. Teachers should avoid all misconduct that are threats to good school climate and could affect the students.

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Qualitative Study on Values, Challenges and Socio-Cultural Significance for sustainable Development of Rural Areas in Nigeria

Kontagora, Ibrahim Kabir

Email: kabir036@yahoo.com

Tel: +2348100953700

Agricultural Education Department, Federal College of Education Kontagora, PMB 39, Niger State, Nigeria

Abstract

Sustainable development involves addressing the needs of impoverished populations in a manner that empowers them to achieve self-sufficiency and actively engage in the economic, political, and social progress of their communities. However, this was not the case in most emerging nations, such as Nigeria, where most of the population lives in rural areas. Rural areas are typically acknowledged for their significance in the realms of agricultural production and job opportunities across Africa. Despite the obstacles faced by rural areas in the present day, their attributes hold significant global importance. Rural areas are integral to global sustainable development due to their contributions encompassing food production, as well as the preservation of natural, social, and cultural values, distinctiveness, and diversity. This study first explores the definition of "rural" and then outlines the main ideals connected to rural communities. The Paper provided a historical review of regional rural development efforts. The study looks at ways to support more sustainability in rural areas, using information from linked projects, development plans, legislation, and research endeavours. The significance of the social aspect of rural sustainability has been acknowledged, and special emphasis has been placed on understanding the attributes and dynamics of rural communities in the research efforts. Recognizing that a significant portion of contemporary spatial research primarily concentrates on urban settings, resulting in a reduced emphasis on rural studies, the objective is to help rectify this acknowledged imbalance by making a valuable contribution.

Keyword: Rural area, social values, Cultural heritage, and Sustainable development

Introduction

In previous scholarly works, the term 'rural' is often described by comparing it to the idea of 'urban.' For example, in the study conducted by Ratcliffe, Burd, Holder, and Fields in 2016, they characterize a rural area as any geographic area situated outside of small towns. This would mean that every non-urban area is rural. Nevertheless, this perspective may not offer a complete grasp of this concept, especially given the worldwide trend of transitioning from rural to urban lifestyles. This shift has led to the emergence of hybrid communities that don't neatly fit into either the urban or rural classification. In some instances, these communities display attributes of both categories. The factors influencing the formation of human settlements evolve over time, in conjunction with shifts in socio-economic conditions. This ongoing transformation results in a constantly evolving perception of what constitutes rural and urban areas. In the present day, various countries worldwide formulate their unique definitions of rural areas, typically relying on specific population density thresholds, in combination with associated economic and social conditions. These definitions are often derived through statistical analyses of administrative units.

As an illustration, in Nigeria, a region with a population of 20,000 individuals or less is categorized as a rural area (Olisa et al., 1992; Farrell, 2018; Wineman A, Alia DY, Anderson, 2020). In the United Kingdom, a rural area is generally characterized as being located outside a settlement with more than 10,000 inhabitants, (Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs, 2016). In the United States, the Census Bureau classifies a rural area as a town with fewer than 1,000 people per 2.6 square kilometers (square mile), and surrounding areas with fewer than 500 people per 2.6 square kilometers (square mile) (Hilary Costa et al., 2023). In Canada, the definition of a rural area is a region situated beyond a community with a population of at least 1,000 residents and characterized by a population density of no less than 400 people per square kilometer (Statistics Canada, 2009). To establish a uniform framework, the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) has created a fresh regional typology. This typology categorizes the regions within member countries into three main groups: 'predominantly rural,' 'intermediate,' and 'predominantly urban' regions (Directorate for Public Governance and Territorial Development, 2011). The OECD classifies regions based on the percentage of their population residing in rural local units. Regions are categorized as 'predominantly urban' if the rural population share is below 15%, 'intermediate' if it falls between

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15% and 50%, and 'predominantly rural' if the rural population share exceeds 50%. While population density is an important indicator, relying solely on it to differentiate between urban and rural areas is inadequate. The term 'rural' is associated with various meanings, as noted by Hart, Larson, and Lishner (2005). Pizzoli and Gong (2007) have contended that incorporating additional factors such as agriculture and economic specialization, human resources and skills, land cover, and the spatial aspects of social life would greatly enhance the accuracy of determining the likelihood of areas being classified as either rural or urban. The features like population density, agricultural landscapes, abundant vegetation, open spaces, sparse building density, underdeveloped infrastructure, standalone houses, low-rise buildings, and the integration of living with other functions are primarily physical or material characteristics of rural areas. In contrast, immaterial or intangible characteristics are related to social constructs, economic conditions, and traditional cultural values.

Significance of rural areas for sustainable development in Nigeria

Despite the challenges that rural areas face in the contemporary world, their characteristics hold significant global importance (Tewelde Gebre and Berhanu Gebremedhin, 2019). Rural areas play a vital role in the sustainable development of global society, contributing to various aspects such as food production, preservation of natural resources, nurturing social and cultural values, and promoting distinctiveness and diversity (Wen, H. and Jiang, L, 2023). To protect rural areas, it is essential to emphasize their intrinsic values and tackle the challenges that endanger these values (United Nations, 2021). This approach allows for the exploration of potential solutions to ensure the preservation of rural areas. In this context, the acknowledged values of rural areas are enumerated in Figure 1 (adopted in journal of rural studies, 2022).

Figure 1. The values of rural areas

Individuals residing in small towns and rural outskirts tend to report higher levels of happiness compared to those living in large cities (Berry and Okulicz-Kozaryn, 2013; WHR, 2020). Lower population density is associated with a sense of happiness, while urbanization is linked to feelings of dissatisfaction (Okulicz-Kozaryn, 2015; Mouratidis, K., and Yiannakou, A. 2022). Additionally, high population density and overcrowding in urban areas can result in elevated levels of violence, a loss of employment opportunities, and a prevailing sense of insecurity and peril (Haddad, and Meyer-Lindenberg, 2013; Wen, L., Kenworthy, J., and Marinova, D. 2020). In contrast to the natural serenity of rural areas, the absence of vegetation and the high concentration of environmental pollutants in urban areas can exacerbate both physical and mental health issues, negatively impacting overall well-being. According to the findings from a study presented by Schaller (2012), there is a connection between the higher levels of stress in urban areas and an elevated measurement of blood pressure when compared to rural areas. Social interactions among rural residents in Nigeria are marked by greater stability and continuity due to deeper relationships and more frequent face-to-face contact (Balogun, 2022). The shared common experiences, customs, traditions, and knowledge among rural residents serve as the fundamental building blocks of rural communities (World Bank, 2021). The transmission of these values from one generation to the next plays a vital role in safeguarding rural culture, identity, and, consequently, promoting diversity (Dei, G.J.S., Karanja, W., and Erger, G. 2022). Cultural diversity, on one hand, leads to increased flexibility, reduced vulnerability, enhanced resilience, and ultimately improved social stability (Gram-Hanssen, I. 2019; Emmanuel, 2020). Local knowledge and traditional cultural values like customs, personal values, beliefs, and norms within

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rural communities in Nigeria constitute the intangible aspects of rural heritage (Falola, 2022). In contrast, traditional handicrafts, notable buildings, and other heritage artifacts and sites are tangible components of rural culture (Covarrubia, 2019; Zhang, X., Li, Y., Lin, J., and Ye, Y. 2021). Rural landscape is a close determinant of rural areas. This encompasses both the material and physical aspects as well as the intangible existential values and symbols (Agnoletti, M. 2014; Primdahl, J., and Van Eetvelde, V. 2020). As such, rural landscape is not only a mere picture of the environment, but also a living and changing structure (Agnoletti, M. 2014). For rural inhabitants, “landscapes appeared both as an expression of the farming systems and as the material basis of social, cultural, and political units” (Almeida *et al.*, 2016). The importance of the rural landscape becomes evident through the establishment of place attachment, the reinforcement of a community's identity, and the enhancement of its resilience (Agboola, O. P. 2022; McAreavey, R. 2022). Even though modern food production is less reliant on human labour, it remains a fundamental characteristic of rural areas (Woodhill *et al.*, 2022). Gardening, agriculture, and farming play crucial roles in both the economic development of a country, and the local development of rural areas (Rohne Till, E. 2022). Food production and local food markets therefore provide various economic and social benefits (Dorneich *et al.*, 2023; Mkhize, X., Mthembu, B. E., and Napier, C. 2023).

Contemporary Rural Challenges for sustainable development in Nigeria

Current challenges in rural areas can be categorized as economic, environmental, and social, as illustrated in Figure 2. A significant focus has been noted in both the positive aspects and difficulties within the social sphere. This observation underscores the importance of giving priority to the examination of social factors in the context of rural sustainability. However, understanding the interrelationships between these three groups of identified issues necessitates a comprehensive analysis.

Figure 2. Rural problems today

The phenomenon of deruralization, also known as depopulation, rural flight, or rural exodus, signifies the expression of rural population migration, which several scholars have labeled as 'the new phase of globalization' (Czaika and Haas, 2014). Conversely, migration is a result of various economic, social, or environmental challenges that persist in rural regions (Akinbami, 2021). If the ongoing trends of rural depopulation persist, it is predicted that the entire world could become entirely urbanized by the year 2152 (Kovács, 2009). Deruralization, as a process, could potentially lead to the erosion of a significant portion of cultural traditions, ultimately resulting in a society that is culturally impoverished and characterized by homogeneity, lacking a distinct identity, as suggested by Kovács in 2009. Considering that deruralization is occurring concurrently with urbanization, achieving rural sustainability can only be accomplished in parallel with urban sustainability (Yavuz, A., 2016). The urbanization of rural regions alters the customs, behaviours, and requirements of rural residents, leading to a transformation of rural culture (Berdegué *et al.*, 2014). The unregulated influx of urban culture into rural areas impacts both the tangible and intangible aspects of local cultural heritage in Nigeria, resulting in the erosion of rural traditions and the diminishment of local rural diversity (Selod, Harris; Shilpi, Forhad. 2021; Tavares, D. S., Alves, F. B., & Vásquez, I. B. 2021; Mthiyane, D.B., Wissink, H. & Chiwawa, N., 2022).

Agricultural issues, along with the dearth of employment opportunities, technology access, and services in rural Nigeria, give rise to economic hardships that are directly linked to global concerns related to rising poverty rates and discontentment among rural populations (Ayim *et al.*, 2022). The rural economy is primarily reliant on natural resources.

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Horticulture, crop production, mining, farming, forestry, fishing, and more recently, tourism, serve as the primary income sources for rural residents (Surchev, 2010; Bakshi *et al.*, 2022). However, inadequate maintenance and management of these resources, along with the community's attitude toward them, significantly alter rural landscapes and contribute to unsustainable development in rural areas (Smith, Convery, Ramsey, and Kouloumpis, 2016). The agrarian landscape is currently undergoing transitions and transformations for various reasons, as documented by scholars such as Kosanović, Fikfak, and Popović in 2016. These changes can make rural residents increasingly wary of change, as they perceive current conditions and prospects as being uncertain and unstable, ultimately heightening their vulnerability, as noted by Palang *et al.*, 2006. However, the deterioration of rural landscapes can also occur due to the presence of new residents who may not share the same level of interest in rural values as farmers or permanent residents, as indicated by Gorka in 2016.

While a low-density built environment typically implies a greater presence of natural elements, it is often associated with underdeveloped infrastructure, restricted mobility for residents, and, as a result, increased isolation. Rural poverty is not solely characterized by a scarcity of job opportunities but also by the fact that rural workers tend to earn lower wages than their urban counterparts, as highlighted by Thiede, Lichter, and Slack in 2016. Rural communities are currently grappling with a range of pressing issues, including poverty, the migration of residents from villages to cities, restricted mobility, inadequate access to healthcare and education, subpar housing quality, the departure of young individuals and the arrival of older adults, disparities in gender roles and status, a scarcity of social services, limited leisure and recreational options, cultural conservatism, and social stratification. To attain rural sustainability, it is imperative to formulate fresh perspectives on the entire way of life, extending beyond economic and technological aspects, (Čolaković Prguda in 2015; Ogunkan, D. V., 2022). Without a shift in human consciousness and lifestyles, and an alignment with environmental, economic, and social sustainability, progress toward these goals may remain elusive (Breyer, C., Heinonen, S., & Ruotsalainen, J. 2017; Ashby, M.A., 2021).

Working Toward the Sustainability of Rural Areas in Nigeria

Sustainability-related plans for rural areas should primarily address the prevention of further deruralization. To that end, it is believed that the intensification of research about social-cultural issues could assist in providing better outcomes towards the achievement of sustainability of rural areas (Joel R. Matthews, 2017). The sustainability of rural communities should be understood as a cornerstone of the sustainability of rural areas. Whether it is a place of living or work, interests, attitudes, actions, habits, or customs, community is characterised by shared commonality. This can further be connected to the shifts in identity and belonging as important agents that bond communities from the inside. Therefore, there are certain codes of behaviour and, more deeply, the desired emotions (like empathy) connected to identity and attachment, that play a role in sustaining the existing and building new, sustainable, rural communities. The inevitable process of urbanisation must be redirected from undermining to enhancing the survival of rural communities. Daskon and Binns (2009) and Zheng *et al.*, (2021) have pointed out the importance of interaction of culture, sustainability of living conditions, and community development. According to these authors, the transfer of traditional cultural values to future generations is crucial to strengthening the safety of a community, and to its sustainability. In the past, Berkes and Folke (1994) and Obiero *et al.*, (2023) contended that indigenous knowledge enables individuals to effectively address the inherent challenges of their surroundings. By using traditional skills and knowledge, a community adapts better to newly emerging situations, which strengthens its resilience (Daskon & Binns, 2009; Mekonnen *et al.*, 2021). Since both the physical and immaterial aspects of a region are intricately woven into its landscape, it serves as a significant component of community identity. "Local traditional communities possess a robust sense of identity, vividly articulated through the landscape and notable landmarks," (Claval, 2005; Ogunkola *et al.*, 2020). Hence, the conservation of the agrarian landscape as a cultural heritage should be given top priority in sustainability strategies.

An Overview of Strategies and Research Findings

Early considerations regarding rural areas in various international agendas have emphasized the need for effective management, planning, and enhancement of rural settlements, educational initiatives, agricultural waste management, improvements in agricultural mechanization, as well as the exchange of knowledge and experiences in agricultural practices (United Nations, 1972); the promotion of sustainable agriculture and rural development involves efforts to boost food production, enhance food security in a sustainable manner, provide economic incentives, and advance the adoption of new technologies, as advocated by the United Nations in 1992; this entails inviting diverse institutions, agencies, both governmental and non-governmental organizations, to collaborate in order to enhance productivity among farmers in a sustainable manner (Economic and Social Council, 1995); etc. A growing interest in rural issues on a global scale was expressed at the Rio+20

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United Nations Conference on Sustainable Development, organised in 2012, where a need to create a policy that will strengthen sustainable forms of agriculture by transforming unsustainable, industrial farming practices into systems that protect biodiversity, increase soil fertility, and ensure safe and nutritious food for all have been initiated (United Nations, 2012). Recent recognition of the social problems in rural areas has resulted in the development of several strategies, plans, policies, and various forms of activities aimed at enhancing the development of sustainable rural communities worldwide (Housing Executive, 2016; Partnership for Sustainable Communities, 2011; and The Rural Coalition, 2010).

Researchers propose multiple approaches to promote the sustainability of rural areas, with a central emphasis on rural communities. These approaches include fostering age-friendly environments and inter-generational support within the community, as suggested by Spina and Menec in 2013 and Camarero, Cruz, and Oliva in 2014; enhancing educational prospects and reinforcing the familial support system to encourage young adults to stay in their rural communities, as suggested by Homan, Hedrick, Dick, and Light in 2014, the involvement of rural businesses and social enterprises to create employment opportunities in rural areas, as advocated by Steinerowski and Steinerowska-Streb in 2012, as well as Steiner and Atterton in 2015; importance of local leaders role and their relationship with the processes of governmentality (Beer, 2014); The significance of community land ownership in the sustainable reconstruction of rural development (McMorran, Scott, and Price, 2014); the benefits of rural branding (Eugenio-Vela and Barniol-Carcasona, 2015). According to Swinney, Lang, and Runyan (2012), the “intensity of emotions among residents can serve as a compass for future community development”, and efforts in place branding, coupled with community engagement, can bolster its identity and impact economic growth. Another research investigation has demonstrated the importance of shared recollection in shaping community identity and how communities perceive and address environmental challenges (Messer, Shriver, & Adams, 2015).

For Sunblad and Sapp (2011), “practices and development strategies that create greater levels of interaction among and between neighbours might prove to strengthen local residents’ attachment to their communities”. Community attachment is also linked to a reduced likelihood of rural youth engaging in problem substance use and delinquency (Van Gundy et al., 2011), while, being connected to a specific place, underscores the vital relationships between people and their environment, which serve as a motivating factor for sustainable practices (Baldwin, Smith, and Jacobson, 2017). Thus, primary sense of empathy, strong identity, and attachment capacity are the characteristics of rural communities that improve their resilience and sustainability. An examination of rural regions in central Italy underscores the significance of traditional farming practices and various other activities, such as craftsmanship, in playing a role in the sustainability of rural areas. It suggests strategies that have the potential to enhance residents’ attachment to their locality and transition the local community into a more resilient and adaptable socio-ecological system (Gobattoni et al., 2014). Another study, referring to the context of economic crisis, resulted in a set of factors, closely linked to the resilient character of the territories, according to which rural areas may develop (Sánchez-Zamora et al., 2014). Pender, Weber, and Brown (2014) have emphasized the need for improved data and research concerning wealth creation in rural areas. They also underscored the importance of employing approaches tailored to specific rural regions. Additionally, they provided insights into contextual factors and wealth resources that impact the potential for the development of emerging energy industries.

Furthermore, this document recognizes the potential and provides rationale for initiatives aimed at alleviating the financial burden of energy costs on rural households, which would bring about various advantages for rural communities. It is necessary to re-examine the priorities that contribute to the sustainability of rural areas and their communities. Hence, there is a need for a transdisciplinary approach in planning for the sustainability of rural communities, along with the execution of a more extensive array of strategies tailored to specific regions.

Conclusion

In contrast to urban settings, rural environments provide greater natural diversity, increased interaction with the natural world, healthier surroundings, unique cultural characteristics, preserved traditions, adherence to traditional values, and a wealth of heritage. Nevertheless, this picturesque rural landscape experiences profound transformations because of the global trend of urbanization, which significantly alters the rural environment and numerous factors related to its economy, society, and environment. Hence, any deliberation regarding rural areas fundamentally involves contemplating their survival, resilience, and the sustainable nature of their evolution. The sociocultural significance of rural areas in these countries is paramount, as indicated by various studies that explore avenues to enhance rural environments and safeguard the valuable rural values, considering them as integral components of the global cultural heritage, both in tangible and intangible forms. The purpose of social characterisation is to firstly assist in achieving the sustainability of rural communities, and then to actively engage sustainable communities in achieving the sustainable development of rural areas. Numerous hurdles and difficulties have been

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positioned in the path toward attaining rural sustainability. These challenges encompass the inadequacy of effective strategies and sometimes the insufficient implementation of adopted strategies. Additionally, they relate to the prevalence of narrowly focused research studies that do not approach the issue systematically. Furthermore, the introduction of new modern spatial theories has the potential to redefine the concept of rurality in relation to its historical context, further complicating the pursuit of rural sustainability. This paper has demonstrated the significant role that rural areas play in global sustainable development. Consequently, the foremost set of measures for ensuring their sustainability should be focused on mitigating the trend of deruralization. Simultaneously, there is a need to elevate global awareness regarding the significance of rural areas and to involve a considerably larger number of experts, researchers, policymakers, as well as governmental and non-governmental organizations in addressing the present-day challenges faced by rural communities. While efforts to promote the sustainability of rural communities and, consequently, the sustainable development of rural areas should encompass economic, environmental, and socio-cultural dimensions, it is imperative that effective and proactive solutions are customized to address local obstacles, priorities, opportunities, and objectives. These approaches should be developed with a thorough consideration of contextual idiosyncrasies and the imperative to conserve diversity.

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Assessment of Information and Communication Technology in Teaching and Learning Activities among State Tertiary Institutions Lecturers in Yobe State, Nigeria

Garba, Umar¹

Email: alhumar14@gmail.com

Tel: 08067063899

Jumare, Abubakar Muhammad²

Tel: 08027388097

¹Department of Education, Yobe State University, Damaturu

²Institute of Education, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria

Abstract

The study examined assessment of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) on teaching and learning activities among tertiary institutions lecturers in Yobe State, Nigeria. In line with the stated objective, one corresponding research question was raised and one null hypothesis was formulated for the study. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The total population of the study consists of 2447 (2050 male and 397 female) lecturers during the 2021/2022 academic session in all the state tertiary institutions of learning in Yobe State. 333 (249 male and 84 female) lecturers constitute the sample size of the study using stratified sampling technique. Self-developed questionnaire titled “Assessment of Information and Communication Technology on Teaching and Learning Questionnaire” (AICTTLA) was used. Pilot test was conducted and a reliability coefficient of 0.87 was obtained. Data collected in the study were presented in a tabular form and responses were calculated using frequency counts and percentages. The formulated hypothesis was tested using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) at a 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that: Inadequate Information and Communication Technology gadgets, Provision of an e-learning system to store research materials negatively impacted academic staff performance in tertiary institutions in Yobe State. Therefore, the following recommendations were made; adequate capacity-building training for staff on the need to make the best use of ICT to justify the significant investment made by the tertiary institutions among others.

Keywords: Information, Communication, Technology, Teaching, Learning

Introduction

Technological advancement in the 21st Century has necessitated its adoption by institutions of higher learning globally such as colleges of education, polytechnics and universities for carrying out its core function of teaching, learning and the promotion of research activities of staff, students and other external partners. The adoption of information and communication technologies by tertiary institutions has positioned staff and students to have the privilege of accessing different information materials and also to learn at their own convenient time and place. In support of this assertion, Petrides and Nodine (2003) cited in Lawrence, (2019) opined that the growth and development of tertiary institutions lie squarely on the knowledge they created, the medium of transferring the knowledge they created to others and the relationship they are able to establish with other sister institutions.

Information and Communication Technology (ICT), has become an integral part of every aspect of human endeavour. The use of ICT extends from health care, education and governance, to entertainment. ICT has brought about significant changes in the way people communicate, share information and conduct various activities (Fakandu, 2019). In tertiary institutions, the use of ICT has enhanced the teaching and learning and impacted the overall growth of their institutions. ICT has been a key factor in improving teaching and learning activities in tertiary institutions. The use of computers, software applications and internet facilities has enabled academic staff members to carry out their duties efficiently and effectively. With the use of ICT, lecturers can easily keep track of students' progress, communicate with other staff and carry out administrative duties such as grading and attendance keeping. Similarly, Adeoye, Oluwole, and Loto, (2013) cited in Oyedokun, and Adeolu-Akande, (2022) maintained that ICT can make the tertiary institutions more efficient and productive, through its variety of tools to enhance and facilitate teachers' professional activities. ICT is the application of technology to communicate, share, retrieve and transmit

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information through electronic means. With the increase in the use of technology in various fields, educational institutions are no exception. The use of ICT in teaching, learning and research has become an essential aspect of tertiary institutions.

Teaching and learning are two processes that work together to change students' knowledge, abilities, attitudes, and behaviors. The teacher and learners engage with content in a classroom setting that is supportive of learning, using appropriate approaches and mediums. At every level particularly at the tertiary level of education, the main purpose of instruction is to substantially change the student. According to Ayeni (2011) cited in Isa et al (2020), teaching can be defined as a systematic process of transmitting knowledge, attitudes and skills in accordance with professional principles. In the traditional epoch, many teaching practitioners widely apply teacher-centered methods to impart knowledge to learners compared to student-centered methods. The ideal situation in Yobe State tertiary institutions would involve the effective integration and utilization of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in teaching and learning activities. This would enhance student engagement, improve academic achievement and foster innovation and academic excellence.

However, the real situation in the state tertiary institutions presents a significant gap in the effective application and utilization of ICT in teaching and learning activities. According to the the present state of ICT utilization in education at all levels is not commensurate to the public attention generated over the years (Onwuagboke, et al. 2015) need for ICT integration for effective instructional delivery in Nigerian tertiary institutions (Yobe State tertiary institution inclusive) as various in Nigerian schools is at low ebb (Awolaye, et al 2008, Jude, et al. 2012). The persistence of this problem can be attributed to several factors. Firstly, there is inadequate ICT infrastructure and resources, such as computer laboratories, effective internet connectivity and up-to-date software and hardware in some of the tertiary institutions. This hampers the application and effective utilization of ICT in teaching and learning activities. Additionally, there are inadequate training and professional development opportunities for academic staff to acquire the necessary digital skills and knowledge required for successful ICT application.

The implications of not addressing this problem are significant. Without the effective integration and application of ICT in teaching and learning activities, state tertiary institutions may struggle to meet global educational standards and keep up with the evolving demands of the 21st-century workforce. This could result in a lack of competitiveness and hinder the overall development and progress of the educational sector in the state. To address this issue, this study intends to propose a unique intervention focused on enhancing ICT infrastructure, providing comprehensive training programmes for academic staff and developing policies that promote the effective application of ICT in teaching and learning activities. Therefore, it is against this backdrop, that, the study assessed the integration of ICT on teaching and learning activities among tertiary institutions lecturers in state tertiary institutions in Yobe State, Nigeria.

The Objective of the Study

The objective of the study is to:

Assess the mean response of application of Information and Communication Technology on teaching and learning activities among tertiary institutions lecturers in Yobe State.

Hypothesis

There is no significant difference between the application of Information and Communication Technology on teaching and learning activities among state tertiary institutions lecturers in Yobe State.

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The total population of the study consists of 2447 (2050 male and 397 female) lecturers during the 2021/2022 academic session in all the state tertiary institutions of learning in Yobe State. 333 (249 male and 84 female) lecturers constitute the sample size of the study using a stratified sampling technique. A self-developed questionnaire titled "Assessment of Information and Communication Technology in Teaching and Learning Questionnaire" (AICTTLA) was used. The Instrument was divided into two sections (A & B). Section "A" deals with the types of institutions of the respondents, while section B deals with data related to the research questions raised. The questions posed for the study guided the construction of the questionnaire which was structured as strongly agree (SA) = 5 Points, Agree (A) = 4 Points, Undecided (UD) = 3 Points, disagree (D) = 2 Points and strongly disagree (SD) = 1 point. The instrument was subjected to face and content validation by experts in the Department of Education, Yobe State University, Damaturu. To determine the reliability of the instrument, copies of the instrument were administered to a sample of 25 respondents in College of Education and Legal Studies, Nguru who were not part of the study. Cronbach alpha reliability test was used to analyze the

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data. The computation gave a reliability index of 0.87. The instrument was administered personally to the respondents by the researcher and three other research assistants. A total of 333 copies of the instruments were administered and retrieved. Data collected were analyzed using frequency, mean and standard deviation, while Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test the hypothesis at a 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Hypothesis Testing

The non-parametric statistical tool of F-test One-way ANOVA was used for data analysis which allows us to make a conclusion and the summary as presented in Table 2.

Ho1: There is no significant difference between the application of Information and Communication Technology on teaching and learning activities among lecturers in state tertiary institutions lecturers in Yobe State.

Table 2: Summary of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on the Assessment of ICT on Teaching and Learning Activities among Lecturers in State Tertiary Institutions in Yobe State

Status	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-ratio	F-crit.	P.Value	Decision
Between Groups	14.492	3	4.831	1.065	5.05	0.32	Retained
Within Groups	231.175	300	.955				
Total	245.557	333					

Source: Field Survey, (2023)

Table 2 shows the One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) test. It revealed that the calculated f-ratio value of 1.065 is less than the 5.05 F-critical value while the calculated P-value of 0.32 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance set for the study. Therefore, the null hypothesis is hereby retained. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the opinions of respondents on the impact of knowledge of ICT on academic staff performance in tertiary institutions in Yobe State.

Discussion of Findings

The result in Table 1 was an analysis of the respondents' opinions on information and communication technology teaching and learning activities among lecturers in state tertiary institutions. From the details provided in the table, it is clear that the majority of the respondents' integration of ICT enhances the efforts of the lecturers to enhance teaching and learning which leads to innovation in my institution. Also, the use of ICT in the teaching and learning process has been shown to improve academic staff productivity. This was in keeping with Onodugo, et al.'s (2015) assertion that ICT can become a major tool for enhancing academic staff performance in tertiary institutions by boosting the quality of teaching, learning, and research. Other research projects have been conducted to evaluate the effects of ICT in the field of education. Solar et al (2013) cited in Wael, (2018) stated that implementing ICT promotes learning and raises educational standards. This is in line with the findings of a study by Gallego et al. (2014), who contend that effective ICT policies and regulations must be implemented nationwide for a country to successfully increase the quality of education.

Conclusion

The study examined how ICT enhance teaching and learning in tertiary institutions and calls for a multifaceted approach that takes into account infrastructure, the requirement for ongoing training and development programs to improve academic staff members' ICT skills, and the integration of ICT into curricula to improve teaching and learning activities.

Recommendations

Following are some recommendations based on the findings:

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The management of tertiary institutions should propose a unique intervention focused on enhancing ICT infrastructure, providing comprehensive training programmes for academic staff and developing policies that promote the effective application of ICT in teaching and learning activities.

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Impacts of Banditry Activities on Quality Education: An Overview of Government Schools in Jibia Local Government Area of Katsina State

Ladan, Suleiman Iguda¹

Email: suleiguda@hukpoly.edu.ng

Tel: 234 8169805626

Abdulfatah, Ahmed Tijjani²

Email: abdulfattahmedtijjani@gmail.com

Tel: +234 9023040371

¹Department of Basic and Applied Sciences, Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic, Katsina, Katsina State.

²Department of Education, College of Vocational and Technical Education, Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic, Katsina, Katsina State

Abstract

This study explores the impacts of banditry on government schools in the severely affected Jibia local government area of Katsina State. The study employed a qualitative procedure, which involved documentary analysis, revealing adverse effects on education quality, including school closures. Despite efforts from state and local governments, parents, and teachers, persistent challenges remain. The study concludes that banditry significantly impacts education quality and recommends decisive measures to enhance school security and curb banditry.

Keywords: Banditry, Impacts, Education, Jibia, Katsina State.

Introduction

In different parts of the world organized crimes have existed and are existing up till the present times. Organized crimes at present threaten all countries in both developed and developing countries (Vursavas: 2015). Organized crime refers to a group of people involved in serious criminal activities for financial gain using violence and threat of violence in most cases (DOJ: 2022). Examples of organized crime are varied which include money laundering, armed robbery, human trafficking, counterfeit currency making, drug trafficking and banditry. Banditry is a kind of organized crime committed by outlaws in remote or lawless area where there is little or no presence of government as an institution. Nigeria Crime Watch (NCW)(2011) defined banditry as an organized crime that involves the occurrence or prevalence of armed robbery or other violent crimes including the use of force or threat to that effect, to intimate a person with the intention to rob, rape or kill. It is a common genre of crime in some societies where the rule of law is almost absent as well as causing violence in contemporary societies especially in developing countries (NCW, 2011). Historical records have shown that banditry has existed in different parts of the world since the 19th century (Ladan: 2023). In Europe, bandits have operated on mountainous regions of Greece, Italy, Spain and Turkey while in Asia the bandits have also operate in mountainous regions, rocky areas and river valleys of China, India, Iran and Philippines (Ladan: 2023a). In North America, the bandits have also once existed in isolated less populated region of Mexico and USA. But in these, countries a combination of increase security presence and strict legislations against banditry including capital punishment for bandits have ended banditry.

In the continent of Africa, banditry has existed even before independence, when some of the bandits directed their aggression and violence against the colonial administration in Ethiopia/Eritrea for example (Okoli: 2021 & Rufa'i : 2021). The West African sub-region is presently bedeviled by several forms of insecurity created by armed groups one of which is the bandits. The bandits are found in several countries such as Chad, Mali, Niger Republic and Nigeria where they move freely within the porous borders. They are taking advantage of the weak security architecture in these countries and the proliferation of Small and Light Weapons (SALW) following the collapse of the late Libyan leader Colonel Mouamar Gaddafi in 2011 (Ladan & Suleiman: 2023). In Nigeria, banditry began also in 2011 as a result of the escalation of the farmers-herders conflict which has assumed a deadly and destructive dimension. It started from Zamfara State, from where it spread to all the neighboring states such as Kaduna, Katsina, Kebbi, Niger and Sokoto. The bandits have camps in abandoned forests and forest reserves in these states from where they move on motorcycles armed with dangerous weapons to launch attacks on villages inhabited by farmers. They engage in arson, murder, robbery, cattle rustling, kidnapping for ransom and sporadic shooting to

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scare the people (Okoli: 2021). Based on these criminal activities of the bandits, it is quite obvious that banditry will affect the socio-economic activities of the inhabitants of the areas such as education at all levels. Banditry has affected primary, secondary and tertiary education in virtually all the States of the North West geo-political zone. The recent tactics adopted by the bandits to kidnap large number of pupils and students in primary and secondary schools has further worsened the situation. The first major kidnapping incident was on December 11th 2020 when a group of armed bandits kidnapped 344 students of Government Science Secondary School (GSSS) Kankara, Katsina State. Other kidnappings followed in succession in Niger, Kaduna and Zamfara States. It was following the kidnapping of some pupils from a Universal Basic Education (UBE) Primary School in Rema in Binin Gwari LGA Kaduna State on March 14th 2021 that former Vice President Atiku called on the Federal Government to declare ‘State of Emergency’ on the education sector in order to halt further incidences of kidnapping and save the educational sector from collapse (Nasiru, 2021). The kidnapping incidences and other activities of bandits led to the closure of 11,536 schools in the North West region from December 2020 to April 2022 which has impacted the education of approximately 1.3 million children in the 2020/2021 academic year (UNICEF, 2022).

Some studies have been conducted about banditry and education or the impacts of banditry on education in north western Nigeria. Sale (2021) studied the impacts of banditry on education in Faskari Local Government Area (LGA), Katsina State. The study found out that the education of school children has been severely disrupted as they were forced to leave their villages to take shelter at the local government displaced person’s camp. Smiley *et al* (2021) studied the negative impacts of violence on children’s education and wellbeing, evidence from northern Nigeria. The study found out that children who experience any kind of violence are more likely to be out of school, have reduced learning and are less likely to feel safe traveling to and from school. Rosenje *et al* (2022) examined armed banditry and the collapse of education in north western Nigeria. Findings of the study showed that armed banditry incidences hindered teaching and learning due to closure of schools, withdrawal of students from schools, decrease in school enrolment etc. Ojeleye (2022) studied insecurity as a predictor of students’ learning in Zamfara State, Nigeria. The findings revealed that insecurity has made students to develop a phobia to attend school as they skip lessons and school activities. The students lose interest in school activities leading to drop out, boys move into trade while girls settle down for early marriage (Ojeleye *et al.*, 2022). Sa’adu and Lawal (2023) explore the perceived effects of banditry activities on pupil’s enrolment in selected public primary schools in Gusau LGA of Zamfara State. The findings revealed that banditry activities have negative effect on children’s enrolment in public primary schools with respondents expressing concerns about the safety of their children.

From the literatures reviewed above, it can be observed that only the study by Sale (2021) focuses on one of the LGAs affected by banditry in Katsina state. This study is focusing on the impacts of banditry activities on quality education among government schools in Jibia LGA, one of the seven LGAs sharing boundary with Zamfara State (Zurmi LGA) and also one of the most affected by banditry.

Education in Jibia Local Government Area

On the state or condition of education in Jibia LGA, data presented in Table 1 indicated that education is in detrimental condition. This is because most of the schools are dilapidated, lack enough teachers, instructional materials for quality teaching and learning process. The Table also shows that the schools are in relatively good condition in terms of school buildings, and number of teachers and instructional materials. These respondents are referring to the community and private schools that are established mainly in the local government headquarter Jibia town. Furthermore, the insecurity created by banditry has led to the concentration of schools in Jibia town to the detriment of other villages whose people have migrated there or elsewhere. The tables 1, 2 and 3 below show the schools and institutions in Jibia town.

Table 1: Public Primary and Secondary Schools in Jibia town, Jibia LGA, Katsina State

S/N	Name of School	Ownership	Certificate Awarded
1	Gatari Duma Primary School, Jibia, Jibia LGA	Katsina State Government	Primary School Leaving Certificate West African Senior Secondary School Certificate
2	Government Day Secondary School (GDSS) Jibia, Jibia LGA	Katsina State Government	Senior Secondary School Certificate
3	Government Girls Unity Secondary School (GGUSS) Jibia, Jibia LGA	Katsina State Government	Primary School Leaving Certificate Primary School Leaving Certificate
4	Muhammad Rabiu Model Primary School Jibia, Jibia LGA	Katsina State Government	Primary School Leaving Certificate

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|---|--|
| 5 | Sule Mai Mota Primary School, Jibia, Katsina State Government
Jibia LGA |
| 6 | Tudun Tukare Primary School, Jibia, Katsina State Government
Jibia LGA |

Source: JLGEA (2023a).

From Table 2 above it can be observed that Katsina State Government owns three primary and three secondary schools to provide education for pupils and students in the LGA. Since the schools are public places they, often serve as make-shift camps for persons displaced by the activities of bandits especially Muhammad Rabiu Model Primary School Jibia.

Table 2: Community Primary, Secondary Schools and Tertiary Institutions in Jibia town, Jibia LGA

S/No	Name of school/institution	Ownership	Certificate awarded
1	Hajara Community Nursery and Primary school, Jibia	Jibia Community Members	Nursery and Primary School Leaving Certificates
2	Madina Community College of Arabic and Islamic Studies, Jibia	Jibia Community Members	Senior Secondary School Leaving Certificate
3	Madina Community College of General Studies Jibia (Affiliated to Ahmadu Bello University Zaria, Kaduna state)	Jibia Community Members	National Diploma Certificate
4	Women College of Arabic and Islamic Studies, Jibia	Jibia Community Members	Senior Secondary School Leaving Certificate.

Source: JLGEA (2023a).

From Table 2 above, it can be observed that the members of the community in Jibia made efforts to establish four schools and an institution of higher learning to cater for the education of the people. This is in view of the obvious inadequacy of the six primary and secondary schools in the town as the population grows. However, none of the schools and the tertiary institution has been used as make-shift camp for those displaced by banditry.

Table 3: Private Nursery, Primary and Secondary Schools in Jibia town, Jibia LGA

S/No	Name of School/Institution	Ownership	Certificate Awarded
1	Citadel Group of Schools, Jibia	Private	Nursery, Primary and Secondary School Certificates
2	Citadel Group of Schools, Jibia (Diploma Section) Affiliated to ABU, Zaria	Private	Diploma in Education in various disciplines
3	Ibn Abbas Nursery and Primary School, Jibia	Private	Primary and Secondary School Leaving Certificates
4	Jibia Academy Nursery, Primary and Secondary Schools Jibia	Private	Nursery and Primary School Leaving certificates
5	Jibia International Nursery and Primary Schools, Jibia	Private	Nursery and Primary School Leaving Certificates
6	My Jeeb Academy of Science and Tahfizul Quran, Jibia	Private	Nursery, Primary and Secondary schools leaving certificates
7	Tarbiyya Nursery and Primary School, Jibia	Private	Nursery and Primary School Leaving Certificates

Source: JLGEA (2023a).

From Table 3 above, it can be observed that the private sector is active in establishing schools and a tertiary institution to complement the efforts of the state government and members of the community. The establishment of some of the schools is in response to the demand for education following the relocation of some households to Jibia town due to the insecurity created by banditry in the LGA.

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Impacts of Banditry on Quality Education in Jibia Local Government Area

With regards to the impacts of banditry on quality education in Jibia LGA, data in Table 4 indicates that banditry has negatively affected education in a number of ways. The ways include creating insecurity, kidnapping of pupils, students and teachers, occupying schools to prevent schooling, forcing closure of schools, creating shortage of teachers, and school drop-outs, destroying schools, incapacitating parents, negative impacts on teacher training among others. Table 4 – 9 shows the first six ways by which the banditry affected education in Jibia LGA

Table 4: Some banditry activities that creates insecurity among government schools in Jibia LGA

S/N	Date and name of school	Banditry activities	Impacts of the banditry activities
1	May 7 th 2020 at Kange Nomadic Primary School, Jibia LGA	Bandits broke into the office of the Head Teacher to rest in the afternoon during weekend.	The Head Teacher had to run away without completing the work he went to do.
2	October 5 th 2020 at Farfaru ‘A’ Primary School, Jibia LGA	Bandits invaded part of the school as pupils were just returning from Covid-19 induced break	Closure of the school for one week as pupils became terrified seeing men with guns.
3	December 12 th 2021 at GGUSS Jibia	Bandits kidnapped 344 students from GSS Kankara Kankara LGA	Fear gripped the boarding students thinking they would be the next target of the bandits. The State government ordered the closure of all boarding schools in the State.
4	July 12 th 2021 at Gurbin Magarya Primary School, Jibia LGA	Incessant attacks on the village at night that led to the kidnapping of the mother of the Village Head.	Some parents with their children left the village for fear of being kidnapped to migrate to Jibia town.
5	September 1 st 2021 at Garin Jita Government Pilot Primary and Junior Secondary School Jibia LGA	Bandits stormed the premises of the schools holding dangerous weapons and riding their motorcycles recklessly.	Fear gripped teachers, pupils and students as Head Teacher/Principal directed the closure of the school after consulting the Local Government Education Secretary
6	May 12 th 2022 at Government Day Secondary School, Jibia	Bandits passed through the school to attack residents close to the school at night as the school had no fencing	Most of the teachers and students left the school without doing evening games/prep.
7	Mrch 20 th 2022 at Gangara Primary School, Jibia LGA	Bandits intercepted the Head Teacher along Kukar Babangida to Gangara road to snatch his motorcycle	The motorcycle snatching incident and bandit’s other nefarious activities continued leading to the closure of the school
8.	July 26 th 2022 at Government Day Secondary School Daddara, Jibia LGA	Information received at the school that bandits are approaching the school premises area	Teachers and students abandoned the National Examination Council (NECO) Biology Theory exams holding on the day.

Source: Ladan (2023b).

From table 5 above, it can be observed that there were several activities of the bandits that created insecurity which hindered teaching, learning and extra-curricular activities. The activities include breaking into offices, invading schools, reports on kidnappings, incessant attacks and passing through school premises. The impacts of the activities include inability to complete school work, closure of the schools, migration to the local government headquarters and leaving the school without doing games. These impacts in general have negative impacts on teaching and learning in the schools as they cannot take place in an insecure environment.

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Table 5: Pupils, students and teachers kidnapped at Jibia LGA

S/N	Date and location	Pupil/students or teacher kidnapped	Status/condition
1	December 19 th 2019 at Garin Gado village	A teacher of Garin Gado Primary school was kidnapped during an attack at home at night.	Released after 15 days in captivity and payment of N500, 000 ransom.
2	March 29 th 2021 outside GGUSS Jibia	A teacher of the school was kidnapped outside the school premises at night.	The teacher managed to escape but was in trauma due to the kidnapping ordeal and had to be hospitalized.
3	October 5 th 2020 at school premises Farfaru 'A' Primary school, Jibia LGA	Kidnap of two pupils of the school who were just returning from Covid-19 induced break.	Released after one week and payment of N200, 000 ransom.
4	February 5 th 2021 at Jibia township	A female student of Madina Community College of Arabic and Islamic Studies was kidnapped at gun-point on her way to the institution	The bandits called her father to demand for N20million but she was able to escape before any payment
5	March 7 th 2022 at Farfaru village	Teachers' son and pupil at Farfaru 'B' primary school kidnapped at the outskirts of the village	The pupil spent 30 days in captivity but released after the random payment of N200, 000.
6	June 4 th 2022 at Farfaru	Four pupils of Farfaru 'A' and 'B' primary schools among 80 people kidnapped during a reprisal attack on the village.	Released from captivity after one week due to the intervention of the Fulani elders of the area.

Source: Ladan (2023a).

From table 5, above it can be observed that the kidnapping incidences occurred even at the local government headquarters, Jibia. This is happening as the bandits are gaining more strength thereby becoming more daring while also employing the services of informants who live in towns and villages with the people. Two teachers were kidnapped, with one managing to escape while in the other, case ransom was paid. Eight pupils and students were kidnapped in the four instances shown on table 6. In two instances, ransom was paid which tend to impoverish the parents and even the teachers considering that the average monthly salary of a teacher in Katsina State is N70, 000. This clearly indicated that most families in the State had to sell their properties and even life savings in order to be able to pay the huge amount of money demanded as ransom by the bandits. Furthermore, the Katsina State Ministry of Education and the Nigerian Union of Teachers (NUT) Katsina State Chapter do not assist teachers in the payment of ransom.

Table 6: Primary and secondary schools forced to close temporarily due to banditry in Jibia LGA

S/M	Name of school	Reasons for closure	Length of time closed
1	Government Girls Unity Secondary School Jibia	State government directed the closure of the school after kidnapping of GSSS Kankara	December 12 th 2020 to date.
2	Zandam Primary School Zandam Jibia LGA	Incessant attacks by the bandits made the people to flee to Magama and Jibia towns. Bandits stormed the school premises armed with dangerous weapons causing chaotic situation	January 2 nd 2021 to May 8 th 2022
3	Government Pilot Primary and Junior Secondary School Garin Jita	The whole village people fled following the withdrawal of security forces providing security	September 1 st 2021 to March 30 th 2022.
4	Shimfida Primary School, Shimfida Jibia LGA		March 10 th to August 8 th 2022 March 10 th to August 8 th 2022

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5	Government Day Secondary School Shimfida, Jibia LGA	The whole village people fled following the withdrawal of security forces providing security	May 9 th to July 18 th 2022
6	Muhammad Rabi Model Primary School, Jibia	Displaced persons from Shimfida and Farfaru villages occupied classes as temporary shelter	June 4 th to July 3 rd 2022
7	Farfaru 'A' and 'B' Primary Schools, Farfaru	Large scale attacks on the village involving killings, kidnappings, looting and burning of houses	October 5 th 2020 to date (2023)
8	Government Day Secondary School Gangara, Jibia :GA	Incessant attacks on the village by the bandits made the people to flee to other villages	

Source: JLGEA (2023b), Ladan (2023a)

From table 6 above, it can be observed that various reasons are responsible for the closure of the schools. In the first instance, it was a directive by the State Government following the GSS Kankara incidence. The students of the schools were relocated to Government Girls College Katsina when the school resumed. Other directives to close the schools were made by the Education Secretary of the local government in order to ensure the safety and security of the pupils, students and teachers. The length of time of the closure differs depending on the reason for the closure. Only in one instance did the occupation of the school by displaced persons led to the closure of the school with the pupils divided among other primary schools in Jibia town. It is important to observe here that while the school listed on table 7 remain closed though temporarily, other schools in the State remained open with their pupils and students engaging in learning. In instances where the pupils were moved to another school, the receiving school became overpopulated and congested making teaching and learning difficult.

Table 7: Schools presently occupied by bandits, displaced persons and security forces in Jibia LGA

S/No.	Name of school	Those occupying the school	Reasons for the occupation of the school
1	Fafara Primary School Fafara	Bandits occupied the school sleeping during the day time and relaxing in the classrooms	Bandits have taken over the village due to lack of security forces to guard the village like nearby Shimfida.
2	Government Girls Unity Secondary School Jibia	Displaced persons from Zangon Farfaru and Kwari villages	No any vacant public building in Jibia town to serve as displaced person's camp
3	Government day Secondary School Gangara	Bandits using the school building to rest and relax	Most of the inhabitant of the village have fled and nobody at the school
4	School Shimfida	About 2,000 soldiers occupy the school as their base to secure the villages against banditry	No any vacant public building that can accommodate the number of the soldiers in the village.
5	Tsamben Radi Primary School, Tsamben Radi	Bandits have occupied the school using it as a transit point while coming out of their forest hideout.	Most of the people of the village have fled due to incessant attacks with nobody to enforce law or order.
6	Tagwaye Primary School, Tagwaye	Bandits occupied the school as a transit point in and out of their forest hideout.	The whole village has been displaced with the inhabitants fleeing to Gurbin Baure or neighboring villages in Niger Republic.

Source : Abdullahi (2023) and Ladan (2023b).

From table 7 above, it can be observed that all the six schools were occupied by bandits, displaced persons or security forces. In the case of Fafara Primary school, (serial number 1) some of the ex-students of the school who attended secondary school at Shimfida have become bandits themselves according to one of the teachers. In serial numbers 2 and 4, it was because of lack of any vacant public building to accommodate the troops and displaced persons that led to the occupation of the schools. For serial number 3, 5 and 6 the villages have been taken over or most of the people have fled which led to the occupation. In all the six cases there are no any teaching and learning activities going on in the schools which is detrimental to their educational development.

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Table 8 : Primary and secondary schools closed from October 2020 to date in Jibia LGA

S/no	Name of school	Ward school is located	Reason for closure
1	Falale Primary School, Falale	Bugaje ward	Incessant attacks on the village as it is close to a cattle route leading to forest den of the bandits
2	Gangara Primary School Gangara	Gangara ward	Attacks on the people including blocking of the road coming into the village
	Tankuri Primary School, Tankuri	Gangara ward	
	Yangayya Primary School Yangayya	Gangara ward	Increasing frequency of attacks on the village has made it insecure forcing most of the people to flee.
3	Matso-Matso Primary School	Yangayya ward	
	Matso-Matso	Yangayya ward	
4	Mazanya Primary School, Mazanya	Yangayya ward	Attacks on the people have created insecurity leading to migration out of the village
5	Farfaru “A” Primary School, Farfaru	Mazanya ward	Attacks on the people, robberies and kidnapping has made the whole village insecure.
	Karauki Primary School, Karauki	Farfaru ward	Sporadic attacks on the village as some bandits have camped in nearby Zandam forest
6	Tsayau Primary School. Tsayau	Farfaru ward	Bandits have made the school insecure as they pass around the school armed with guns
	Kyabbo Nomadic Primary School		Incessant kidnapping incidences as village lies along road intersected by cattle route
7	Kyabbo	Faru-Maje ward	
		Mallamawa ward	Incessant kidnapping incidences as the village lies along a road intersected by cattle route
8		Mallamawa ward	The Fulani people and their children who inhabit the village have fled due to cattle rustling
9		Mallamawa ward	

Source : JLGEA (2023b)

From table 8 above, it can be observed that ten schools from seven wards were closed after the Covid-19 induced break in October 2020 to date (September 2023). The schools were closed due to the insecurity arising from banditry either on the village where the schools are located or on the schools themselves. According to the JLGEA (2023b) the total number of pupils from the schools is 8,576 comprising 3,674 males and 4, 576 females. Thirty percent (30%) of the pupils of the schools have been relocated to other more secure school while seventy percent (70%) could not be relocated due to the distance involved from the villages and even most of the inhabitants have been forced to flee (Abdullahi, 2023). Banditry has negatively affected education by creating shortage of teachers. This occurred as many teachers refuse posting to schools where villages are affected by banditry. Even in situations where they accepted and start to report for duty, they then seek for re-posting out of the schools. For example, Gurbin Magarya primary school, Gurbin Magarya with a population of 938 pupils has only six teachers but at one time only one teacher was attending the school due to banditry. This occurred as the other five teachers sought for transfer out of the village.

Banditry has led to school dropouts as many pupils and students in the LGA were forced to stop going to school. Many students whose schools were forced to close due to the activities of the bandits hardly join or enroll into another school. Also most pupils and students whose parents migrated to Jibia town to stay at make-shift camps drop out as they have limited access to learning facilities. This happened as there is no existing government policy for immediate transfer of pupils/students to another school as a result of the displacement. Furthermore, most students who became orphans due to banditry drop out of school as they had nobody to support them to go back to school (Ladan and Liman, 2021).

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Banditry has negatively affected education by incapacitating parents who find it difficult to engage in farming and cattle rearing. The results are that they have no money to enroll or register their children into schools, buy school uniforms and books and pay for examination fees when the need arises. The payment of ransom to the bandits to secure the release of loved ones further impoverish them especially as there is no any form of assistance from the State or local government council. Banditry has negatively affected teacher training in Jibia LGA and others LGAs affected by the activities of bandits. For example, in May/June 2022 teachers attending the Teacher Development Training Programme for 32,000 Katsina State Public School Teachers requested the Facilitator to summaries the training module. This was to allow them to go back to their respective destinations before it got dark, which was the time bandits come out of their hide outs to launch attacks. This was the same during the training of teachers from Kankara LGA at Malumfashi when the training program closed by 3.00pm instead of 5.00pm.

Banditry has made some teachers to incur food and economic loss. This occurred as some enterprising teachers posted to villages engaged in farming activities which allowed them to cultivate and harvest food crops. For example, a teacher based at Jibia town but posted to Shimfida village hired a farmland to cultivate 100 bundles of guinea corn and 50 bundles of millet every farming season in 6-years. Another teacher posted to Government Day Secondary School Gangara cultivated and harvested beans within the school premises including guinea corn and sesame seeds. Both the teachers have presently been deployed to Katsina and Jibia where such lands are not available. Banditry has led to the destruction of schools in the form of setting the school buildings and facilities on fire. For example, following the withdrawal of security forces and the people from Shimfida village on March 18th 2022 the bandits set the primary and secondary schools on fire. Besides destruction through burning, the bandits have been engaged in removing the roofing sheets and wood loggings of primary, secondary and community junior secondary schools at Gangara and Tankuri villages from March 29th – 31st 2023. The destructions make the schools inhabitable for any teaching and learning process and will require rehabilitation in a situation when banditry ceases and security returns.

Response of Katsina State Government on Banditry Activities

Katsina State Government has responded in a number of ways to the negative impacts of banditry on education in Jibia LGA and the state in general.

1. Following the kidnapping of 344 students of GSSS Kankara on December 11th the State government on December 12th 2020 directed the closure of all boarding secondary schools in the state. In line with this directive GGUSS Jibia, a girl's secondary school was closed and the students directed to go home.
2. The Education Secretary of Jibia LGA after receiving complains about the insecurity arising from banditry also directed for the closure of schools on temporary basis. Some of the schools were reopened when the security situation improved in the affected villages.
3. The Education Secretary also carried out inspection visits to some schools in Jibia and Magama where he urged teachers deployed to the most affected villages to report to his office for reposting in order to guarantee their safety and security.
4. The Local Government Education Authority (LGEA) has provided a make-shift structure close to Muhammad Rabiou Model Primary School Jibia that served as a school for the children of the persons displaced from March 10th to August 8th 2022. However, the parents who stayed at GGUSS Jibia lamented that their children numbering over 3,000 were not taught as well during the same period (Ibrahim, 2022).
5. From June 2022 – May 2023 the State Government sponsored a radio announcement aired by Katsina State Radio Service with the voice of former Governor Masari urging parents, pupils and students to return to school. The announcement also urged parents that bandits should not be allowed to destroy the education of the children of the State.
6. Katsina State government under Governor Masari was reported to have spent the sum of N88.6m in order to rehabilitate the two schools burnt by the bandits including the burnt houses of the people of Shimfida (Taoheed, 2022). This is important as it enabled the pupils and students of the two schools to resume schooling after the displacement incident.
7. The State Ministry of Education directed all schools to form security committees and appoint a security master to take charge of security issues in both primary and secondary schools throughout the State. In boarding schools, improvements were made in wall fencing and there was the provision of mobile policemen at the entrance gate to monitor movements in and out of the schools.

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Response of Parents and Teachers on Banditry Activities

Parents and teachers as stakeholders in the educational sector have express concern about the impacts of banditry on education in the LGA. They have responded in a number of ways which are outlined below:

1. Some parents have migrated out of Jibia LGA to relocate to Katsina, the state capital or to Maradi, the capital of Maradi region in Niger Republic just 50kms away from Jibia town. This occurred as even Jibia town was attacked by the bandits five times from 2019 – 2023.
2. Most of the parents have withdrawn their daughters from GGUSS Jibia due to fear of kidnapping and enrolled them into other schools which are mostly day secondary schools. This is the situation with most of the parents in the State following the GSS Kankara kidnapping incident in December 2020.
3. Most of the teachers posted to the most affected areas demand for transfer to another school to avoid an encounter with the bandits. Those teachers who could not get transferred avoid regular attendance and as such select some days to go to school while staying at home on some days.
4. Teachers do not wear new clothes to schools and as such wear old ones thereby avoid looking rich or wealthy which will attract the attention of the bandits to plan kidnapping or robbery.
5. Teachers who ride motorcycles to go to school make the motorcycles to look old to avoid snatching by the bandits. Also, the teachers do not maintain one route while going to school and as such use to change routes to avoid monitoring and targeting for kidnappings by the bandits.
6. Some of the teachers have joined the local vigilante groups that engages in regular patrol of the residential areas particularly at night to prevent attacks by the bandits. In situations where the attacks are occurring, they try to foil such attacks by counter attacking the bandits using locally made weapons.
7. Some of the teachers of the LGA have organized themselves into a coalition of Civil Society Organization (CSO). The CSO was able to collect statistics about primary and secondary education in the LGA which was presented to the candidates of the political parties contesting for membership of the Federal House of Representatives and the Senate for intervention to save education in Jibia LGA in March 2023.

Conclusion

Banditry activities has negatively impacted the quality of education throughout north western Nigeria from 2011 to date (2023). Katsina State is the first State in the North West zone that witnessed the kidnapping of a large number of students from their school. Jibia LGA is one of the areas most affected by banditry activities as it shares boundary with Zurmi LGA of Zamfara State and in close proximity to Dumburum forest, one of the major hubs of the bandits. This besides, other forest areas within the LGA such as Shabba and Tsayau forests that also served as hideouts to the bandits. The results is that banditry has negatively impacted the quality of education by creating insecurity in schools, kidnapping of pupils, students and teachers, occupying schools, creating shortage of teachers and school drop-outs, incapacitating parents to send their children to schools, closure of schools, affecting teacher training, food and economic loss to the teachers and destruction of schools. The State and local governments have responded in a number of ways with a view to reducing the negative impacts. But the responses have not been adequate and effective in substantially reducing the impacts on quality of education in the LGA. It is based on this those parents and teachers on their own adopted measures aimed also at responding to the insecurity arising from the banditry activities. It is therefore time for the federal and State governments to adopt new measures and strategies to end banditry in the North West geopolitical zone to save the education of the present generation.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are offered towards reducing the negative impacts of banditry on education in Jibia LGA and Katsina State:

1. School safety and security should be taught at all levels of education from primary to secondary school to serve as guidance to pupils and students on what to do in case of any security breach by bandits or other criminals.
2. The International Day to Prevent Education from Attacks September 9th should be well celebrated particularly in primary and secondary schools. This can be done through lectures, drama and symposia to create awareness about safety and security in schools including tertiary institutions.
3. The Local Government Education Authority of Jibia should try to recruit teachers who are natives of the villages where the schools are located. This strategy will allow teaching to go on as it is observed that bandits usually target teachers who come from other places for kidnapping or robbery.

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4. Primary and secondary schools destroyed by bandits should be rehabilitated especially the recent ones whose roofings and wood loggings were removed. Also part of the renovations should include perimeter wall fencing to prevent trespassing by unauthorized persons such as the bandits.
5. The State Government through the State House of Assembly should formulate policies to ensure that there is immediate transfer of pupils and students displaced to other school where they have relocated. Displaced persons camps should be built in some local government headquarters to provide accommodation to those displaced instead of using primary and secondary schools.
6. Teachers deployed to the most affected villages should be trained adequately on security with a view to equipping them with more strategies of responding to the threats posed by the bandits to them and the school environment.
7. Katsina State Government in conjunction with Jibia Local Government Council should provide hazard allowances to teachers posted to schools whose villages are frequently attacked by bandits. This will provide some form of encouragement for the teachers to be attending to their lessons and reporting to duty regularly.
8. The President and Commander in-chief of the Nigerian Armed Forces should as a matter of urgency declare state of emergency on the security situation in the North West. After which a massive air and ground offensive should be launched on the forest hideouts of the bandits to decimate them once and for all.

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Pattern of Distribution and Utilization of SMC Intervention on the Prevention of Malaria among Children Under-5 in Sokoto State

Muslim Adamu¹, Abdullahi Sabo Muhammad², Yahaya Saleh³

¹Department of Public Health, Postgraduate School, Maryam Abacha American University Maradi, Niger Republic

²Faculty of Health Science Maryam Abacha American University Maradi, Niger Republic

Abstract

An accurate diagnosis of malaria has become increasingly important as *Plasmodium falciparum* becomes resistant to commonly used antimalarial drugs, posing a major threat to the global effort to 'Roll Back Malaria', especially in rural areas where malaria is more severe and frequent. This study aimed at evaluating the pattern of utilization of SMC implementation in Sokoto state over five years (2015-2019) among children under-5 years. This study was carried out as descriptive-analytical study. Inclusion criteria were strictly based on those children under 5 years that were eligible for SMC. All those children above 5 years of age were excluded from the study. Caregivers in Sokoto state had a high level of knowledge on seasonal malaria chemoprevention. Caregivers' perceptions of SMC's effectiveness were largely positive, and the program's acceptability was acknowledged to be highly valued by parents and other stakeholders. Parents and caregivers place a high value on their children's health and have vowed to support the SMC intervention as well as any other community initiative focused at improving their children's health. Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention is an intervention with great potential in Sokoto state, and along with other interventions, it could significantly contribute to approaching the threshold where elimination strategies will be envisioned. During the mass drug administration in all 23 LGAs, comprising 244 wards and 8269 settlements, the intervention significantly reduced hospital visit, admission, and malaria indicators in children.

Keywords: 5-year, SMC, Intervention, Prevention, Malaria and Sokoto State

Introduction

An accurate diagnosis of malaria has become increasingly important as *Plasmodium falciparum* becomes resistant to commonly used antimalarial drugs, posing a major threat to the global effort to 'Roll Back Malaria', especially in rural areas where malaria is more severe and frequent (WHO, 2019). The diagnostic approaches most commonly used in Nigeria are the syndromic approach, followed by microscopy and rapid diagnostic tests (RDT) (Cox, 2002). Due to the poor or absence of laboratory facilities, malaria diagnosis in many health centres has continued to be based on fever or history of fever. Microscopy, considered the gold standard for malaria diagnosis, is generally unavailable at primary healthcare centres only available at the secondary and tertiary level hospitals. However, it is often not used and has an accuracy of only 70-75% (Crutcher and Hoffman, 1996). Microscopy depends on well-maintained equipment, an uninterrupted supply of quality reagents, trained staff, regular quality monitoring and supervision. Maintaining quality microscopy is a major challenge, and it is unsuitable for routine use at a community level (Yeung *et al.*, 2004). RDTs based on detection of Plasmodium-specific proteins can be used if microscopy is unavailable, but cost, availability, false-positive tests, false-negative tests and lack of parasite density information are important limitations, particularly in high transmission areas. Deploying RDTs did not affect the overdiagnosis of malaria in febrile patients (Nkwenti *et al.*, 2019).

With *Plasmodium falciparum*'s resistance to conventional antimalarial drugs escalating, precise malaria diagnosis gains paramount significance. This resistance poses a formidable threat to the global initiative to 'Roll Back Malaria,' particularly in rural regions where malaria prevalence is heightened. The World Health Organization (WHO, 2019) underscores the urgency of accurate diagnosis as a pivotal strategy in navigating the complexities of drug-resistant malaria. In rural areas, where the malaria burden is pronounced, timely and precise diagnoses not only inform effective treatment but also contribute crucially to the broader goal of mitigating the global impact of this persistent and evolving public health challenge.

In Nigeria, prevalent diagnostic methods for malaria predominantly rely on the syndromic approach, microscopy, and rapid diagnostic tests (RDT), as outlined by Cox (2002). The syndromic approach, which often hinges on the presence of fever or a history thereof, is particularly emphasized due to challenges posed by inadequate laboratory facilities in numerous health centers. The scarcity of resources impedes the widespread implementation of advanced diagnostic tools, leading to a reliance on clinical symptoms, which can result in misdiagnoses. This situation underscores the urgent need for improved diagnostic infrastructure and the incorporation of more accurate and accessible tools like RDTs. Enhancing diagnostic capabilities

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becomes pivotal not only for ensuring effective malaria management but also for addressing the challenges posed by drug resistance, contributing to a more targeted and resilient approach in combating malaria in Nigeria.

Microscopy, deemed the gold standard for malaria diagnosis, encounters accessibility challenges as it is typically limited to secondary and tertiary-level hospitals, frequently absent at primary healthcare centers. Despite its status, its practical application is hindered, contributing to an accuracy rate of only 70-75%, as indicated by Crutcher and Hoffman (1996). This underscores a significant diagnostic gap, particularly in primary healthcare settings where malaria burden is substantial. The constraints in microscopy availability at the frontline of healthcare pose challenges in timely and precise diagnoses. Given its suboptimal accuracy and limited accessibility, there's a pressing need for alternative, more widely applicable diagnostic tools such as rapid diagnostic tests (RDTs) to ensure prompt and accurate identification of malaria cases, particularly in resource-constrained regions where primary healthcare is the frontline defense against this pervasive disease.

The effectiveness of microscopy as a malaria diagnostic tool hinges on a multitude of factors, including well-maintained equipment, a consistent supply of high-quality reagents, adequately trained staff, and continuous quality monitoring and supervision, as highlighted by Yeung et al. (2004). Sustaining these prerequisites poses a formidable challenge, particularly in resource-constrained settings. The intricate demands for equipment maintenance, reagent supply, and skilled personnel make microscopy impractical for routine use at the community level. The exigencies of quality control and supervision render it more suited for secondary and tertiary healthcare facilities, accentuating the urgent need for alternative diagnostic strategies. Emphasizing accessible and reliable tools like rapid diagnostic tests becomes imperative to surmount the limitations of microscopy, ensuring widespread and accurate malaria diagnoses, particularly in communities where advanced healthcare infrastructure is limited.

Rapid diagnostic tests (RDTs), relying on the detection of Plasmodium-specific proteins, serve as viable alternatives when microscopy is unavailable, yet they come with significant limitations. The cost, availability, and reliability of RDTs are crucial concerns, especially in resource-constrained settings. False-positive and false-negative test results, compounded by the absence of parasite density information, pose challenges in accurate diagnoses, particularly in regions with high malaria transmission. The limitations of RDTs underscore the nuanced complexities in deploying diagnostic tools that balance accessibility, accuracy, and cost-effectiveness. Addressing these challenges necessitates a comprehensive approach, potentially involving advancements in RDT technology, coupled with strategic implementation strategies and ongoing quality assurance measures to enhance their reliability and applicability, especially in areas where access to sophisticated diagnostic facilities remains a persistent challenge.

The deployment of rapid diagnostic tests (RDTs) has been observed not to significantly impact the overdiagnosis of malaria in febrile patients, as indicated by Nkwenti et al. (2019). Despite their intended role in providing a rapid and accurate diagnosis, certain factors may contribute to persistent overdiagnosis. Issues such as test sensitivity, user interpretation, and the prevalence of other febrile illnesses can influence diagnostic outcomes. This finding underscores the complexity of malaria diagnosis in febrile patients and suggests that while RDTs offer advantages in terms of speed and accessibility, addressing overdiagnosis requires a multifaceted approach. Enhancements in test sensitivity, continuous training for healthcare providers, and a broader consideration of alternative causes of fever are imperative to refine the utility of RDTs and ensure more accurate diagnoses in febrile patients.

Objectives of the Study

1. Evaluate the level of knowledge among caregivers in Sokoto state regarding seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC).
2. Investigate caregivers' perceptions of the effectiveness of SMC in preventing malaria among children in Sokoto state.
3. Assess the overall acceptability of the SMC program among caregivers, parents, and other stakeholders in Sokoto state.
4. Explore the extent to which parents and caregivers in Sokoto state value their children's health.
5. Assess the commitment of parents and caregivers to support the SMC intervention, as well as their willingness to endorse other community initiatives aimed at improving children's health.

Research Questions

1. What is the extent of knowledge among caregivers in Sokoto state regarding the principles, benefits, and implementation of seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC)?
2. How do caregivers in Sokoto state perceive the effectiveness of SMC in preventing malaria among children, and what factors influence these perceptions?
3. To what degree is the SMC program accepted by caregivers, parents, and other stakeholders in Sokoto state, and what are the key factors contributing to or hindering its overall acceptability?

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4. How do parents and caregivers in Sokoto state prioritize and value the health and well-being of their children in the context of preventive measures such as SMC?
5. What level of commitment do parents and caregivers in Sokoto state express in supporting the implementation of the SMC intervention?

Methodology

Having adopted a descriptive-analytical study design, this research comprehensively examined the utilization patterns and impact of Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention (SMC) among children under the age of 5 in Sokoto state. Conducted in Sokoto state, Nigeria, the study encompassed all 23 Local Government Areas (LGAs), 244 wards, and 8269 settlements. The primary study population included children under the age of 5 eligible for SMC in Sokoto state, with the inclusion of parents and caregivers, health workers, and relevant stakeholders involved in the SMC program. A multistage sampling technique was employed, starting with the random selection of LGAs, followed by the random selection of wards within the chosen LGAs. Settlements and households within wards were then chosen to obtain a representative sample. Statistical software was used for data analysis, encompassing descriptive statistics to summarize utilization patterns and inferential statistics to explore associations.

Ethical approval was obtained from relevant institutional review boards, and informed consent was secured from participants, along with a guarantee of confidentiality and anonymity. Ethical guidelines for research involving human subjects were followed, recognizing potential limitations such as recall bias, information bias, and generalizability constraints due to the specific regional focus (Haruna, 2010). Additionally, pre-testing of survey instruments was conducted to ensure clarity and relevance. Data collectors and interviewers underwent training to maintain consistency and quality, with regular monitoring of data collection processes to resolve discrepancies promptly.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the extent of knowledge among caregivers in Sokoto state regarding the principles, benefits, and implementation of seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC)?

Figure 1: SMC administered during the reporting period

Research Question 2

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How do caregivers in Sokoto state perceive the effectiveness of SMC in preventing malaria among children, and what factors influence these perceptions?

Figure 0: SMC redose of the failed administered SP+AQ

Research Question 3

How do caregivers in Sokoto state perceive the effectiveness of SMC in preventing malaria among children, and what factors influence these perceptions?

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Figure 3: Sick children referred from the community to health facility

Research Question 4

How do parents and caregivers in Sokoto state prioritize and value the health and well-being of their children in the context of preventive measures such as SMC?

Figure4: Quantity of SP+AQ used during the reporting period

Research Question 5

What level of commitment do parents and caregivers in Sokoto state express in supporting the implementation of the SMC intervention?

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Figure 0.1:

Adverse drug reaction recorded
 Figure 0.2: Target population of children treated with SP+AQ during SMC cycles in Sokoto

Figure 0.3: Average population of children enrolled in SMC according to LGAs in Sokoto

Figure 0.4: Average population of children enrolled in SMC cycles in Sokoto according to senatorial zones

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Figure 0.5: Total number of functional health facilities in LGAs in Sokoto

Figure 0.6: Average population of children enrolled for SMC cycles in each of the 23 LGAs in Sokoto state

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Figure 0.7: Number of children who received RE dose of SP+AQ

Figure 0.8: Impact of SMC among children under-5 years in Sokoto

Discussion of Findings

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This section indicates the SMC data coverage within the reporting period. A survey conducted in four states of the north-western Nigeria comprising of Zamfara, Katsina, Jigawa and Sokoto state (the study area) by the Oxford Policy Management funded by the Malaria Consortium indicated that despite the decline in the coverage in some settlements. SMC has still contributed immensely in reducing the incidence of both simple and severe malaria disease and the associated anaemia, it has also reduced significantly hospital visits by the targeted age group resulting in healthier, stronger children able to develop and grow with limited interruption by the disease episode (MC 2018 end of round survey Nig). In another report by 3 ACCESS SMS, it was revealed that Over the three seasons of delivery 2015, 2016, and 2017 it has been estimated that the ACCESS-SMC project may have prevented over 10 million malaria cases and 60,000 deaths.

The data also obtainable at the Sokoto State Malaria Elimination Agency revealed that the implementation of SMC was associated with a substantial reduction in hospital admission and all-cause mortality (SOSMEA, 2020). Another study was conducted in Nigeria within the northwest region, cases were recruited in the outpatient department of general hospitals of Gwadabawa and Wurno LGAs in Sokoto State, and Kaura Namoda and Tsafe LGAs in Zamfara State. For cases and their matched controls, SMC status was determined as of the day the case was detected. Three categories of SMC exposure were considered: SMC in the last 28 days, SMC 28-42 days ago, and as the reference category, those who received SMC more than 42 days ago or had not received SMC. Conditional logistic regression was used to estimate the odds ratios for exposure to SMC within 28 days (OR₀₋₂₈), and for exposure in the period 29-42 days (OR₂₉₋₄₂), relative to SMC more than 42 days before, in each year and country, adjusted for age, use of LLIN, socio-economic status of the household, and caregiver education, using State versions 15 and 16. Random-effects meta-analysis was then used to obtain pooled estimates of the odds ratios for the countries/years combined. These odds ratios are estimates of incidence rate ratios, and 100x(1-OR₀₋₂₈) and 100x(1-OR₂₉₋₄₂) are estimates of the percentage effectiveness of SMC (the percentage reduction in the incidence rate of clinical malaria) in the corresponding period, relative to SMC more than 42 days before.

Conclusion

Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention is an intervention with great potential in Sokoto state, and along with other interventions, it could significantly contribute to approaching the threshold where elimination strategies will be envisioned. During the mass drug administration in all 23 LGAs, comprising 244 wards and 8269 settlements, the intervention significantly reduced hospital visit, admission, and malaria indicators in children.

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Evaluation of Factors Associated with Malaria Infection Among Children Under-5 Years Who Received SMC

Adamu Muslim¹, Muhammad Abdullahi Sabo², Saleh, Yahaya²

¹Department of Public Health Postgraduate School, Maryam Abacha American University Maradi, Niger Republic

²Faculty of Health Science Maryam Abacha American University Maradi, Niger Republic

Abstract

Malaria is a major public health problem in Nigeria where it accounts for more cases and deaths than any other country in the world. Malaria is a risk for 97% of Nigeria's population. The remaining 3% of the population live in the malaria-free highlands. There are an estimated 100 million malaria cases with over 300,000 deaths per year in Nigeria. This study aimed at evaluating the factors associated with malaria infection among children under-5 years who received SMC. This study was carried out as descriptive-analytical study. Inclusion criteria were strictly based on those children less than 5 years that were eligible for SMC. All those children above 5 years of age were excluded from the study. Few children were noted to come up with malaria fever despite taken the SMC medication which might be due to poor adherence to day 2 and day 3 medication (AQ), not combining SMC programme with other preventive measures against malaria such as the use of LLIN, fumigation and good environmental management. The most alarming was that some of the children coming up with malaria have been participating in the SMC programme for 2 or 3 years, and this might likely be due to the pfmdr1 86Y mutation which is associated with the AQ resistance which is very rare. Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention is an intervention with great potential in Sokoto state, and along with other interventions, it could significantly contribute to approaching the threshold where elimination strategies will be envisioned. During the mass drug administration in all 23 LGAs, comprising 244 wards and 8269 settlements, the intervention significantly reduced hospital visit, admission, and malaria indicators in children.

Keywords: Factors Associated with Malaria Infection, Children Under-5 Years and Who Received SMC

Introduction

Malaria is a major public health problem in Nigeria where it accounts for more cases and deaths than any other country in the world (Strachan, et. al., 2016). Malaria is a risk for 97% of Nigeria's population. The remaining 3% of the population live in the malaria-free highlands. There are an estimated 100 million malaria cases with over 300,000 deaths per year in Nigeria. This compares with 215,000 deaths per year in Nigeria from HIV/AIDS (Strachan, et. al., 2016). Malaria contributes to an estimated 11% of maternal mortality. Malaria accounts for 60% of outpatient visits and 30% of hospitalizations among children under five years of age in Nigeria. Malaria has the greatest prevalence, close to 50%, in children age 6-59 months in the South West, North Central, and North West regions (Zongo, et. al., 2015). Malaria has the least prevalence, 27.6 per cent, in children age 6 to 59 months in the South East region (Antwi, et. al., 2016). Literature Review: Evaluation of Factors Associated with Malaria Infection Among Children Under-5 Years Who Received Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention (SMC).

Malaria remains a significant public health concern, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa, where children under the age of five are disproportionately affected. Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention (SMC) has emerged as a crucial intervention strategy to prevent malaria-related morbidity and mortality in this vulnerable population. Understanding the factors associated with malaria infection among children under-five who received SMC is essential for optimizing the effectiveness of this intervention. This literature review aims to synthesize existing research on the evaluation of factors influencing malaria infection among children under-five who have received SMC.

Numerous studies have assessed the efficacy of SMC in reducing malaria incidence among children under-five in malaria-endemic regions. High efficacy rates have been reported, with SMC significantly reducing the burden of clinical malaria and severe malaria cases in treated populations (Bojang et al., 2011; Cissé et al., 2016). However, variations in efficacy have been observed across different settings, highlighting the importance of contextual factors in influencing the effectiveness of SMC programs (Diawara et al., 2017).

Adequate coverage and compliance with SMC treatment regimens are critical for achieving optimal protection against malaria. Studies have identified factors influencing coverage and compliance, including accessibility of healthcare

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services, community awareness and acceptance of SMC, caregiver knowledge and perceptions of malaria prevention, and socioeconomic factors such as household income and education level (Ajayi et al., 2018). Strategies to improve coverage and compliance, such as community engagement, health education, and integrated service delivery, have been proposed to enhance the effectiveness of SMC programs (Kabaghe et al., 2015; Nsabagasani et al., 2020).

Malaria transmission exhibits seasonal variability, with peak transmission coinciding with the rainy season in many endemic regions. Environmental factors such as rainfall, temperature, and humidity influence the abundance and activity of malaria vectors, thereby affecting malaria transmission dynamics and the efficacy of SMC interventions (Mogeni et al., 2020). Understanding seasonal patterns and environmental determinants of malaria transmission is essential for optimizing the timing and delivery of SMC campaigns.

The emergence of drug-resistant malaria parasites poses a significant challenge to the effectiveness of antimalarial interventions, including SMC. Studies have reported the presence of resistance markers in malaria parasite populations, raising concerns about the potential impact on SMC efficacy and long-term effectiveness (Kalinaki et al., 2017; Kamya et al., 2018). Surveillance efforts to monitor parasite resistance patterns and adapt drug regimens accordingly are essential for sustaining the efficacy of SMC programs.

The evaluation of factors associated with malaria infection among children under-five who received SMC is multifaceted and influenced by various contextual, biological, and programmatic factors (Haruna, 2015). Efficacy of SMC, coverage and compliance, seasonal patterns and environmental factors, and malaria parasite resistance are key considerations in optimizing the effectiveness of SMC interventions. Future research should focus on addressing knowledge gaps, enhancing programmatic strategies, and monitoring the long-term impact of SMC on malaria transmission and morbidity among vulnerable populations.

Objective of the Study

The main objective of the study is to assess the factors associated with malaria infection among children under-five who received SMC in Sokoto State.

Research Question

What are the factors associated with malaria infection among children under-five who received SMC in Sokoto State?

Methodology

Sokoto State was carved out of the then North-Western State on February 3rd, 1976 by the former regime of General Murtala Mohammed. Its capital and largest city is Sokoto. The state is named after its capital Sokoto, a city with a long history and the seat of the Sokoto Caliphate. This study was carried out as descriptive-analytical study. Inclusion criteria were strictly based on those children under 5 years that were eligible for SMC. All those children above 5 years of age were excluded from the study. Interviewer administered questionnaire through the research assistant were used which was adopted from the Sokoto state Malaria Elimination Agency SMC campaign for the purpose of this study. It consists of the following sections: SPSS Statistics version 22.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, New York, USA) was used to analyse the data. The analysed data were presented in form of figures and tables and expressed as means \pm SEM (Standard Error of Mean). Statistical differences were compared by simple descriptive analysis, a *p*-value of ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Few children were noted to come up with malaria fever despite taken the SMC medication which might be due to poor adherence to day 2 and day 3 medication (AQ), not combining SMC programme with other preventive measures against malaria such as the use of LLIN, fumigation and good environmental management. The most alarming was that some of the children coming up with malaria have been participating in the SMC programme for 2 or 3 years, and this might likely be due to the pfmdr1 86Y mutation which is associated with the AQ resistance which is very rare.

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Figure 1: Is there at least one child from 3 months to 5 years old in the compound

Figure 2: Was the compound ever visited by a CHWs/distributor this year for SMC

Figure 2: If No, are there any children 3-59 months living in this compound

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Figure 4: If yes, how many times have they visited

Figure 5: Were any of your children under 5 years of age sick with fever within the last month?

Figure 6: If yes, how many cycles of SMC have they take?

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Figure 7: Did you bring/send them to the health centre

Figure 8: Did your children sleep under a mosquito net last night?

Figure 9: Has anyone sprayed the interior walls of your dwelling against mosquitoes at any time in the past 6 months

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Figure 10: How many households are there in this compound?

Figure 11: Was there any other child at any other time, who normally doesn't live in this compound, but who was there during one or more cycles, and was treated at least once

Figure 12: Does the child have an SMC card?

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Figure 13: Do you / did you know the CHW/distributor who came to the compound to treat your child

Figure 14: Is the CHW/distributor that treated your child from your community/village, or is he coming from outside

Figure 15: Can you confirm if the CHW/distributor did administer the first dose to the child on day 1?

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Discussion of Findings

The responses of the respondents if there is at least one child from 3 months to 5 years old in their compound, 85% respondent selected yes while 15% of the respondents selected no, this was similar to the joint study conducted comprising of Sokoto, Jigawa, Katsina and Zamfara by Malaria Consortium in 2018 of which about 99% of the compound heads confirmed to have children under 5 in their compounds. From our current study 86% of the respondents when interviewed reported that SMC Community Drug Distributors visited their households, while only 13.9% choose not to respond to the question, none of the respondents reported no to the interviewed question. This was also similar to the result obtained during the end of the SMC round survey in 2018 in which 88.2% of all responding compounds with children under 10 was reached by SMC teams while 92.9% of children 3-59 months (programme population target) were treated during the programme. More children were reached and treated in Jigawa (94.5%) than in the other three programme states. Out of all the children within the programme's target age (3-59 months) across the four states, about 6.9% of them were never reached by the SMC programme. This was most common in Katsina (8.2%) and Sokoto (7.0%) and least common in Jigawa (5.5%). From the results obtained in this study work almost all the houses with children aged 3 to 59 months were reached with none skipped during the Mass Drug Administration within the study period [4].

On the frequency of visits during the SMC drugs delivery to ensure completeness of the campaign and effective coverage, the data obtained in this current study shows that 8.4% of the respondents interviewed reported that the community drugs distributors visit their households only once in the cumulative data, while 8.8% recorded two visits, 17.9% recorded three visits, while the majority of the respondents reported recording complete four visits depicting 64.9%. This was analogous to the evaluation report in the four north western states (Sokoto, Jigawa, Katsina and Zamfara state) in 2018, Out of the proportion of under 5 children (93%) that received SMC treatment at any of the program's cycles, about 82% reported receiving just one visit and 1 treatment, 76% received two visits and 2 treatments, 66% received three visits and 3 treatment and about 57% received four visit and 4 complete treatments across the survey states.

A progression in the coverage rate was observed in Jigawa and Zamfara states from cycle one to two with about 4% and 1% increase for the second cycle respectively, while other states reported a decrease in the proportion of the children that received the cycle two treatment indicating two visits within each round relative to cycle one response. Across states, sixty-eight per cent of caregivers in Katsina reported that children received two visits indicating two treatments while 69% of caregivers in Sokoto state reported dose administration in cycle two. There was a slight coverage increase in Katsina from cycle three to four of about 2%. Across the states, Zamfara reported the highest percentage of children 3–59-month-old, who received at least three cycles (73%). About 68% of respondents in Jigawa state reported having received at least 3 cycles of the SMC treatment whilst 53% and 52% in Katsina and Sokoto respectively also received 3 cycles. The majority of the caregiver of children 3-59 months reported not receiving the four-cycle treatment. About 37% of children 3-59 months were reported covered by all four cycles across all the surveyed states [5]. These ranges from 53% in Zamfara, 41% in Jigawa, 30% in Katsina and 26% in Sokoto state, the obtainable data show a wide margin in the percentage scores in the current study. In the current study, the proportion of children that come-up with fever after taking SMC medication was equally analysed and the obtainable data shows that the caregiver that responded Yes to that were 18.7%, 80% of the respondents said no to that and 1.3% decline to respond to the question, this is not unconnected to the fact that SMC is often implemented alongside other malaria preventing measures that strengthen the effectiveness of the campaign, such as the ownership and intensive use of LLIN, mosquito vector control strategies and adherence to full course of the SMC medication, a high proportion of children coming up with malaria fever after taking SMC medication were not sleeping under the long-lasting insecticidal net to compliment the SMC medicine taking, not sleeping under LLIN negatively affect the effectiveness of the chemoprevention as children keep coming-up with malaria after treatment and the reasons given by the caregivers is that the net was temporarily unavailable (62%), while about 15% said the net was damaged and same proportion said they forgot to prepare the net for the child to sleep under.

In contrast to the present study, Rek *et al.* [6]. in their study non-adherence to long-lasting insecticide-treated bed net use following successful malaria control in Tororo, Uganda reported non-adherence was greater among children under the age of 5 years and school-aged children between the ages of 5 and 17 years, while inhabitants of poorer families were less adherent [6]. From the observation made on the child record card that was issued to caregivers and the interviewed conducted the result obtained shows 18.7% of respondents that said yes from the previous response depicting 219 caregivers, it was noted that 47% of the respondents' children only took one cycle of treatment, 32% took only the two cycles of treatment, 14% took three cycles

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of while only 8% took the full four-cycle of treatment. This shows non-compliance to the three days course of treatment which contradicts the concept of SMC medication with only the 18% that complies. Moreover, the effectiveness of SMC goes in line with adherence and compliance to the full course of treatment. Coverage of SMC among eligible children in the study area was relatively high. Over 80% of children received at least the first day's SMC treatment either in their household which is the gold standard or in the health facility after referral during the first cycle of treatment. However, this proportion decreased over the consecutive cycles based on interviews conducted and SMC cards observation. This was similar to the result obtained during Malaria Consortium annual survey in 2014 where the result obtained show coverage per cycle slightly declined at subsequent cycles from 75 per cent in cycle one through to 55 per cent in cycle four [7]. This is in cases where information could be obtained, SMC distribution at each cycle was equitable. 61.8% of all children for whom data was collected received at least 3 cycles of SMC. Several factors could explain the limited coverage for households and children, notably their absence during the rainy season. Indeed, it is common for some household members to spend all day in the fields. Some even leave their homes and temporarily live in shelters closer to the fields as reported by [7]. Also, it is common practice in both rural and urban communities for young children to stay with their mother during the day and accompany her wherever she goes. This could explain why, even if a household was visited, some children did not receive SMC treatment.

The result of the interview conducted with the healthcare providers on if they sent their children to healthcare centre after a referral from the community revealed 62% of respondents selected yes they ensure the referral linkage is sustained and the affected children were taking to the health facility while 38% of responded selected no, this was because not all the health facilities are PMI supported site that provides both testings with mRDT and treatment with the first line antimalarial (ACT) is provided free with no payment required to assess such services. Most caregivers in this study work sought treatment from health facilities after referral or when their children fail sick with symptoms of malaria, this was similar to the result obtained in 2018 survey by the Malaria Consortium which shows Katsina having 67%, Jigawa and Sokoto having 61% of caregivers that visited health centres for the care of their sick children. Still on the 2018 survey information on the health outcome for children under 5 whose caregivers sought treatment at health facilities were also considered. Amongst those treated with SMC drugs, caregivers reported that about 78% on average were tested at the health facility during the child's visit. The proportion among those who were reported to have tested positive for malaria was 84% across all states. Sokoto state had the highest rate of positive cases reported by the respondents 90% which is contrary to the result obtained in this current study. These results are based on respondents recall; no record was access to confirm the malaria incidence [8].

On the use of Long-Lasting Insecticidal Net (LLIN) the proportion of children under 5 years of age that sleep under the LLIN on the previous night, it was reported that 85% of children within the required age bracket sleep under a mosquito net last night, while 15% selected no implying that they did not sleep under a mosquito net as obtained from the result of the interview with the caregivers in the study area. A similar study conducted by Cissé *et al.* [9] indicated that the use of mosquito net among children treated and not treated during the cycles after assessment shows that the majority of the children who were treated across the states sleep under a mosquito net on the average (74%). Also, a very high proportion of sleep under a mosquito net among those not treated (70%). In another survey conducted in 2014, the result shows that in all the households visited, 80.7% of all children at baseline and 73.1% at end line slept under a net the previous night. However, in only net owning households, 90.8% of children slept under a net. This proportion significantly increased to 93.8% at the end line. Usually, about 90 per cent of children sleep under a net in these communities which is similar to the result obtained in our current study [10]. From the study conducted on the issue of vector control the result obtained from the participants when asked if anyone had sprayed the interior walls of their houses in the study areas shows that 52% responded Yes to the question, 15% responded No, while 35% of the responded has no answer to the interviewed question. Occasionally, Indoor residual spray exercise and larviciding are being conducted by the state in the LGAs in Sokoto state aimed to reduce the vector density and also to clear the breeding sites of the mosquito vector. The 2018 survey result shows that about 95% of the compounds visited were not sprayed by anyone in the past 6 months before the survey. This was also the case for compounds not visited during the treatment period as it equally depicts 98% of the respondents during the survey. Although, few respondents had disclosed having received visits from personal intending to spray houses, but were prevented by some households due to cultural reasons. In this current study the number of households presents within each compound were inquired on the number of households in the respondents' compounds and Information gathered from respondents on the survey shows that 79% of them are 1 householder, 15% are 2 householders while 6% of them are 3 householders [11].

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Conclusion

Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention is an intervention with great potential in Sokoto state, and along with other interventions, it could significantly contribute to approaching the threshold where elimination strategies will be envisioned. During the mass drug administration in all 23 LGAs, comprising 244 wards and 8269 settlements, the intervention significantly reduced hospital visit, admission, and malaria indicators in children.

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